

Deliverable 4.1 Policy Analysis Report

30 September 2024

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5	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	BE	DK	RTD
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8	Université de Genève	UNIGE	AP	CH	RTD
9	The University of Manchester	UNIMAN	AP	UK	RTD

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Table 1. The SINCRONY Consortium

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WP3	Assessment of existing practices in an intersectional lens	UTU
WP4	Power-based analysis of social narratives and experiences	UNIGE
WP5	Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways	ALDA
WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Impact	WeDo

Table 2. The SINCRONY Work Packages

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the findings from an analysis of policy documents that impact young people's daily lives across the six countries involved in the SINCRONY project: Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. This analysis focuses on contemporary policy documents and on how they shape political and social participation, either reducing or exacerbating social exclusion among young people. The central question is whether EU and national policy narratives recognize young people's needs, diverse identities, and roles as citizens, and their potential to drive social change and contribute to democracy. Specifically, the analysis examines how these policies address intersectionality, considering both general youth needs and the unique challenges faced by those at the intersection of various disadvantaged identities. An intersectional perspective was applied to identify factors that enhance or hinder inclusive participation, particularly for marginalized youth.

The Deliverable draws on materials collected, summarized and analyzed by the six consortium partners - AAU, UNIBO, U.PORTO, UNIMAN and UTU - with the UNIGE team responsible for preparing the guidelines and conducting the final analysis. It is important to note that our analysis is limited by different factors but most notably by the small sample size and the limited number of policy documents reviewed within a specific timeframe. As a result, our report does not provide an in-depth view of the overall situation of young people at the UE level nor within the six countries studied, rather it offers a general understanding of some themes and issues currently being discussed both at the UE and national levels, as reflected in the documents analyzed.

Our analysis highlights variations in policy approaches across the six countries, particularly in five key areas: Education, Employment, Health, Housing and Participation. Most countries have policy documents that aim to include young people, particularly in Education, Health and Participation sectors. However, Housing policies frequently maintain the status quo or even exclude some young people. Participation policies documents often highlight opportunities for young people involvement, in particular on youth councils, volunteering and youth-led initiatives are present at both national and local levels. At the local level, policies tend to be more explicit and local initiatives often provide more concrete actions for young people compared to broader national strategies. While most countries recognize that young people are not a homogenous group and implicitly mention some intersections, most documents refer to young people as a general group, but with differences across countries and levels.

At the European level, the analysis of 25 policy documents reveals a focus on youth social inclusion and participation across areas such as Employment, Housing, Education, Health, and Participation. While 20 documents address youth social inclusion, concrete measures are most prevalent in Employment, with fewer actions in Housing and Education. Opportunities for youth participation are mostly emphasized in Participation and Education policies but are largely absent in Housing. Many documents acknowledge youth diversity and consider young people as a heterogenous group, however, they often lack in offering targeted solutions for specific subgroups, with limited attention to intersectionality.

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PART I: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Often referred to as "citizens in the making" (Marshall 1950) or the citizens of tomorrow, young people are increasingly recognized as active participants by institutionalized authorities. For example, 2022 was designated the European Year of Youth, an initiative to highlight the necessity of prioritizing young people in policymaking. The objective was to "not only listen to them, but also elevate their voices to positions of equality and responsibility," as Katrīna Leitāne, Chair of the European Economic and Social Committee's Ad Hoc Youth Group, observed¹. In May of the same year, the European Parliament proposed a regulation to standardize European electoral rules, including the establishment of a uniform voting age of 16 across the EU, with exceptions for countries where the voting age is 17 or 18 (Mańko, 2023). While the majority of EU member states maintain the voting age at 18, Germany and Belgium joined Austria and Malta in lowering it to 16, while Greece has set it at 17. More generally, since 2018, the Council of the European Union and the Council of Europe have placed considerable emphasis on the right of young people to be involved in the policy-making processes and as well in the implementation of policies affecting them (Council of the European Union, 2018; Council of Europe, 2020, Rottach et al. 2022). The 2018 Council Resolution on the European Union Youth Strategy (EUYS) outlined a framework for 2019-2027, emphasizing youth participation as both a goal and guiding principle, addressing challenges such as uneven representation. It aligns with Article 165 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, which aims to encourage young people's engagement in democratic life (Day, McGrath, Percy-Smith and Petkovic, 2020). Nevertheless, the right to participate and be engaged is inextricably linked with experiences of inclusion and exclusion, particularly for those facing structural disadvantages (Cammaerts et al., 2016; EURYKA, 2017).

This integrated report, compiled from national reports provided by consortium participants, summarizes the key findings of Subtask 4.1.1. The primary objective of Subtask WP 4.1.1 is to offer a comparative assessment of current public policies and practices concerning social inclusion, the opportunities to participate of young people, with particular attention to the vulnerable and marginalized youth populations in six countries: Denmark, Italy, Finland Portugal, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom.

Recognizing that young people represent a heterogeneous group (SINCRONY, 2024), the report underscores the challenges of avoiding overly simplistic categorizations when conceptualizing how social locations shape young people's experiences of power. Considering, therefore the ongoing debate about defining young people solely based on age limits—an approach that oversimplifies the diverse experiences of children and young people (Burman 2008; SINCRONY 2024: 22)—we opted for a broader perspective. Our analysis includes a wide age range, from teenagers to individuals in their early thirties. This approach allows us to consider a variety of intersecting identities and life stages, extending our focus to individuals up to 34 years of age.

Our analysis primarily focuses on the most recent policy documents (2024) but also considers earlier documents when relevant. In this report, social inclusion is defined as the integration of diverse groups, including young individuals with disabilities, ethnic minorities, migrants, and sexual minorities (LGBTQI+).

¹ <https://www.eunews.it/en/2024/04/12/young-people-belong-at-the-heart-of-eu-politics-and-policies/>

Furthermore, we conceptualize opportunities for participation in a broad sense, encompassing both political engagement and involvement in policy-making processes.

1.2. Aims and scope

Subtask WP4.1.1 aimed at providing an understanding of dominating social narratives through which youth as citizens are represented by policy and policymakers. The central question of this subtask was to determine the extent to which narratives in EU and national policies recognize young people's needs, diverse identities, and multiple affiliations as citizens, as well as their potential for driving social change and contributing to democracy (SubTask 4.1.1). Previous research and European projects like CATCH-EyoU, EURYKA have highlighted that concepts such as "young citizens" and "young European active citizenship" remain underdeveloped both theoretically and empirically. The literature can take normative stance, juxtaposing youth active citizenship with notions of responsibilities and civic engagement defined by governmental and national boundaries. Research reveals a range of interpretations across multiple disciplines and ideological perspectives, often neglecting critical, inclusive, and anti-democratic dimensions (e.g. Banaji et al. 2017). Moreover, it seems there is a tension between the critical studies that challenge these normative assumptions and some empirical studies that do not. For example, Banaji et al. (2017) analyzed a broad literature review and textual analysis to identify significant gaps in how young European citizens are represented and understood, advocating for an integrated theory that incorporates diverse perspectives on "European," "youth," and "active citizenship". This raises important questions about how not only scholars, but policymakers and practitioners as well interpret and portray *young people* in their policymaking, laws, and reports at both the EU and national levels. To address this, SubTaskWP4.1.1 examined the narratives around youth inclusion, power, and participation in policies and among policymakers (SubTask 4.1.1). This analysis sought to uncover how political structures could influence paths to political power and youth engagement, with particular attention to marginalized youth.

In the specific, WP4 subtask 4.1.1 investigated how young people are portrayed in policy document narratives—whether they are recognized as a diverse group—and examined the ways in which these policies either include or exclude them. The SubTask also explored the role of youth participation in these policy documents, analyzing how and to what extent young people were involved in the decision-making processes that impact them. In summary, we have explored the following perspectives: the representation of youth in policies, how these policies either include or exclude them, and whether there are opportunities for youth to participate and have their needs heard. It is important to note that the analysis does not aim to highlight the overall legal situation of young people in the UE nor in the six countries studied. Instead, our analysis provides a general understanding of the themes and issues related to young people that are being discussed at both the UE and national levels, as well as how policymakers refer to them. Our analysis does not provide an in-depth view of the actual situation of young people in each country. The small sample size and the restricted number of documents reviewed within this specific timeframe limit the analysis. Therefore, our findings and this deliverable need to be interpreted with these limitations in mind.

The next section provides a more detailed analysis of these aspects.

1.3. Overall Approach

As previously stated, SubTask 4.1.1 examined how EU and national policy documents narratives recognized and addressed the diverse needs, identities, and experiences of young people. It focused on understanding whether these narratives reflect the potential of youth to contribute to social change and democracy and assessed whether they took into account for the complexity of youth identities through an intersectional lens. Therefore, the analysis considered how policies account for intersectionality, ensuring they address not only general youth needs but also the specific challenges faced by individuals at the intersection of various identities (e.g., gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status). This approach ensured that policies are inclusive and responsive to all young people, acknowledging the diverse experiences within this group. Building on the representation of youth in policies, SubTask 4.1.1. analyzed how public policies addressed social inclusion and exclusion, and the extent to which they broaden or restrict opportunities for youth participation. The analysis covered two key analytical angles:

- a. *Social Inclusion.* This analytical angle assessed the effectiveness of social inclusion policies by examining the presence of one or more dimensions, including but not limited to:
 - Recognition: Whether policies acknowledge and respect the diverse experiences of different youth groups. This included considering how well the unique challenges and identities of marginalized youth are recognized.
 - Representation: How well policies incorporate the interests of all young people, particularly those from marginalized communities. This aspect looked at how inclusive the policymaking process is in reflecting the voices and needs of various youth groups.
 - Accessibility: The extent to which services, resources, and information are available to all youth, focusing on whether these essential elements are equally available to young people regardless of their background.
 - Non-discrimination: Efforts to eliminate barriers and biases that might exclude certain groups from full participation.

The impact of these policies on social inclusion was then evaluated on a scale of -1, 0, and 1, indicating whether they hinder (-1), have no effect on (0), or promote (1) social inclusion for youth.

- b. *Opportunities for Political Participation.* This second analytical angle explored whether public policies expand or restrict opportunities for youth political engagement by examining the presence of one or more dimensions, including but not limited to:
 - Youth Councils, Volunteering Programs, and Political Engagement: These are formal opportunities for youth involvement in civic and political life. Their presence in the document could support or limit these avenues for youth participation.
 - Educational Involvement and Digital Platforms: Spaces where youth could express their views, both in educational settings and online.
 - Youth-led Organizations: Assessed the level of support provided to initiatives driven by young people, empowering them to take leadership roles and contribute meaningfully to political processes.

Figure 1

Figure 1 shows graphically the different processes that each document underwent for analysis. The objective was to gain insight into how current policies across a range of themes that impact the daily lives of young people address the narrative surrounding youth. To this end, an examination of different policy areas was conducted, with the recognition that youth policy, in comparison to other social policy areas (Dibou 2012; EURYKA 2017), extends beyond its common associations with education and criminality (Burrowes et al. 2016). Youth policy encompasses a wide range of areas that directly influence the lives of young people, including, for example, health, housing, culture, transportation, education, and employment. In this regard, the *Toolkit on Quality Standards for Youth Policy* developed by the European Youth Forum emphasizes the importance of a cross-sectoral approach. The toolkit acknowledges that policies in these broader sectors significantly shape the opportunities and well-being of young people (Burrowes et al., 2016). For instance, youth-friendly policies in housing are essential for providing young people with the resources and autonomy needed to participate fully in society. Consequently, the toolkit advocates for the integration of youth perspectives into broader policy frameworks, ensuring that youth-related issues are mainstreamed across all sectors of governance (Burrowes et al., 2016: 6). Based on this understanding, we have chosen to focus on the following policy domains: education, health, housing, employment, and participation. In each of the documents linked to the policy areas, our analysis focused on two main aspects: first, how young people were represented in terms of social inclusion, and second, the opportunities for

participation that are provided to them. The goal was to position the countries analysed on a scale from -1 to 1 based on their level of inclusion/exclusion and opportunity/restriction for participation. Therefore, teams evaluated their country on these axes by examining whether the documents addressed inclusion, exclusion, opportunities, and restrictions. Specifically:

- **Frequency:** The analysis assessed the frequency and strength of inclusion and opportunity narratives across five key documents. This analysis aimed to determine whether the approach to inclusion was robust or limited. In the specific, the evaluation examined whether the documents consistently emphasized the inclusion of young people, indicating a strong commitment to these principles. Conversely, it also evaluated the extent to which issues of exclusion and restriction were addressed, noting whether these concerns were discussed in a recurrent and substantive manner or mentioned only sporadically, thus signaling a weaker narrative.
- **Content:** The analysis assessed whether the narrative explicitly addressed inclusion and whether it promoted or restricted rights and access. It also examined who the policies targeted—whether they were directed at young people in general or at specific groups. When specific groups were mentioned, the analysis assessed how many intersecting identities were considered. This approach was applied to the evaluation of opportunities and restrictions.

We outline some of the key combinations used in the document analysis, as follows:

1. **No mention of inclusion/exclusion²:** Inclusion/exclusion are not addressed in the analyzed document.
2. **Inclusion is mentioned, but the status quo is maintained:** Inclusion is referenced but without any significant changes or improvements in the analyzed document.
3. **Inclusion is mentioned with attempts to integrate youth:** Inclusion is acknowledged and there are efforts to actively incorporate youth.
4. **Exclusion or restriction of rights/access:** There are indications of exclusion or limitations on rights and access.

This comprehensive approach allowed for the categorization of countries based on the strength and frequency of their narratives regarding inclusion, exclusion, opportunities, and restrictions. It provided insights into how policies were framed in favor of or against young people and marginalized groups. A simplified explanation of how teams have given scores for evaluating a policies document could be the following score:

Example 1: A document analyzed for the health area, tackles health inequities by expanding mental health support for young girls and promoting preventive health education. It shows a commitment to the social inclusion of youth through improved access to healthcare services and an emphasis on health equity. As a result, it receives the following scores:

- Inclusion: Presence (1), Inclusion (+1). The document effectively includes young girls in its health initiatives.

² The same approach was applied to opportunities and restrictions, but to maintain brevity, only inclusion and exclusion are detailed here.

- **Opportunities:** Presence (0). While the document addresses health needs, it does not specify how young girls will be involved in or benefit from these policies beyond healthcare access. There is no mention of their role in shaping or participating in the policy implementation process.

Example 2: A document analyzed for the participation area, outlines reforms aimed at increasing voter turnout among established demographics and mentions youth participation in passing. However, it mainly targets general adult demographics and lacks specific strategies or measures to actively engage young people. Therefore, it scores as follows:

- **Inclusion:** Presence (0)– It does not address the specific needs or barriers faced by young people, leading to an implicit exclusion of youth from the benefits of the proposed reforms.
- **Opportunities:** Presence (0) – The document fails to provide concrete opportunities for youth engagement in the voting process.

Finally, to achieve the evaluation and cross comparison among countries, we developed a Theoretical Analysis (Table 2) to position a country based on the score received on each policies area for both inclusion/exclusion and opportunities / restrictions.

Presence/ Absence	Inclusion/ Exclusion	Mean of all documents within each policy area	Opportunities / Restriction	Mean of all documents within each policy area
Absence (0)	-	-	-	-
Presence (1)	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}	Opportunities (1)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}	Restrictions (-1)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Inclusion (1)	\bar{x}	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Inclusion (1)	\bar{x}	Opportunities (1)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Inclusion (1)	\bar{x}	Restrictions (-1)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Exclusion (-1)	\bar{x}	Status quo (0)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Exclusion (-1)	\bar{x}	Opportunities (1)	\bar{x}
Presence (1)	Exclusion (-1)	\bar{x}	Restrictions (-1)	\bar{x}

Table 1 : Theoretical analysis table

We first identified the presence of inclusion versus exclusion, as well as opportunities versus restrictions, as outlined in the first column as one of the key goals of this analysis was to assess the frequency of narratives presented by policymakers. Next, we evaluated whether these narratives reflected exclusion, maintained the status quo, or actively promoted inclusion (second column). The same approach was applied to opportunities and restrictions, with a specific focus on the direction of the policies—whether they enhanced or restricted opportunities for young people, particularly when considering intersecting identities (fourth column).

Finally, we calculated an average score for each policy area (third and fifth columns). This score represents the average of the ratings assigned to relevant documents within each policy area, based on the dimensions of inclusion and opportunity. For example, if three documents received a score of 1, another received 0,

and a fifth scored -1, the average would indicate the overall trend in that specific policy area for each country. This is illustrated in Figure 2, which gives an example how scores translate into a visual representation. This approach enabled us to position countries on a scale, reflecting the cumulative impact of their policies in each area. It is essential to underline that while we did indeed use graphical comparison, as in Figure 2, to aid in the interpretation and understanding of the analyzed documents, these should be viewed as guidance for the reader rather than a direct cross-countries comparison. This approach is tied to the small size documents analyzed and its methodological limitations as further details in the Methodological section.

Figure 2

In conclusion, our theoretical analysis offers a broad framework for examining how young people are included and the opportunities available to them across different policy areas and countries, based on the documents analyzed. This approach allows us to start identifying some key trends and differences in national policy strategies in the specific timeframe of our deliverable. The following section outlines the methodology used for sampling and selecting European and national policy documents by each team.

PART II: METHODOLOGY

1.1. Policy Documents' Selection

As previously mentioned, we analyzed policies concerning and affecting youth such as education, health, housing, employment, and participation. Our analysis aimed to determine how policies acknowledged young people's needs and concerns, intersectional diversity and marginalization, and youth participation in decision-making.

UNIGE established selection criteria for policy documents and provided content analysis procedures (see guideline in the appendix). UNIGE analyzed EU policies and policy processes related to the selected issues, while each participating country analyzed at least five policy areas and two regional/ local policies. The analysis updated and integrated previous EU research outputs (e.g. CATCH-EyoU, EURYKA).

European Union Level

Although two of the six countries participating in the national analysis (Switzerland and the UK) are not EU members, to gather the relevant documents, we opted for two resources: the European Union law website (Eur-lex) and the parliamentary committee documents website (Europarl). The Eur-lex repository provided all legislative enactments of the European Union, while the Europarl repository offered documents created by European Union committees, such as reports, amendments, and recommendations. Together, these sources allowed us to analyze the social narratives concerning youth within EU public policies.

Our choice to use these two resources was well-justified for several reasons. Firstly, Eur-lex was the definitive source for EU legislation, ensuring that we accessed the most accurate and official legal texts. This comprehensive database included all treaties, regulations, directives, and decisions, which were essential for understanding the legislative framework affecting youth policies. Secondly, Europarl provided a complementary perspective by offering insight into the parliamentary process and the considerations behind legislative decisions. The documents from Europarl, such as committee reports and amendments, revealed the discussions and debates that shaped policy development. By combining these two sources, we obtained a view of both the legal foundations and the political discourse surrounding youth issues in the EU.

We decided not to use the youth.europa website because its documents were also available through the Eur-lex or Europarl repositories and were, in most cases, outdated. Additionally, we chose not to use the European Petition Portal and the European Citizens' Initiative Portal due to their bottom-up nature. Since petitions and initiatives were authored by citizens, they were not suitable for analyzing the social narratives surrounding youth in European public policies.

During our document search process, we encountered limitations with the search tools. Unfortunately, the European Union law website restricted complex searches to a maximum of two keywords (x AND y; x OR y). This limitation was even more severe for the Parliamentary committees documents website, which did not allow searches for combinations of keywords. Due to these search tool limitations and our focus on documents centered on young people, we decided to search for documents containing one of the chosen keywords related to youth in their titles. The selected keywords were: young* OR youth OR teenager* OR

generation* OR Gen OR minor* OR adolescent* OR millennial*. The documents found with at least one of these keywords in the title amounted to 5,665 documents on the Eur-lex website and 60 on the Europarl website. Due to the large number of documents, we used category filters to select relevant documents whenever available on the Eur-lex website. When we did not have the possibility to filter by topic, we adapted the search process as follows:

- Policy area housing: Finding no documents with housing-related and youth-related words within the title, we widened the search by looking for documents with housing-related keywords in the title and youth-related words in the text.
- Policy area health: Youth-related keywords filtered under the category "health" yielded no results. Therefore, we tried searching without any category filter, looking for titles containing the keyword "health" combined with various terms related to young people.

Given the abundance of documents discussing youth across various policy areas, we decided to add the category "general".

Through our search for documents containing youth-related keywords in the title, we identified a substantial number of publications addressing youth in the areas of "education", "employment", and "participation". Additionally, several documents discussed youth across multiple policy domains. However, we did not find any documents specifically focused on young people in the category of "housing", and identified only one document pertaining to "health".

National and local level

Each team considered the guidelines detailed in the Appendix, with additional specifics available in the national reports for each country (see Part IV). In summary, each team created a sample of national-level policy documents, including laws, public programs, and government reports. The selection of a broad range of documents aimed to comprehend how contemporary policies address the narrative surrounding youth across different themes that impact their daily lives. This approach was intended to provide a nuanced understanding of how various policy areas engage with youth-related necessities. Therefore, it was intended to provide a valuable complement to the overviews of their legal situation that had previously been studied by projects as EURYKA (2017).

Teams reviewed policy documents, including laws, public programs, and government reports, in reverse chronological order, starting with the most recent (2024) and working backward. The focus was on identifying documents that specifically mentioned *young people*. To analyze how youth were framed in these policies, it was essential for the term *young people* to appear in the documents. This approach allowed us to examine the explicit presence of youth in policy frameworks, rather than those where they might be omitted or invisible. Consequently, all analyzed documents included references to *young people*, and our analysis was limited to these visible references rather than instances where youth were not mentioned.

All teams followed the same format for keyword searches, including but not limited to the following terms as "young individual," "young people," "youth," "young," "teenagers," or more specific terms like "minor," "adolescent," "younger generation," "Generation Z," "Gen Z," "Generation Alpha," "millennials/Generation Y," or "young students." This broader approach aimed to capture the diversity of youth representation in policy documents, enabling a deeper understanding of how youth are considered across different policy areas.

Each team then examined various websites to compile the document sample but faced challenges due to the diverse areas of focus and, in some cases, the limited availability of relevant documents. For example, the AAU team identified the most recent national policy documents using the Retsinformation.dk database, which archives all Danish laws and policies. Documents were gathered by reviewing relevant laws, decisions, and policies adopted by the Danish government. However, participation at the national level was largely overlooked, with only one of the 24 documents addressing youth participation. This law, specific to Sorø Akademi, lacked broader application, underscoring the absence of national policies affecting youth participation (See National Report AAU Team).

The UTU team conducted the sampling of national-level documents using the official database VALTO, which archives publications from ministries since 2016, and Finlex, a database for legislative and judicial information. The team searched for relevant documents using youth-related terms (e.g., nuoret, nuori, nuorten, nuoriso) and terms related to the selected themes (e.g., koulu, koulutus, työllisyys, terveys). A major challenge was finding housing-related documents specifically referencing youth, and documents on youth employment were limited, leading to the review of the 'Young Workers' Act' from 1993 (See National Report UTU Team).

The UNIBO team retrieved relevant governmental policies, laws, and public programs by searching institutional websites of ministries and public programs, as well as databases of national and regional laws and regulations (See National Report UNIBO Team). Databases such as Normattiva and Demetra were searched for youth-related terms (e.g., giovani, minori, adolescenti, etc.) and provided access to recent national and regional laws, decisions and related documents. Institutional websites of the Youth Policies Department, the Labour and Social Policies Ministry, the Education Ministry, the Health Ministry and the Emilia-Romagna Region, provided overview of the current policy programs and plans in the selected topics and further additional materials. Documents on youth employment, education, participation and health were more readily available. Housing policies that mentioned young people were more challenging to retrieve – recent policies either did not consider youth, were vague or they were very technical budget-related documents. The selected documents for analysis included ones that were less recent with respect to other areas (e.g., a 2015 document) and ones related to more specific issues that intersect with health and social services policies such as residential services for minors.

The U.PORTO team mainly used the online platform of the official legislative database of the Portuguese Parliament, *Diário da República*, the official webpages of national authorities, such as the National Directorates of Health, Education and Higher Education, and the official webpages of other relevant Youth related organizations, such as the National Youth Associations Federation, to select relevant national policies. At the local level, the official webpages of Portuguese Municipalities were also used, which helped in overcoming some difficulties in finding local policies specifically focused on the areas pre-selected for analysis. To overcome these difficulties, more general local policies were also included in the sample and the analysis process was focused on relevant contents for the housing and participation areas (See National Report U.PORTO Team).

The UNIGE team principally used two platforms to search for documents: the Federal Law Publication Platform (Fedlex) and the Federal Administration website. These platforms were selected to ensure a comprehensive collection of national policy documents. Fedlex provided access to federal laws and related documents, while the Federal Administration website offered additional materials from various federal commissions, including the Federal Commission for Children and Young People. Documents on young

people were most accessible in the areas of participation, education, and health. However, finding relevant documents in employment and housing policies was more difficult. As a matter of fact, two out of five employment policy documents and all housing-related documents only briefly mentioned young people (See National Report UNIGE Team).

The UNIMAN team faced the challenge of youth policy being devolved to the national administrations of England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland, with no single ministry responsible for youth policy. In England, this responsibility lies with the Civil Society and Youth Directorate within the Department for Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS). The team selected national policy documents across the five areas by first searching the <https://www.gov.uk/> website for the relevant ministries or departments using youth-related terms. For areas without a clearly responsible department (e.g., participation), they searched across all ministries under “policy papers and consultations”. This was cross-checked with a search of the DCMS website for youth-related policies. Additional searches were conducted on the House of Commons and House of Lords Library websites for policy summaries, and relevant All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) sites were also reviewed for relevant documents (See National Report UNIMAN Team). Despite these challenges, each team (AAU, UTU, UNIBO, U.PORTO, UNIGE, UNIMAN) managed to compile a sample of national documents.

As previously stated, our deliverable has indeed limitations. First of all, the small sample size limits indeed our analysis. Our analysis does not provide an in-depth view of the actual situation of young people in each country. The limited number of documents reviewed within this specific timeframe further limits our findings. Moreover, as our analysis focuses on a specific time period, different results could potentially change if a wider timeframe were considered. Secondly, it was challenging to achieve a clear and consistent sampling strategy across countries due to contextual differences. Although we did indeed identify five policies areas, thematic variations still exist in each country. The challenge lied in balancing comparability while allowing teams to choose themes present in their countries. As a result, while policy areas are similar, the documents analyzed reflect distinct contexts and timeframes. Thirdly, the nature of the documents varied significantly. As we aimed to capture policy narrative, this led us to analyze a diverse range of documents, from legal frameworks to strategic reports, adding complexity to our analysis. Fourthly, the coding process presents interpretative challenges. Although teams conducted preliminary inter-coder reliability tests, variations in coding interpretation might remain due to the diverse academic backgrounds of teams. While this diversity can be seen as a limitation, it also enriches our analysis by providing a broader and interdisciplinary perspective on our findings. Overall, our findings should be understood within these limitations. It is also important to refer to the national reports for more detailed insights into each analyzed documents present in our deliverable.

The following section provides an in-depth examination of the five key policy areas—education, employment, health, housing, and participation—at the European level.

PART III: ANALYSIS

1.1. European Union Level

At the European Union level, we have analyzed a total of 25 documents across each of the areas listed in the table below.

Country	Policy Area	N° Documents
EU	Education	5
EU	Employment	5
EU	Health	5
EU	Housing	5
EU	Participation	5

Table 2

As noted in the methodology section, although we identified documents for each policy area, there were difficulties in finding relevant documents specifically related to housing. Initially, no documents containing both housing-related and youth-related terms in their titles were found. Therefore, we expanded our search criteria to include documents with housing-related keywords in the title and youth-related terms in the text. Ultimately, we broadened the scope of our research to ensure a more comprehensive analysis.

The following Bar Chart (see Figure 3) provides an initial overview of our analysis. As previously discussed, we considered the number of documents (up to a maximum of five) and the presence of references within them. Specifically, we looked for mentions of inclusion or exclusion (in red) and whether the documents addressed expanding or restricting opportunities (in blue) for young people to participate – in this case we understand “young people” as all young people are considered without intersections. Before breaking down our analysis of Bar Chart 1, it is important to highlight that, although 25 documents were analyzed in total, this chart only includes those that had our dimension’s analysis, in the specific inclusion/exclusion and or the broadening or restricting of participation among young people. This selection follows the theoretical framework outlined in Figure 1 (see Overall Approach for more details). If all documents were represented, there would be 5 per policy domain across each dimension. However, as shown in Bar Chart (see Figure 3), there are differences in the presence of both dimensions.

Figure 3

The analysis of 25 EU documents revealed a narrative focused on youth inclusion across various policy areas, with 20 documents explicitly addressing this topic. The first axis of analysis, which examined concrete measures for youth inclusion (+1, in blue), was present in 15 of these documents (see Figure 4). In the employment policy area, this focus was particularly strong, where all five analyzed documents included recommendations or measures aimed at enhancing inclusion. In the specific, *Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on youth work policy in an empowering Europe* (D1), *Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on youth work policy in an empowering Europe* (D2); *Motion for a resolution on empowering European youth* (D3), aimed to positively impact young people by recognizing their diverse backgrounds and needs, highlighting the importance of equal access to work opportunities. *Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on a Council Recommendation and a Commission proposal on Youth Employment Support* (D4) emphasized fair remuneration and the need for stronger measures to address forms of discrimination in the workplace. Whereas *Opinion of the Committee on Employment and Social Affairs for the Committee on Fisheries on attracting young people to the fishing industry* (D5) focused on attracting young people to the fishing industry, acknowledging the need to ensure gender equality. In contrast, the emphasis on youth inclusion was less consistent in other policy areas. For example, only three documents in both the housing and education policy areas proposed practical measures, while the participation and health policy areas each had only two documents offering concrete solutions. Interestingly, although all analyzed documents linked with the participation area indeed addressed the inclusion of young people, the level of action varies significantly. As a matter of fact, this is the area that most maintains the status quo (0), where some documents vaguely promote inclusion without clear outcomes (D3), others indirectly acknowledge that young people are at higher risk of exclusion and inequalities, yet only proposing fostering inclusion through broad political participation (D4), and still others recognizing the exclusion issues among young people but failing to offer concrete solutions (D5).

Considering now the health field, *Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on using sports to encourage inclusion and social wellbeing among young people* (D2) emphasized in the need for equitable access to sports to mitigate generational injustice and proposed practical solutions, such as calling for the

European Social Fund to incorporate objectives for greater accessibility, inclusion, solidarity, and social cohesion through sports. Whereas the *Conclusions of the Council and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to the mental health of young people* (D4) called for action to enhance both inclusion and participation opportunities for young people, with particular attention to those in vulnerable positions.

Figure 4

Regarding the second axis of analysis, which concerns participation opportunities, 15 of the 25 documents addressed this aspect, with 14 proposing measures to expand these opportunities for young people (see Figure 5). The participation policy area showed the strongest emphasis, with all five documents suggesting ways to enhance participation. The education policy area followed, with four documents recommending measures to boost youth participation. In the health policy area, three documents offered practical measures, whereas the employment policy area showed less focus, with only two documents addressing ways to increase participation opportunities. None of the documents in the housing policy area mentioned opportunities for youth participation.

Figure 5

Interestingly, documents from various policy areas frequently highlighted the importance of involving young people in decision-making and policy design. For instance, *the Conclusion of Council and Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to mental health of young people* (D4 health-focused document) emphasized the need to include young people in the development of public mental health programs, particularly those aimed at representing young people in vulnerable situations such as ethnic minorities, LGBTI young people, young people with disabilities and those in youth care institutions. The document called for ensuring that young people, particularly those facing these challenges should be actively involved in decision-making processes and represented in the design of public policies, therefore offering young people a platform to voice their concern and shape the policies affecting them.

Examining the frequency and nature of the narratives across both axes of analysis reveals several key insights. Firstly, no policy area suggests the exclusion of any subgroup of young people or recommends limiting their political participation. Second, most of the policies analyzed propose concrete measures to enhance youth involvement, indicating a preference for proactive engagement over maintaining the status quo. Third, it is important to highlight the uneven distribution of these efforts across different policy areas. For example, while the participation policy area strongly emphasizes expanding opportunities for youth engagement, other areas, such as housing, do not feature any mention of youth participation. This is consistent with the difficulties we encountered in locating housing policies that explicitly focus on young people, underscoring a significant gap in policy attention.

The lack of a targeted youth perspective in housing policies may indicate a broader issue of underrepresentation in areas critical to young people's lives. In 2023, the average age at which individuals in the EU left their parental homes was estimated at 26.3 years³ and approximately 75% of those aged 15-29 still lived with their parents, though this varied significantly across EU member States. It is important to note that our findings are limited by the documents analyzed and do not directly address the overall legal status or rights of young people in the EU. However, what is evident from the analysis is the apparent lack

³Source: Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/yth_demo_030/default/table?lang=EN)

of consideration for their participation in housing policies. Further investigation is needed to determine whether youth participation is indeed overlooked and, if so, to advocate for more comprehensive policies that address the diverse needs of young people across all sectors. Moreover, while some policy areas did indeed include measures to involve young people in decision-making, this is not uniformly applied, particularly in sectors like as noted housing and health.

In examining now how young people are portrayed across various policy areas, we analyzed the frequency and distribution of terms in the documents, as visualized in the Word Cloud (Figure 6). Larger terms represent those most frequently mentioned, while smaller terms occur less often. Specifically, 8 out of the 25 documents analyzed referred to the general term *young people* without any further distinction or mention of intersectionality. In contrast, 4 documents distinguished young people as a broader category but implicitly acknowledged intersectionality, noting that young people are not a homogenous group; they have diverse identities, needs, resources, and backgrounds, although no specific intersections were explicitly identified.

As a consequence, a total of 12 out of the 25 documents referred to young people generally, either without mentioning intersectionality or only addressing it implicitly. Among the remaining documents, 10 explicitly addressed "thin" intersectionality, referring to young people with one additional characteristic, such as young women or young migrants. Lastly, 3 of the documents referred to "thick" intersectionality, describing young people with two or more additional characteristics, such as young migrant women.

Figure 6 : Word Cloud

It is important to note that most of the documents analyzed did acknowledge the diversity within youth populations. However, this is often done by listing various socio-demographic characteristics that could lead to discrimination or disadvantage. As reflected in the Word cloud, terms like 'disadvantaged,' 'background,' 'discrimination,' 'economic,' and 'opportunities' appear frequently. Commonly referenced groups include young women, LGBTQ+ youth, racialized youth, ethnic minorities, young people with disabilities and those from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Despite the recognition of youth diversity, a significant shortcoming is the lack of specificity in addressing the distinct needs of these groups. While the documents discuss youth diversity in broad terms, their recommendations tend to be general rather than offering targeted solutions for different subgroups. For instance, *Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States*

meeting within the Council on strengthening the multilevel governance when promoting the participation of young people in decision-making processes (D4 focused participation) indeed mentions vulnerable groups and gender inequality yet not extensively differentiate between subgroups within the youth population, and when it comes to practical points, it simply talks about increasing participation among *all young people*.

Furthermore, most documents list socio-demographic characteristics without addressing the compounded impact of intersecting forms of discrimination. While a few documents recognize the significance of multiple and intersecting identities—one highlights this complexity—most did not explore how these overlapping identities affect young people. For example, (D2 focused housing) the *Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on eradicating homelessness in the European Union* highlights various intersections such as being homeless and identifying as LGBTIQ, calling for action from EU members. However, it does not explore how the intersection of identifying as a LGBTIQ young person and part of a marginalized community can intensify vulnerabilities. On this note it must be underlined that the European Committee raises concerns not only about the lack of official EU data on (all category combined) homelessness but also about the absence of a standardized European definition of homelessness. To address this gap, it suggests that member States should adopt the ETHOS classification (European Typology on Homelessness and Housing Exclusion), which covers rooflessness, homelessness, insecure housing, and inadequate housing. Furthermore, the European Committee urges the European Commission to focus on homelessness in all relevant EU policy initiatives, including the EU Child Guarantee, EU Disability Strategy, EU LGBT Strategy, EU Gender Equality Strategy, EU Roma Framework, EU Youth Guarantee, Social Economy Action Plan, EU4Health Programme, EU Migration Pact, and the EU Affordable Housing Initiative. The concern therefore involves both the need to consider intersections, such as identifying as LGBTIQ and part of a marginalized community, and the lack of a standardized definition and reliable data on homelessness. Without these critical elements, efforts to effectively address the intersectionality and vulnerabilities of youth remain limited in scope.

Analyzed documents often did not explicitly address structural barriers encountered by young people, placing more emphasis on individual-level solutions while neglecting to consider and tackle systemic issues. For example, *Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport* (D4 education) a policy document on education suggested measures to enhance participation in the Erasmus program for those with fewer opportunities, yet did not engage with the underlying systemic inequalities that could hinder marginalized youth from accessing such opportunities as their peers. While another policy document on employment, *Motion for a resolution on empowering European youth* (D3 employment) yet acknowledged youth unemployment but lacked a comprehensive strategy to address the structural drivers of economic exclusion, such as precarious employment conditions and wage disparities.

It is important to note the limitations of our analysis due to our sampling strategies and the small sample size, as detailed in the Methods section (see 1.1. Policy Documents' selection). The results presented here are indeed influenced by these limitations and further analysis should consider a broader range of documents and more detailed exploration within each category. Moreover, the nature of the documents at the EU level needs to be understood within the broader context in which the EU operates and navigates challenges. This context may also explain why EU recommendations provide sometimes general guidance while referring to *young people* in more general terms. Specific policy recommendations can limit member states' willingness to engage with EU policies and restrict a countries ability to adapt policies to their specific circumstances (Thomann, E. and Zhelyazkova, A. 2019). Moreover, specific recommendations might face further challenges due to varying political landscape, differing priorities within member states and potential

resistance from domestic policies. Therefore, these results should be interpreted with an understand of the EU's structural context and the challenges facing the EU and its member states.

The following section provides an analysis of the documents reviewed, comparing them across policies areas across Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. It explores how policymakers in each country approach and address five critical areas—education, employment, health, housing, and participation— by examining the primary policy frameworks that inform and shape their current practices regarding young people.

1.2. National Level

Before delving into the detailed analysis, it is essential to present a frequency table summarizing the total number of documents reviewed by the research teams. A total of 147 documents were analyzed, selected in reverse chronological order starting from 2024. These documents include a variety of sources, such as laws, public programs, and government reports, all of which were chosen by each national team to examine how policymakers frame the inclusion and/or exclusion and identifying opportunities and restriction for youth participation for young people within the policy landscape. It is essential that while we used graphical comparison to aid in the interpretation and understanding of the analyzed documents, these should be viewed as guidance for the reader rather than a direct cross-countries comparison. This approach is tied to the small number of documents analyzed (147).

Country	PolicyArea	N° of Documents
CH	Education	5
CH	Employment	5
CH	Health	5
CH	Housing	5
CH	Participation	5
DK	Education	5
DK	Employment	5
DK	Health	6
DK	Housing	5
DK	Participation	3
FI	Education	5
FI	Employment	5
FI	Health	5
FI	Housing	3
FI	Participation	5
IT	Education	5
IT	Employment	5
IT	Health	5
IT	Housing	5
IT	Participation	5
PT	Education	5
PT	Employment	5
PT	Health	5
PT	Housing	5
PT	Participation	5
UK	Education	5
UK	Employment	5
UK	Health	5
UK	Housing	5
UK	Participation	5

Table 3: Frequencies Table

The Bar Chart (Figure 7) illustrates the distribution of documents across six countries (CH, DK, FI, IT, PT, and UK) and highlights two key angles of analysis: Inclusion/Exclusion (red) and Opportunities (blue) for young people overall, without considering intersections, providing a general overview. Each country's analysis is broken down into the several policy areas: education, employment, health, housing, and participation.

Figure 7

As previously stated for the European level, this first Bar Chart (see Figure 7) highlights the presence or absence of inclusion/exclusion and opportunities/restrictions in the documents analyzed. Although teams reviewed a total of 147 documents, the Bar Chart, as the following ones, only includes those that align with our dimensions of analysis. If therefore all documents contained both dimensions, there would be 5 documents for each dimension and policy area. However, when a dimension is missing, it indicates that it was not present in the reviewed documents. Moreover, at this stage, we do not yet have information about the direction (-1, 0, +1), but we can observe how these two dimensions are distributed across: countries, policy areas and analyzed documents (0-5).

As a first sight, there is considerable variation not only across countries but also across policy areas. In particular, we can observe differences in the presence of inclusion/exclusion versus opportunities/restrictions in the analyzed documents. For example, inclusion/exclusion appears more frequently than opportunities/restrictions across the countries. All countries show the presence of social inclusion/exclusion in every policy areas, with Italy and the UK leading, followed by Finland and Denmark. Switzerland has the lowest overall presence across all categories of inclusion/exclusion. When considering now the second dimension, opportunities/restrictions, we can observe that their presence is less frequent across both countries and policy fields compared to inclusion/exclusion. On this note, participation is the only policy area where opportunities are consistently present across all countries. Denmark stands out as

the country with the least presence of opportunities/restrictions, followed by Switzerland and Finland. Whereas Portugal, Italy, and the UK show similar levels of presence in this regard.

These first results at the national level give us an initial comprehension of our analysis, which will be important for further analysis. As a matter of fact, the presence or absence of inclusion and/or opportunities provides a first indicator of frequency (in terms of the number of documents) and helps us understand how this is addressed in the content. The analysis focused on the frequency and strength of inclusion and opportunity narratives across five key documents, aiming to determine whether the approach to inclusion is strong or limited. Moreover, it is important to point out that this analysis reflects the presence of current relevant policies through the two dimensions of inclusion/exclusion and opportunities/restrictions, however it does not directly address the overall legal status or rights of young people in these countries. For example, considering Denmark, where only one document addresses the presence of opportunities, it could be that opportunities for participation across policy areas are already well-established, or not. What this first analysis highlights whether policymakers take these dimensions into account when shaping policy within our sample.

Moving deeper into the analysis and considering our first dimension, social inclusion, we can now observe in the Bar Chart (Figure 8). not only the number of documents but also their direction: whether they restrict (-1, in red), maintain the status quo (0, in green), or aim to include young people (+1, in blue). Again, in the second bar chart, all young people are considered without intersections.

Figure 8

At first sight, each policy domain shows the presence of social inclusion in its respective areas. Across the policy areas, and perhaps unsurprisingly, education has the highest score, with 22 policies promoting

inclusion across all countries, followed by health, employment, participation, and finally, housing, which has 14 documents related to social inclusion. Status quo (0) is less present and mainly appears in employment and housing, with health showing the highest level of policies where the status quo is maintained: inclusion is referenced, but without any significant changes or improvements.

When it comes to exclusion (-1), housing exhibits the highest number of exclusionary policies, followed by employment and health. It is important to clarify that while some young people are excluded under these policies, the reasons behind these exclusions must be understood. In some cases, these restrictions serve a protective function, while in others, they exclude and increase vulnerabilities among young people, as seen in Denmark. Specifically, certain employment policies limit young people's access to particular types of work, but these restrictions are intended to ensure their protection and safety. For instance, (D3) excludes young people under 18 from operating heavy machinery unless they have vocational training, prioritizing protection over exclusion. Similarly, (D4) excludes those under 18 from operating construction lifts, with exceptions for those over 15 in vocational training. However, there is also an exclusionary policy, (D2), which reduces unemployment benefits for recent graduates who have not secured a job within three months, potentially increasing their vulnerability and risk of social exclusion. In the health policy areas, a similar pattern is seen. For instance, Denmark's (D1) policy implements stricter measures to prevent young people under 18 from purchasing cigarettes, e-cigarettes, and alcohol. A similar pattern can be observed in the UK with a research briefing by the independent House of Commons research team (D2) and a government Policy Paper, an initiative presented by the government to Parliament (D3). D2 aims to restrict access to vapes for those under 18, inclusion a ban on the non-nicotine vapes to minors. Whereas the initiative presented by the government (D3) discusses the possible introduction of legislation to prohibit anyone born on or after January 1st 2009 from purchasing tobacco products. Considering these exclusions, though designed with a protective intention, it still restricts the inclusion by limiting young people's rights compared to other groups in the population.

Taking a closer look at the health policies, nearly one-third of the documents analyzed across countries are linked to mental health documents. In the specific, this includes as previously mentioned Denmark (D2 and D6), Finland (D3 and D4), Italy (*Provisions and Delegation to the Government on the Prevention and Fight against Bullying and Cyberbullying* (D1) and *National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee: Health* (D4)), Portugal (*Programa Cuida-te+ Portaria 258/2019* (D1), *Gerações Mais Saudáveis: Políticas Públicas de Promoção da Saúde das Crianças e Jovens em Portugal (Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2018* (D2)), the UK (*Children and young people's mental health: policy and services (England)* –(D1) and *Mental Health Act Reform - Children and Young People-* D5) and Switzerland (*Mental Health of Children and Young People: Stepping Up Prevention and Guaranteeing Access to Care* (D1). Mental health also appears as a cross-cutting theme in other policy areas, such as in employment and in education (for example see further details in the UNIMAN National Report UK in employment policy areas D3 and in educational D2). It is interesting to note how these policy areas are present across countries within a specific time frame, possibly reflecting the impact of post-Covid consequences on young people and how national policies try to address them. Others recurring themes echoed several countries, as smoking bans, which are mentioned in Switzerland (*Fully Protect Children and Young People from Tobacco Advertising* (D2) and *Message concerning the amendment of the Federal Law on Tobacco Taxation* (D3) and the UK as Finland (D1).

Turning now the high number of exclusionary policies in housing, we can point out several examples. For instance, in Denmark, (D1) a law was introduced allowing staff in foster or institutional care to confiscate drugs, alcohol, and electronic devices, such as phones and gaming consoles, if deemed necessary for the

young person's well-being. In Portugal, there are four documents addressing the first angle of analysis - inclusion/exclusion - and among them, one implies a process of exclusion. In the specific, (D4) is a decree-law aimed at facilitating homeownership for young people up to 35. While the law acknowledges the challenges posed by rising housing prices and offers guarantees to credit institutions, it restricts eligibility to those with incomes below a certain threshold and excludes young people who already own property. As a result, the measure excludes unemployed youth, higher earners, and property owners, limiting its scope to a narrow section of the youth population despite its broader intent to improve access to housing. Finally, in the UK both documents (D2 and D5) illustrate exclusionary policies. The first document (D2), a House of Lords article, outlines the issues and government policies ahead of a debate on young people's housing needs, emphasizing how rising prices and the discontinuation of the Help to Buy ISA in 2019 have further excluded young people from homeownership. Similarly, D5 sets government guidelines on Housing Benefit eligibility, excluding full-time students from receiving housing support, further marginalizing a specific group of young people based on their student status. Finally, although not an exclusionary document, Switzerland has only one document in this area of analysis, and it was scored as a status quo. The report, commissioned by the Federal Office for Housing, *Homelessness in Switzerland: Understandings, Policies, and Strategies of the Cantons and Communes*, found that cantonal awareness of people at risk of homelessness rarely, if ever, mentions children, young people or young women who face specific vulnerabilities. While the report highlighted the exclusion of these children, young people and young women, it does not address this issue in its recommendations (See National UNIGE Report).

These examples from our sampling offer an initial insight into how current housing policies across different countries may exclude specific groups of young people. Moreover, it must be noted that housing policies are mainly absent in the second dimension of our analysis, namely the opportunities for participation as illustrated by the Bar Chart (Figure 9). Most of the research teams had indicated their difficulties finding relevant documents (for both axes of analysis). In the specific, for the Finnish case, the team observed that only three documents related to housing were included as housing policy in Finland is primarily a local-level responsibility and not a prominent policy topic (See National UTU Report). Within the three documents analysed, two did not contain specific policy measures. The most relevant document for the analysis was the "*Housing Policy Development Program for the Years 2021–2028*" (2021). The second one, "*Housing for Students? Survey on the Current State and Production Needs of Student Housing*" (2018) was not inclusive because although it focused on the development and evaluation of student housing it failed to address the diversity of youth or the needs of different youth groups (See National UTU Report).

For the Italian case, the team pointed out that housing policies was challenging due to their short-term, annual nature and either vague or technical details (See National UNIBO Report). This complexity led to the exclusion of relevant documents like the *Decreto Sostegni bis* (2021), which provides subsidies for first-time home purchases for youth. Moreover, as the *Italia Generativa* (2023) report highlighted that Italian policies lack a long-term perspective and are often based on yearly financial aids. Overall, housing policies were integrated into broader strategies to address marginalization and poverty, with recent focus on residential services for unaccompanied foreign minors and care leavers, and university housing (See National UNIBO Report). For the Swiss case, it must be mentioned that of the documents analysed (D2), commissioned by the Federal Office for Housing. This report noted that cantonal knowledge about people at risk of homelessness rarely, if ever, mentions young people or women. In particular, young women are rarely recognized for their specific vulnerabilities. Although the report recognized the exclusion of young people, particularly young women, it does not pursue this recognition in its recommendations. Furthermore, it did not address participation opportunities for young people. In Switzerland, the concept of homelessness had

not been legally defined, and there is no universal legal right to housing in the Federal Constitution (See National UNIGE Report). The first national report on homelessness (see *Homelessness in Switzerland*) had only recently been published, revealing a lack of comprehensive data and a gap in policy on youth inclusion. Finally, in the UK case—the only country with a document offering opportunities for young people to participate (D1)— the team underlined how access to housing has been a central topic in the national debate on intergenerational inequality (See National UNIMAN Report). The dominant focus of the policies was on youth homelessness (D1 and D3). In the specific, D1, the Debate Pack, prepared by the House of Commons research team, provides MPs with data on youth homelessness and an overview of current legislation and government policy. It outlined measures aimed at supporting young people at risk of homelessness and helping local authorities tailor interventions to specific groups. By highlighting several categories of at-risk youth, the document demonstrates an awareness of how intersecting lived experiences shape opportunities for young people. It also noted the continuation of funding for a programme that ensures the voices of young homeless people are heard, signaling opportunities for participation. Although this is a critical public concern, the policies identified deal only with extreme cases, positioning young people as "vulnerable" or "at risk" rather than addressing broader systemic barriers to accessing affordable, independent housing (See National UNIMAN Report). The most positive housing-related policy was aimed at young Ukrainian refugees under the 'Homes for Ukraine' scheme. However, while youth-friendly, it only addresses a small group, and the scheme itself shifts the responsibility for refugee housing from the state to individual citizens (See National UNIMAN Report).

Figure 9

Across all countries, participation policies represent the most significant area of expansion in terms of engaging young people. Portugal stands out as the country with the most documents offering broader opportunities for youth participation, across all categories considered (10). On this note, when considering

documents in the participation area, all documents seek to promote young people's civic and political engagement by creating channels for active involvement. As a matter of fact, each analyzed document focuses on empowering young people to shape policies and participate in democratic life through various forms of governmental support. For example, *Orçamento Participativo* (D1) regulates the Youth Participatory Budget, enabling young people aged 14-30 to submit and vote on community projects, aimed at combating disengagement from political participation. A program which promotes active citizenship among youth through financial support. In a similar way, *Regime Jurídico do Associativismo Jovem e Programa de Apoio Juvenil* (D3) provides not only financial aid but also technical, formative, and logistical support to youth associations to help them operate effectively. Finally, *Regime Jurídico dos Conselhos Municipais de Juventude* (D5) establishes the legal framework for Municipal Youth Councils, defining their roles and responsibilities in shaping youth-related policies and ensuring their representation in local decision-making processes (See National U.PORTO Report).

The second countries that stand out with the most documents offering broader opportunities for youth participation are the UK and Italy. Both have nine documents focused on broadening or supporting youth participation. The UK is the only country within the policy area to have documents evaluated as maintaining the status quo (0), specifically *Political Disengagement in the UK* (D4) and *National Youth Guarantee* (D5). The UNIMAN research team highlighted an absence of any national-level policies directly aimed at promoting youth participation (see National UNIMAN Report). Among the analyzed documents, those rated +1 tended to focus more on reporting rather than implementing long-term strategies, with references to programs designed to increase young people's political engagement. In the specific, *Government secures future of UK Youth Parliament* (D1) focused on securing the future of the UK Youth Parliament by appointing the National Youth Agency after the collapse of the British Youth Council. While the document emphasized the importance of including young people in representing peer views, no new opportunities for participation are introduced, merely preserving the existing system. *We all have a voice': Disabled children's vision for change* (D2) centered on the voices of disabled children in anticipation of the government's Disability Action Plan. It highlighted inclusion by representing disabled children alongside other intersecting categories. It is important to be noted that thousands of children, young people, and parents, including those with disabilities, contributed to the report, highlighting opportunities for disabled youth to have their voices heard. Finally, *Youth Engagement Impact Study* (D3) advocates for expanding inclusion by broadening access to youth engagement programs. It underscores the intersection of factors such as class, rural residence, age, ethnic background, status (e.g., NEET), and special educational needs, all of which affect opportunities for youth participation (see National UNIMAN Report).

Considering now Italy, opportunities for participation predominantly center around volunteering (see National UNIBO Report). The team highlighted that youth participation in civic and political spheres is addressed through specific policies, with a particular emphasis on volunteering. For example, the Universal Civil Service serves as a key tool in the country's youth participation policy (*Three-Year Plan for the Programming of the Universal Civil Service 2023-2025*, D2). Additionally, the *Regulation concerning the approval of the Statute of the Italian Youth Agency* (D1) highlighted the renewal of an agency dedicated to promoting active citizenship, further demonstrates this focus. The team evaluated it as expanding opportunities for participation, particularly through its role in promoting volunteering programs and supporting civil society organizations for youth. Other documents focused on specific intersections involving young people, for example in the *National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee: Governance* (D4), which emphasized minors' active involvement, and *5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents 2022-2023: Policies for Empowerment* (D5), which targeted children and adolescences.

Moreover, another key aspect of participation concerning minorities is reflected in *National Strategy for Equality, Inclusion and Participation of Roma and Sinti 2021-2030* (D3), (See National UNIBO Report).

Our second dimension of analysis - opportunities to participation- is nearly absent in both Denmark and Switzerland. As highlighted by the AAU team, none of the documents lead to either an expansion or restriction of participation opportunities for young people on a broader scale, with the exception of one law (D1). This law reserves two seats on the board of Sorø Akademi for its pupils. While similar rules for student participation exist in other schools, this policy only applies to the pupils of this particular school (See National Report AAU).

Considering the Swiss documents analyzed, a total of seven address youth participation, with most falling under the participation policy area, while the remainder are linked to education (D2 and D3). Within the participation area, several key initiatives are highlighted: D1 proposed improvements in school curricula while also recommending the promotion of youth involvement in associations; D2 emphasized the need to strengthen digital forms of participation to enable political engagement for young people with social anxiety or reduced mobility; D3 supported the proposal by the Federal Commission for Children and Youth to allow the Youth Session and Children's Conference to submit their petitions and proposals to relevant committees. Practical measures outlined in D4 include the creation of time-limited, easily accessible opportunities, the strengthening of digital participation, and the use of simple, understandable language. Finally, D5 encouraged youth involvement in the entire process of initiating, planning, and implementing activities, offering financial support for model projects that promote participation in extracurricular activities and political engagement at the federal level (See National CH Report). Finally, Finland follows a similar pattern to Switzerland when considering this second dimension of analysis, with the addition of one extra document focused on health (D5). In the participation area, each document addressing this theme included methods for politically engaging youth, with concrete proposals for participation tools presented extensively (See National FI Report).

While participation policies vary scope and focus across countries, each country underscores the importance of considering diverse and (more) accessible opportunities for engagement for young people. It is now crucial to explore who these policies are being framed for, as the following section will offer an initial picture into this analysis.

1.2.1 Young people: how are they portrayed ?

In total, we have 147 documents that address various aspects of young people. Among these, 45 documents refer to *young people in general*, without any specific mention of intersectionality. In contrast, 16 documents treat young people as a heterogeneous group while implicitly acknowledging the presence of intersectionality. Yet, these references do not go into detail about which specific intersections are involved or how they operate. Finally, a significant number of documents, for a total of 81, refer to at least one or more intersections. The Bar Chart (Figure 10) provides a first visual representation of these frequencies, highlighting the varying levels of intersectional engagement across the documents analyzed in the six different countries.

Figure 10

Considering all policy areas combined, the distribution of how young people are portrayed reveals different patterns in how documents refer to young people. In some countries, documents more frequently refer to young people in general, without specifying intersectional categories. In contrast, other countries have documents that more often refer to young people with one or more intersections, indicating a more detailed classification of their identities or social categories, greater emphasis on young people with more than one intersectional factor, highlighting a more detailed approach to inclusion. In the specific, countries such as Portugal, Finland, Italy, and the United Kingdom tend to emphasize multiple intersections when referring to young people. In contrast, Denmark, and Switzerland more often provide general references to young people, with Portugal and Denmark also including implicit mentions of intersectionality. Finally, this implicit category is entirely absent in the case of Switzerland.

As teams documented the groups referenced in each policy document, it allowed for capturing a broad overview of which groups were explicitly mentioned. The Word Cloud (Figure 11) provides a visual representation of the most frequently referenced terms, with "young people" being the most prominent, as previously indicated. In addition to this general category, more specific groups stand out, such as "children", and "young people with disabilities" and "Special Education needs and Disabilities (SEND)".

Figure 11: Word Cloud

The intersection of youth and education also is dominant, with frequent references to groups such as “students”, “international students” and “pupils”. Additionally, specific attention is given to youth in foster care, young people under 18 years old, homeless youth, and young LGBTQ people. Interestingly, the Word Cloud (Figure 11) appears to reference to vulnerable groups, though the emphasis appears to be placed more on the circumstances surrounding these groups than on the groups themselves. Terms such as “risk,” “disadvantaged,” and “economic background” seems to suggest a focus on the socio-economic and educational contexts in which young people are positioned.

Now, going further into the details and incorporating to our analysis the policies areas in which young people were mentioned, we can observe the following two graphs. The first Graph (Figure 12) illustrates the analysis from the dimension of inclusion versus exclusion, based on the average coding of policies for each country (see Section 1.3: Overall Approach for more details). This graph specifically highlights the intersections of at least two intersecting categories (e.g. young women). The size of each point in the graph corresponds to the number of documents that address both inclusion and exclusion, offering a visual representation of how frequently these concepts are considered. This allows us to assess whether the narrative is sporadic (e.g., in just one out of five documents) or more pervasive (e.g., present in the majority or all documents). For instance, the larger the point, the more documents reflect themes of inclusion, highlighting how policies frame opportunities or restrictions for specific groups of young people. Each country is represented by a distinct color: Denmark (DK) in yellow, Finland (FI) in green, Italy (IT) in light blue, Portugal (PT) in dark blue, Switzerland (CH) in red, and United Kingdom (UK) in pink-purple.

Figure 12: Graph 1

Considering education and participation areas, we can observe that all countries have an inclusive approach (as all the countries are aligned in the 1 of the mean direction), though the extent of intersectionality varies across nations. This variation is not only reflected in the number of documents addressing intersectionality but also in the depth to which these intersecting categories are explored. For instance, Denmark (DK) provides two documents with inclusive educational policies (D1 and D3), though only *LOV nr 685 af 11/06/2024: Lov om ændring af SU-loven* explicitly addresses more than one intersectional category. This document outlines a policy in which students typically receive a stipend for 58 months (about five years, covering both bachelor's and master's degrees). However, students with special circumstances—such as disabled students and single parents—are eligible for an additional 12 months, totaling 70 months of financial support (See National Report AAU).

Countries such as Finland (FI), Italy (IT), and the United Kingdom (UK) show a higher degree of intersectionality in their documents on educational policies. This is reflected in the broad range of intersecting categories addressed from the more expected groups, such as pupils and students, to more specific ones, including: young people with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (present in all UK documents), SEND pupils from disadvantaged economic backgrounds; pupils with mental ill-health, to youth who students who speak foreign languages; students belonging to religious communities; foreign students, young students LGBT+, minors in conditions of absolute poverty. These countries are positioned higher, reflecting their stronger emphasis on inclusivity for diverse groups of students with overlapping identities, as highlighted in the analyzed documents. Although not immediately apparent from this first Graph, Switzerland (CH) also appears among the overlapping countries. However, it only has one document

addressing inclusion, specifically focusing on young women students. This singular document could suggest that Switzerland's document on educational policies may not consider the multiple identities that can influence a student's access to education as comprehensively as other countries do. Finally, in Portugal, all five documents are inclusive, with most addressing two intersecting categories such as economically underprivileged students, displaced students, immigrant students, young women and men, students with dyslexia, and students with speech impairments. These documents highlight the importance of addressing the needs of children and young students at intersectional positions, whether due to gender, socioeconomic background, nationality, or physical and/or psychological limitations (see National Report U.PORTO).

Unlike the education policy area, in the participation area, we observe countries following very similar patterns, with most having inclusive policies for young people that also address at least two intersecting categories. As stated by the UTU team, policy documents on youth participation, which included a focus on various intersectional groups like ethnic minorities and LGBTQ+ youth, methods for political engagement were thoroughly covered. However, the internal diversity within youth groups was less emphasized. For instance, documents from Sanna Marin's government (2019-2023) addressed minority groups and adopted an intersectional approach in 'The Youth, Peace, and Security Action Plan.' Finland's governmental policy documents reflect an awareness of the diverse experiences, identities, and aspirations of youth. The recognition of various intersectional groups highlights the multifaceted nature of youth identities. These policies frequently acknowledge the different backgrounds and needs of immigrant youth, marginalized groups, and those facing social exclusion. Additionally, youth requiring extra support, youth in child protection, and NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) youth are repeatedly mentioned in the documents (See National UTU Report). The UNIBO team observed that while many policies address social inclusion and frequently acknowledge differences in access and experience among young people, they often focus on specific social disadvantages with positive actions aimed at promoting equality. Moreover, the team suggested that this results in a fragmented framework that either treats young people as a homogenous, disadvantaged group with little attention to specific identity dimensions or addresses various forms of disadvantage as separate issues or prerequisites for accessing support for inclusion and integration. Policies on more specific topics, such as LGBTQIA+ inclusion, addiction, or Roma and Sinti people, often place youth concerns in the background, with fewer and less targeted actions, particularly in the health sector. This fragmented approach fails to fully address the barriers preventing young people from achieving full social and political agency (see National Report UNIBO).

We can observe much more variation in both the health and housing sectors. For example, for the UK most analyzed documents in health policies considered the inclusion of young people only in general terms, followed by Denmark. Considering Switzerland and Finland, although both countries rank high in inclusive policies with intersectionality, it is important to highlight a nuance. In Switzerland, health documents discussed the impact of discrimination on the mental health of young people, identifying various forms such as racism, sexism, and homophobia. However, the policies opted for general prevention measures against discrimination, rather than proposing targeted actions. Additionally, only two documents addressed an inclusive policy with two intersecting categories. While Finland across all health-related policy programs, apart from one document, efforts were consistently made to enhance youth inclusion. As pointed out by the team, each document considered various youth groups, and intersectional groups were mentioned multiple times in relation to inclusion. The groups referenced were diverse, including young people in different educational settings, young girls and boys, socially disadvantaged youth (such as those from low-

income backgrounds), representatives of minority groups (LGBTQ+ and ethnic minorities), and other young people in vulnerable situations (See National Report UTU).

The second graph (Figure 13) follows a similar approach from the first Graph (Figure 12), but this time it focuses on opportunities for participation versus restrictions on participation, representing the second axis of our analysis. This comparison provides a clearer understanding of how policies either broaden or limit the participation of young people, particularly those with at least two intersecting categories. The size of each point in the graph corresponds to the number of documents that address both opportunities and restrictions, visually representing how frequently these dimensions are considered. For instance, larger points indicate a greater number of documents reflecting these themes, offering insights into how analyzed policies documents considers participation for different groups. As in the first graph, the colors representing each country remain the same.

Figure 13

It is important to note, as previously mentioned, that unlike the first graph (Figure 12), the opportunities dimension is less prominent in both countries and areas. The most significant policy area here is participation, both in terms of the number of documents and the opportunities offered for youth involvement. However, there are fewer instances of intersectionality within these policies than for the first dimension of analysis. Taking into account DK, as pointed out by the team, two policies were aimed at ensuring disabled young people to participate in special summer camps which may empower them to lead more autonomous lives, and one policy aimed to empower young people at risk of committing crimes by giving them the right to have a “pocket money-job”(see National Report AAU). Interestingly, in Portugal most of the documents although increasing possibility to participate among young people most usually

referred to *young people* in general. The U.PORTO team suggested that these national policies, in their effort to reflect universality, perhaps tended to target young people in general. This approach may have led to the lack of explicit mention of the need to include specific segments of Portuguese youth (see National Report U.PORTO).

On the opposite end, housing policies show limited presence, with only Italy and the UK having relevant documents. Italy's document offers broader opportunities for young people but refers to them in general terms, emphasizing a participatory approach through existing youth networks without addressing specific groups (D3). In contrast, the UK focuses on selected young homeless individuals, addressing at least two intersections, though the policy largely maintains the status quo.

In the final graph (Figure 14), it is possible to observe the intersection between our two dimensions of analysis - inclusion and opportunities – where analyzed documents are present in both categories. Moreover, unlike the previous Graphs, this analysis combines all categories of young people. Each country is represented by a distinct color: Denmark (DK) in yellow, Finland (FI) in green, Italy (IT) in light blue, Portugal (PT) in dark blue, Switzerland (CH) in red, and United Kingdom (UK) in pink-purple. At first sight, we can observe fewer documents across countries compared to the earlier graphs, highlighting the limited presence on addressing both dimensions within the analyzed documents. Additionally, there are notable differences among countries. Moreover, all six countries show the presence of both dimensions in Education and Participation. As expected, Housing is the policy area with the least representation, appearing only in Italy and the UK. Whereas Health and Employment display similar patterns but involving different countries.

Figure 14

Figure 16

Each local region shows a different approach while framing young people in the analyzed documents. For example, Vantaa, Espoo, Turku, and Oulu (FI) show a strong tendency to address young people by considering one or more intersections. In the specific, UTU team underlined how, apart from a document from Vantaa (D1), all local analysed documents recognized various youth groups. It appeared that at the local level, young people and different youth groups were addressed more concretely and specifically than in governmental-level documents. For instance, the UTU team pointed out that youth from diverse language and cultural backgrounds, immigrant youth, and youth with special needs were highlighted several times in the documents of different cities (See National Report UTU).

Local regions as Geneva (CH) and the Municipalities of Arcos de Valdevez, Porto, Santa Maria da Feira and Pombal (PT) had as well an overall strong presence of documents mentioning young people with one or more intersections. In contrast, Copenhagen City Council (DK) and Emilia-Romagna region (IT), have higher counts of addressing young people in general terms. In the specific, in the case of Copenhagen City (DK), AAU team pointed out that one document addressed young people without citizenship, one young Jewish people, and one addressed financially challenged young people. Thus, the policies only framed few marginalized positions among young people (See National Report AAU). Whereas for Emilia-Romagna region (IT), the UNIBO team underlined that nearly all of the participation documented referred to youth as a general category. When specific identities or intersections were mentioned (e.g., gender and sexual orientation, NEET or disadvantaged youth), it was either not related to youth, or it was done in a very limited. In only one case, a couple actions of the guidelines were specifically aimed at improving participation of youth with a migration background (See National Report UNIBO).

The Greater Manchester Combined Authority (UK), the Municipalities of Arcos de Valdevez, Porto, Santa Maria da Feira and Pombal (PT), followed by Geneva (CH) show higher score where young people are implicitly mentioned in relation to intersectionality. Considering more in details the analysis of GMCA, the UNIMAN team indicated a strong awareness to barriers faced by young people, such as transport costs that might hinder access to employment, training and participations in various cultural activities. For example, the UNIMAN team pointed out *Our Pass* (D5) which provided free bus travel for 16–18-year-olds across the

city region as well as a range of other benefits, therefore recognizing a commitment to include young people (See National Report UNIMAN).

As different teams could select two out of the five policy areas, comparing analyzed documents at the local level presents greater challenge. Therefore, for our next analysis we focus on the policy areas common to all teams: participation, with a total of 30 documents analyzed from local contexts.

The following Bar Charts (Figure 17 and Figure 18) show the distribution of documents across six local regions: Copenhagen City Council, for Denmark; Vantaa, Espoo, Turku, and Oulu, for Finland; the Emilia-Romagna region, for Italy, the Municipalities of Arcos de Valdevez, Porto, Santa Maria da Feira and Pombal for Portugal; the canton of Geneva, for Switzerland; and the Greater Manchester Combined Authority (GMCA) for the United Kingdom. As seen at the European level and at the national level, the Bar Chart (Figure 17 and Figure 18) highlight the presence of inclusion/exclusion and opportunities/restrictions for young people overall, without considering intersections in the documents analyzed. At this stage, we are able to identify in which direction the policy documents aimed (-1, 0, +1) and how there are distributed across local regions. Interestingly, there is little variation across local regions. In particular, with the exception of Geneva and Copenhagen city, all other local regions consider, in the analyzed documents, inclusion and offer broader opportunities. This is the case for the local region of FI, IT, PT and the UK. For instance, the UTU team in Finland focused on youth welfare, equality, and equity plans, which are mandatory for municipalities. Across all cities, there was a clear focus on enhancing inclusivity, particularly in participation. City-level policies were more explicit and detailed than national-level documents, offering specific suggestions like youth councils, participatory budgeting, and direct youth involvement in decision-making. These local policies often included clear action plans and timelines, highlighting a stronger commitment to operationalizing inclusivity and youth participation at the municipal level (See National Report UTU).

Figure 17

Figure 18

This echoes what UNIMAN team pointed out in the local analysis, underlying that references to ‘empowerment’ were more prevalent in policies focused on ‘participation,’ highlighting a strong emphasis on youth voice and empowerment particularly evident at the local level compared to the national one (See National Report UNIMAN). Similarly, the UPORTO team found that local policies on Participation differ from national ones. Local policies focused more on including young people from diverse genders, geographic areas, and socioeconomic backgrounds, while national policies address broader societal issues. UPORTO suggested that this contrast may be due to the different scopes of national versus local policies, with local documents providing broader recommendations and national ones focusing on specific regulations (See National Report UPORTO). Although UNIBO team pointed out that all analyzed documents in the Participation policy area did indeed include and broader the opportunities to participate, interestingly in their case, most documents referred to young people as a general category without addressing specific cases or complexities. An intersectional approach was not adopted, and references to specific identities (e.g., gender, sexual orientation, NEET, or disadvantaged youth) were more vague and lacked concrete actions (See UNIBO National Report).

Geneva (CH) features the higher number of local level documents that largely reflect the status quo. On this note, it is important to point out that the majority of these documents were proposals for laws, projects or amendments, highlighting the current debates among policymakers but without significantly altering the existing conditions for young people. Interestingly, as it the case for others local regions, local policies tend to be more specific an action oriented, as proposal to lower the voting age (D3) or extend protections for young refugees (D5). Moreover, young people are considered an heterogenous group, represented by for example: age (14 up to 21 years old), professional and educational backgrounds (D1), status as students (D2), age, citizenship’s status and residency status in Geneva (D3), their citizenship status, socioeconomic background, and social benefits (D4) or unaccompanied minor refugees (D5).

Finally, only one document restricted and excluded young people and it can be found in the Copenhagen City Council (*Borgerrepræsentationen, 30.05.2024: Forespørgsel til børne- og ungdomsborgmesteren om styrkelse af ungeinddragelse i Københavns Kommune - D3*). AAU team pointed out that the document is a request in addressing the 20% cutbacks of Copenhagen’s Youth Council’s yearly budget, which is expected to harm the democratic participation of young people. While the mayor seemed to downplay the impact, AAU team underlined the possible negative effect on the cutbacks on young people’s opportunities for engagement in the city’s political life (See AAU National Report).

It is essential to consider and underline the limitations of the analysis, as the number of documents represents a small sample size, and a comparison at the local level are particularly challenging. Consequently, this provides only a general overview of how young people are framed across different documents analyzed within a specific time frame. We invite the reader to explore the national reports included in the deliverable for a deeper understanding of the context and, more important, of the documents analyzed. This approach provides valuable insights across all three levels examined in the deliverable.

CONCLUSION

While it is not surprising to scholars and to citizens that European democracies often prioritize the interests of older and more powerful groups over younger and marginalized citizens, the key issue here was if and how this tendency is translated into policy an analysis of policy documents. In the specific, this Subtasks 4.1.1.1 examined how this potential bias affects the portrayal and treatment of young people in policymaking. Moreover, this is particularly important considering that in 2023, young people all category combined aged 15 to 29 were the 16.2% of the UE population, representing 72'827'000 young people⁴.

Drawing inspiration from the intersectional methodological tools present in the first deliverable (SINCROny 2024: 14, 45), we sought to apply an intersectional lens, shedding light in the complexities and contexts in which power dynamics operate. In the specific, this approach helped us to better understand if diverse groups of young people experiencing life in democratic societies were mentioned and when it was the case, in which policy documents. It is however crucial to acknowledge the methodological limits that are present in this deliverable, including spanning from the limited sample size, the selection criteria for policy documents and the inherent difficulties in making a document cross country comparison. These challenges, further elaborate in the Methodological section, underline the limitations of our analysis. We aimed to adopt an intersectional perspective where possible, by for example identifying and highlighting the youth specific groups mentioned within the analyzed documents. However, the scope remains limited, as applying an intersectional lens is inherently more complex and requires a deeper analysis. We therefore invite the reader to further explore the national reports included in the deliverable for a deeper understanding of the context and, more important, of the documents analyzed. This approach provides valuable insights across all three levels examined in the deliverable despite the noted limitations.

The analysis of policy documents from the European level and countries, across five policies domains as Education, Employment, Health, Housing and Participation, reveals some preliminary findings. First, the analysis across EU level, national and local levels reveals commonalities and as well differences in addressing young people inclusion and opportunities to participation. EU level policy documents generally emphasize inclusion of young people particularly within employment, education and participation. However, the level of commitment varies by sector. While some analyzed policy documents, such as those in employment, focus significantly on inclusion, others, like housing and health, often lack a concrete or targeted solutions for the marginalized youth. Considering our second dimensions, opportunities to participate, beyond the expected focus in the participation domain, some policies in education and health also consider involving young people in decision making process. For instance, *the Conclusion of Council and Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to mental health of young people* (D4 health-focused document) emphasized the need to include young people in the development of public mental health programs, particularly those aimed at representing young people in vulnerable situations such as ethnic minorities, LGBTI young people, young people with disabilities and those in youth care institutions. The document called for ensuring that young people, particularly those facing these challenges should be actively involved in decision-making processes and represented in the design of public policies, therefore offering young people a platform to voice their concern and shape the policies affecting them.

⁴Source : Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/yth_demo_020/default/table?lang=EN)

Unlike national policies and local ones, no analyzed document suggests the exclusion of any youth groups nor limits their political participation. It is important however to highlight the uneven distribution of efforts across different policy areas. For example, while the participation policy area strongly emphasizes expanding opportunities for youth engagement, other areas, such as housing, do not feature any mention of youth participation. This is consistent with the difficulties we encountered in locating housing policies that explicitly focus on young people, underscoring a significant gap in policy attention.

Taking a closer look at how young people are framed in the policy documents, there was the acknowledgement that young people are not a homogenous group, often highlighting the diversity within youth populations, recognizing intersections of identity, such as gender, migration background, and socio-economic status. However, despite this recognition, there is often only a broad mention of these intersections, with little detail about how intersecting identities could shape specific challenges or experiences of exclusion, indicating a broader focus on diversity rather than a deeper engagement with intersectionality.

Considering now policy documents countries comparisons, the analysis of 147 policy documents across six countries from Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, highlights varying approaches to *young people* inclusion and opportunities for participation across the five key policy areas. Inclusion is more frequently addressed than opportunities to participation, with education policies leading in promoting inclusion, followed by health and employment. Housing policy documents, in contrast, show a higher number of exclusionary measures, especially regarding access to housing and benefits for certain youth groups (e.g., students, young people with higher incomes). Differently from the EU level, there are presence of exclusionary measures such as restricting access to tobacco or limiting certain job types for young people under 18. Housing policies documents had as well restricted access to housing benefit for full time student.

At the national level, documents referred to young people in various ways, with 45 of the 147 analyzed documents referring to youth in general, without considering intersectionality. However, a significant portion (81 documents) recognizes at least one intersection (e.g., gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status), highlighting the understanding that youth is not a homogenous group. It is important to underline that the approach to framing young people as an heterogeneous groups varies among documents, with some countries addressing young people in general terms and others incorporating multiple identities when discussion inclusion or opportunities to participate. This pattern is more evident at the local level, where some documents are more specific and detailed compared to those at the national level. Participation policies also differ significantly, with many promoting active citizenship through youth councils, volunteering, and participatory budgeting. However, national-level policies often are less targeted towards vulnerable groups and are notably absent in critical areas like housing.

As mentioned throughout the deliverable, it is essential to underlined that our analysis has several and important limitation. Firstly, it focuses only on documents explicitly mentioning 'young people,' potentially overlooking policies where youth might be implicitly addressed. Secondly, reviewing documents in reverse chronological order may also introduce bias towards recent policy trends, missing historical shifts in how youth are considered. Thirdly, the limited sample size emphasizes visible references to youth, potentially missing contexts where youth are impacted. Fourthly, we further emphasis further research to adopt an intersectional approach which can enable the understanding how structural conditions and identity factors

are intertwined and inseparable. This perspective goes beyond simply adding various social categories together; it can help recognize how these aspects interact and shape one another, influencing the experiences of young people in multifaceted ways. A nuanced understanding of these interactions is crucial for creating policies that reflect the diverse realities of youth. More generally we want to stress how it is essential to consider dynamics of power when drafting laws or public policies that affect young people, as the meanings and experiences of class, level of education, migration background, race, gender, and disability status can vary significantly depending on the legal or policy framework.

REPORT EUROPEAN UNION (UNIGE)

Introduction

In 2023, there were 72'827'000 people aged between 15 and 29 in the European Union 5, representing 16.2% of the EU population.⁶ The following sections highlight the main challenges faced by these young people in five policy areas: participation, education, employment, health and housing.

Participation

Looking ahead to the upcoming European elections, the report of the European commission "youth and democracy" (2024) reveals that 64% of young EU citizens express their intention to vote, while a mere 3% have decided not to participate. Education plays a pivotal role in shaping these voting intentions: 72% of those with postsecondary or higher education plan to vote, compared to 55% of those with secondary education or lower.

Regarding participation, over the past year, 48% of young Europeans declare to have taken concrete actions to effect societal change, such as signing petitions, participating in rallies, or contacting politicians. However, the rate of participation varies significantly across EU Member States, with Romania showing the highest level of engagement at 57%, while Cyprus, Luxembourg, and Sweden report the lowest levels, ranging from 31% to 34%. Moreover, individuals with post-secondary or higher education (42%) were significantly more likely to have participated in social change efforts than those with only a secondary education or less (35%). Additionally, the study notes that 64% of young people have been involved in organizational activities over the past 12 months, with young men participating at higher rates than young women. (European Commission, Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, et al., 2024).

Education

The COVID-19 pandemic has created an unprecedented disruption in the education and training systems across the EU. This disruption has highlighted and, in some cases, exacerbated existing inequalities, particularly affecting students from disadvantaged backgrounds (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, European Commission, 2021).

The rate of early school leavers has been on a decline over the past decade but remains above the EU's target of less than 9% with an average of 9.9% across the EU countries (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, European Commission, 2021). There are notable disparities, with higher dropout rates among young men (11.8%) compared to women (8%). Additionally, foreign-born students and those living in rural areas are more likely to leave school early, indicating significant regional and demographic inequalities (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, European Commission, 2021).

Migrant students and those from ethnic minorities, such as the Roma, face significant barriers to educational success. These groups are more likely to underachieve and have higher dropout rates. The challenges faced by these students have been compounded by the pandemic, which has made access to education even more difficult for vulnerable populations (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, European Commission, 2021).

⁵ Source : Eurostat

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjangroup_custom_12686529/default/table?lang=en

⁶Source : Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/yth_demo_020/default/table?lang=EN)

Employment

In June 2024, 2.831 million people with less than 25 years old were unemployed in the European Union.⁷ Moreover, young people are nearly twice as likely to be forced to work with temporary contracts because they could not find a permanent job (European Commission. Statistical Office of the European Union., 2022) and seem to be more inclined than the rest of the population to have strong fears about their job situation (Eurofound et al., 2022).

Economic restrictions and job losses due to Covid led to a rise in the number of young people neither in employment nor education or training (NEET), which reached 13.8% in 2020. Since 2021, however the NEET rate has been on a steady decline, reaching 11.2% in 2023.⁸ The NEET rate among young women in the EU remains a particular concern. In 2020, 15.5% of young women aged 15–29 was classified as NEET, and although this rate has decreased to 12.5% in 2023, it still exceeds the 10.1% rate for young men.⁹ In almost all Member States, young women, particularly young mothers, are more likely to be NEET due to family responsibilities.

Health

Given that age is an important predictor of physical health, it is not surprising that younger individuals report the highest rates of general health compared to other age groups (European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, 2024).

However, the number of young people struggling with mental health issues is notably high. A report by the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (2024) indicates that nearly half (46%) of young people surveyed have experienced emotional or psychosocial issues, such as depression or anxiety, within the past year. These issues are more common among young women, with 55% reporting such problems, compared to 38% of young men. Conversely, young men are 2.1 times more likely than young women to develop a substance use disorder. Factors like lower education levels and economic difficulties are associated with psychological conditions such as depression and anxiety (European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, 2024).

Housing

In the EU in 2023, the average age at which people left their parental home was estimated at 26.3 years.¹⁰ Around 75% of those aged 15-29 still lived with their parents, although this varied significantly across Member States. For instance, in Sweden, 31% of young people lived with their parents, whereas in Malta, the figure was 95% (Eurofound, 2024).

According to a recent report by the Eurofound (2024), those living with their parents are more likely to report difficulty making ends meet and inability to afford unexpected expenses. This indicates that living with parents does not necessarily protect young people from financial strain and that financially disadvantaged individuals are less able to afford to move out of the family home.

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-euro-indicators/w/3-01082024-ap#fragment-15944082-grio-inline-nav-2>

⁸ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/neets>

⁹ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/neets>

¹⁰Source: Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/yth_demo_030/default/table?lang=EN)

Housing affordability and availability remain significant obstacles for young people across the EU. High living and housing costs, coupled with a shortage of suitable housing, hinder the transition to independent living people (Eurofound, 2024). Although living with parents offers some level of housing security, it also reflects the financial strain experienced by these households. Additionally, the aspiration gap between the desire for a different housing situation and the reality seems to be associated with increased risk of depression among young people (Eurofound, 2024).

Furthermore, in Europe, the number of homeless young people appears to be increasing, with members of the LGBTQ+ community, migrants and people with mental health problems being particularly vulnerable (Mayock & Parker, 2023).

Participation

The first document contains the Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on promoting youth mainstreaming in policy decision-making processes in the European Union. It emphasizes that the design of youth-oriented policies should adopt a rights-based approach, ensuring inclusivity and targeting the diverse young population across Europe. Regarding opportunities for participation, the document underscores the importance of upholding young people's right to participate in decision-making and policy design. Throughout the document, young people are treated as a heterogeneous group; it recognizes the specific vulnerabilities of, for example, LGBTI persons, young people with disabilities, ethnic minorities, young women, those not in education, young people with migrant backgrounds, and unemployed young people. Moreover, it acknowledges that their vulnerability is exacerbated by the intersectionality of the different forms of inequality that affect them or by the different forms of exclusion that they experience.

The second document is the Council Recommendation of 5 April 2022 on the mobility of young volunteers across the European Union (Text with EEA relevance) 2022/C 157/01. One of the aims of the policy is to promote social inclusion through volunteering activities, which include providing accessible accommodations and targeted support for young people with fewer opportunities. Regarding opportunities for participation, the policy aims to expand participation by facilitating access to transnational volunteering experiences, especially for young people with fewer opportunities, by promoting targeted and accessible information and outreach efforts. The document does not treat young people as a homogeneous group; it recognizes the unique challenges faced by young people with disabilities, those from migrant backgrounds, and others facing economic, social, cultural, or geographical barriers and calls for paying particular attention to these groups of young people to overcome the barriers they face.

The third document contains the Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on safeguarding and creating civic spaces for young people that facilitate meaningful youth participation. While it does not explicitly talk about social inclusion of young people, the proposed policy underlines the importance of youth participation for social cohesion. In terms of opportunities for participation, the document strongly advocates for expanding these opportunities. It calls for safeguarding civic spaces and ensuring they are accessible to disadvantaged young people, such as those with disabilities and young migrants. It emphasizes that a one-size-fits-all approach is insufficient and highlights the importance of considering diverse youth backgrounds to enable meaningful participation.

The fourth document contains the Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on strengthening the multilevel governance when promoting the participation of young people in decision-making processes. It details various initiatives and recommendations aimed at enhancing youth participation in democratic life in Europe. The document acknowledges that young people are at higher risk of exclusions and inequalities; however, it only indirectly proposes to foster inclusion through the political participation of all young people. The proposed policies aim to expand opportunities for youth participation by mainstreaming and supporting active and sustainable structures for youth engagement in policy development. However, while the document acknowledges the diverse needs and circumstances of young people in general terms, it treats them as a somewhat homogeneous group in the context of expanding participation opportunities. It mentions vulnerable groups and gender inequality but does not extensively differentiate between various subgroups within the youth population, and when it comes to practical points, it simply talks about increasing participation among "all young people."

The fifth document is the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'Towards structured youth engagement on climate and sustainability in the EU decision-making process' (own-initiative opinion). At the beginning of the document, it acknowledges that young people are disproportionately affected by economic crises and face serious problems inherited from previous generations. It also talks about the challenges and exclusion faced by the most disadvantaged among young people and acknowledges the existence of obstacles due to some young people's socio-economic background, sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression, ethnicity or race, migratory status, disability, and/or other status. While it touches on the problem of exclusion, it does not propose solutions. The document mainly addresses the participation of young people, emphasizing the need for their meaningful engagement throughout institutional processes, from preparatory phases to evaluation, and calls to support this participation. Moreover, there is a specific mention of creating regular dialogues between young people and EU decision-makers, with initiatives such as the Youth Climate and Sustainability Round Tables. While the document highlights the need to address social, economic, and cultural obstacles to participation, in practical proposals, it does not account for the diverse experiences and barriers faced by different groups within the youth population, simply referring to young people in general.

Summary

All the documents about participation address the inclusion of young people, with varying degrees of action and consideration of intersectionality. The first and second documents emphasize the need for inclusive policies, acknowledging the unique vulnerabilities of various subgroups, such as youth with disabilities, and young migrants. The third document vaguely promotes inclusion without clear outcomes. The fourth document indirectly supports inclusion through political participation but lacks direct action. The fifth document recognizes significant exclusion issues among young people without offering solutions.

All the documents advocate expanding participation by involving young people in policy development or civic engagement, with some recognizing the need for targeted support for disadvantaged groups more than others. The first, second, and third documents emphasize nuanced approaches, facilitating access to opportunities, especially for those with fewer resources, and recognizing varied experiences within young people. The fourth document underscores the need for youth representation at all governance levels; however, despite acknowledging their diverse needs, it treats young people somewhat homogeneously.

when expanding participation opportunities. The fifth document emphasizes meaningful engagement and resources for youth participation but treats young people as a homogeneous group.

Education

The first document is the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on learning opportunities (learning mobility) abroad in Europe for everyone, updating and repealing the Council Recommendation of 28 June 2011 'Youth on the move' — promoting the learning mobility of young people. The initiative aims to make cross-border learning more accessible by addressing obstacles such as financial constraints, not only for young people but for everyone. Thus young people receive no advantage.

The second document is the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'Empowering youth to achieve sustainable development through education' (own-initiative opinion). It addresses the challenges faced by young people from disadvantaged backgrounds, those with fewer opportunities, and vulnerable groups. However, it does not specify who these disadvantaged young people are. In terms of opportunities for participation, the policy highlights the value of informal education methods, such as youth-led projects, in fostering a sustainable future and providing a learning space that contributes to shared awareness and collective action.

The third document is the European Parliament resolution of 13 September 2022 on the impact of COVID-19 closures of educational, cultural, youth and sports activities on children and young people. The document advocates for inclusive measures and highlights the importance of developing equitable and gender-responsive education systems that address the needs of LGBTQ+ youth, racialized young people, and those with pre-existing mental health needs. It underscores the importance of giving young people a voice in decision-making processes and calls for extending participation and co-determination rights in various educational institutions. Additionally, it encourages greater involvement of young people, particularly young women, in research and program design.

The fourth document is the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport. It explicitly addresses young people's inclusion by proposing measures to improve participation in the program among those with fewer opportunities, including individuals facing economic, social, cultural, geographical, or health challenges, those with a migrant background, and those with disabilities or educational difficulties. Moreover, the Erasmus programme supports youth participation activities aimed at encouraging young people's involvement in democratic life and fostering dialogue between young people and decision-makers.

The fifth document contains the Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on education and training of youth workers. Although it does not specifically address inclusion, it highlights the importance of involving youth organizations in the ongoing development of youth worker education and training. The document refers to young people in general, without considering their individual differences.

Summary

The analyzed EU policy documents on education address inclusion and opportunities for participation to varying extents. Some provide comprehensive measures targeting specific disadvantaged groups, while others offer broader, less specific aims. Three out of five documents discuss and promote inclusion, with varying degrees of emphasis on intersectionality. The second document mentions "vulnerable groups of

young people" without clearly defining the category, while the fourth document provides a broad definition including economic, social, cultural, geographical, health reasons, migrant background, disability, and educational difficulties. The third document specifically identifies LGBTQ+ youth, racialized young people, and young people with disabilities as disadvantaged and marginalized groups.

Regarding opportunities for participation, four out of five documents aim to increase young people's participation. The second document focuses on empowering youth to achieve sustainable development through transformative learning and youth-led projects, explicitly including those from disadvantaged backgrounds. The third document emphasizes expanding opportunities for political participation by involving young people in decision-making and program design, particularly highlighting young women's involvement. The Erasmus+ programme described in the fourth document supports activities that help young people engage in civic society and foster dialogue with decision-makers, though it lacks specific details. The fifth paper, on the other hand, addresses the involvement of young people from youth organisations in voluntary activities, seeing them as opportunities for education and training rather than direct participation.

Employment

The first document is the Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on youth work policy in an empowering Europe. It addresses the inclusion of young people by emphasizing the need for equal access to youth work, particularly for young people with fewer opportunities. The policy recognizes young people's diverse identities, backgrounds, and needs, acknowledging the multitude of identities among young people. Additionally, the document focuses on expanding opportunities for participation by encouraging youth engagement in the design of public spaces, promoting participatory budgeting, and recognizing volunteer youth work. It aims to create inclusive, safe environments that cater to the varied experiences and requirements of young people from all backgrounds, thereby fostering their agency and civic engagement.

The second document is the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the equal treatment of young people in the labour market (own-initiative opinion). It addresses the inclusion of young people, emphasizing the importance of ensuring they are fully integrated into society and have access to the same working opportunities as others, underlining that youth unemployment can lead to various forms of social exclusion. This policy calls on the Commission to work closely with the Member States to gather data and share best practices to create equal opportunities for young people. The document highlights the intersectionality of issues affecting different subgroups of young people, such as young people with disabilities, students, and marginalized youth; however, it does not provide any indication of how to address their issues. Regarding opportunities for participation, the document promotes work as part of broader civic and democratic participation, which is essential for young people to understand their role in society and advocate for themselves. However, it does not offer new opportunities for participation.

The third document is a Motion for a resolution on empowering European youth, which addresses the inclusion of young people, particularly fostering their access to quality, stable, and well-paid employment. The proposed policy aims to positively impact young people's inclusion by prioritizing the fight against youth unemployment, especially for vulnerable groups. Young people are treated as a heterogeneous group; the document emphasizes intersectionality by recognizing the diverse challenges faced by young Roma, young people with disabilities, young LGBTIQ+ individuals, young migrants, young women, and those from disadvantaged backgrounds, and by calling on the Member States and the Commission to pay particular

attention to these groups. Regarding opportunities for participation, the document advocates for youth involvement in policy development through the EU youth dialogue, youth work, and youth organizations. In this case, young people are treated as a homogeneous group.

The fourth document contains the Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on a Council Recommendation and a Commission proposal on Youth Employment Support. It calls for stronger measures to address forms of discrimination in the workplace, such as those based on race, sexual orientation, and migrant status, implicitly recognizing the heterogeneity of young people and trying to improve the inclusion of young people affected by this discrimination. The document addresses opportunities for youth participation by encouraging regional and local authorities to create partnerships between different stakeholders, among which youth organisations. In this case, however, young people are treated as a homogeneous group.

The fifth document contains the opinion of the Committee on Employment and Social Affairs for the Committee on Fisheries on attracting young people to the fishing industry. It emphasizes the need for appropriate actions to encourage young people's involvement in coastal fishing activities and acknowledges that these actions must ensure gender equality and consider the role of women, implicitly recognizing the needs of young women. Regarding opportunities for participation for young people, the document does not address this aspect.

Summary

All documents address the inclusion of young people, albeit with varying degrees of specificity. The first, second, and third documents propose policies that aim to positively impact young people by recognizing their diverse backgrounds and needs, highlighting the importance of equal access to work opportunities. However, while the second document acknowledges the diversity of young people and the challenges faced by some of them as a result of their identities, it falls short of providing concrete measures to address those challenges. Conversely, the fourth document, though emphasizing fair remuneration and the need for stronger measures to address forms of discrimination in the workplace, implicitly recognizes the heterogeneity of young people. The fifth document, focusing on attracting young people to the fishing industry, acknowledges the need to ensure gender equality, implicitly recognizing the needs of young women.

Regarding opportunities for participation, only the first, third and fourth documents analyzed aim to increase opportunities for participation for young people. The first document stands out by promoting youth engagement in public space design, participatory budgeting, and volunteer work, recognizing the varied experiences of young people and fostering their civic engagement. The second document, while linking work to broader civic participation, does not introduce new specific opportunities. The third document advocates for youth involvement in policy development through established EU frameworks but treats young people as a homogeneous group, which could limit the effectiveness of its proposals. The fourth document encourages the authorities to create partnerships between youth organisations and other stakeholders, but without mentioning differences between young people. The fifth document instead do not address youth participation. Overall, the documents present a mixed picture, with some proposing inclusive policies, while others either treat young people uniformly or overlook significant aspects of their participation and inclusion.

Health

The first document is a call for action at the EU level to protect young people from harm caused by novel tobacco and nicotine products. There is no mention to any form of exclusion of young people neither to opportunities for participation.

The second document contains the opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on using sports to encourage inclusion and social wellbeing among young people. It emphasizes the need for equitable access to sports to mitigate generational injustice. The document proposes practical solutions, such as calling for the European Social Fund to incorporate objectives for greater accessibility, inclusion, solidarity, and social cohesion through sports. However, it treats young people as a homogeneous group, not acknowledging their diversity. In one of his points the document aims to enhance inclusivity within sports governing bodies to safeguard the rights of vulnerable groups such as youth, females, LGBTQIA+ individuals, disabled individuals, and migrants. However, while various groups are mentioned, the heterogeneity of young people is not addressed. The document also highlights opportunities for young people's participation, advocating for innovative methods in sports to enhance participatory democracy, active participation, and civic engagement. The policy recommendations seek to expand opportunities for youth engagement through sports initiatives. However, the document again treats young people as a uniform group, failing to recognize their varied needs and experiences.

The third document presents the Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on the role of cities as health promoters. It references young people only to urge local governments to take an active role in raising awareness about the negative health impacts of nicotine and in restricting access to alcohol. However, it does not address any form of exclusion of young people or provide opportunities for their participation.

The fourth document presents the Conclusions of the Council and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to the mental health of young people. It calls for action to enhance both inclusion and participation opportunities for young people, with particular attention to those in vulnerable positions. In its preamble, the document provides examples of vulnerable young people, including ethnic minorities, LGBTI individuals, persons with disabilities, and those in youth care institutions. It explains that discrimination and inequality increase the risk of mental health issues, especially when young people face multiple forms of discrimination or disadvantage. Consequently, it acknowledges that young people are not a homogeneous group and recognizes that multiple discriminations or disadvantages can heighten their vulnerability. Among other points to promote the mental health of young people the document emphasizes the importance of addressing the unique needs of young people in the EU, particularly those in the most vulnerable situations, and aims to support their reintegration and social inclusion. It stresses the need to involve young people in decision-making processes and to ensure that those in vulnerable situations are represented in the development of public policy programs on mental health. Additionally, it advocates for the creation of channels that allow young people in vulnerable situations to voice their concerns.

The fifth document is an opinion from the European Economic and Social Committee regarding the EU Global Health Strategy. It advocates for a comprehensive approach to health, addressing social, economic, and environmental determinants, and emphasizes the need for global action against diseases. It mentions the importance of taking into account the health needs of different categories of people, including young people, with a focus on intersectional issues. However, it does not provide any practical measures to achieve this. Furthermore, it does not mention any opportunities for young people's participation.

Summary

Of the five health-related documents, only the second, third and the fourth document address the inclusion of young people. The second document recognizes and encourages the role of sports in promoting inclusion among young people but treats them as a homogeneous group. The fourth document calls for actions to enhance inclusion to improve young people's mental health. It emphasizes the need to consider that young people facing discrimination and inequality, such as ethnic minorities, LGBTI individuals, and persons with disabilities, are more at risk of exclusion. It highlights the particular vulnerability of those experiencing multiple forms of discrimination and stresses the importance of paying special attention to those in the most vulnerable situations. The third document instead highlights the need to consider the health needs of various groups, including youth, and the need to focus on intersectional issues. However, it lacks practical measures.

The same two of the five health-related documents addressing inclusion also address young people's opportunities for participation. The second document advocates for innovative methods in sports to enhance participatory democracy, active participation, and civic engagement, seeking to expand opportunities for youth engagement through sports initiatives. However, this document again treats young people as a uniform group. In contrast, the fifth document calls for actions to enhance participation opportunities for young people and, as with young people's integration, emphasizes the need to pay particular attention to those in vulnerable positions. It recognizes that their vulnerability increases when they face multiple forms of discrimination.

Housing

The first document presents the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on homelessness strategies based on the Housing First principle. It briefly mentions the increase in homelessness among young people and other groups but does not propose specific solutions for young people or address opportunities for their participation.

The second document contains the Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions on eradicating homelessness in the European Union. It describes homelessness as a severe form of social exclusion affecting diverse groups, including young people. It aims to positively impact young people by advocating for a strong focus on homelessness in various EU initiatives, such as the EU Youth Guarantee. Additionally, the document calls for raising awareness and promoting youth care centers and shelters, thereby expanding opportunities for participation and support for young people, particularly those who are LGBTIQ. However, it does not address specific opportunities for young people's participation.

The third document is a European Parliament resolution on access to decent and affordable housing for all. It describes homelessness as a severe manifestation of social exclusion in Europe and identifies various vulnerable groups, including young people, especially the unemployed. It specifies that individuals from these groups are particularly vulnerable if they are LGBTIQ persons, migrants, refugees, persons with disabilities, people with physical or psychiatric illnesses, and people from marginalized communities, such as the Roma. It recognizes the heterogeneity of young people and calls on Member States and the Commission to take measures and implement programs for young people at risk of homelessness. It also requests the creation of tools for enhanced data collection on LGBTIQ youth homelessness. However, the resolution does not discuss opportunities for young people's participation.

The fourth document is the European Parliament resolution of 24 November 2020 on addressing homelessness rates in the EU. It lists groups at risk of homelessness, including young people. One of the resolution's points calls on the Commission and Member States to ensure that the revised Youth Guarantee contributes to tackling youth homelessness. Nevertheless, the resolution treats young people as a homogeneous group and does not discuss opportunities for their participation.

The fifth document is the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the initiative "Universal access to housing that is decent, sustainable, and affordable over the long term". It mentions young people, noting that housing exclusion, homelessness, and poor-quality housing currently affect young people, single-parent and large families, workers, and the middle class more broadly. However, it does not specifically discuss the situation of young people, nor does it address their inclusion or opportunities for their participation.

Summary

The housing policies vary in addressing the inclusion of young people. The first and the fifth documents mention young people but lack specific solutions or policies, resulting in neither positive nor negative outcomes. The other documents propose solutions to improve young people's housing situations, with different degrees of acknowledgment of intersectionality. The fourth document treats young people as a homogeneous group. The second document calls for special attention to the problem of youth LGBTIQ homelessness. The third document not only calls for attention to youth LGBTIQ homelessness but also acknowledges that young people are more at risk of homelessness if they are migrants, refugees, or persons with disabilities. None of the housing policies, however, provide frameworks for expanding young people's participation.

References documents analysed

On Participation

- 1) Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on promoting youth mainstreaming in policy decision-making processes in the European Union (29/11/2023)
- 2) Council Recommendation of 5 April 2022 on the mobility of young volunteers across the European Union (Text with EEA relevance) 2022/C 157/01 (05/04/2022)
- 3) Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on safeguarding and creating civic spaces for young people that facilitate meaningful youth participation 2021/C 501 I/04 (13/12/2021)
- 4) Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on strengthening the multilevel governance when promoting the participation of young people in decision-making processes 2021/C 241/03 (21/06/2021)
- 5) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'Towards structured youth engagement on climate and sustainability in the EU decision-making process' (own-initiative opinion) (11/12/2020)

On Education

- 1) Proposal for a Council Recommendation on learning opportunities (learning mobility) abroad in Europe for everyone, updating and repealing the Council Recommendation of 28 June 2011 'Youth on the move' — promoting the learning mobility of young people (08/02/2023)
- 2) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'Empowering youth to achieve sustainable development through education' (own-initiative opinion) (15/12/2022)

- 3) European Parliament resolution of 13 September 2022 on the impact of COVID-19 closures of educational, cultural, youth and sports activities on children and young people in the EU (2022/2004(INI)) (13/09/2022)
- 4) Regulation (EU) 2021/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013 (Text with EEA relevance) (28/5/2021)
- 5) Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on education and training of youth workers 2019/C 412/03 (09/12/2019)

On Employment

- 1) Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on youth work policy in an empowering Europe (13/05/2024)
- 2) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the equal treatment of young people in the labour market (own-initiative opinion) (15/06/2023)
- 3) MOTION FOR A RESOLUTION on empowering European youth: post-pandemic employment and social recovery (09/02/2022)
- 4) Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions — Youth Employment Support: a Bridge to Jobs for the Next Generation Reinforcing the Youth Guarantee (26/03/2021)
- 5) OPINION on Fishers for the future: Attracting a new generation of labour to the fishing industry and generating employment in coastal communities (18/03/2021)

On Health

- 1) A call for action at the EU level to protect young people from harm caused by novel tobacco and nicotine products: - Information from the Latvian delegation on behalf of the Cyprus, Estonian, Finnish, Irish, Latvian, Lithuanian, Luxembourg, Maltese, Netherlands, Portuguese, Slovenian and Spanish delegations (17/06/2024)
- 2) Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions – Building a values-based, bottom-up European sports model: a vehicle for encouraging inclusion and social wellbeing among young Europeans (09/02/2024)
- 3) Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions – The role of cities as health promoters (09/02/2024)
- 4) Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to the mental health of young people in the European Union (30/11/2023)
- 5) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: EU Global Health Strategy — Better Health for All in a Changing World (COM(2022) 675 final) (21/09/2023)

On Housing

- 1) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on For an EU framework for national homeless strategies based on the principle of ‘Housing First’ (own-initiative opinion) (13/12/2023)
- 2) Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions — Eradicating homelessness in the European Union: the local and regional perspective (02/12/2021)
- 3) European Parliament resolution of 21 January 2021 on access to decent and affordable housing for all (2019/2187(INI)) (21/01/2021)
- 4) European Parliament resolution of 24 November 2020 on tackling homelessness rates in the EU (2020/2802(RSP)) (24/11/2020)
- 5) Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on ‘Universal access to housing that is decent, sustainable and affordable over the long term’ (own-initiative opinion) (16/09/2020)

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PART IV: NATIONAL REPORTS

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK (AAU)

INTRODUCTION

Education

Equal and free access to education for all: The Danish education system aims to ensure equal and free access to education. Education is open to all and generally tuition-free. Every Dane over the age of 18 is entitled to public support for their further education regardless of social standing (Ministry of Higher Education and Science). By 2024, the students' grant is 6,820 DKK per month before taxes.

Most children and young people attend municipal schools (Eurydice). The quality of schools varies, and social challenges of the pupils likewise.

We see an increase of the number of young people completing upper secondary education on a national level. Upper secondary education status of young people 18-25 by 2023:

- Completed upper secondary education (67,3%)
- Undergoing education (17,63%)
- Discontinued education (6,65%)
- No registered education (8,28%) (Statistics Denmark)

Denmark has a tradition of free schools, "efterskole" (form level 9 and 10) and folk high schools (not ISCED). The efterskole is a unique Danish independent residential school for students between 14 and 18 years old. Presently some 30.669 students attend one of the app. 240 schools throughout Denmark (Efterskolerne). A folk high school is a non-formal residential school of a typical stay is 4 months. There are no academic requirements for admittance, and there are no exams. In 2020, a total of 38,869 students attended folk high schools in Denmark (Videncenter for Folkeoplysning).

In Denmark, 42% of 25-64-year-olds have a higher education degree. Of these, 4.9% have a short-term higher education, 20.9% have a medium-term higher education, while almost 14.7% have a long-term higher education (Universities Denmark). Admission to higher education is based on the applicants' grades from upper secondary education (BEK 104). After graduating upper secondary education many young people take one or several gap years before applying for higher education. The average age of graduates from the universities is 28,2 (Ministry of Higher Education and Science).

The research within the field of educational studies in Denmark point out various challenges faced by young people. Some of the barriers are based on social status and disadvantages such as social class (see e.g. Thomsen 2013) and psychosocial problems (Wulf-Andersen et al. 2022). The research shows a tendency of performance pressure among many young people which affects their wellbeing within the educational system and in general (Katznelson et al. 2022).

Health

Residents are entitled to all public healthcare benefits. The public health insurance allows free treatment from doctor and specialists and subsidies for medicine, dental care, physiotherapy, podiatry, chiropractor, and psychologist.

There has been a decrease in the use of cigarettes and of alcohol for children and young people in Denmark, which has been a health issue for decades (ESPAD). According to the national health profile from 2021, 22% of 15-year-old girls and 27% of 15-year-old boys drank alcohol weekly in 2022. By 2022, 44% of girls and 48% of boys in 9th grade (15–16-year-olds) will have tried being drunk at least twice (Danish Health Authority). In 2021, 15% of 16–19-year-olds smoked daily or occasionally. In 2010, the figure was 24.8%, so there has been a significant decrease in smoking in this age group over a 10-year period. From 2017 to 2021 alone, daily smoking among 16-19-year-olds has halved (Kræftens Bekæmpelse).

Well-being of young people has been a major topic of political and public awareness the last years in Denmark. The Danish government has appointed an expert commission to investigate the well-being of children and young people after challenges in children's and young peoples' well-being has been shown in various national, municipal, and school based surveys, and loneliness has increased among young people (BørnUngeLivs ungeprofilundersøgelse 2019/2020; Roskilde Ungdomsprofil 2021).

Employment

Graduate unemployment has declined both in vocational and professional higher education and in the university sector. By May 2024, 2.9% are unemployed (Statistics Denmark). The overall employment rate for graduates with a vocational qualification was 87% in 2022 (Ministry of Higher Education and Science). New unemployment data for higher education graduates shows that unemployment for recent graduates is at its lowest level since before the financial crisis in 2008. While the unemployment rate for higher education graduates has remained relatively stable at around 10-12% for the past decade, it has almost halved - from 12.5% in 2019 to 6.5% in 2021.

From 2021 to 2022, there has been an increase in the proportion of young people who are neither in education nor in work. The proportion rose from 5.9% in 2021 to 6.4% in 2022, and on October 1st, more than 43,000 young people between the ages of 15 and 24 had no connection to education or the labor market (the Danish Agency for IT and Learning).

Atypical employment is particularly prevalent among young people. Almost 57% young people in employment are in some form of atypical employment. Excluding students etc. and focusing specifically on those who have work as their primary occupation, this applies to around one in three (34%). In both cases, this is significantly higher than among other Danes aged 30 or over.

Part-time employment is most common, but some young people are also employed on a temporary basis and on 0-hour contracts: Around 42% young people in employment are employed part-time, and for young people in fulltime employment this applies to 19%. In addition, around 13% of fulltime employed young people are on a temporary basis, and for those in primary employment this is 10%. Finally, 10% of primarily employed (not students) are employed on a 0-hour contract (The Danish Youth Council).

Housing

The average age for young people in Denmark leaving home is 21 years old (Statistics Denmark 2018). Most young Danes move into rented accommodation the first time they leave home (Finance Denmark 2018). Most move to the major Danish cities (Ministry of Economic Affairs and the Interior 2017; Statistics Denmark 2018). Two-thirds of young people move into rented accommodation (Finance Denmark 2018). 35% of young people rent with others, while 16% rent alone. 17% live in a home that

the young person owns, 9% live in a home that their parents have bought, while 6% live in student accommodation (Nordea 2018). In the major cities there is a shortage of student housing (Boligøkonomisk Videncenter 2018). In the Greater Copenhagen area alone, there was a shortage of 8,500 student housing units (Dansk Byggeri 2018). Moving in Denmark is expensive; 64% of young people rely on savings (Statistics Denmark 2018).

The number of 18–29-year-olds experiencing homelessness has decreased by approximately 18% from 1,928 young people in 2019 to 1,586 people in 2022 (Rådet for Socialt Udsatte). Escalating property prices and rental rates in urban areas challenge young people from low-income backgrounds in getting a place to live, especially in Copenhagen.

Participation

In 2023 more than 10,500 people under the age of 30 were members of the political parties' youth organisations (Videncenter for Folkeoplysning). 76% of young people aged 16-25 have participated in political activities in the past year and 12% of the young people have participated in at least one demonstration during the last year, which is 3 times more than the total population.

By 2024, 54% of young people worried about misinformation, which is an increase from 55% in 2023. Also, only 47% of young people have high democratic self-confidence, which is a barrier for political participation. Another challenge for young people's political involvement is time and energy. But 66% of young people have an opinion on how Denmark and the world should develop, and 31% of 16-25 year olds and 26-35 year olds do voluntary social work across different types of organizations (VIVE's Frivillighedsundersøgelse 2020).

Frequency analysis of minorities among YP

In this frequency analysis the number of minorities among young people is based on the available data. As there is not available statistics of the share of the population in the age 14-35 years, we present data of the general population of Denmark. 1,687,764 people in Denmark are currently in the age 14-35 years old which is 28.27% of the population (5,969,774 in total) (Statistics Denmark 2024).

Disability status is not registered in Denmark. However, major studies show that around 30% of Danes aged 16-64 years consider themselves to have a major or minor disability. This includes all age groups with disabilities. According to Danish Center for Social Science Research (2020), 120,164 Danes have a major mental disability and 313,155 have a major physical disability, which is 2,01% of the population. We see an increase of how many reports mental disability e.g. ADD, ADHD and autism. Also, research shows more people get diagnoses earlier in life. The proportion who reports the mental disability occurred before the age of 27 years have increased from 53% in 2012 to 67% in 2020 (VIVE 2020).

In 2024 84,2% of the population is from a Danish origin, 5,7% of a Western origin, 5% from the MENAPT countries, and 5,1% from other origins¹¹ (Ministry of Immigration and Integration 2024).

LGBT+ people in Denmark make up a significant proportion of the population, approximately 8%, corresponding to 1 in 13 and approximately 275,000 people aged 16-64 (based on Statistics Denmark's

¹¹ The MENAPT countries are Syria, Kuwait, Libya, Saudi Arabia, Lebanon, Somalia, Iraq, Qatar, Sudan, Bahrain, Djibouti, Jordan, Algeria, United Arab Emirates, Tunisia, Egypt, Morocco, Iran, Yemen, Mauritania, Oman, Afghanistan, Palestine, Gaza, West Bank, East Jerusalem, Pakistan and Turkey.]

2020 population figures). Of the 8%, approximately 6.5% identify as homosexual, bisexual, asexual or have a different sexual orientation. 0.5 - 1.4% identify as transgender or nonbinary. 1.7% is born with variations in gender characteristics (The Danish Institute for Human Rights).

According to Statistics Denmark (2023), the number of people in relative poverty fell by 19,100 to 213,900 people from 2021 to 2022. This means that 3.7 per cent of the total Danish population excluding students living away from home lived in families with relatively low income and wealth in 2022, compared to 4.2 per cent of the population in 2021. The half percentage point drop in the share of people in relative poverty from 2021 to 2022 should primarily be seen in light of the strong employment growth and falling unemployment during 2022. The share of children under the age of 18 in relative poverty was 4.2 per cent in 2022 and has been declining since 2017, when it peaked at 5.6 per cent (Statistics Denmark 2023).

SAMPLING PROCEDURES

National Level:

To identify the most recent national policy documents, we used the Retsinformation.dk database, which archives all Danish policy documents and laws as they are enacted. We focused on documents that address children and youth, specifically within the five selected themes.

The documents were gathered by reviewing all relevant laws, decisions, and policies adopted by the Danish government on Retsinformation.dk. We included any documents that mention young people, using terms such as pupils, minors, and students (henceforth referred to as YP). The results were sorted by publication date, in accordance with the guidelines.

Local Level:

At the local level, we focused on policies and decisions made by the Copenhagen City Council. Our sampling concentrated on the policy areas of participation and education, as these were the most prominent in the Council's decisions.

The local documents primarily consist of adopted amendments and requests from City Council members to one or more mayors. These requests typically involve questions about municipal issues, requiring the mayor to clarify the relevant policy of their department or the City Council as a whole. As with the national level, we sorted the results by publication date, following the guidelines.

NATIONAL LEVEL

Education

Document 4 is a change in the law regarding SU (monthly stipend given to all students over 18). The stipend is given for, in most cases, 58 months (app. 5 years of studying, amounting to a bachelor's degree and master's degree). A student cannot receive the stipend for more than 70 months. This change in the law that's declared in document 4 gives students with special circumstances (students who are disabled or single parents) 12 more months of the stipend than other students. Therefore, we have assigned it a score of 1 in *inclusion* and *direction* and 2 in *intersection*, since the change in the law takes into account that some students have special circumstances that may require prolonging

their education. It is awarded a score of 0 in *participation*, however, since it does not give students, disabled or not, access to political participation, influence etc.

Document 5 makes minor changes to the overall law regarding free schools and “efterskole” (for description of this type of school, see subtask 4.1.1 introduction), such as regulation regarding the principal’s role. The document does not address inclusion or participation and does not have any clear consequences for in- or exclusion or participation for YP. Therefore, we have awarded it 0 in both *inclusion* and *participation*.

Document 6 makes changes to an existing law about FGU schools, which are schools for YP under 25 to help prepare them to for high school or vocational training or to get a job. Typically, this is offered to YP without a connection to the educational system or the labor market, thus more vulnerable YP. This document provides more flexibility for the schools, allowing them to take in new students several times a year, and creates a smoother transition into the schools for the students. We have awarded it a score of 1 in *inclusion*, because it makes FGU schools, and therefore getting an education or a job, more accessible for vulnerable YP. The document does not address intersectionality, as it’s directed at “students” or “pupils” and doesn’t address marginalized positions or identities among them. We have awarded it 0 in *participation*, because it doesn’t address, neither directly nor indirectly, opportunities for participation.

Document 7 introduces a trial to change the division of theoretical and practical learning in the hairdressing education. Typically, a hairdressing student would attend school for months, then have practical learning in a salon for months, then back to school and so on. This document introduces a trial with a 4/1 model where the student will be at school for four days a week and in a salon for one day a week instead. We have awarded this a score of 0 in both *inclusion* and *participation*, since neither inclusion nor participation is addressed, and there’s nothing in the law to indicate more inclusion or participation for students or YP in general.

Document 8 is a new law in vocational education and in professional bachelor’s degrees such as social worker, nurse, or pedagogue which addresses the abilities of the Ministry for Education and Research to delegate tasks to the Board for Education and Research whose primary purpose is to implement the laws that are introduced in government. For this reason, we have awarded the policy a score of 0 in both *inclusion* and *participation*, as neither are addressed.

Employment

Document 9 is a new law stating that YP between 13 and 17 years old at risk of committing crimes have the right to a “pocket-money job”. It’s the responsibility of their respective municipalities to help them, and if they move to a different municipality, the new one must help them find a new job. By “at risk of committing crime” is meant YP suspected of having committed serious crime, or YP who have either been convicted to serve time in prison for a crime that endangered others, crimes related to drugs, weapons, or knives, and are estimated to be at risk of committing further crimes. We have awarded the law a score of 1 in *inclusion* and *direction* and of 2 in *intersection*, because the law aims to include YP at risk of committing crimes into society by ensuring their right to a job with a, albeit small, salary. We consider this a thin intersection, as YP at risk of committing crime is a complex experience of childhood and youth which leaves them marginalized and vulnerable.

Document 10 describes changes to the law concerning unemployment insurance, “dagpenge”, which is an insurance funded partially by private membership, partially by the state. Members who become unemployed for one reason or another receive a fixed amount of money in unemployment benefits each month for up to two years. The law in this document states that graduates (of university) who haven’t gotten a permanent job three months after graduation receive a smaller amount each month than other unemployed people. We have awarded this document a score -1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it excludes graduates from the same rights as other unemployed people, and because the low amount leads to vulnerability and a risk of exclusion from social life. We have awarded the document 0 in *participation*, because there’s no direct or indirect mention of political, democratic, or other types of participation. The document refers to ‘thin’ intersectionality because it refers to and is directed at graduates.

Document 11 states that YP under 18 are not allowed to operate cranes, forklifts, and similar heavy machinery used in construction work unless they have gotten the relevant certificates as part of their education (vocational education). We have awarded this document a -1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it excludes certain YP from operating machinery on work sites that others are allowed to operate. However, we see this as playing into the discussion of inclusion vs. protection of YP and thus, although it is exclusionary, do not consider it a negative outcome for the YP affected. The document has been awarded the score of 1 in *intersection* because it only refers to YP, and a score of 0 in *participation*, because there’s no direct or indirect mention of participation.

Document 12 states that YP under 18 are not allowed to operate lifts going up or down in relation to construction work, because this is considered particularly dangerous. YP over 15 who are learning to operate lifts as part of their education (vocational education) are however exempt from this. We have awarded this document a score of -1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, 1 in *intersection*, and 0 in *participation* for the same reasons as stated for document 11.

Document 13 states that the government can give financial support to young farmers and gardeners (aged under 41) to help them start their own farming- or gardening businesses. We have awarded this document a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* because leads to inclusion of YP in careers where it may be hard to get established, and a score of 2 in *intersection* because it’s directed at a specific, although not marginalized, group of YP. We have awarded it a score of 0 in *participation* because there is no mention directly or indirectly of democratic, political, or other types of participation.

Health

Document 14 states how new prevention measures to keep YP from smoking electronic and/or regular cigarettes and alcohol consumption will be instated. It makes it easier for the authorities to control that YP under 18 are not able to buy cigarettes and alcohol and introduces “tobacco surrogates” (such as electronic cigarettes) to the law on prevention. The law is directly aimed at YP under 18 but concerned with the health of all YP. We have awarded this a score of -1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it further excludes and restricts YP from tobacco and alcohol consumption, 1 in *intersection* because it refers to YP (under 18) in general, and 0 in *participation*. Similar to document 11 and 12, however, this type of exclusion we would expect to lead to positive outcomes for YP.

Document 15 is a law regarding the implementation of municipal-level treatment offers for YP with mental health issues and symptoms of mental illness. It states that children and YP with mental health issues or symptoms of mental illness should have easy access to treatment and help. The background

for this is that wait lists for mental health care across all of Denmark are very long. We have awarded this document a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because YP's need for mental health care is taken into consideration and mental health care may likely lead to more inclusion in society (education, labor market, social life etc.), 2 in *intersection*, because the law is directed at YP with mental health problems and/or diagnoses, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 16 states that dental care is free for YP under 22 instead of under 18, which was previously the case. We have awarded this document a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* (the law leads to positive outcomes for YP) and *intersection* and 0 in *participation*.

Document 17 states that YP between 15 and 18 have a right to change doctor (general practitioner) without parental consent. YP under 18 are automatically placed with the same doctor as their parent or legal guardian, and YP under 15 need parental consent to change their doctor. We have awarded this policy a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because YP are given more autonomy and thus included in decisions regarding their own life and health, 1 in *intersection*, because it applies to YP (within this age group) in general, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 18 states that YP under 26 can be awarded financial aid to help pay for basic or diagnostic dental care. For people above 26, financial aid for basic dental care can only be awarded if it's part of the treatment of an illness. We have awarded this document a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, as this has a positive outcome for YP (particularly those who are financially challenged, although this is not mentioned in the policy) and can lead to inclusion because it lifts a potential economic burden, 1 in *intersection* because the policy refers to YP in general, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 19 is a law changing the law concerning use of force in psychiatric treatment. It states that anyone over 15 years old can give informed consent to treatment, hospitalization, and stays in psychiatric facilities. When the patient is under 15 it's enough to get informed consent from the parents or legal guardian, but regardless of informed consent from parents it's considered use of force if there is not informed consent from the young person. Previously, the law stated that it was not considered use of force if the patient was under 15 and their parents or legal guardian had given informed consent to treatment, hospitalization, and/or stays in psychiatric facilities. We have awarded this law a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it improves the legal rights of YP under 18 and gives them more autonomy, thereby including them in decisions regarding their own life, a score of 2 in *intersection* because it's directed at young psychiatric patients and therefore YP with mental disabilities or mental illnesses, and a score of 0 in *participation*.

Housing

Document 20 is a law changing the law concerning use of force with children and YP placed in foster or institutional care. It makes it possible for employees at institutions to, by use of force, take away drugs, alcohol, and electronic devices used for communication (mobile phones, game consols etc.) if this is considered necessary to ensure the health, development, and well-being of the young person. This is included under housing because it determines living conditions for institutionalized YP. We have awarded this a score of -1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because the removal of especially communication devices excludes the young person from communicating with friends and family, and general communication with the outside world through social media, news outlets etc. In *intersection*, we have given it a score of 2 because it refers to children in foster care, and in *participation* we have given it a score of 0.

Document 21 is a policy stating that children who live in institutions, such as boarding schools or foster care institutions, are covered by the law on occupational injuries and related insurance, meaning that YP who are injured while living in some type of educational or residential institution can receive financial compensation for loss of work ability following an accident. We have awarded this a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it provides more safety for children who are living in public or private institutions, 2 in *intersection*, because part of the law concerns YP in foster care, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 22 is a change in the law about urban planning which states that youth and student housing must be included in plans for development. We have awarded this a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* because it requires that affordable housing is built for YP and/or students, 1 in *intersection* because it refers to YP in general, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 23 is a legal guidance document on applications for funding to establish a shelter for YP in Western Denmark. We have awarded this a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it includes YP in considerations concerning homelessness, violence, or threats of violence in the home, etc. We give it a score of 1 in *intersection*, because it's aimed at YP in general, and 0 in *participation*.

Document 24 is a policy concerning the framework (economic, leadership wise etc.) around YP's stays in correctional institutions. We have awarded this a score of 0 in both *inclusion/exclusion* and *participation*, because it doesn't address, and there's no indication that it will affect, inclusion, exclusion, or participation for YP.

Participation

The government very rarely makes or changes policies concerning participation; thus, only three policy documents were found within this policy area.

Document 1 describes how the high school and boarding school, Sorø Akademi, must have at least two pupils on their school board. The policy does not address other schools. Since the document requires the inclusion of young people (henceforth YP), we have assigned it a score of 1 in *inclusion* and in *direction*. It also provides direct opportunity for participation for YP through the school's board. However, since it only refers to pupils, not intersections of pupils or YP, we have assigned it a score of 1 in *intersection*.

Document 2 is an official guideline on support for disabled children and YP and their parents, a big part of which addresses the opportunity for mentally and/or physically disabled children and YP and their families to participate in special clubs and other activities. Since this document ensures the inclusion of disabled YP, we have assigned it a score of 1 on *inclusion* and *direction* and score of 2 on *intersection*. However, as it does not provide opportunities for participation, we have assigned it a score of 0.

Document 3 is an official declaration for organizations on how to apply for funding to host camps for disabled children and YP. This receives a score of 1 in *inclusion*, because it enhances disabled YP's chances of inclusion in opportunities that are also awarded to able-bodied youth, and possibly gives disabled YP tools to participate in society on a broader scale. However, it receives the score of 0 in *participation*, as it does not give disabled YP access to influence or other ways of political participation

LOCAL LEVEL

Education

Document 6 is an adopted amendment stating that public schools in the municipality should have a bicycle workshop. We have awarded this a score of 0 in both *inclusion/exclusion* and *participation* because it does not, neither directly nor indirectly, address or affect inclusion or participation for young people.

Document 7 is a request asking the Mayor of Copenhagen and the Mayor of Children and Youth about the well-being of children and young people enrolled in the Royal Danish Ballet School which is located in Copenhagen and receives funding from the municipality. This stems from a large debate that ensued after it was revealed that students at the ballet school were mistreated, including comments on their bodies, denied water and bathroom breaks etc., resulting in poor well-being among students. The response is that the school is handling the situation on their own, and thus the policy does not address inclusion or participation of young people, so we have awarded this policy a score of 0 in both.

Document 8 is an adopted amendment stating that certain schools in fast-developing districts of Copenhagen can continue to reject accepting new pupils who do not live nearby if the school deems that they have too many students. We have awarded this a score of -1 in *inclusion/exclusion* because it results in some pupils being excluded from attending the schools, and 0 in *participation*, because it does not address this. In this case, it's also important to note that exclusion is not necessarily bad – while it may be negative for the pupils who aren't accepted to the schools, not setting a limit of how many students can be accepted may also have negative consequences for pupils in overcrowded classes. We have awarded it a score of 1 in *intersection* because it refers to pupils in general.

Document 9 is a request asking the Mayor of Children and Youth about problems with antisemitism in public schools. The background for the request is a news article describing a situation where a Jewish pupil in a public school is threatened by another student. The mayor responds that, while they are following the cases, they believe that the school in question can handle the case themselves and that the municipality does not plan to make changes to their policy. We have awarded the policy a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* and 0 in *direction* because, while it addresses problems of inclusion and exclusion of pupils, children and young people with Jewish backgrounds, it does not propose changes and thus can't be said to lead to either inclusion or exclusion. We have awarded it a score of 2 in *intersection* because it addresses young Jewish people, children, and pupils. We have awarded it a score of 0 in *participation* because it does not address, directly or indirectly, participation for young people in general or with Jewish backgrounds.

Document 10 is a request asking the Mayor of Children and Youth about meals served in public schools, including the cost of them for the pupils, the effects on health, well-being, health inequality, etc. The mayor presents the policy of the school meals, including that there are no plans to change the contents or the price of them. He emphasizes that the current system means that pupils from low-income families, who don't always eat breakfast or bring lunch, are able to get a meal at school. We have awarded this a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* but 0 in *direction* because, while inclusion of pupils from low-income families is addressed, there is no indication that the current policy will result in either inclusion or exclusion. We have given it a score of 0 in *participation* and a 2 in *intersection*, because it's primarily concerned with pupils from low-income families.

Participation

Document 1 is an adopted amendment stating that the Economic Administration in Copenhagen Municipality will examine possibilities of hosting a “democracy event” for 18-year-olds or first-time voters each year to teach them about the importance of democracy, as well as sending out a letter when people turn 18 to welcome them to “our democratic society”. It’s also emphasized that the event and letter should not only be informative about “official” channels for democratic participation, such as elections or other things that require citizenship, but should also inform YP about alternative ways of democratic participation (protests, writing letters to politicians etc.). This because many YP in Copenhagen Municipality are not Danish citizens. We have awarded this policy a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion*, because it works towards the inclusion of YP in democracy, 2 in *intersection*, because it specifically refers to YP without citizenship, and 1 in *participation*, because the purpose of the amendment is to inspire and provide YP with the tools to participate in democratic channels.

Document 2 is a request asking about the use of community centers funded by the municipality for activism and political events involving children/YP under 18. This is a response to a debate about an event in which YP under 18 learned about the situation in Gaza, made banners and peace doves, etc. The Mayor of Culture and Leisure responds that the policy of the municipality is that community centers can be booked for events, also of a political nature, as long as these don’t break the law. The policy is also that freedom of speech, also for YP under 18, goes a long way, regardless of what one’s educational opinions on the matter are. We have awarded this a score of 1 in *inclusion/exclusion* and *participation* but 0 in both directions, because, while the request and the policy addresses both inclusion and exclusion of YP from freedom of speech and political participation, it results in no changes one way or the other. We have awarded it a score of 1 in *intersection* because it addresses YP in general.

Document 3 is a request addressing the 20% cutbacks of Copenhagen’s Youth Council’s yearly budget, whether it’s expected to harm the democratic participation of YP, and what the Council proposes to do to make up for potential loss of participation. The Mayor of Children and Youth responds that it is not expected to have a negative effect on participation. We have awarded this a score of -1 in *inclusion/exclusion* and *participation* because, while the mayor states that it will not have an effect on democratic participation, the lower budget is still likely to lead to exclusion of YP from democratic events, debates and hearings, because they will have fewer employees to help them arrange their attendance and navigate the political systems, and thus likely to decrease YP’s political participation – also because the cutbacks are a deprioritization of YP’s channel for democratic participation in the city. We awarded it a score of 1 in *intersection* because it addresses YP in general.

Document 4 is from 14/3 2024 and states that the actions agreed upon in document 5, which were adopted on 14/12 2023, have been carried out. We have awarded this a score of 1 in all categories, because it aims towards, and expects to lead to, increased voter turnout among young people in the EU elections in June 2024 and thus both young people’s inclusion and participation. It addresses young people in general.

Document 5 is an amendment adopted on 14/12 2023 stating that Copenhagen Municipality must work towards initiatives that will increase the voter turnout among young people at the EU elections in June 2024. Suggested initiatives include mobile ballot stations, campaigns to make young people aware of the election, what it’s about, and its relevance for them, and others. We have awarded this amendment a score of 1 in all categories for the same reason as document 4.

CONCLUSION

Most of the national documents (20 out of 24) deal with in- or exclusion in one way or another, although very few of them address inclusion or exclusion directly. Most of them we expect will lead to inclusion (14 out of 20), while some (5) we expect will lead to exclusion. Laws within the area *health* are overwhelmingly focused on inclusion with a focus on better access to mental health care, for which the waiting lists are currently very long, and increased financial aid for dental care for YP, as dental care is not covered by the public health insurance. Meanwhile, the area *education* doesn't deal much with inclusion, and the area *labor* is the most exclusionary of the areas, with three of five laws resulting in exclusion of YP. In this case, however, it's important to take into consideration that exclusion of YP is not necessarily negative. In two of the three labor laws that lead to exclusion, YP under 18 are prohibited from operating heavy machinery in construction work to protect them from injuries. The same goes for another document, this under *health*, which excludes YP under 18 from regular and electronic cigarettes and alcohol. This is also exclusion, but not with a preventive outcome. Only two of the national documents that deal with in- or exclusion, we expect might lead to negative outcomes for YP – one which makes it possible for caretakers in institutions for foster children to remove communication devices, e.g. phones, by force, and another which grants graduates lower unemployment benefits than other unemployed people. Although the former is also meant to protect YP, and while it may lead to positive outcomes for them, the use of force and the exclusion from communication with the outside world, including family and friends, may also have a negative outcome. The latter is purely a negative outcome, seeing as it provides graduates less economic security than other unemployed people.

On the local level, only a little over half of the policies (seven out of ten) deal with in- or exclusion with two of them leading to exclusion and two of them leading to neither negative nor positive outcomes. The negative outcome is a result of a 20% cutback on funding for Copenhagen's Youth Council's secretariate which we expect will have negative outcomes for the Youth Council's abilities to participate in democratic events and proceedings. The two policies which aren't expected to have neither negative nor positive effects are because, although possible problems are presented to the Council for Jewish and financially challenged pupils, respectively, the policies do not present new actions or solutions, but instead argue that the policies already in place are sufficient.

Focus on participation on the national level is nearly non-existing with only one of the 24 documents addressing participation for YP. This is a law stating that the board of a specific school, Sorø Akademi, has two seats on their board specifically for pupils of the school. While many schools aside from this one have similar rules for pupil participation in school boards, this policy only benefits the pupils at one school. Thus, none of the documents address or lead to neither an expansion nor restriction of opportunities for participation for YP on a broader scale.

On the local level, the focus on participation is more prevalent with five of the ten documents addressing participation. These are all five documents from the policy area *participation*, while none of the policies from *education* address participation. Three of the policies we estimate will lead to an expansion of participation, while one restricts participation, and one does neither. Thus, there is very little focus overall in the laws, mostly nationally but also locally, on YP's access to democratic, political, and/or civic participation, and when it is discussed, only half aim to ensure YP's democratic participation, while the other half risks restricting it.

Only eight of the 24 national documents and three of the ten local documents address a specific group of YP while the rest address YP or, in documents about education, students or pupils in general. All of them are ‘thin’ intersections, while no documents, national or local, address or deal with ‘thick’ intersections. On the national level, the marginalized group of YP that is most addressed in the documents is physically and/or mentally disabled YP (three documents), followed by YP with mental health issues (two documents), graduates (one), YP in foster care (one), and young farmers and gardeners (one), although it’s worth questioning whether this counts as a “complex experience” among YP. On the local level, one document addresses YP without citizenship, one addresses young Jewish people, and one addresses financially challenged YP. Thus, the policies only address few marginalized positions among young people, and not for example race/ethnicity, sexual orientation, or gender/gender identity. It is however important to mention that many of the included documents on both national and local level are directed at YP under 18, which is still within the age group of this study, but also a group of YP with needs, living conditions, and general rights that differ from YP over 18 years old.

The documents on both levels do not necessarily address *complex experiences* of YP with intersecting marginalized positions or identities. Firstly, because none of the documents address more than one marginalized position or identity among YP, and secondly because, when they address one marginalized position or identity, they do not address the complexity of being in this marginalized position *while also* being young. The intersection of being young and in one of the marginalized positions does however have an effect within some of the laws. One example is document 20, where rules regarding use of force are different for minors living in institutions than would be possible for people over 18 living in institutions. In this case, both their status as institutionalized *and* their age negatively impacts their rights and inclusion. The complexities of YP’s experiences are thus, in these documents, dealt with through laws specifically aimed at the certain groups. For example, laws aimed at disabled YP to ensure access to special camps.

YP are typically addressed in general terms, such as “young people”, “pupils”, “students”, or “graduates”. In some cases, policies address disabled YP or YP without citizenship. In other cases, the policies are directed at a group of YP who are marginalized without addressing them as a certain group with specific needs, such as policies directed at YP who are in foster care, financially challenged, or vulnerable in terms of mental health. Inclusivity is not addressed directly in any of the documents on the national level, and only in four of the policies, those under *participation*, on the local level. Empowerment is only addressed indirectly on both the national and local level a few times. Locally, one policy aims to empower YP to democratic participation in- and outside of elections and one policy aims to empower YP to participate in the EU elections. Nationally, two policies are aimed at ensuring disabled YP can participate in special summer camps which may empower them to lead more autonomous lives, and one policy aims to empower YP at risk of committing crimes by giving them the right to have a “pocket money-job”. All in all, the policies in general lack a focus on empowerment.

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NATIONAL REPORT FINLAND (UTU)

PART I: INTRODUCTORY SECTION

Young people in Finland in 2024

Statistics taken from Tilastokeskus (Statistics Finland), THL (Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare), Valtion nuorisoindikaattorit (State Youth Indicators), Kela (Finnish Social Security Institution), Tietoa nuorista (Allianssi - Information about Youth), Tem työllisyyskatsaus (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland - Employment Bulletin), State reports

According to Finnish legislation, people under 29 are categorized as “young.” Here, the age range for “young” is determined by the availability of statistics and information.

	Year of statistic	Definition of young	
Background			
Population of Finland	2022	N/A	5 563 970
Number of young people in Finland	2022	15-19	957 295
Disabilities			
Young people with physical disabilities	2017	14-29	10000*
Gender			
Women	2022	15-29	464 448
Men	2022	15-29	492 847
Immigration/ethnic background			
Young people with immigrant background	2021	12-29	113 115
First generation			78 %
Second generation			22 %
Ethnic and linguistic minorities**			
Finland Swedes	2022	15-29	48 257
Sami (indigenous people)	2022	15-29	346
Romani		0-110	10000-12000*

Notes: * an estimate ** Statistics based on language, not identity. Especially many people belonging to the indigenous Sami people have lost their connection to Sami languages due to colonialistic politics.

No statistics on transgendered or others, sexual orientation, very little information about disabilities.

EDUCATION

New legislation was implemented in 2021: obligatory education now lasts until the student reaches 18 or finishes upper secondary education. Only students outside of the EU/ETA have to pay tuition fees in Finland. Otherwise, education is free in Finland. The Finnish state supports students by paying student allowance for all students (with some limitations, e.g., if the student earns too much from a job). The sum is affected by the student's age, school, whether they live alone or with parents, are married and whether they have children. It is between 43-421 euros per month. In addition, students can take state-warranted student loans of 600 euros per month. Students are also typically eligible for housing benefits. For students under the age of 18, the Finnish state also pays for all materials they need to use in their education. Number of young people who are left outside of education has dropped drastically since 2001.

Education in numbers

Students in education that aim at a degree (2022): 1 397 733

Number of young people enrolled in mandatory school (2022): 563 100

Percentage of young people outside of education and employment (15-29-year-olds) (2022): 9.1

Percentage of young people dropping out of education (2021/2022): 7

Number of students getting student benefits (2021/2022): 291 310

(From university students, 54 % and university of applied sciences students, 59 % got student benefits 2021/2022)

EMPLOYMENT

We have a specific term, “syrjäytyminen” (the literal translation is “exclusion”), that refers to being excluded from societal systems, such as school or work, and to other related issues, such as substance abuse or indebtedness. This is a common worry in Finland, and statistics from 2023 suggest that there are around 64,000 “syrjäytyneitä” young people. Risk factors for this are low education, long-term unemployment, issues with finances, and substance abuse.

Employment in numbers

Young people (0-34) living only on basic social security: 122 002

Young people seeking employment (march 2024) under 25-year-olds: 31 600

Societally excluded young people (2023): 64 000

HEALTH

Results from THL (The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare) studies in 2022 and 2023 show that the majority of children and young people feel they are in good health. Around ¼ of young people feel their

health is average or bad. However, mental health issues have become more prevalent since 2019. Young girls are doing worse than boys in Finland in different health and inclusivity indicators, and young girls, for example, rate their mental health significantly lower than young boys. The reasons behind this trend are unknown. In addition to mental health, self-harm has increased in Finland. Suicide is the cause of death of every fourth death of 15-24-year-olds. In European comparisons, young people's death by suicide is common in Finland. In general, around 750 people commit suicide yearly in Finland (which is, e.g., three times more than deaths in traffic).

Health in numbers

Suicides (2022, 10-29-year-olds): 146

Reported mental health issues: different studies suggest a 20-25 % rate of mental health issues among young people in Finland

Depression medication takers (18-24-year-olds, 2021): 7.8%

Suicidality: repetitive and serious thoughts of suicide 10-15 %, attempted suicide 3-5 %, 1/3 of young people cut themselves without suicidal aims.

HOUSING

Low-income people in Finland are eligible for housing benefits from the state. The current government just cut housing benefits (in March 2024). The housing benefit can currently be a maximum of 70 % of housing cost and is only given to low-income people. Students are currently in the same housing benefit system as the general population. However, the current government will move students to their own housing benefit system in August 2025, which will negatively affect students' economic situation. Living alone is typical, especially in bigger cities; living in shared housing is not prevalent (9 % of students lived in shared housing in 2022 (not spouse)). Student apartments are available in major study cities, and student apartments are cheaper than the market rent and provide students with lower-cost housing. In addition, municipalities in Finland offer communal housing, and some organizations offer special housing for under 30-year-olds (also non-students).

Housing politics is (mostly) a local level policy issue in Finland and in general not a prevalent policy topic.

Housing in numbers

Homeless young people (2022, under 25-year-olds): over 800, in 2023: 530

Student housing (2022): 23% of students live in student housing

PARTICIPATION

Finland provides many opportunities for youth participation. Youth councils (aimed mostly at teenagers) have been mandatory (since 2015/2017) in all of Finland's 360+ municipalities. Statistics show that 95 percent of Finnish municipalities actually have a youth council (or equivalent group). After a structural reform of social welfare and healthcare and the establishment of a regional level of

governance, youth councils are also mandatory on the regional level. Other opportunities for youth participation for those under 18 years include, for example, party membership (from 15), membership in a youth organization, engagement in participatory budgeting initiatives (available in many municipalities also for minors), and municipality initiatives. Informal participation forms for young people include protest, consumer politics, online politics, and lifestyle politics. After turning 18, young people in Finland can participate in national citizens' initiatives in addition to voting in elections.

Participation in numbers

Activity in at least one organization (2020), 15-29-year-olds: 46 %

Voter turnout 18-24 in 2023 parliamentary elections: 58 %

Voter turnout 25-29 in 2023 parliamentary elections: 62 %

SAMPLING PROCEDURES

PART II: NATIONAL ANALYSIS

The sampling of the national-level documents was conducted using the Finnish Government's official database, VALTO, which includes all the publications from the ministries from 2016 onwards, as well as some earlier publications and those of governmental agencies (<https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/>). In addition, laws and regulations were sampled from Finlex, an online database providing up-to-date legislative and other judicial information for Finland (<https://www.finlex.fi/>).

Terms related youth (e.g., nuoret, nuori, nuorten, nuoriso) were used to search for documents relevant to the analysis, along with terms related to the themes under analysis (eg. koulu, koulutus, oppiminen, työllisyys, työ, terveyst, asunto, asuminen, osallisuus, osallistuminen). The most significant difficulty was finding documents on housing that specifically referred to youth or young people. Additionally, documents related to youth employment were scarce, necessitating a review of the "Young Workers' Act", which came into force in 1993.

See the excel file for the detailed coding and analysis.

SUMMARIES OF THE ANALYSIS

EDUCATION

The documents related to the education policy area all aimed at promoting inclusivity. All the documents highlighted various youth groups targeted by specific policy measures. Because the documents focused on education, they did not always explicitly mention "youth," but often referring instead to "students" or "pupils." For instance, "students needing special support" was a recurring group mentioned in several documents.

Two of the documents are laws: the "Act on General Upper Secondary Education" (2018) and the "Act on Vocational Education and Training" (2017). Both laws are relatively recent and regulate the objectives, structure, and organization of upper secondary education in Finland, ensuring equal access to quality education that meets labour market needs while promoting further studies, general education, and lifelong learning. Since students in upper secondary education are typically young

people, these laws were considered crucial for the analysis. Both laws also address student participation, such as student councils within educational institutions. However, other documents related to this policy area did not address youth participation.

EMPLOYMENT

The documents related to the labour policy area generally aimed for inclusivity, with one exception: the "Strategy for Lifelong Guidance 2020–2023" (2020), which did not focus on inclusivity. All the documents mentioned specific youth groups, including intersectional youth groups. Several documents, in particular, highlighted groups such as NEET youth, youth in child protection services, youth in vulnerable situations, and unemployed youth — groups that are directly connected to issues of employment and work participation.

The 2015 documents, such as "Better Solutions for Supporting Young People Outside of Education and Employment" and the "Youth Guarantee Working Group's Final Report and Recommendations for Further Action," showcased a broad range of youth groups. This focus likely reflects the context in Finland, where there was significant youth unemployment in 2015 and it was higher in 2015 compared to previous years. Additionally, the Sipilä government, which took office in 2015 and served until 2019, aimed as one of its key goals to increase Finland's employment rate.

One of the documents analyzed is the "Young Workers' Act," which came into force in 1993 but is still applied in Finland to regulate work done by individuals under 18 (young workers). The act is inclusive in the sense that it protects and supports young workers equally, aiming to ensure that they can participate in the workforce safely and without discrimination, given that stricter safety regulations apply to those under 18 compared to those over 18.

None of the documents related to the policy area mentioned opportunities for political participation.

HEALTH

In each of the health-related policy programs, except for one document, efforts were made to increase youth inclusion – only one document did not include actions or proposals to enhance youth inclusion. All the documents considered various youth groups, and intersectional groups were mentioned multiple times in each document regarding inclusion. Overall, the mentioned groups regarding inclusion were numerous, covering, among others, young people studying in different educational institutions, young girls and boys, socially disadvantaged youth (such as those from low-income backgrounds), representatives of diverse minorities (such as LGBTQ+ and ethnic minorities), as well as other young people in vulnerable situations. However, these policy documents addressed few ways to politically engage youth: only the "European Child Guarantee action plan" provided pathways to increasing youth participation, but it did not consider the internal diversity of youth in this context.

Some older documents, such as the "European Child Guarantee - Finland's Action Plan" (2022), take a broader approach in addressing children and youth from various minority groups compared to some more recent documents, such as "Strengthening Young People's Wellbeing through Multidisciplinary Measures - National Youth Work and Youth Policy Programme 2024–2027" (2024). There are likely many reasons behind this, one of which could be that the previous Marin left-center government

(2019–2023) adopted a relatively ambitious approach to strengthening equality, inclusivity, and intersectionality. In contrast, the current Orpo center-right government (2023–) has tended to avoid these themes. The new government includes the right-wing populist Finns Party, which is reluctant to emphasize the issues of several minority groups and intersectionality.

HOUSING

Only three documents related to housing were included in the analysis because housing policy in Finland is primarily a local-level responsibility and not a prominent policy topic. This made it difficult to find relevant documents for this policy area. Ultimately, three documents were selected for analysis, but two of them are evaluative documents and do not contain specific policy measures. The most relevant document for the analysis was the *"Housing Policy Development Program for the Years 2021–2028"* (2021). The other documents aimed at inclusivity, but the *"Housing for Students? Survey on the Current State and Production Needs of Student Housing"* (2018) was not inclusive because although it focuses on the development and evaluation of student housing (and thus considers policies related to youth), it failed to address the diversity of youth or the needs of different youth groups.

Intersectional youth groups were highlighted in the documents, even though no specific policy measures were proposed for these groups. For example, housing-related groups such as homeless youth, homeless youth using drugs, and students living in student housing were mentioned. However, none of the documents addressed factors related to political participation.

PARTICIPATION

In the policy documents concerning participation, each aimed to increase youth inclusion and address diverse groups of young people. Except for the Youth Act, the documents mentioned several intersectional groups regarding inclusion, such as youth from ethnic and LGBTQ+ minorities, disabled youth, immigrant youth, asylum-seeking youth, and many others.

Additionally, each document on this theme included methods for politically engaging youth—concrete proposals for participation tools were presented extensively. Some documents mentioned certain intersectional groups in the context of participation methods, but overall, the internal diversity of youth was not emphasized as much in the context of political participation methods as it was otherwise. However, youth from ethnic minorities, for example, were considered in several documents.

Overall, the internal groups of youth were addressed quite comprehensively in the documents from the Sanna Marin's government (2019–2023). These documents paid significant attention to various minority groups. Additionally, "The Youth, Peace, and Security Action Plan" has an explicitly intersectional approach in line with the government's stance.

LOCAL LEVEL ANALYSIS

The sampling of the local-level documents was conducted using the municipalities' websites and statistical databases. In Vantaa, the official website (<https://www.vantaa.fi/>) along with the statistics

and research website was used (<https://www.vantaa.fi/fi/kaupunki-ja-paatoksenteko/tietoa-vantaasta/tilastot-ja-tutkimukset>). In Espoo, the official website (<https://www.espoo.fi/fi>) and the statistics and research website (<https://www.espoo.fi/fi/kaupunki-ja-paatoksenteko/tutkimus-ja-tilastot>) were utilized. In Turku, the official website (<https://www.turku.fi/>) and Turku Info (<https://www.turku.fi/en/turku-info>) were used. For Tampere (<https://www.tampere.fi/>) and Oulu (<https://www.ouka.fi/>), their official website were used.

Terms related to youth (e.g., nuoret, nuori, nuorten, nuoriso) were used to search for documents relevant to the analysis, along with terms related to the themes under analysis (eg., koulu, koulutus, oppiminen, osallisuus, osallistuminen).

See the excel file for the detailed coding and analysis.

SUMMARIES OF THE ANALYSIS

EDUCATION

At the local level, all documents related to education aimed to increase youth inclusion. Most documents addressed various youth groups and minorities in the context of inclusion, and all documents discussed at least a few intersectional groups related to inclusion. The mentioned groups regarding inclusion were among others, disabled youth, youth belonging to gender and sexual minorities, youth from ethnic and linguistic minorities, and so on. Three documents did not address youth political participation, whereas two documents aimed to create pathways for increasing youth participation. Only one of these specifically considered the internal diversity of youth in the context of political participation.

PARTICIPATION

For analysis, we aimed to select the children's and youth well-being plans from each city regarding political participation since, in Finland, every municipality is required to develop such a plan. That would ensure that the analysis would be as comparable as possible. However, the well-being plans were not usable for every city, so the analysis includes the well-being plans for Espoo, Turku, and Oulu. For Vantaa, the "Child-Friendly Vantaa Action Plan 2022-2023" (2022) was included, and for Tampere, the city's "Participation and Community Plan" (2023) was used.

All the documents related to participation aimed to increase youth inclusion. With the exception of the document from Vantaa, all documents also recognized various youth groups. In fact, it appears that at the local level, young people and different youth groups are addressed more concretely and specifically than in governmental-level documents. For instance, youth from diverse language and cultural backgrounds, immigrant youth, and youth with special needs were highlighted several times in the documents of different cities.

Since the documents were focused on participation, each one also addressed youth political participation. The concrete actions taken by the cities related to youth political participation mainly involved youth councils or regional participation groups, as well as participatory budgeting, which aimed to include young people. In Finland, the "Local Government Act" (2015) requires every municipality to establish a youth council to ensure young people have opportunities to influence decisions. The "City of Oulu's Children and Youth Well-being Plan 2022" (2022) even highlighted

political participation by including immigrant youth and youth from various language and cultural backgrounds in regional participation groups.

CONCLUDING SECTION

Do governmental policies deal with inclusion or exclusion? If yes, to what extent do these policies result in positive or negative outcomes for young people?

Governmental policies at both the national and local levels in Finland largely aim to foster inclusion rather than exclusion. The various policy documents analyzed reveal a clear commitment to improving the status and opportunities for young people. This is particularly evident in the former prime minister Sanna Marin's government era (2019-2023), where a significant number of documents emphasized inclusivity.

Positive outcomes for young people can be observed in the form of increased recognition and support. However, while the general intent and rhetoric support inclusion, the actual impact varies. Policies often lack specific, actionable measures and detailed implementation strategies, which can limit the practical benefits of these inclusive intentions.

Do governmental policies deal with opportunities for participation? To what extent do they expand or restrict opportunities for participation?

Governmental policy documents frequently address the importance of political participation among young people. Initiatives such as youth councils, forums for youth consultation, and the Youth Parliament are mentioned as means to enhance youth engagement in political processes. These initiatives aim to create platforms where young people can voice their opinions and influence decision-making.

However, often, the governmental policy documents highlight the necessity for improved participation but fall short of detailing comprehensive mechanisms to achieve this. Thus, the opportunities for participation are present in theory, but their effectiveness in practice depends on the execution and the actual empowerment provided to young participants.

If governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations, how governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations?

Finland's governmental policy documents show an awareness of the diverse experiences, identities, and aspirations of youth. The mention of various intersectional groups indicates a recognition of the multifaceted nature of youth identities. Policies often acknowledge different backgrounds and needs, such as those of immigrant youth, marginalized groups, and youth facing social exclusion. Also, youth needing additional support, youth in child protection and NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) youth are mentioned in the documents several times.

Despite this awareness, there is a tendency to address these complexities more in the background or introductory sections of policy documents rather than integrating them into the core policy measures. The nuances of youth experiences are acknowledged but not sufficiently acted upon in practical terms.

Does governmental policy typically categorize young people using general terms, or does it incorporate considerations for intersectionality? Are inclusivity, empowerment addressed comprehensively within governmental policy?

The incorporation of intersectionality in governmental policy is present but not deeply embedded. Policies do recognize different groups and their specific challenges; however, the treatment of these groups often remains at a general level. In many cases, the policy proposals do not delve deeply into tailored solutions that address the intersectional nature of these challenges.

Inclusivity and empowerment are addressed within the governmental policy framework, but the degree of comprehensiveness varies. While the intent to be inclusive is clear, the policies could have a more detailed and integrated approach that ensures the various dimensions of youth identities are consistently and thoroughly considered.

Local level policy documents

In our analysis of local level documents, we focused primarily on youth welfare plans and equality and equity plans, as these documents are mandatory for each municipality in Finland. In a few cases, the relevant documents were not useful for our analysis because they did not mention young people; in these instances, we included other relevant documents. Across all the cities analyzed, there was a clear intention to enhance inclusivity. Regarding participation, city policy documents were generally more explicit about improving opportunities for youth engagement and provided more concrete suggestions for enhancing youth political participation compared to national-level documents.

The suggestions in city documents were generally more specific, such as emphasizing the role of youth councils, participatory budgeting, and other mechanisms for involving young people in the municipal decision-making process. For instance, most cities highlighted the importance of youth councils as platforms for youth representation and influence. They also detailed how participatory budgeting could be used to give young people a direct voice in deciding how municipal funds are allocated, thus fostering a sense of ownership and involvement in local governance. Furthermore, these documents often outlined clear procedures and stages at which youth consultation would be integrated into the decision-making processes, demonstrating a commitment to ensuring that youth voices are heard and considered.

Additionally, local level policies frequently provided detailed action plans and timelines for implementing these initiatives, which were often absent in national-level policies. This suggests that at the municipal level, there is a stronger emphasis on operationalizing inclusivity and participation in practical terms

Overall conclusion

Overall, Finnish governmental and local level policies show a commendable effort towards inclusion and participation of young people. The intent to create an inclusive environment and provide opportunities for youth engagement is evident across various documents and initiatives. However, to fully realize these goals, policies should move beyond general acknowledgments and incorporate

detailed, actionable strategies that address the specific needs of diverse youth groups. Even though the recognition of intersectionality and the complexities of youth identities is present, all documents did not take into account how this recognition translates into concrete actions.

NATIONAL REPORT ITALY (UNIBO)

Policy narratives in Italy

This report provides an overview and content analysis of the current situation of policies that address young people in Italy and in the Emilia-Romagna region, specifically regarding the issues of education, employment, health, housing and participation.

Introduction

Young people in Italy (frequency analysis)

In Italy youth aged 18–34 are about 10,200,000 (ISTAT, 2023a), and those aged 11–19 years are 5,144,171, namely 8.7% of the total population (ISTAT, 2023b). In the Italian population the prevalence of women grows with age: among the youth, men are slightly more than women, and a balance is reached when the age reaches 40–44 (ISTAT, 2023c). According to IPSOS (2024), around 7% of Italian adults over 18 identify as LGBTQ+, and usually prevalence is higher among Gen Z youth when compared to older generations.

The proportion of “foreign” youth aged between 11 and 19 in 2024 is 497,464, namely 9.7% of Italian youth of the same age (ISTAT, 2023b). In 59.5% of cases they are actually born in Italy (although they do not have Italian citizenship, according to Italy laws): 11.7% were born abroad and arrived in Italy before the age of 6, 17% migrated during school age (between 6 and 10), and 11.8% arrived at 11 years old or more. The Eurochild 2022 report points out that Italian children living in absolute poverty are 1,346,000 (13.5%), and that 27.1% are at risk of poverty and social exclusion (Eurochild, 2022).

When it comes to disability, ISTAT data from 2022 (ISTAT, 2022) reveal that in the population aged 0–44 around 1.5% have severe limitations in daily activities due to disability, and 6.6% meet non-severe limitations. In school, for every 100 students, 4.4% in primary school and 3–4.5% in secondary school have a disability. Among these, 209,738 have an intellectual impairment, 8316 a motor impairment, 5679 a hearing impairment and 3917 a visual impairment.

Education

The issue of the right of access to quality education in Italy is a crucial one. Reports on the issue point out that the country suffers from a severe education crisis (CNG, 2024). In the last 20 years, Italy has shown some progress in closing the gaps in the education level reached by youth (down to 14.9% of 20–24-year-olds with no more than middle school diploma in 2022) and early school leaving rates (down to 11.5% in 2022) in comparison to the EU27 average (ISTAT, 2024a). The data however show a two-speed country: it is in fact southern Italy that suffers most early school leaving, with regions such as Calabria (14%), Campania (16.4%), Apulia (17.6%) and Sicily (21.1%) registering the most alarming results.

A critical issue remains addressing educational poverty¹² – data shows that there is strong territorial variability in the composite indexes of educational poverty outcomes and resources, as several regions present difficult situations (e.g., Sardegna, Sicily, Calabria, but there are also weaknesses in rural zones in Emilia-Romagna; ISTAT, 2024a). Material poverty affects learning outcomes and, indeed, adolescents living in families with socio-economic disadvantage show greater early school dropouts and higher lack of minimum competences in the main disciplines (Save the Children, 2022). Metropolitan cities also distinguish

¹² Defined as “the deprivation of children and adolescents from the opportunity to learn, experience, develop and allow their abilities, talents and aspirations to flourish freely” (Save the Children, 2022)

themselves negatively with respect to schools, where the percentage of school buildings without a certificate of fitness reaches 70% (62.8% is the average in Italy), and the presence of a communal space, canteen, gymnasium, technical or computer classrooms is lower than the country's average, which is already marked by serious deficiencies: a gymnasium is lacking in three out of five schools, a communal social space in more than one out of three, and technical and computer classrooms are a dream for at least half of the underage students (Save the Children, 2023).

The school inclusion of students with disabilities is a priority in Italian educational policies, but data show the persistence of some weaknesses (ISTAT, 2024b). The rate of students with disabilities is growing (4.1% of the total in year 2022/2023), as is the share of support teachers (+10%), but 1 in 3 do not have specialized training and 12% are assigned late. Critically, there is strong discontinuity in teaching: 60% of pupils with disabilities change support teachers from one year to the next, 9% during the same school year. Moreover, 27% of schools do not have enough computer workstations adapted for pupils with disabilities, while only 40% of schools are accessible to pupils with motor disability.

The overall education level in the population aged 25-34 also remains below other European countries. These are joined by data on university dropouts at 7.3% in the first year after enrolment (CNG, 2024). Non-academic tertiary vocational courses (offered by *Istituti Tecnici Superiori*, ITS) suffer poor dissemination with only 2.5% of newly enrolled students choosing them, even though almost 80% of graduates find occupation within 12 months. Moreover, allocation of resources such as scholarships and state funding for tertiary education is deemed insufficient as it is estimated that all Italian regions have at least 15% of uncovered needs (students who are eligible but do not receive funding).

Employment

Young people in Italy suffer lack of access to employment and job security. The share of unemployed 15–24 year-olds has been rising to 21.8% in comparison to a stable total unemployment of 7.2% in January 2024 (ISTAT, 2024a). As with other social conditions, there are situations of profound heterogeneity in the country, with unemployment rates close to 3.8% in the autonomous province of Bolzano and peaks close to 34% in Campania and Sicily.

The issue of the high rate of Italian youth Not in Education, Employment, or Training (NEET) is also well documented – the BES report evidenced that in 2019 Italy was in the first place for NEET incidence in the EU with 22.3% rate compared to 12.8% EU average (ISTAT, 2022). This gap has been closing in post-pandemic years as NEET youth in Italy have decreased to 16.1% in 2023, although the country remains the second in terms of incidence in the EU (ISTAT, 2024). An important influence is found in the educational opportunities, as the share of the NEET condition rises among those with lower education level or with vocational school title. The phenomenon is also higher among young women.

The incidence of individual absolute poverty on average decreases as age increases. In 2023, the highest incidence of absolute poverty is recorded for those under 18 years of age (14.0% of minors are poor, compared to 9.8% of the population average, totalling 1.3 million minors). Higher values than the national average are also recorded for 18–34 year olds (11.9%; ISTAT, 2024).

Regarding the level of occupation, in Italy, slightly more than one in five employed young people work with a part-time contract (22.6%), a share that drops by about 5 p.p. if the age group considered is broadened. According to estimates, about a quarter of these young part-timers would be willing to work full-time (involuntary part-time). The estimated probability of transition from one job to another (job-to-job) is higher

for young workers (15-24 years old) – 10% – than for the broader population group (15–74 years old; Rapporto Italia Generativa, 2023).

In terms of salary, previous data show that it is precisely young people and, in particular, women under 30 who earn less in Italy: between the ages of 20 and 24, the average is EUR 11,456 gross for men and EUR 8,063 gross for women, with values just above EUR 15,000 on average in the 25-29 age group. It should be emphasised that, with regard to salary wages, the data show a different trend according to the level of education of young people: research shows that there is a 40% leap in earnings among those with a school diploma and a master's degree.

There are also significant barriers to youth entrepreneurship. In 2022, youth enterprises were just over half a million, or 11.7% of the total. And, in just over ten years, around 20% of under-35 companies in Italy have been closed, especially in the Centre-South.

Health

Generally speaking, in many health-related aspects Italian youth seem to be in good conditions when compared to the EU average (Rapporto Italia Generativa, 2023): this is the case, for example, of levels of obesity, depressive symptoms, suicide rate, smoking and alcohol use (although, when it comes to smoking and drinking, Italian levels were only slightly below EU average). Nevertheless, youth perception of their mental and physical health has worsened during and immediately after the pandemic. According to the Italian Institute for Health (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, 2023), in recent years, young people's perception of being in good health has decreased when it comes both to physical symptoms (e.g., headache, sleep troubles) and mental wellbeing. For instance, during and immediately after the pandemic 49.4% youth reported having experienced anxiety and depression, and 20.7% of under 25 youth had increased their alcohol and other substance consumption (AIG, 2022). Other issues that deserve being mentioned are gambling, which is a relevant issue for Italian youth, with data showing high levels of episodes of gambling over the course of a year (40% of young males, 20% of young females; Rapporto Italia Generativa, 2023) and sexual behaviors. Concerning this aspect, a recent study about sexually transmitted infections in adolescents and young adults (Cannovo et al., 2024) points out that youth aged 13–18 show precocious sexual activity but little attention to their sexual health in terms of getting tested for STI. In this sense, young women, especially when aged 15–19, seem to be more aware, attentive of the risk and show greater attention to their health. Another phenomenon that must be considered when dealing with mental health of young people is bullying: according to the national report Health Behavior in School-aged Children (2022), prevalence of bullying are more or less stable (20% in 11-yrs old that decreases with growing age), but cyberbullying is increasing in 11–13 years old teenagers, with no distinction of gender.

When it comes to children and teenagers that are not Italian citizens (although, according to the Italian law, this category includes children born in Italy from a foreign family), in the last decade there has been a strong increase (+201,8%) of non-Italian minors who turned to mental health public services, compared to Italians (+51,7%) according to a 2024 Emilia-Romagna region local report (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2024) The most frequent diagnoses are language disorders, learning disorders, intellectual disability, autism.

Lastly, different sources point out that LGBTQ+ youth's health should be particularly object of care and attention. To provide a couple of examples, a 2021 Italian study (Scandurra et al., 2021) reveals that young transgender and gender non-conforming people had higher levels of mental health problems, when compared to older participants. Moreover, a recent report (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2024) shows that 12% of LGBTIQ Italian respondents reported thinking often or always of committing suicide in the year before the survey.

Housing

It is (unfortunately) well known that in Italy the average number of young people living in the parental home is quite higher when compared to the European average. In fact, according to Eurostat (2022) data, Italy is one of the European countries with the highest percentage of young people aged 18–34 living with their parents: 69.4% (72% of young men, 66% of young women), which is even higher than the percentage registered in 2013 (62.5%). In Europe, the average age at which young people leave the parental home is 26.4 years; in Italy, the average age is 30 years (along with other countries especially in southern Europe, such as Spain, Greece, Croatia, Malta). As reported in the Italia Generativa 2023 report, the roots of this phenomenon may be identified in cultural reasons, on the one hand, and on the other to economic barriers related to accessing work, housing, achieving independence and increases in housing costs. Also relevant is the phenomenon of minors and young adults involved in homelessness. A 2023 report by Save the Children indicates that homeless minors in Italy are nearly 13.000 – a phenomenon that can also have been exacerbated by crises such as pandemic impacts and rising cost of living and housing, according to Eurocities (2023). Two additional issues that deserve attention. The first is the situation of care leavers (namely, young adults that turning 18 have to exit the care system they entered following removal from their family of origin on the basis of a court order), who are forced to make a sudden transition to the “adult” world and who require preventive and protective actions of psychosocial risks to which they may be exposed, and which has seen the implementation of a project and establishment of a dedicated Youth Conference promoted by the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy, as part of the fight against poverty and social exclusion. The second is the situation of unaccompanied foreign minors (Minori Stranieri Non Accompagnati, MSNA), who are identified as being in a condition of particular vulnerability, making it necessary to set up appropriate modes of reception in specialized facilities and residential services.

Participation

According to the *Global Youth Development Index*, Italy has an especially critical performance in the area of political and civic participation – it is in 125th place. Disillusionment with electoral politics among young people is a long-running phenomenon in the Italian context. Recent voting data indicate a strong disinterest among young people in voting, with abstention levels among 18 to 34-year-olds reaching 42.7% in the last political elections, compared to 36.1% recorded by the Ministry of the Interior for the entire electorate (Eures, 2024). Electoral disaffection is even higher – 50% – among youth in conditions of socioeconomic marginality (ASVIS, 2024). Previous opinion poll data also shows that of those who went to the polls, about 90% declare that they did so purely out of critical sense (CNG, 2024). Beyond distrust and protest, abstentionism among youth is heavily impacted by barriers such as the impossibility of voting at distance (10% of those with right to vote are non-residents who would need to travel to vote) and the difficult process of obtaining citizenship for youth with migrant background, even if born in Italy (ASVIS, 2024).

At the same time, there has been a drastic reduction in the representation of young people in formal politics: the recent cut in Parliamentarians, provided for by a Constitutional Amendment after a referendum in 2020, has in fact affected almost exclusively the youngest component (up to 35 years of age) which has suffered a decrease of 80% between 2018 and 2022 – from 133 to 27 elected representatives, i.e. from 21.1% to a marginal 6.8% of the total. At the same time, the average age of those elected has risen by over 5 years, going from 44.1 years in 2018 to 49.3 years in 2022 (Eures, 2024). Local politics sees a similar lack of representation as only 3.7% of Italian municipalities (287 out of 7,718) have a mayor who is under 35, and among these there is no provincial capital. Only two provinces, Forlì and Reggio Emilia – both in the Emilia-Romagna region, – have presidents under 35 and no regional president is under 35 (CNG, 2024).

The diminishing influence of youth is also reflected in their perceptions of institutional unresponsiveness, as opinion poll data shows that 85% of respondents believe that the level of political attention on youth issues is inadequate (Eures, 2024), while 74% would like to see greater protagonism of young people in politics (ASVIS, 2024).

In general, youth political participation in Italy is lower than that of other age groups – 40% carried out at least one political activity in 2023 compared to 55% of the general average. Youth participation in political life has also progressively become more dematerialized, with the possibility of expressing opinions on social or political issues or participating in consultations and votes via the web, activities that are more widespread in this segment of the population – 34% carried out at least one of the two activities in 2023 and these represent the only form of political and civic participation for more than 1 in 10 young people (ISTAT, 2024a).

Reports on youth participation in Italy, however, note that distance from traditional politics has been generally accompanied by a higher social and civic activism among younger people (CNG, 2024). Recent years have seen an important decrease of such participation. While prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, the 14–24 years age group showed higher active involvement in demonstrations and protests – e.g., in 2019, 12.8% in comparison to 3.9% in the general population, – in 2023 the rate has fallen to 6.8% of young people compared to 5.7% among the general population (ISTAT, 2024a).

Volunteering has also been historically higher among the younger population in Italy and in 2023 the rate of volunteering (i.e., free activity for voluntary associations or groups) among the 16–24 age group was 8% (ISTAT, 2024a). In the progressive exit from Covid, participation in volunteering is growing again, especially among the very young (14–17 years old) – for whom, due to the health emergency, the possibility of carrying out such activities had collapsed to 3.9%. In 2022 it grew by 2.5 points, the most significant increase compared to the different age groups. Overall, social participation (i.e., in cultural, recreational, political, civic and sports associations) among 14–24-year-olds is high (close to 40% in comparison to the average 30%) and they are the age group with higher involvement in associations focused on rights, environment and peace (ASVIS, 2024).

According to ISTAT data, the non-profit organisations (NPOs) that identify as their target population minors and young adults up to 34 years old were 25,9% of the NPOs active in 2021, while 51,8% do not identify specific age target for their activities (ISTAT, 2023d). Gender differences in volunteering seem to emerge among adult age groups (over 30 years old), while shares of younger men and women volunteering in NPOs are much closer (8.1% and 7.5%; ISTAT, 2023d, 2024a).

Another indicator of the civic participation of Italian youth is the significant interest in the Universal Civil Service (UCS), instituted in 2017 as the primary governmental tool that aims to promote volunteering among 18 to 28-year-olds – it is evidenced by the consistent excess of applications with respect to the available places (e.g., 105,098 applications for 71,550 places in 2023; ASVIS, 2024). It is also highlighted, however, that there is significant dispersion within the complex procedural process of application and taking service, as the percentage of volunteers who complete the service is approximately 74%.

Policy Analysis

The retrieval of relevant governmental policies, laws and public programs followed different strategies – the researchers performed searches in institutional websites of ministries and public programs, as well as in databases of national and regional norms and laws. Potentially relevant documents in each policy area were reviewed starting from the most recent ones – adopted in 2024 – and going backwards. The final selection

of 25 national level and 10 regional level documents prioritized those that contained substantial focus on youth (i.e., documents with isolated mentions of young people were excluded) and rich content in terms of description of political aims, as well as in terms of importance and impact within the specific policy area (i.e., brief deliberations and decrees with limited changes to existing laws or with only funding distribution were excluded).

The following sections present the analysed documents, their scope and the evaluation according to the analytical criteria. Within each area, documents are organised from the most recent to the least recent one.

National Level

Education

Educational policy documents were found to address specific educational needs, especially regarding students with disabilities (Document 1 and 2). Comprehensive actions for inclusive schools are outlined in Italy's main childhood policy plan (Document 4), as well as the principal financing programme through EU funds the National Programme School and Skills (Document 5). Attention to specific needs of LGBTQIA+ students was found in the relative national strategy (Document 4).

6 Urgent provisions ... for educational support for students with disabilities, for the regular start of the 2024/2025 school year and on universities and research
<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2024/05/31/24G00089/CONSOLIDATED>

Entry into force: 31 May 2024 with decree law by the President of the Republic

The decree law 71/2024 provides provisions aimed at the enhancement of specialization training in activities of education support for students with disabilities and at ensuring the continuity of temporary teachers in support positions in order to protect the rights of students with disabilities. The measures seek to meet the current need for support teachers by providing alternative channels for training on an extraordinary and temporary basis, as well as by giving priority to the hiring of teachers with experience in temporary support positions, even if without a specialization qualification for teaching students with disabilities. While the measures deal with inclusion and the right to education, they are emergency reductions of issues with providing the essential educational services and do not expand the existing policies for inclusion of students with disabilities.

Another provision is the assignment of a teacher dedicated to teaching Italian to foreigners for classes with a number of foreign students, who are enrolling for the first time in the National Education System and who do not possess basic linguistic skills in Italian, equal to or greater than 20% of the students in the class. Moreover, further measures for facilitating the full school inclusion of foreign students are identified and assigned funding from the National Programme Schools and Competences (Document 10). These measures contribute to the increase of social inclusion for foreign students ("thin" intersectionality"). The document does not deal with opportunities for participation.

7 Corrective Provisions for the Adoption of the National Model of Individualized Educational Plan and Related Guidelines
<https://www.miur.gov.it/web/guest/-/decreto-ministeriale-n-153-del-1-agosto-2023>

Entry into force: 1 August 2023 with ministerial decree (Ministry of Education and Ministry of Economy and Finance)

The Individualized Educational Plan (*Piano Educativo Individualizzato*; PEI) is the main educational and teaching design tool that promotes the inclusion of students with disabilities and guarantees their right to fully participate in school life and realize their potential. The analyzed decree modifies the Operational Working Group for Inclusion (GLO), the actions, the models, and the guidelines for the PEI model, defined in 2020. It seeks to resolve some of the critical issues raised in court over the last two years.

In general, the PEI model “identifies educational and study objectives, tools, strategies and methods to create a learning environment in the dimensions of relationships, socialization, communication, interaction, orientation and autonomy, also on the basis of educational co-responsibility interventions undertaken by the entire school community to satisfy the identified educational needs”. It involves, based on observation of the student, the preparation of a profile, the definition of personalized or differentiated education path, specific learning objectives and criteria, activities of support and integration, and personalized evaluation modalities. The GLO responsible for drafting and managing the PEI is composed of co-titular teachers or the class council, including the specialized teacher for teaching support, and chaired by the school principal or his delegate, other professional figures of support, as well as the student’s parents. The active participation of the student is also guaranteed according to the principle of self-determination.

The corrective provisions clarify: the composition and functioning of the GLO, by including further professional figures (e.g., guidance and specialist assistants); the systematic observation activities; the disciplinary evaluation method. It defines the need of a shared request by family and healthcare specialists to concede continuous absence; and a new modality of identification of the need of professional support resources and amount of assistance in terms of hours. It also expands the communication assistance service to students with visual and hearing impairment (rather than only to those “deprived of sight or hearing”).

Overall, the PEI seeks to expand social inclusion of students with disability in terms of recognition, accessibility, and non-discrimination in school contexts. It does not address the involvement of students with disability in decision-making, even through school participation activities (e.g., councils, unions or participative programs).

8 **5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents 2022-2023: Policies for Education and Equity**
https://www.minori.gov.it/sites/default/files/idi_quintopianoazione_220725-2.pdf

Entry into force: 25 January 2022 with decree by the President of the Republic

Within the area of education, the 5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents 2022-2023 [*V Piano di azione per l’infanzia e l’adolescenza 2022-2023*], recalls the importance of co-responsibility pacts between schools, students, families, local networks and the third sector, as well as the transversal teaching of civic education, introduced by law in 2019. It also draws on previous policies that position schools as important context for health promotion and risk prevention – e.g., the Integrated Policy Guidelines for Schools that Promotes Health (see paragraph 2.1.4 Health, Document 20), which aim to promote the inclusion of health promotion as a continuous and integrated educational proposal throughout the entire school curriculum.

The identified actions highlight the role of schools as inclusive contexts that can facilitate contrasting inequality and marginalization, especially through the collaboration with students, families and local communities and propose to: develop new recommendations for co-responsibility between school, students and families; activate modules on childhood and adolescence rights within the teaching of civic education; define protocols for extra-school activities in public spaces; involve the educating community (including students) in consultations for the integration of guidelines on risk prevention and cyberbullying.

These are all actions addressed to students in general without any mention of specific complexities and conditions of disadvantage. Other actions, however, focus on contrasting poverty and vulnerabilities in the school context, and aim to “expand the range of services and opportunities available to minors and, in particular, those in vulnerable conditions”: extending the school lunch service starting from places with high educational poverty toward universal access; ultra-broadband connectivity provision for schools; support for activities aimed at the acquisition of digital skills and for teaching at distance; financial support for connectivity services for families with low income; realization of experimental projects for minors in conditions of absolute poverty, to combat educational poverty, digital divide and school dropout, through a personalized educational plan of support defined with the participation of minors and their parents.

Overall, the Plan outlines a strong effort for the social inclusion of minors, and especially minors in conditions of economic vulnerability, in terms of recognizing their diverse needs for services in support of their education; making sure services are available to everyone and ensuring that their interests are taken into account (e.g., consultation for guidelines or participation in defining their personal education plan). Even though participation is generally mentioned, however, the actions do not point toward concrete provisions that expand opportunities for enacting political participation/decision-making within the education sector.

9 National Strategy LGBT+ 2022-2025: Education

<https://www.unar.it/portale/documents/20125/113907/Strategia+nazionale+LGBTI%2B+2022+rev+A.pdf/8f04f55a-ee93-92b5-2bf3-d5bd59e7c163?t=1665040970207>

Entry into force: 6 October 2022 with a directorial decree by the Department for Equal Opportunities

The National Strategy LGBT+ 2022-2025 is aimed at preventing and fighting discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. It contains “measures to strengthen the protection of the rights of LGBT+ people and promote equal treatment and non-discrimination with a view to the full inclusion of all people, in line with the European Strategy for LGBTIQ Equality 2020-2025”. It outlines the plans regarding strategic objectives and concrete actions broken down in the priority areas of occupation and welfare, safety, health, education/training/sport, culture/communication/media, database/monitoring/evaluation. Its development has been supported with a social dialogue with LGBT+ associations within the Consultation Table for the Protection of LGBT+ Rights (participative body aimed at drafting proposals and actions).

The area of education is intended as transversal to contrasting discrimination, especially through specific training “in all areas where there is a perceived lack of knowledge of the issues related to LGBT+ issues” – e.g. operators in public administrations, justice, information, healthcare, and the sports sector.

In schools, promoting education on respecting differences, training for school managers, teachers, ATA staff and dissemination of good practices is implemented through: establishment of a Table with the Ministry of Education to share needs and develop concrete actions; teaching modules on discrimination within civic education; monitoring homo-lesbian-transphobic bullying and cyberbullying in schools; training courses for staff; monitoring and dissemination of good practices; increasing courses at distance on LGBT+ topics; development and dissemination of measures for the inclusion and well-being of students and employees in schools, with the involvement of public/private bodies and the competent Ministries.

In universities, the actions involve: establishment of a Table with the Ministry of Education to share needs and develop concrete actions; implementation of measures of inclusion and monitoring in the Gender

Balance and the Gender Equality Plan (GEP); include among the tasks carried out by anti-violence desks and the equality advisor also the listening of LGBTI+ people; promote the right to study of transgender people in universities also through the alias career and the "double booklet"; develop a multi-level, inclusive and comprehensive educational offer of LGBTI+ issues; promote theses and research work in universities on LGBTI+ issues, also through the establishment of specific scholarships; plan teaching modules based on Gender Medicine, related to Occupational Medicine; design training courses on an online platform aimed at technical-administrative staff, teachers and researchers; strengthen networks between universities to exchange information on good practices adopted in terms of curricular and post-graduate training, research and inclusion; encourage third mission actions aimed at the territory; plan and implement an inclusion index aimed at monitoring the different university realities.

Moreover, it is intended to "provide opportunities, tools and activities to encourage the activation of young people... as well as to inform and raise awareness among young people on LGBT+ issues"; specifically, through links relating to LGBT+ issues on the web platform "GIOVANI2030", with the aim of promoting and raising awareness of greater youth inclusion.

Overall, the Strategy foresees many actions of greater youth LGBT+ social inclusion in schools and universities. Opportunities for participation in decision-making, however, are scarce and unclear – the establishment of collaboration with the Ministry of Education is included, but it is not clear what level of participation is intended and no specific role of young people is specified in these actions.

10 National Programme School and Skills 2021-2027

<https://pn20212027.istruzione.it/programma-nazionale/>

Entry into force: 1 December 2022, modified on 9 October 2023 with European Commission Implementing Decision

The National Programme School and Skills 2021-2027 under the ownership of the Ministry of Education and Merit and financed through ERDF and ESF+ funds, contains the strategic priorities of the education sector and runs for seven years.

The Programme contributes to the achievement of Policy Objective 4 of the Cohesion Policy, 'A more social Europe', by aiming to improve the quality, inclusiveness, effectiveness and labour market relevance of education and training systems, to promote equal access to and completion of inclusive and quality education, including through infrastructure development and distance learning, and to enhance lifelong learning.

Specific attention is given to social inclusion in education in all objectives of the program with attention to accessibility and equality, specifically regarding territorial divide (South Italy and regions with greater difficulties), poverty concentration, migration. Priorities on raising skill levels, guaranteeing a quality education system, supporting students with vulnerabilities or special educational needs are aimed at reducing the phenomenon of 'educational poverty' and guaranteeing a level of citizenship skills that enables active participation in social and political life. "Disadvantaged groups" are specifically mentioned regarding interventions of expansion of school time, inclusion and combating school drop-out – in particular, specific actions are addressed towards integration of diverse cultures, territories where the rate of students from migrant backgrounds is high, students with special educational needs and disabilities, Roma, Sinti and

Caminanti¹³, reduction of poverty. Actions of enhancement in the use of technology, laboratory equipment, and digital teaching infrastructure are also meant as inclusive tools for students with special educational needs and disabilities, and marginalized students with limited access to digital devices and the Internet, including those living in remote or segregated areas. The principle of promotion of equality, inclusion and non-discrimination is integrated in all actions. However, participation and dialogue regarding the planned interventions is considered in relation to local networks and partnerships or the third sector, with no specific consideration of young people's voice.

Overall, the program has strong objectives regarding social inclusion of diverse youth in the education sector with "thin" intersectional attention to specific groups of students. It does not offer opportunities for participation.

Employment

Labour policies in Italy have been focused on youth significantly, as the issues of unemployment and NEET incidence have become crucial priorities. Recent provisions are aimed at supporting youth (self-)employment (Documents 11 and 13), youth entrepreneurship (Document 12). The current reference funding programme on youth employment is Youth, Women, and Work (Document 14), while the plan New Competences outlines the focus on training for employability with specific attention to youth (Document 15).

11 Further Urgent Provisions on the matter of Cohesion Policies

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2024/05/07/24G00077/CONSOLIDATED>

Entry into force: 7 May 2024 with decree law 60/2024 by the President of the Republic

The Decree Law 60/2024 provides provisions on the use of resources within the European Cohesion Policies. It contains actions in support of youth self-employment and entrepreneurship, and of the stable employment of young people.

The measures contain the financing of economic initiatives aimed at starting self-employment, entrepreneurial and freelance activities, on an individual or collective basis, for young people under the age of 35 who meet one of the following requirements: (a) condition of marginality, social vulnerability and discrimination, as defined by the National Plan Youth, Women and Work 2021 – 2027 (see Document 15); (b) unemployed, inactive and unemployable; (c) unemployed recipients of the measures of the active policy programme Employability Guarantee for Workers. Greater amounts for financing are recognized to such economic initiatives started in the South Italy regions.

Moreover, the provisions define and enact the Youth Bonus (Art.22) which recognizes an exemption from the payment of social security contributions for employers who hire young people (up to 35 years old) with open-ended contracts according to the criteria set out in the National Programme for Young People, Women and Work 2021 – 2027 (see Document 15). The bonus is aimed at increasing the stable employment of young people. The sum limit for the exemption is extended for employers in the South Italy regions with the aim to reduce territorial divides. An even greater sum limit is destined for young people who take up an entrepreneurial activity operating within strategic sectors for the development of new technologies and the digital and ecological transition (Art. 21).

¹³ a nomadic group spread throughout Sicily

Overall, the provisions are aimed at the social inclusion of young people in employment, with particular attention to unemployed youth and youth in conditions of marginality, social vulnerability and discrimination. Participation is not addressed.

12

Provisions for the Promotion and Development of Youth Entrepreneurship in the Agricultural Sector

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2024/03/26/24G00054/ORIGINAL>

Entry into force: 15 March 2024 with decree law 36/2024 by the President of the Republic

The Decree Law 36/2024 is aimed at the promotion and support of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector and the revitalization of the agricultural production system through (financial) measures that encourage the establishment and permanence of young people and generational change in the agricultural sector, in compliance with European Union regulations. The provisions establish a funding amount and criteria to encourage young people to start activities in agriculture for the first time, a facilitated tax regime for the first establishment of young enterprises in agriculture, reductions in the sale and purchase of rustic land, tax credit for expenses incurred for participation in training courses, tax concessions for the expansion of cultivated areas, etc. The target for all measures is defined within the limits of 18 to 41 years old and none of them consider any intersectional complexities. The establishment of a National Observatory for Entrepreneurship and Youth Work in Agriculture (Art. 10) provides for the involvement of associations of young people working in the agricultural and agri-food sectors (among other actors) in providing (among other functions): advice and support to administrations and public bodies for the planning and implementation of initiatives; promotion of active policies, including training activities, by public administrations and bodies to support the growth of young farmers; the promotion of rural development policies by public administrations and bodies through the creation of infrastructure and services in rural areas; stimulating and supporting governmental action, in relation to the objective of promoting entrepreneurship and youth work in agriculture.

We evaluated the provisions as inclusive for youth in general, while the National Observatory for Entrepreneurship and Youth Work in Agriculture provides an opportunity for associations representing youth to influence the planning, implementation and design of initiatives and governmental action.

13

Urgent Measures for Social Inclusion and Access to Work

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2023/05/04/23G00057/CONSOLIDATED>

Entry into force: 4 May 2023, with decree law 48/2023 by the President of the Republic

The Decree Law 48/2023 provides new measures for social and labour inclusion, particularly the *Assegno di inclusione* (Inclusion Allowance), as a national measure to combat poverty, fragility and social exclusion of vulnerable groups through paths of social inclusion, as well as training, employment and active labour policy. It is a measure of economic support and social and professional inclusion, conditional on means-testing and adherence to a personalised pathway of activation and social and labour inclusion. It is granted to family units with at least one member who is: with disability, minor, over sixty years old, or in a disadvantaged condition¹⁴ and included in care and assistance programmes of the territorial social-health services certified

¹⁴ The disadvantaged condition is defined by Ministerial Decree 154/2023 and includes specific categories certified by public administrations: mental health disorders, certified disabilities, pathological addictions, trafficked persons, ex-prisoners, homeless people, persons identified as carriers of specific social fragility and placed in

by the public administration. Citizenship requirements – EU citizen or in possession of an EU long-term residence permit with residence in Italy of at least 5 years – and low income and value of assets must be met; for minors, fulfilment of compulsory education must be documented. Among the beneficiaries for the allowance, a special category of disadvantage is found for young adults, aged between 18 and 21, living outside their family of origin because of a court order.

Other interventions in labour policies are specifically addressed toward supporting youth employability and include an incentive granted to private employers for new hirings of young people under 30 years old, who are neither in employment nor education or training (NEET) and who are registered in the National Operational Programme Youth Employment Initiative. Another measure establishes a special fund that is aimed at enhancing the professional skills of young people with disabilities and their direct involvement in various statutory activities, including productive activities, and in the entrepreneurial initiatives of entities, organisations and associations in the Third Sector, voluntary organisations and social promotion associations, non-profit organisations of social utility. An incentive is recognized for each person with disabilities, under the age of 35, hired with an open-ended employment contract.

Overall, the measures provide positive social inclusion, particularly to young people in acute social and economic disadvantage, young people with disabilities and NEET youth. Some exclusionary requirements are present in the conditions for accessing the inclusion allowance, however. Participation is not addressed in the document.

15 National Programme Youth, Women and Work 2021-2027

<https://www.anpal.gov.it/documents/552016/1371382/Programma+PN+Giovani%2C+donne+e+lavoro+FS+E%2B+2021-2027.pdf/5b296260-5030-534a-6527-f2021d960f47?t=1671526799329>

Entry into force: 1 December 2022 with European Commission Implementing Decision C(2022) 9030

The NP Youth, Women and Work 2021-2027 “fits into the framework of the strategic lines outlined in the Partnership Agreement, positioning its scope of intervention within Strategic Objective 4 “A more social and inclusive Europe” through the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights and supporting, through the ESF+, active policy interventions aimed at improving employment and employability”, with special attention to “youth, women and all people in condition of vulnerability”. The Program is declined in four main priorities: 1) youth employment, 2) employment of women and other vulnerable people who are distant from the labour market, 3) new competences for the digital and green transitions; 4) modernization of the labour service and the active policies.

Regarding youth employment, the objectives is to “improve access to employment and activation measures for all job seekers, in particular young people, especially through the implementation of the Youth Guarantee, and for the long-term unemployed and disadvantaged groups in the labour market, as well as inactive people, including through the promotion of self-employment and the social economy”. The actions include support for: job orientation and accompaniment; training, internships and apprenticeships; the Universal Civil Service (see paragraph 2.1.1 Participation, Document 2); incentives for hiring and self-employment; creation of networks and partnerships with the Third Sector and associations, schools and institutions; activation and self-employment opportunities within the social economy. These are addressed to young people aged 15-34, including third-country nationals, migrants and beneficiaries of international

reception facilities or in emergency housing intervention programmes, young adults, aged between 18 and 21, living outside their family of origin on the basis of a court order.

protection. Specifically, the main target groups are: NEETs in the strict sense, i.e. those not looking for work and not participating in training activities, even informal ones (inactive); young people who have just finished education and training and are looking for a job; young people who are not in education or training and are looking for a job; young people who, although not looking for a job, are available and maintain a high level of attachment to the labour market; young people who are 'unavailable' for active participation because of family responsibilities or health problems.

Other measures target people with disabilities, those experiencing conditions of social vulnerability, if not marginality, such as prisoners or ex-prisoners, recent immigrants from third countries, people in the care of social and socio-medical services, LGBTQIA+ people, members of the Roma, Sinti and Caminanti communities, but do not mention youth specifically. Female employment is also a separate objective of the programme, while considering specific disadvantages related to disability and migration for women.

Overall, the employment measures are aimed at increasing the social inclusion of young people in the labour market, particularly NEET and unemployed young people, with the inclusion of migrant youth. In this sense, some complexity is mentioned, but it is worth highlighting that gender and other social vulnerabilities are addressed completely separately with no consideration of possible intersections with age. Participation is also not addressed.

14 National Plan New Competences

https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/do/atto/serie_generale/caricaPdf?cdimg=21A0764900100010110001&dg u=2021-12-28&art.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2021-12-28&art.codiceRedazionale=21A07649&art.num=1&art.tiposerie=SG

Entry into force: 14 December 2021 with a decree by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies

The National Plan New Competences aims to “reorganize the training of transitioning and unemployed workers, through the strengthening of the vocational training system and the definition of essential quality levels for upskilling and reskilling activities in favour of the beneficiaries of support instruments, the beneficiaries of citizenship income and workers who benefit from extraordinary or derogation wage supplementation instruments. The Plan will also integrate other initiatives, regarding measures in favour of young people – such as the strengthening of the dual system (...) – and NEETs, as well as actions for adult skills, starting with people with very low skills...”.

The Plan foresees personalized paths for upgrading and retraining the skills of unemployed people within the Workers Employability Guarantee programme, which includes among the beneficiaries: young NEET under 30 years old under the category of fragile and vulnerable workers and unemployed young people under the category of unemployed people with fewer employment chances. Among the declared key characteristics of the Guarantee is the focus on personalization of the employment training and reintegration paths according to a multidimensional evaluation.

Young people between 15 and 25 years old are a specific target in the plan, in a prevalent way within the dual system program¹⁵ – “a learning method based on alternating moments of classroom training (at a

¹⁵ As noted in the document, the "Italian way to the dual system," initiated with the reform of the discipline of apprenticeship contracts in 2015, unlike other European experiences, is characterized as a typical modality that is not exclusive to the professionalizing preparation in that alternance and dual apprenticeship can be implemented within the study paths of every order and degree.

training institution) and moments of practical training in work contexts (at a company/organization), thus fostering policies of transition between the world of training and the world of work, so that young people can orient themselves in the labour market, acquire spendable professional skills and shorten the transition time between training and professional experience”.

Thus, the Plan seeks to increase social inclusion of young people in labour through the strengthening of vocational training and opportunities for dual system training. Consideration of social complexities among youth is very limited, addressing specifically unemployed and NEET young people. In this sense, we consider the plan as not addressing intersectionality. Participation is also not addressed.

Health

Youth health has been addressed particularly in policies on the Child Guarantee (Document 19), as well as in prevention both in general within schools (Document 20) and in relation to specific issues such as bullying and cyberbullying (Document 16). Other general policies that mention young people and hold potential interest for their health deal with addictions (Document 17) and LGBTQIA+ policy (Document 18).

16

Provisions and Delegation to the Government on the Prevention and Fight against Bullying and Cyberbullying

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2024/05/30/24G00086/ORIGINAL>

Entry into force: 17 May 2024 with law 70/2024 by the President of the Republic

The law on Provisions and Delegation to the Government on the Prevention and Fight against Bullying and Cyberbullying integrates a previous one in terms of considering both bullying and cyberbullying when it comes to contrast to discrimination and promotion of mental health, underlying the importance of educational interventions, awareness-raising, monitoring of the phenomenon and prevention. Mental health support for victims of cyberbullying and bullying is also enhanced. The dimension of participation is not discussed, except for a short mentioned in the context of social inclusion of youth responsible of bullying, for which a series of educational activities are recommended, such as engagement in creative and social activities (such as artistic activities and social theatre), together with the involvement of the families and other institutions (school, socio-educational services, sports organization). Overall, the document refers to ‘minors’ without addressing specific intersectionality or complexities.

17

National Plan of Action Addictions 2022–2025

https://www.pand-dpa.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/PAND_booklet_A4_digital.pdf

Entry into force: Finalized in October 2022 by the Department of Anti-drug Policies, unclear if approved formally and implemented

National Plan of Action Addictions 2022–2025 [*Piano di Azione Nazionale Dipendenze 2022-2025*] is a plan that addresses the issue of addiction and at-risk behaviors and it includes specific actions and goals dedicated to youth, e.g., enhancing youth’s knowledge in mathematics in order to contrast addiction to gambling.

In terms of social inclusion, the document aims at the contrast to marginality and promotion of health, but it never mentions any kind of complexity/intersectionality and no action is referred to specific categories of youth. When it comes to participation, a few actions are referred to youth participation, albeit in a limited and vague way (e.g., promoting peer education and training positive peer leaders).

18 National Strategy LGBT+ 2022-2025: Health

<https://www.unar.it/portale/documents/20125/113907/Strategia+nazionale+LGBTI%2B+2022+rev+A.pdf/8f04f55a-ee93-92b5-2bf3-d5bd59e7c163?t=1665040970207>

Entry into force: 6 October 2022 with a directorial decree by the Department for Equal Opportunities

The National Strategy LGBT+ 2022-2025 is aimed at preventing and fighting discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. It contains “measures to strengthen the protection of the rights of LGBT+ people and promote equal treatment and non-discrimination with a view to the full inclusion of all people, in line with the European Strategy for LGBTIQ Equality 2020-2025”.

The document includes little reference to youth in terms of social inclusion (no action in the domain of health includes a dimension of participation), but a few actions are related explicitly to promotion of health in minors and young adults, such as creating dedicated support and orientation services, and it is recommended that specific guidelines for minors are developed in the future. When a more intersectional approach is adopted (e.g., LGBT+ migrant people), it is not referred to youth.

19 National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee: Health

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/infanzia-e-adolescenza/Documents/PANGI.pdf>

Entry into force: 29 March 2022 with approval by the National Observatory on Childhood and Adolescence

The National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee [*Piano di Azione Nazionale per l'Attuazione della Garanzia Infanzia, PANGI*] is the programmatic document drawn up in compliance with the provisions of the Council Recommendation (EU) of 14 June 2021 establishing the European Child Guarantee in order to implement the rights of girls, boys and adolescents with the aim to combat inequalities and implement the essential level of service (see paragraph 2.1.1 Participation, Document 4, for further details).

The health-related area aims at increasing support and access to public services, such as general practice or psychological support, both for minors in general (acknowledging the potential complexities and differences of this category) and with actions that are dedicated specifically to specific social categories – e.g., establishing of a working group among different institutions to address the situation of minors with disabilities; compulsory inscription to the national health system for minors with a migration background, or enhancement of access to mental health care for migrant youth. In this sense, PANGI adopts an intersectional perspective to social inclusion in health services. Within the area of health, no specific aspects related to increasing youth participation are included, but the plan identifies actions in the sphere of participation in governance as evidence in paragraph 2.1.1 Participation, Document 4.

20 Integrated Policy Guidelines for the School that Promotes Health

https://www.salute.gov.it/imgs/C_17_notizie_3607_listaFile_itemName_0_file.pdf

Entry into force: 17 January 2019 with an agreement between the government, the regions and the autonomous provinces within the Presidency of the Council of Ministers.

The Integrated Policy Guidelines for the School that Promotes Health aim at enhancing the role of school context in the promotion of health because of its privileged position in terms of raising new generations and mediation with families and communities. The interaction between school and health system is discussed and its value is promoted, with actions such as adopting the 'global' approach recommended by WHO or including health literacy in school curricula. Nevertheless, the dimension of participation is only mentioned (as school is considered important in promoting active citizenship in youth), and when it comes to social inclusion, the document only refers to youth in general (e.g., enhancing empowerment and skills for personal development and social inclusion).

Housing

The selection of documents in this area was particularly challenging. In general, as the Italia Generativa (2023) report points out, Italian policies to date do not appear to have adopted a long-term perspective and are based on annual financial help and subsidies that are extended from year to year. The policies also seem to be either rather limited and vague, on the one hand, or very technical, on the other, making it difficult to carry out content analysis. For the latter reason we did not analyze an otherwise conceptually relevant document, which we highlight for the measures in support of youth housing: the *Decreto Sostegni bis* [Decree Support] (2021), which puts in place, in the context of first home purchase, a subsidy for the purchase of the first house for youth under 36.

Overall, housing is addressed within policies and guidelines that usually concern the fight against marginalization and poverty. Other specific issues which recent policies have addressed are the reception in residential services and university housing.

21 Guidelines for Reception in Residential Services for Minors

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/documenti-e-norme/strumenti-il-sociale-2-linee-indirizzo-accoglienza>

Entry into force: 8 February 2024, approved in Unified Conference

The Guidelines for Reception in Residential Services for Minors is a revision of the 2017 guidelines on the topic of implementation and coordination of services to sustain families and minors in a situation of difficulty, during which minors can be temporarily assigned to a 'host family' or person. Again, the document does not address the dimension of participation but only the dimension of social inclusion, which, however, includes various specific actions aimed, for example, at children with migrant backgrounds or with disabilities (e.g., training families that will host children with disability or health conditions, or the involvement of cultural mediators for minors with a migrant background).

22 New implementation measures of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan regarding housing and residences for university students

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2022/09/23/22G00154/CONSOLIDATED/20240816>

Entry into force: 24 September 2022, with Law 144/2022 by the President of the Republic

One of the few recent measures related to university students' rights, particularly housing, provides funds for the construction of student housing, with the goal of increasing the number of places available for students by 2026. The analysis highlights the lack of reference and argumentation of issues such as social inclusion, participation, and complexities among young people in a document that deals with such a relevant issue for youth.

National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee: Contrasting Poverty and Right to Housing

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/infanzia-e-adolescenza/Documents/PANGI.pdf>

Entry into force: 29 March 2022 with approval by the National Observatory on Childhood and Adolescence

It is a set of actions and guidelines aimed at protecting children in general and combating inequality in various areas, among which passages relevant to housing (and related actions) were selected (7.4). Again, the narrative on housing does not seem to focus on young people; in this case, however, the discourse is brought on families and housing, and thus indirectly also on minors. Concerning the dimension of participation, adopting a participatory approach with youth is emphasized, also through the involvement of existing youth networks and acknowledging an intersectional approach (youth with a migrant background, Rom and Sinti youth, youth with disability are mentioned); however, these passages are not explicitly focused on housing. When it comes to social inclusion, the plan's actions mainly involve increasing knowledge and accessibility to existing subsidies and promotion and awareness-raising actions aimed at combating poverty. In general, (lack of) access to housing is seen as a consequence of a condition of marginality, and therefore the document and related actions are more generally focused on the contrast of poverty (e.g., providing funds for families that face economic difficulties). A concrete approach to intersectionality is very limited, with the exception of MSNA, for whom a specific action is put in place (an extension of funds dedicated to them).

National Plan of Social Interventions and Services 2021-2023

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/priorita/Documents/Piano-Nazionale-degli-Interventi-e-dei-Servizi-Sociali-2021-2023.pdf>

Entry into force: 28 July 2021, approved by the Network for Protection and Social Inclusion

The National Plan of Social Interventions and Services 2021-2023 is a plan promoted by the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy that concerns the promotion of welfare and contrast to poverty and exclusion through the programming of interventions and services for the population. Specific sections were selected concerning the themes of housing and youth (2.3.2.3, 2.7.6, 2.7.7). In this document, the issue of housing is not addressed specifically and, in any case, not for young people, except for the case of care leavers and MSNA (UFM, unaccompanied foreign minors). As in the previous document, the dimension of participation in relation to young people is not addressed; regarding social inclusion, young people are mentioned considering some specific categories and related actions (although, for example, in the case of UFM, the focus is more on family placement than housing), but the approach is still rather vague regarding the topic of housing (e.g., enhancing youths' autonomy and involving them in building their own future through placement in residential services with low-assistance). Therefore, we found the intersectional approach to be vague and not actualized in concrete actions.

Guidelines for Combating Grave Adult Marginalization

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/poverta-ed-esclusione-sociale/Documents/Linee-di-indirizzo-per-il-contrasto-alla-grave-emarginazione-adulta.pdf>

Entry into force: 5 November 2015 with approval by the Unified Conference

Despite it being not recent, the Guidelines for Combating Grave Adult Marginalization are still the reference document on the issue of homelessness. The document initially describes the phenomenon of homelessness in Italy and how it is present among diverse categories; among these, there are some passages dedicated to young people, with an emphasis on the importance of prevention, service approach, and the 'reactivation' of resources, especially for youth. Specific actions are identified to deal with young homeless people, such as dedicating specific spaces and introducing dedicated work placement services to them. As for the analysis, no reference is made in the document about the dimension of participation. Regarding social inclusion, some more 'complex' categories are mentioned (e.g. migrant homeless youth), but no specific actions are identified, which is why we assigned a score of 2 and not of 3 with regard to intersectionality.

Participation

Youth participation in the civic and political spheres is addressed with specific policies, especially regarding volunteering. The Universal Civil Service is one of the main tools of youth participation policy in the country (Document 2), but the attention is also evident in the renewal of an agency promoting active citizenship (Document 1). Minors' active involvement is an important focus of plans regarding the Child Guarantee (Document 4) and Italy's childhood and adolescence plan of action (Document 5). Another type of focus on minorities' participation was found in the strategy addressing Roma and Sinti people, which considers youth specifically (Document 3).

1 Regulation concerning the approval of the Statute of the Italian Youth Agency

<https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2024/03/13/24G00042/ORIGINAL>

Entry into force: 24 January 2024 with decree by the President of the Republic

The regulation approves the Statute of the Italian Youth Agency [Agenzia Italiana per la Gioventù, AIG], a non-economic public body the Law n. 41 of 21 April 2023 within the measures for implementation of the National Plan for Recovery and Resilience. It took over in all respects the functions previously carried out by the National Agency for Youth within the scope of the objectives identified by the European programmes.

According to the stated objectives, the Agency promotes European citizenship, active citizenship and the participation of young people in the social and democratic life of the Nation; supports the acquisition of transversal skills, research, training and educational processes; encourages the values of solidarity, tolerance and social cohesion; promotes European and international cooperation in the field of youth policies. It manages the European Youth Programmes in Italy: Erasmus+| Youth and Sport and the European Solidarity Corps (volunteering programme).

Other activities of the AIG are:

- the promotion of mutual knowledge and understanding among young people from different nations through training and the promotion of exchanges and intercultural dialogue;
- the contribution to improving the quality of support systems for youth activities and the capacity of civil society organizations in the sectors, in particular, of youth and sport, through cooperation at local, regional, national, European and international levels;
- cooperation activities in the sectors of youth and sport policies, including at international level and with communities of Italians abroad, in agreement with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation;

- coordination, promotion and implementation of studies and research, in particular on European citizenship, active citizenship and youth participation;
- performs the functions of an authority authorized to train socio-educational animators;
- authorized to provide technical-operational support to the Department for Youth Policies and Universal Civil Service of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, through the stipulation of specific agreements or memoranda of understanding

All activities and priorities of the Agency are addressed towards young people in general. Thus, the establishment of the Agency is evaluated as providing an expansion of the opportunities for participation, specifically through its role in the promotion of volunteering programs and support to civil society organizations for youth, without any attention to intersectionality. No particular consideration of the social inclusion of youth is given in the document.

2 Three-Year Plan for the Programming of the Universal Civil Service 2023-2025
https://www.politichegiovani.gov.it/media/hwsnlrej/pt2023-2025_piano_triennalescu_def.pdf

Entry into force: 20 January 2023 with decree by the Ministry of Sport and Youth

The Three-Year Plan for the Programming of the Universal Civil Service 2023-2025 [*Piano Triennale per la Programmazione del Servizio Civile Universale 2023-2025*] is a programming document that guides the actions of the Universal Civil Service (UCS), which is the main tool for promoting youth volunteering on a national level since its institution in 2017.

The Plan provides: (1) an overview of the general framework of the UCS: regulatory framework, actors, adhesion, resources; (2) the strategic framework of objectives, priorities and ongoing experimentation; (3) the programming guidelines: criteria for financing, guidelines for formulating intervention programs and quality standards; (4) a description of the process for updating the Plan.

The UCS is positioned as aiming to promote both active citizenship and employability of young people, especially since the National Plan for Recovery and Resilience (PNRR) project framed these experiences as tools for acquiring key competences for employment. In this sense NEET youth are a key target of the UCS. As the main aim of the UCS is to provide channels of access to volunteering programs, it is one of the most important policies that seek to expand civic participation and civic competences among youth.

In terms of promoting inclusion, the UCS plan declares special attention to “youth with fewer opportunities”, intended as those who “for different reasons related to their specific condition, encounter greater difficulty in feeling like active citizens, in feeling interested in social life, in facing the path of research to access occupation”. According to the Provisions for the drafting and presentation of universal civil service intervention programs, cited in the plan, these conditions include youth with recognized disabilities, with low levels of education, with economic difficulties, care leavers (i.e., young people who after the age of eighteen live outside their family of origin by virtue of a judicial order), and young people subject to temporary conditions of personal or social fragility who are taken care of by social and health services and/or employment centers¹⁶. While the proposed civil service projects should be addressed to the wide general population and should not be exclusive to one category of youth, the presence of such elements of disadvantage is rewarded in the evaluation process. The plan also states the intention to put into action

¹⁶ Throughout the descriptions we report target populations, terms and abbreviations identifying social groups and categories as they are used in the text of the document. Note that there are inconsistencies between the different documents.

further empowerment actions for youth with disability conditions. It thus deals with social inclusion as it makes the effort to make available the civil service programs available to all young people, including some marginalized groups (availability).

The policy of the UCS is evaluated as both inclusive and as expanding participation opportunities, with “thin” intersectional attention in both dimensions to several specific conditions of disadvantage among youth – disability, general educational and economic disadvantage, judicial separation from the family of origin and temporary personal or social fragility.

3 National Strategy for Equality, Inclusion and Participation of Roma and Sinti 2021-2030

[https://www.unar.it/portale/documents/20125/113907/Strategia Nazionale di uguaglianza inclusione partecipazione di Rom e Sinti 2021-2030+%28ITA%29.pdf/1e4ccc9c-aeba-e7b2-864d-ee1eced7e4df?t=1653399043993](https://www.unar.it/portale/documents/20125/113907/Strategia+Nazionale+di+uguaglianza+inclusione+partecipazione+di+Rom+e+Sinti+2021-2030+%28ITA%29.pdf/1e4ccc9c-aeba-e7b2-864d-ee1eced7e4df?t=1653399043993)

Entry into force: 23 May 2022 with directorial decree by the Department for Equal Opportunities

The National Strategy for Equality, Inclusion and Participation of Roma and Sinti 2021-2030 [*Strategia Nazionale di uguaglianza, inclusione e partecipazione di Rom e Sinti 2021-2030*] contains the policies and measures for non-discrimination and the social and socio-economic inclusion of Roma and Sinti, adopted as implementation of the Council Recommendation (EU) of 12 March 2021.

One of the main aims of the EU Strategy, and the national implementation, is the promotion of participation of Roma and Sinti people in all their diversity – “citizens of the Member State in which they live and citizens of other States, marginalized and integrated people, women, children and young people”. In Italy this aspect has received particular attention with the establishment of the National Platform Roma and Sinti and the Communities Forum in 2017. These represent operative instruments of dialogue between institutions and civil society for the definition of policies. The current strategy aims to enhance and consolidate the platform and one of the implementing proposals is to promote the participation of young Roma and Sinti – involved by associations in empowerment and training paths – in thematic subgroups, activating effective collaborations and an active role in decision-making processes. The activation of processes of empowerment is deemed especially useful for more disadvantaged groups, such as youth and women, and several strategic facilitating actions are aimed at young Roma and Sinti people (e.g., training, laboratories and collaborations with youth agencies). The strategy also cites the need to counter “the phenomenon of intersectional discrimination: it is important to acknowledge the specific needs or vulnerabilities of certain groups, including women, young people, children, LGBTI+ people, older people, people with disabilities, third-country nationals or stateless persons and Roma with non-Italian citizenship”. The document and the proposals within do not reflect further on the intersections between these different conditions of disadvantage. Other objectives and actions for young Roma and Sinti people are identified for the access to job orientation and employment, and to all levels of education.

Overall, the Strategy is deemed inclusive and expanding opportunities for participation with a specific focus on young Roma and Sinti people.

4 National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee: Governance

<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/infanzia-e-adolescenza/Documents/PANGI.pdf>

Entry into force: 29 March 2022 with approval by the National Observatory on Childhood and Adolescence

The National Plan of Action for the Implementation of the Child Guarantee [*Piano di Azione Nazionale per l'Attuazione della Garanzia Infanzia, PANGI*] is the programmatic document drawn up in compliance with the provisions of the Council Recommendation (EU) of 14 June 2021 establishing the European Child Guarantee in order to implement the rights of girls, boys and adolescents with the aim to combat inequalities and implement the essential level of service. The aim is therefore to improve access and increase participation in all services by minors in difficulty and their families, also paying specific attention to those who experience disadvantages. The Child Guarantee Plan is intended to complement and support the 5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents (Document 5), together with which it forms the National Strategy for Children and Adolescents.

The sections of the PANGI included in this evaluation were those related to Governance, which identified actions to increase opportunities for participation in decision-making. In particular, we highlight:

- the definition of essential level of service related to the right of participation of children and adolescents in decision-making on all matters affecting them, and in the design and implementation of policies and programmes aimed at achieving the 17 Sustainable Development Goals;
- ensuring the application of the guidelines on participation developed and approved by the National Observatory on Childhood and Adolescence and actions 25 and 26 of the 5th National Childhood and Adolescence Plan, as well as the participation of beneficiaries in the design, implementation and monitoring of programming acts in relation to the priorities of the National Childhood Guarantee Plan, in particular through the Youth Advisory Board, the body for the participation of girls and boys for the implementation of the Childhood Guarantee in Italy;
- enhancing an experimental educational project (GET UP) whose purpose is to promote interventions that are based between school and territory for and promote self-management and autonomy skills of minors and develop their participation in the social context of the city through volunteering, cooperative student associations and service learning.

Within the identified target population for involvement, the PANGI actions on participation in the governance of the Child Guarantee highlight “the categories of minors most at risk of poverty and social exclusion as identified in the Child Guarantee Recommendation, aged between 13 and 21, respecting gender equality”. The overall framework identifies the following groups in difficulty: minors coming from Ukraine, homeless minors or minors in serious housing difficulties, minors with conditions of disability, minors with a migrant background, unaccompanied foreign minors and minorities, minors with mental health problems, minors in alternative care facilities. Specific attention is given to reducing barriers for the access to rights due to migrant background – the actions include reforming the law on citizenship and reducing the years of residence required for obtaining social inclusion benefits (citizenship income).

Considering the highlighted objectives, we evaluated the PANGI sections on governance as both inclusive and as expanding the opportunities for participation with “thin” intersectional focus on specific conditions of disadvantage.

 5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents 2022-2023: Policies for Empowerment
https://www.minori.gov.it/sites/default/files/idi_quintopianoazione_220725-2.pdf

Entry into force: 25 January 2022 with decree by the President of the Republic

The 5th Plan of Action for Children and Adolescents 2022-2023 [*V Piano di azione per l'infanzia e l'adolescenza 2022-2023*] is a programmatic and guiding tool that identifies priority interventions for subjects in developmental age. One of the thematic focuses of the Plan is the policies for empowerment, which identify three specific actions that aim to make active involvement of children and adolescents more widely available in practice by determining an essential level of service and by promoting, training and spreading the culture of participation: action no. 25, aimed at encouraging and supporting experiences and good practices of participation through the definition of guidelines for participation, innovative projects for participation, and a plan for dissemination and training for operators; action no. 26, aimed at implementing training on the topic of participation; and action no. 27, aimed at regulating and monitoring participation actions through the definition of the essential levels of performance regarding the right to participation of minors.

Moreover, the Plan is also accompanied by the definition of a model of participation and national guidelines for the active involvement of minors both in the drafting phase of future plans and in the monitoring phase of this Plan. The development of the Plan has involved youth through a preliminary inquiry which asked adolescents between 12 and 17 years old to evaluate the proposed contents of the Plan. The planned actions have been oriented according to the results that have emerged from young people's reflections in relation to the priorities and intervention strategies identified by the expert working groups.

Thus, the policy plan deals with social inclusion of minors, as it proposes to reflect their interests in the definition of participation actions (representation). It also seeks to expand participation opportunities for minors through comprehensive development of guidelines, training, projects and norms. Within the thematic focus of empowerment, no specific groups or social conditions are mentioned, and all actions are addressed to the general target of children and adolescents. However, among the interventions dedicated to the system of services for care, protection and safeguarding, the Plan includes the establishment of a permanent working table with institutional and third sector bodies and with the full participation of bodies representing minors, aimed at designing a public, inclusive and integrated system of services and at ensuring the coordination and monitoring of policies for the protection and safeguarding of childhood. The target for this action is identified as "children, adolescents and families in situations of vulnerability and poverty, neglect, mistreatment and abuse; children and adolescents in the reception system (family foster care and residential community); new adults and care leavers; children, adolescents and families in the adoption process; children and adolescents with disabilities in school inclusion processes, unaccompanied foreign minors (UFM), asylum seekers, etc."

Overall, we evaluated the plan as inclusive and expanding opportunities for participation for all minors, while it seeks to promote inclusion and participation in decision-making of minors with vulnerabilities regarding the design and monitoring of social services.

Local Level: Emilia-Romagna Region

Health

6 Guidelines on Social Withdrawal

<https://sociale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/novita/prodotti-editoriali/2022/linee-di-indirizzo-su-ritiro-sociale-prevenzione-rilevazione-precoce-ed-attivazione-di-interventi-di-primo-e-secondo-livello>

The Guidelines on Social Withdrawal (2022) focused on the phenomenon of social withdrawal and provided guidelines to address it. The document widely describes the phenomenon and identifies prevention and intervention axes to be implemented, such as prevention through reinforcement of social skills in the school context, correct identification of primary signals of social withdrawal, and activation of territorial services by also involving the school and family. As said, the dimension of participation is not addressed, except for mentioning it as part of the 'recovery path' (e.g., through volunteering experiences). Youth is addressed as a homogeneous category; at the end of the document, a sort of checklist to help describing the social withdrawal case is provided and dimensions such as gender (binary) or the presence of SLD are reported, but no further indication is given.

7 Guidelines and Action for the New Generations 2022-2024: Health

https://www.giovazoom.emr.it/it/partecipazione/youz/carovana/documenti-carovana/linee-di-indirizzo-e-di-azione-per-le-nuove-generazioni-2013-triennio-2022-2024_dpg-1249-del-25-07-1.pdf/@@download/file

Entry into force: 25 July 2022 with Resolution of the Regional Government

The Guidelines and Action for the New Generations 2022-2024 is a document which is the product of the elaboration of proposals that were developed during the Forum Giovani Youz and that aims at defining the general principles and framework of future youth policies) mentions in fact a few objectives that are specific for gender or migration (e.g., it encourages the adoption of a gender medicine approach); nevertheless, the approach of the document is too broad, refers to youth in a general way and it does not provide specific and concrete actions for the mentioned categories.

8 Foreign citizens in Emilia-Romagna. Health and health services 2024

<https://sociale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/novita/prodotti-editoriali/2024/cittadini-stranieri-in-emilia-romagna-salute-e-servizi-sanitari-anno-2024>

The report Foreign citizens in Emilia-Romagna. Health and health services 2024 dealt explicitly with health in citizens with a migrant background, and although a paragraph seems to adopt an intersectional approach, since it is focused on migrant women, this perspective is not maintained when it comes to youth. In the passages that are focused on youth, instead, the intersectional perspective (migrant youth) is not brought on a further level (thin intersectionality vs thick intersectionality).

9 Regional Prevention Plan 2021-2025

10 Social and Health Plan 2017-2019

[9]: https://servizissir.regione.emilia-romagna.it/deliberegiunta/servlet/AdapterHTTP?action_name=ACTIONRICERCADELIBERE&operation=dettaglioByDatiAdozione&ENTE=1&TIPO_ATTO=DL&ANNO_ADOZIONE=2021&NUM_ADOZIONE=2144

[10]: <https://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:delibera:2017;120>

The Regional Prevention Plan 2021-2025 and the Social and Health Plan 2017-2019 are regional plans and strategies to promote health and prevention, in terms of programming territorial services and interventions. Both documents show the same approach when it comes to dealing with youth: 'youth' and 'minors' are

represented as a homogeneous category. A few references are made in more descriptive paragraphs to potential complexities such as NEET, migrants, or people that live in disadvantaged areas, to trace the needs' analysis for interventions addressing families and minors, but when it comes to more 'operative' sections of the text, again, no concrete actions are described.

Participation

In this section, nearly all documents share the approach of referring to youth as a general category, without actually considering specific cases or complexity. A truly intersectional approach is never adopted, and when specific identities or intersections are mentioned (e.g., gender and sexual orientation, NEET or disadvantaged youth), it is done in a vague and generic way, without providing specific and concrete actions (e.g., youth policy system should be enhanced in order to allow youth participation and inclusion, especially when it comes to disadvantaged and NEET youth). An exception to these considerations is the third analysed document (Guidelines and Action for the New Generations 2022-2024: Participation). The specificities of every document will be further described.

1 Approval of the project proposal on youth policies for the year 2023 "GECO 13"
<https://bur.regione.emilia-romagna.it/dettaglio-inserzione?i=9e9960a26222411fa6e365d57154ac80>

Entry into force: 13 March 2024 with Resolution of the Regional Government

Approval of the project proposal on youth policies for the year 2023 "GECO 13" is a regional deliberation aiming at promoting youth participation in terms of implementing projects developed by youth, encouraging active citizenship, youth organizations and climate responsibility. It also addresses social inclusion among its aims, briefly referring to 'disadvantaged youth' and suggesting the increase of youth work services and aggregation.

2 Rules for the Promotion and Support of the Third Sector, Shared Administration and Active Citizenship
<https://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:legge:2023;3>

Entry into force: 13 April 2023 with Regional Law 3/2023

The regional law 3/2023 *Rules for the Promotion and Support of the Third Sector, Shared Administration and Active Citizenship* aims at enhancing and encouraging active citizenship and community engagement and organizations. The law acknowledges the role of the 'third sector' (private associations) but also underlining the importance of collaborations between them and the public system, for example including representatives of third-sector associations in institutional organs. The law also highlights the importance of involving citizens in local administrations through a participatory process. In this case, the document is not focused on youth in particular, but a few actions concern youth (e.g., promoting youth engagement and participation in the life of the community) also in terms of social inclusion (e.g., promoting youth activities aiming at inclusion and the contrast to educational poverty).

3 Guidelines and Action for the New Generations 2022-2024: Participation
https://www.giovazoom.emr.it/it/partecipazione/youz/carovana/documenti-carovana/linee-di-indirizzo-e-di-azione-per-le-nuove-generazioni-2013-triennio-2022-2024_dpg-1249-del-25-07-1.pdf/@@download/file

Entry into force: 25 July 2022 with Resolution of the Regional Government

The guidelines Guidelines and Action for the New Generations 2022-2024 are the product of the elaboration of proposals that were developed during the Forum Giovani Youz (see Document 4 below), and aims at defining the general principles and framework of future youth policies. We selected for the analysis the paragraph “#participation”, but also read the document in a more transversal way in order to identify the overall representation of youth, since the overall document deals with participation and social inclusion.

The guidelines include references to participation in which, similarly to the other documents, no distinction is made when it comes to referring to “youth”. Nevertheless, a more transversal reading allowed us to identify that in other parts of the document a couple of actions are related to youth with a migration background in order to enhance their active citizenship and promotion of engagement in associations. In this sense, different categories of youth are considered in the document, but when it comes to focus explicitly on participation the document lacks a more intersectional approach and dealing with how to include different perspectives.

4 Youth Forum Youz

<https://www.giovazoom.emr.it/it/bandi/DeliberaForum895.pdf/@download/file>

<https://www.giovazoom.emr.it/it/partecipazione/youz/progetto>

Entry into force: 14 June 2021 with Resolution of the Regional Government

Resolution 895 of 14/06/2021 deals with the implementation of Forum Giovani Youz, a regional youth Forum established in order to promote youth involvement and participation. The Forum is composed of youth that meet periodically to discuss general axes of topics that are pre-established, and the results of these encounters are then discussed in an institutional context with Regional and Municipality organs. This is a more technical document that leaves little room for a complete analysis. Nevertheless, it addresses youth participation in a concrete way, promoting a participatory and deliberative space for youth that includes, among its aims, youth social inclusion. Several topics are listed as object of discussion – gender equality, right to housing, LGBTQ+ community.

It does not address how to promote participation in the Forum of different categories of youth.

5 Law on Participation in the Development of Public Policies

<https://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:legge:2018;15>

Entry into force: 22 October 2018 with Regional Law 15/2018

The regional law 15/2018, Law on Participation in the Development of Public Policies, deals with improving participation and inclusion of the population in participatory processes, through actions such as having an annual session of the regional Assembly dedicated to participation, identifying a specific figure with the role of ‘guarantor’ of participation, devolving funds for participation, and so on.

The law mentions specific attention to categories such as people with disabilities or with a migration background, but when it comes to youth, young people are mentioned only marginally and vaguely (e.g., in terms of promoting youth’s active participation).

Conclusions

i) Do governmental policies deal with inclusion or exclusion? If yes, to what extent do these policies result in positive or negative outcomes for young people?

Overall, nearly all of the analysed policies in Italy deal with social inclusion, seeking greater accessibility to services, representation or recognition for young people. All of the policy areas presented actions of support to greater integration of youth in societal structures – from promoting access to employment and skills training, addressing health risks and promoting mental and physical health for all through prevention, supporting access to housing and residential service, to ensuring access to civil service and increasing participation in youth issues.

ii) Do governmental policies deal with opportunities for participation? To what extent do they expand or restrict opportunities for participation?

The opening up of concrete opportunities for participation is much scarcer in the analysed policies. With the exception of the area Participation, in which documents were chosen to focus on civic and political participation programmes and policies, other areas considered the inclusion of young people's voices in a limited manner. It is worth noting that opportunities for participation dealt primarily with volunteering (in the Participation area) and, in rare cases, with involvement or representative bodies or groups in consultation/advisory role for policy design (in all areas). Labour policies, in particular, showed almost in-existent attention to the possibility of involving young people in decision-making on one of the most developed policy areas in the country tackling an issue of great concern for the political debate, especially regarding youth unemployment and presence of NEET youth. Health policies also almost never referred to participation, and Education policy actions did not provide any measures that would concretely increase student participation in school decision-making, only referring to the importance of (teaching) active citizenship and civic activation of students. Similar limited attention was found in Housing policies, which were revealed to be less developed and youth-focused than other areas, and being often focused on contrasting marginality and poverty with social inclusion rather than participation.

iii) If governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations, how governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations?

The analysed policies seemed to navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations only halfway-through. As a whole, young people are recognized as an important target for inclusive actions, with needs that are different from adults and whose social integration has a great impact in the social fabric. The exception to this rule in Italy seems to be the area of Housing policies, as the reference to young people is quite limited within actions oriented at tackling homelessness and more generally contrasting poverty – in this area, most passages explicitly dedicated to youth were restricted to the management of minors in need of reception in residential services.

As many of the policies tackle social inclusion and frequently recognize differences in access and experience for different young people, often measures identify and focus on specific social disadvantages with positive actions aimed at equality. The result, however, is a piecemeal framework that either treats young people as homogenous (disadvantaged) group, with little or no reference to specific identity dimensions, or treats different conditions of disadvantage as separate issues or even as requirements to access support for inclusion and integration. Policies on more specific issues such as LGBTQIA+ inclusion, addictions, Roma and

Sinti people inclusion, on the other hand, tend to relegate attention to youth to the background, with fewer and less specific actions especially in the Health sector. Such a disaggregated view of the youth condition would not be able to address the issues that hinder young people's full access to social and political agency.

iv) Does governmental policy typically categorize young people using general terms, or does it incorporate considerations for intersectionality? Are inclusivity, empowerment addressed comprehensively within governmental policy?

In general, the documents' analysis showed a lack of a shared and consistent approach in dealing with youth's policies in terms of considering intersectionality.

Many of the policies refer to young people with general terms and address measures to youth or students (in Education) as a whole. However, as anticipated above, either specific actions within plans or entire policy tools sought to tackle a number of social disadvantages. Referring to vulnerabilities in general was common, but most documents outlined specific group targets for socially inclusive action. In this sense, great attention was found for the impact of disabilities, poverty, unemployment and migration. Young people with disabilities were identified as targets in different areas transversally and more specifically in the Education sector with the special education model (PEI). Labour policies were more generic in the identification of young people, but often specified actions for youth in the NEET condition and considered a number of other social conditions requiring particular attention. Policies in the Health area showed a scarcer interest in specific groups – on the one hand, when documents were related to specific groups (e.g., LGBTQIA+ community) or topics (e.g., National Plan of Action Addictions) only short sections or actions seem to be referred to youth; on the other hand, more general documents included and revealed a more careful attention to specific categories of minors (e.g., minors with a migrant background or with disabilities). Within housing, the only concrete policy actions found addressed (at least in part) the cases of unaccompanied foreign minors and care leavers.

On the local level, these considerations seem to be reduced. Within Health policies, very few references to intersections were found, except for documents that are specifically focused on categories such as migrants. For example, in more descriptive parts, most documents referred to specific cases (e.g., NEET, young with a migrant background), but this awareness did not reflect in providing specific and concrete actions.

All considerations of specific needs and conditions, however, were found within actions for social inclusion. Only policies specifically in the Participation area on a national level tackled the non-heterogeneity of young people in actions that would open up channels of participation (as introduced above, primarily regarding volunteering). On the local level, however, nearly all of the Participation policies referred to youth as a general category. When specific identities or intersections are mentioned (e.g., gender and sexual orientation, NEET or disadvantaged youth), it is either not related to youth, or it is done in a very limited, vague and generic way, without showing awareness of the importance of considering different aspects and identities of young people. In only one case, a couple actions of the guidelines were specifically aimed at improving participation of youth with a migration background.

Overall, however, all of the documents considered possible conditions of disadvantage separately (e.g., young migrants vs. youth with disabilities vs. youth at risk of poverty, etc.) and did not adopt an intersectional approach in a meaningful, conscious and 'thick' way. The lack of reflection on how experiences of disadvantage and oppression can intersect was evidenced even in the structuring of many of the policy documents – e.g., strategic programmes within Labour addressed in entirely different sections and with separate actions employment for youth, for women and for vulnerable groups, not mentioning possible

interactions. The very scarce references to intersectional discrimination in policies that enact EU strategies regarding LGBTQIA+ or Roma and Sinti people also did not translate into concrete interventions that tackle the issue comprehensively.

In this sense, we believe that current Italian policies deal with and promote inclusivity but are too scarcely focused on forms of youth participation that go beyond volunteering/joining associations, and show little awareness of the possible complexities of youth identity in an intersectional way, resulting in the lack of a more structured approach capable of promoting promote empowerment.

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NATIONAL REPORT PORTUGAL (U.PORTO)

Introduction

Over the last years, Portugal has been facing a demographic deficit. Statistical data about the Portuguese population shows that, between 2009 and 2019, there was a significant aging effect over the national population, with elderly people (aged 65 or over) surpassing the number of young people (Direção-Geral da Saúde, 2022). In 2022, the number of Portuguese young people (15 to 24 years old) was 1,086,544 (51% male and 49% female), which represented only 10% of the total population (Pordata, 2023). More recently, in 2023, “the aging index, which compares the population aged 65 and over (elderly population) with the population aged 0 to 14 (young population), reached the value of 188.1 elderly people for every 100 young people” (INE, 2024c). Aging of the Portuguese population has been mildly attenuated by recent increases in general birth rates, with the average number of children per woman increasing from 1.42, in 2022, to 1.44, in 2023 (INE, 2024c). Additionally, immigration has also contributed to this attenuation. In 2022, “one in ten young people living in Portugal was born abroad”, meaning that “71.000 young people (6% of the total in this age group) are foreigners: 40% are Brazilian, 8% Angolan and Cape Verdean, respectively, and 5% are from Guinea Bissau” (Pordata, 2023, p. 4). Immigration has also contributed to further increase Portuguese yearly birth rates, with 14% of the births in 2021 being from foreign immigrant women (Pordata, 2022). Thus, immigrants have significantly contributed to an overall increase in the total population of the country (INE, 2024c). As a result, Portuguese young people are increasingly from multiethnic and multicultural backgrounds, which increases the importance of studying potential intersectional discrimination.

Furthermore, Portuguese young people face significant challenges regarding their emancipation, most of which related to limited or unstable access to employment and housing. Although young generations are generally more educated than previous ones, they still struggle to find financial stability early on in their lives, with corresponding adverse effects on their well-being, health, and participation in their society. We will briefly present some of the main challenges faced by Portuguese young people in these areas.

Education

Over the last decades, the Portuguese population has raised its general educational levels (INE, 2010). In 2022, 6 out of 10 young people, between 20 and 24 years old, had finished secondary education, and 3 out of 10 had finished higher education (Pordata, 2023).

In addition to being more educated than previous generations, Figure 1 shows that Portuguese young people are also above the average proportion of the educational levels of young people in other member-states of the European Union (EU).

Figure 1: Proportion of young people (20-24) by level of education

Source: Adapted from Pordata (2023). *Retrato dos Jovens entre os 15 e os 24 anos*. Fundação Francisco Manuel dos Santos

These numbers are also a reflection on the fact that, since 2012, education is mandatory for children and young people between 5 and 18 years old (see Decreto-Lei nr. 176/2012). Additionally, in 2022, Portugal was the 8th country in the EU with the lowest school dropout rate. (Pordata, 2023).

Despite the significant democratization of education in Portugal, higher education fees for students are still quite high, and, in 2018-19, only 63.6% of bachelor's students received universally available grants (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2020). Overall, in 2022-23, 446.028 (155.082 for the first time in first year) students were enrolled in higher education (DGEEC, 2023), which indicates that Portuguese universities are in high demand, not only nationally but also at the international level. In fact, in 2022, 8% of bachelor's students, and 14% of master's students were foreigners, values above the European average (6% and 12%) (Pordata, 2023). High attendance, tuition fees, and relatively low availability of grants has led to significant financial stress on Portuguese citizens and families. This is exacerbated by the fact that many Portuguese students are enrolled in universities away from their place of residence, meaning that they must pay for accommodation in urban areas (such as Lisboa and Porto) that are already facing housing problems and inflated rental prices. To alleviate this problem, the Portuguese Government is trying to significantly increase the number of university residences in cities with higher education institutions that are in high demand.

Housing

The price of housing in Portugal's major urban areas has been on the rise over recent years. In the first quarter of 2024, the prices of houses continued to rise by 5% (when compared to the first quarter of 2023) in most areas of the country (INE, 2024d). In addition to making it difficult for Portuguese young people to buy their first house, this also leads to inflated rental prices. In fact, in the first quarter of 2024, housing rental prices increased 10.5%, when compared to the homologous quarter of 2023. The highest rents were found in Lisboa (12.12 €/m²), Setúbal (9.29 €/m²), Algarve (8.78 €/m²), Autonomous Region of Madeira (8.13 €/m²) and the Porto metropolitan area (8.11 €/m²) (INE, 2024b).

The increasing prices of housing restrict Portuguese young people's capability to emancipate and to leave their parent's house. In 2022, it is estimated that 95% of young people still lived in their parent's house, and that the average age for leaving was 30 years old, 3 years more than the European average (Pordata, 2023). These numbers are both a reflection of high housing costs as well as of young people's struggles to find stable employment and reasonable salaries in Portugal.

Employment

According to Eurostat¹⁷, salaries in Portugal are relatively low when compared to other EU members. Still, young people find even worst conditions in the national labour market. In 2021, the average salary in Portugal of a person aged 35 to 44 (1,510€) was 19.6% higher than that of a young adult aged 25 to 34 (1 263€) (INE, 2023b). Additionally, in 2022, the unemployment rate among young people was four times higher than that of workers aged 25-74 (19% vs. 5%), and, in the first quarter of 2024, the unemployment rate of young people (16 to 24 years old) was estimated to be at 23% (vs. 6,8% for the general population) (INE, 2024). Even when they can find a job, young people are especially vulnerable to professional instability. In 2022, 6 out of every 10 young people (57%) who were employed had only temporary contracts, well above the 14% of workers aged 25-64 in the same conditions (Pordata, 2023). In the same year, there were 5.000 young people officially unemployed and receiving unemployment subsidy (Pordata, 2023).

These circumstances have led many Portuguese young people to leave the country in recent years (Pires et al., 2023) and left many of those that stay especially vulnerable to poverty and social exclusion, since "according to data recorded since 2015, the rate of risk of poverty or social exclusion is always higher among young people when compared to the general population" (Pordata, 2023, p. 16). Faced with this scenario, governmental cabinets have been trying to implement programs that offer tax incentives and encourage emigrated young people to come back to Portugal.

Health

Recent surveys indicate that Portuguese young people worry about their physical and mental health, as is reflected in the opinions that they provided for the creation of the Youth Agenda for Health 2030 (see D20). In terms of physical health, in 2021, almost half said that they did not consume alcohol (48%), 14% reported drinking a few times a week, and only 9% said that they smoked daily (Pordata, 2023). Despite these indicators regarding their physical health, Portuguese young people, and the general population, continue to show a worrying percentage of overweight and obesity. In 2022, it is estimated that 20% of Portuguese 15-year-olds were overweight or obese (OECD/European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2024).

Regarding mental health, in 2019 it was estimated that 22% of the Portuguese population suffered from mental health disorders, which was already one of the highest percentages in the EU (OECD/European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2024). Nevertheless, despite the challenges in access to employment and housing, a survey, in the same year, revealed that more than 70% (above the average for the general population) of Portuguese young people said to be satisfied or quite satisfied with their lives (INE, 2020), although this indicator seems to be on a negative trend since the breakout of the COVID-19 pandemic (Gaspar et al., 2023).

Overall, in 2021, 312 young people died in Portugal: 224 males and 88 females. The main causes of death among men were transportation accidents (25%), suicide (12%) and cancer (12%); while among women, these were cancer (25%) and transportation accidents (11%) (Pordata, 2023).

¹⁷ See "Average annual net earnings (2023)" table at <https://www.euronews.com/business/2024/07/08/european-average-salary-rankings-where-does-your-country-stand>.

Participation

National debates about the participation of young people in the Portuguese society have been dominated by the apparent disengagement of younger generations. Although official data about young people's voting turnout is not available, some studies, using self-reported data, show that, over the last decades, Portuguese young people with electoral capacity (18 to 24 years old) voted less than their older fellow citizens (Magalhães, 2022) and participate in formal politics (engagement in political parties) less than older generations (Lobo et al., 2015). However, the claim that "there is no type of social or political participation in which younger people are above the national average, which is symptomatic of a lack of political involvement" (Lobo et al., 2015, p. 54) has been increasingly contested, since more recent studies found that "when it comes to demonstrations, working for parties and civic movements, signing petitions or boycotting products for political reasons, it is not the youngest who participate least in Portugal" (Magalhães, 2022, p. 3). This seems to point to a relative disengagement of young people from traditional forms of political participation in favour of other forms of civic and political engagement, more akin to activism, that they consider to be more effective in achieving changes in their society (Silva et al., 2022). In fact, it is increasingly visible that young people have been protagonists in non-electoral social and political mobilization in the Portuguese society, especially privileging online political participation (Costa et al., 2022).

Regardless of this discussion, Portuguese politicians have systematically stressed the importance of attracting young people back to formal politics and public institutions have been engaged in the implementation of programs that seek to promote youth participation within the national political system.

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Sample and procedures

The final sample of national (n=25) and local (n=10) documents/policies included in this report was compiled after an online search and selection process for relevant policies in the Education, Housing, Employment, Health, and Participation areas.

At the national level, most documents (n=17) were retrieved from the official legislative database of the Portuguese Parliament, *Diário da República*. The remaining documents were retrieved from the official webpages of national authorities, such as the General-Directorate of Education, General-Directorate of Higher Education, General-Directorate of Health, National Health Council, Tax and Customs Authority. Two of the documents were retrieved from the official webpages of the National Youth Associations Federation and from the private Foundation José Neves. Two additional documents/policies (D1 and D2) were included

in this report for their relevance in national youth policies. These documents were included solely as means to provide a general overview of national priorities in youth related policies and were not submitted to the coding process described in this section.

At the local level, most documents (n=5) were retrieved from the official webpages of the Municipalities of Arcos de Valdevez, Porto, Santa Maria da Feira and Pombal. Two documents were retrieved from the official legislative database of the Portuguese Parliament and from the Official Journal of the Autonomous Region of Açores. Two documents were retrieved from the official webpage of the National Youth Associations Federation and one from the public webpage created for the program *Algarve 2020 Jovem*.

After these procedures, the contents of each document/policy were analysed, summarized and coded (see Annexed Excel document) according to textual evidence of concerns with promoting young people's inclusion/exclusion (Dimension 1) and participation (Dimension 2), as well as explicit or implicit concerns with intersectionality. Two members of the national research team coded each document/policy independently. Differences in coding by each member were discussed and agreement was achieved for the final coding.

National Policy Documents

General

D1 - II Plano Nacional para a Juventude (Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 77/2022).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/resolucao-conselho-ministros/77-2022-200907658>

Document 1 is the “Second National Youth Plan” (SNYP), which is the Government’s framework for youth policies in Portugal for the period of 2022-2024. The SNYP includes over 400 measures in areas “that have an impact on the lives of young people, particularly with regard to education, employment and entrepreneurship, higher education, housing, birth rates, health, quality of life, sports, culture, environment, agriculture, transportation, the sustainability of social security, the fight against poverty, equality and non-discrimination, inclusion and integration, encouraging active citizenship and sustainable development”. This document sets the general objectives and specific measures to improve the societal conditions for young people’s civic and political participation, employment, health, housing, education and culture. Many of the documents that will be presented in this report are efforts to specify and implement concrete actions that aim to achieve the objectives set by the SNYP.

The document seeks to include Portuguese young people in general. It recognizes that “youth is a difficult concept to define”, also because it “is a heterogeneous social group, encompassing girls and boys and/or young women and men, LGBTI+ people, nationals, migrants, descendants, refugees and displaced people in different socioeconomic conditions, with disabilities, who live in rural or urban contexts, among several other characteristics, situations or conditions that are part of their identity and influence or, often, determine the successful access or realization of their rights”. This reflects a noteworthy recognition and importance attributed to intersectional positions of young people in the country. This is also connected to the objective of the SNYP of giving priority to “equality, inclusion and protection of the Human Rights of young people”, which is “present in all axes, aiming to promote and protect the Human Rights of young people; promote specific measures that ensure a positive action approach for specific groups of young people in vulnerable situations”.

Additionally, the SNYP recommends valuing “projects that specify concrete measures aimed at promoting equality in the integration and sports participation of young people (gender equality, young people at risk of poverty, young people with disabilities, young Portuguese Roma people, young migrants, young refugees,

young people deprived of freedom, LGBTI+ young people). [...] Develop and support actions and projects that promote training for associations and civic and political participation, of people from groups discriminated against based on ethnic-racial origin”. Although this document is not included in the final selection that will be systematically coded, we decided to include this brief overview of its contents because they set the tone for the possibility of other documents included in this report to give life to efforts to address the problems of young people in general and at risk of being subject to intersectional processes of sociopolitical exclusion.

D2 - Agenda para a Inovação das Políticas de Juventude, 2020-2030 (Federação Nacional das Associações Juvenis, 2021). https://fnaj.pt/uploads/editor_uploads/files/documento-agenda-inovacao-final-compactado_compressed.pdf

Document 2 is the “Agenda for Innovation in Youth Policies” (AIYP), from the National Federation of Youth Organizations (FNAJ). The document is based on opinions collected with young people and youth organizations regarding pressing issues for young people in Portugal. Based on those opinions, FNAJ defined 25 objectives that the national Government should try to achieve to improve the lives of Portuguese young people. These objectives include: “(1) the rights of youth; (2) access to housing; (3) worthwhile employment; (4) birth and family rights; (5) associative, volunteering and spaces for youth participation; (6) transparent democracy and political literacy; (7) a school for the future; (8) valuing non-formal education; (9) science, entrepreneurship and youth initiatives; (10) financial and labour literacy; (11) truthful information; (12) equality and intersectionality; (13) respect for differences and plurality; (14) equity and social inclusion; (15) rural development; (16) ecological, digital and inclusive transition; (17) fight programmed obsolescence; (18) protection of biodiversity and animals’ rights; (19) sustainable and healthy food; (20) sustainable mobility; (21) sexual and affective health; (22) quality mental health; (23) Youth talents; (24) access to culture; (25) Sports for everyone”.

These objectives also reflect a significant level of concern with issues related to processes of intersectional inclusion/exclusion. Although this document was not included in the document selection that will be analysed in this report, the decision to include it in this general subsection was related to the possibility of finding evidence of concrete actions that seek to address the sociopolitical topics that seem to be of particular interest to Portuguese youth.

Education

D3 – Bolsas no Ensino Superior (Despacho 9619-A/2022).
<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/despacho/9619-a-2022-187049894>

Document 3 is a governmental dispatch reviewing the regulations for the attribution of scholarships to higher education students. It includes “several changes to the process for awarding scholarships, providing for a) the automatic attribution of a higher education scholarship to all students who benefit from the 1st, 2nd or 3rd level of family allowance and who enter through the national competition for access to public higher education; b) the creation of a new supplement to the scholarship, with a maximum value of 250 euros per year, to support the travel of scholarship students between the location of their usual residence and the location of the educational institutions they attend; c) the attribution of additional accommodation to scholarship students who are displaced from their country of usual residence, which will allow accommodation support to students in an emergency situation for humanitarian reasons or beneficiaries of temporary protection as well as for Portuguese emigrants entering higher education in Portugal”. These measures are adopted as ways to “expand and diversify access to higher education and reinforce school social action, with a view to guaranteeing the continuation of studies for all students who wish to do so”.

According to the legislators, it is also “a way of encouraging access to higher education for economically underprivileged candidates”, thus “combating inequalities” and contributing to materialize “equality of opportunities” in higher education attendance. Considering this, the measure addresses specific financial needs of economically underprivileged, displaced and Immigrant students attending higher education in Portugal. It addresses the needs of young people at risk of intersectional exclusion in education and promotes their attendance in higher education courses, but it does not promote young people’s participation.

D4 - Programa +Superior (2018-2019) (Despacho 7103/2018).

<https://www.dges.gov.pt/pt/content/despacho-no-95422017-2a-serie-de-30-de-outubro-0>

Document 4 is a governmental dispatch that regulates the 2018-2019 edition of the “+Superior” program. The program aims, through the attribution of mobility grants, to encourage and support the attendance of higher education in regions of the country with less demand and less demographic pressure by economically underprivileged students who usually reside in other regions, contributing to territorial cohesion through the retention of young people and to achieve the Portugal 2020 targets regarding the number of young people with higher education. Additionally, it assumes “the objectives of combating school dropout, previously pursued by the “Retomar” program, continue to be adopted, by supporting students who interrupted their studies and who re-enter the same course they previously attended, as well as those who changed institutions and/or course”. Furthermore, it is recognized that “positive discrimination continues to be assumed in relation to students who enter through the competition for those over 23 years of age, as well as those who enter professional higher technical courses, in order to expand recruitment and diversify the profile of students entering higher education”. In this light, the program deals with intersectional inclusion/exclusion of young people, specifically those who intend to attend higher education courses. While the program expands the possibility of attendance of higher education by young people that would have otherwise financial difficulties it does not promote young people’s participation

D5 - Programa Escolhas (Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 4/2001).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/resolucao-conselho-ministros/4-2001-239016>

Document 5 is a resolution by the Portuguese Government that approves the “Choices” program. The legislators recognize that “a proactive response to prevent juvenile delinquency and insertion of young people who potentially find themselves on the path to marginality and exclusion is necessary”. It is also acknowledged that “the set of factors that provide paths towards the practice of acts, which criminal law typifies as a crime, include, among many others, accelerated urbanization and migration of nationals and foreigners to the outskirts of large cities, cultural differences, precarious public spaces and housing, low levels of education, insufficient health care, family dysfunction and negligent and inappropriate parental interventions”. Trying to compensate these factors, the Government approved the program, which seeks to achieve: “a) crime prevention and integration of young people from the most vulnerable neighborhoods in the districts of Lisbon, Porto and Setúbal, identified below; b) the personal and social, academic, professional and parental training of young people in the aforementioned neighborhoods”. More specifically, it is stipulated that the “Program is aimed particularly at young people aged 12 to 18 and will be structured around three strategic areas of intervention: social mediation, leisure time and community participation”. Thus, the program is focused on social and educational inclusion of young people in economically underprivileged social neighborhoods, namely by the promotion of activities that can attract young people at risk of marginalization to (re)engage in their education and participation of projects in their community.

D6 - Estratégia Nacional de Educação para a Cidadania (2017). <https://www.dge.mec.pt/estrategia-nacional-de-educacao-para-cidadania>

Document 6 is the “National Education for Citizenship Strategy” (NECS), which “integrates a set of rights and duties that must be present in the citizenship training of Portuguese children and young people, so that in the future they will be adults with a civic conduct that favors equality in interpersonal relationships, the integration of difference, respect for Human Rights and the valorization of concepts and values of democratic citizenship, within the framework of the educational system, the autonomy of schools and the curricular documents in force”. The document outlines general guidelines for the implementation of the subject of “Citizenship and Development”, which is currently a part of the national curricula, from primary to secondary education levels. According to the NECS, this subject should be “a privileged curricular space for the development of learning with a three-dimensional impact on individual civic attitude, interpersonal relationships and social and intercultural relationships”, adopting a whole-school approach that support educational practices that promote inclusion and that “involves students in active methodologies and offers opportunities to develop personal and social skills”. The NECS also defines three groups of topics that should be addressed in the subject of “Citizenship and Development”. The first of these groups – which is transversal to all levels of education – includes the following topics: “Human Rights (civil and political, economic, social and cultural and solidarity); Gender equality; Interculturality (cultural and religious diversity); Sustainable development; Environmental education; Health (health promotion, public health, nutrition, physical exercise)”. In this light, this document refers to the importance of including those that may be vulnerable to intersectional exclusion processes, while also advocating for the active democratic participation of all students in their schools.

D7 - Programa Educação Inclusiva (Revisão 2023-2024) (Decreto-Lei 62/2023).

<https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/1s/2023/07/14300/0000600009.pdf>

Document 7 is a decree-law that amends the rules for adapting the assessment process within the scope of the legal framework of the “Inclusive Education” program and the rules relating to the external learning assessment process. The legislators reinforce that the national Government sees “inclusion as a basic principle of the educational system” and that it continues “to pursue principles of equity, ensuring that all students have access to the necessary support in order to achieve their learning and development potential”. For students in general, this document establishes three national exams as mandatory to finish secondary education. In terms of inclusion, one of the amendments mandates “the use of instruments to support the application of evidence classification criteria to students with dyslexia or specific language impairment, as provided for in the Regulations for external assessment tests”. There is no indication supporting that participation of young people is addressed in this policy document.

Housing

D8 – Porta 65 - Jovem (Decreto-Lei 308/2007). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/308-2007-641166>

Document 8 is a decree-law that institutes the “Door 65 – Young” program and regulates the incentive for young people to rent housing for permanent residence, through the granting of a monthly subsidy under the terms established in this decree-law. Young people aged 18 or over and under 30 can apply, individually or as a couple, to the subsidy. Applications must be submitted via a specific website and, if approved, grants young people renting a house a monthly subsidy that will be paid by the Government over a year. After this period, applicants must submit a renewal application, for a maximum of 3 years, in total. Each beneficiary can only apply once to the program. The program includes special measures regarding “young people with

disabilities”, namely by allowing young people in these circumstances to apply for subsidy to housing above the limits set for the general population (in terms of space and monthly rent).

D9 – Ampliação do Porta 65 Jovem (Decreto-Lei 90-C/2022).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/90-c-2022-205557210>

Document 9 is a decree-law that extends the range of the “Door 65” program. It is argued that the program was “an important instrument to guarantee young people’s access to housing at prices compatible with their income and, in this way, support their emancipation processes”. Considering this, the objective of this policy document is to “increase the range of young people who can access this program, in particular by updating the maximum rent ceilings”. In this sense, the policy points towards the inclusion of young people in bigger households, by allowing them to rent houses with higher rents that are, hopefully, larger and with better living conditions. This policy also includes exceptional measures for the inclusion of young people studying, in formal training or in internships. This document does not include measures focused on increasing the participation of youth in their society.

D10 – Isenção de IMT para compra de habitação própria por jovens (Lei 30-A/2024).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/30-a-2024-869610340>

Document 10 is a law that authorizes the Government to exempt from municipal tax on costly property transfers and stamp duty for the purchase of own and permanent housing by young people up to 35 years of age. This measure seeks to facilitate young people’s purchase of their first permanent house, namely by reducing the amount of taxes paid upon the purchase. The law refers to young people in general, including no exceptions regarding young people in intersectional positions.

D11 – Garantia pessoal a instituições de crédito com vista à viabilização de concessão de crédito à habitação própria e permanente a jovens até aos 35 anos (Decreto-Lei 44/2024).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/44-2024-871466267>

Document 11 is a decree-law that establishes the conditions under which the State can provide a guarantee to credit institutions to make credit available for the purchase of own and permanent housing by young people up to the age of 35. The legislators recognize that “the consecutive increases in housing prices in recent years makes it increasingly difficult for young people, even if they are employed, to have the capital that allow them to pay the price of a property that is not financed by the credit institution”. To allow young people to have access to credit to finance this expense, the Government can provide credit institutions with a guarantee that secures their investment. Despite referring to young people in general, initially, the clauses of the decree-law establish that this measure “should only cover young people aged up to 35 years (inclusive), who have an income up to the 8th level of the national personal income tax table”. Additionally, it also stipulates that “the borrower cannot own an urban building or autonomous fraction of an urban residential building, nor take advantage of the State guarantee more than once. Finally, the value of the transaction cannot exceed 450.000€ and the guarantee to be provided by the State cannot exceed 15% of the value of the transaction. In this sense, the measure implicitly excludes young people who are not employed, those with salaries above a specific value, and those who already own an urban building. This means that, although this measure was said to improve access to housing for young people in general, it only targets a very limited section of youth. The measure does not facilitate or hinder participation of young people.

D12 - Plano de intervenção para a requalificação e construção de residências de estudantes (Decreto-Lei 30/2019). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/30-2019-120272925>

Document 12 is a decree-law that approves an intervention plan for the requalification and construction of student residences, based on the needs of students at higher education institutions and respecting their distribution throughout the national territory. It is recognized that “the provision of accommodation for higher education students who are displaced from their place of residence, in a decent manner and at affordable prices, is essential for the expansion and democratization of access to higher education”. This measure is also intended to relieve the pressure put by the housing necessities of students in higher education institutions on the general housing market. The Government clarifies that the measure will include: “a) The requalification of higher education student residences, namely through the improvement and expansion of infrastructure, re-equipment or improvement of material conditions; b) The creation of new accommodation, namely through the construction, rehabilitation or conversion of properties; c) The provision of temporary accommodation when necessary, namely while rehabilitation, requalification and construction of residences are taking place, in accordance with the previous paragraphs; d) Regular monitoring of the installed capacity of student accommodation, and respective supply and demand, and planning, in conjunction with higher education institutions, of the necessary actions taking into account the monitoring results, and that it will be implemented over a 10-year time horizon”.

As such, this measure is mainly targeting “displaced higher education students” described as “a student who, as a result of the distance between their residence and the location where they attend the study cycle in which they are enrolled need to reside in this location or its borders to attend the curricular activities of the respective course”. Although it seeks to improve conditions for students to attend higher education in institutions located outside their residence area, it does not include any other measure to facilitate participation of young people.

Employment

D13 - Plano Nacional de Implementação de *Uma Garantia Jovem* (Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 104/2013). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/resolucao-conselho-ministros/2013-176884946>

Document 13 is a resolution by the Portuguese Government that defines the National Plan for the Implementation of the Youth Guarantee. The “Youth Guarantee” is a program that “aims to implement in Portugal the European Commission recommendation for the implementation in each member-state of concerted initiatives between various agents in order to provide all young people under the age of 25 with a quality opportunity, whether in employment, permanent training, vocational education and training or internship, within four months of becoming unemployed or leaving formal education”. The program extends the previous “Youth Impulse” program (2013), and the national plan includes axes of intervention, objectives and specific measures to promote employment and education of young people. In Portugal, the Government extends the program to young people up to the age of 30, “recognizing the duration and complexity of the transition paths between education and work and adult life”. The plan addresses issues related to intersectionality and inclusion/exclusion. More specifically, it includes actions to “combat gender stereotypes that lead to the segregation of women and men by sectors and professions, including incentives for hiring people of the underrepresented sex in a given profession”, “boosting specific employability measures for people with disabilities”, “strengthening the participation of young women in training areas and those associated with emerging sectors and skills and in particular technological areas, particularly those linked to science, engineering, IT, electronics, robotics, among others, in order to prevent segregation phenomena professional and under-representation in these areas”. In fact, one of the axes of the plan is focused on the “inclusion of vulnerable audiences”, with support to programs that combat “obstacles to access to education, professional training and decent employment, by young people from particularly vulnerable contexts, aged between 18 and 29, who are in a NEET [those not working and not in

education or training] situation". It is also directed to young people in prison, as well as actions to reduce "the rate of young female NEETs in rural areas and peripheral and disadvantaged urban areas". In addition to these concerns, the plan also seeks to promote active participation of young people in these different programs, with the final objective of facilitating their integration in the labour market.

D14 – Pacto para Mais e Melhores Empregos para os Jovens (Fundação José Neves – com participação da Secretaria de Estado do Trabalho, empresas nacionais e patrocínio do Presidente da República). <https://www.joseneves.org/pacto>

Document 14 presents the "Pact for More and Better Jobs for Young People", promoted by the José Neves Foundation and the State Secretariat for Labor, with signatory enterprises and the patronage of the President of the Portuguese Republic. The pact first recognizes that "young people continue to be one of the most vulnerable groups in the labour market, with a significantly higher unemployment rate than that of the general population", which negatively affects young people's lives, the Portuguese society and the enterprises themselves, since it is argued that "companies with more qualified young workers have productivity gains if the number of young people has a significant weight in the total number of workers". To change these circumstances, the pact brings private enterprises and the Portuguese Government together for the establishment of an agreement on specific measures that can improve young people's employment. In the document, signatory enterprises commit themselves to, for instance: "increase the percentage of young people in new hires, increase the percentage of young people who remain at the company for two consecutive years, increase the percentage of young workers on open-ended contracts, ensure that at least 50% of young workers participate in effective training actions with the support of the company, increase the percentage of young people in the company's senior management boards". On its hand, the national Government, among other public policies that promote youth employment, commits to: "guarantee equal opportunities and combat discrimination of any kind" in the labour market, strengthen active employment policies in their different dimensions, from supporting job creation, inserting young people into the labour market and bringing vulnerable populations and territories closer to the labour market, making these the priorities of public policies, develop innovative methodologies that aim to enhance the employability of young people in more vulnerable situations, particularly young people in a NEET condition, through initiatives such as social employment incubators and others to be developed". In this light, the document indicates relative and somewhat implicitly concerns with the inclusion of young people at risk for intersectional exclusion in the labour market. Conversely, the document does not seem to focus on promoting young people's participation in the measures included in the pact.

D15 – IRS Jovem 2024 (Autoridade Tributária e Aduaneira). https://www.aciab.pt/images/pdf/Folheto_IRS_jovem_2024.pdf

Document 15 is an explanatory pamphlet of the "Youth IRS" – established by the Article 12B of the IRS Code (Law nr. 82-E/2014) -, which is an exemption for young people from paying the normal tax fees for the first five years of professional activity. The rules in 2024 stipulate that applicants must meet the following criteria: (i) be between 18 and 26 years old; (ii) earn income from work; (iii) not be considered dependent of any fiscal household; (iv) have completed a study cycle equal to or higher than level 4 of the National Framework of Qualifications or have completed a study cycle corresponding to level 8 of the National Framework of Qualifications (Doctorate), in which case the age limit for the *IRS Jovem* regime is extended up to and including 30 years of age. It is further clarified that this special fiscal regime is only applicable "to young people, in the first year of obtaining income, after completing a study cycle in the previous year, so the first year to be considered is not the year in which young people complete the study cycle, but rather the following year, in which they obtain the eligible income, thus allowing them to benefit from this exemption for an entire year of income". Eligible young people can benefit from a significant reduction (up

to total exemption) in their taxes for the first five years of professional activity. The criteria established by this policy implicitly excludes specific sections of young people (older than 26 years old, not working or who have not completed a study cycle in the previous year). The document does not address issues concerning young people's participation.

D16 - Estágios ATIVAR.PT (Portaria 293/2022). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/portaria/293-2022-204552591>

Document 16 includes a governmental ordinance that regulates the “Activate.PT” internships measure, which consists of supporting the insertion of young people into the labour market or the professional retraining of unemployed people. The program seeks to facilitate the inclusion of unemployed people and the transition of young people to the labour market by the “a) Complement and develop the skills of the unemployed, particularly young people, in order to improve their employability profile, through practical experience in a work context; b) Support the transition between the qualifications system and the labour market, namely by promoting the insertion of young people with appropriate levels of qualification into active life”. In addition to supporting nine months internships for “people aged 18 years or over and less than or equal to 30 years, holding a qualification at level 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 or 8 of the National Qualifications Framework”, the program also targets other people (young and older) at intersectional risk of exclusion, such as: “d) People with disabilities; e) People who are part of a single-parent family; g) Victims of domestic violence; h) Refugees and beneficiaries of temporary protection; i) Former prisoners and those who are serving or have served non-custodial sentences or judicial measures, in a position to enter active life; j) Drug addicts in the process of recovery; l) Homeless people”. These people can apply for longer internships of 12 months. Thus, the program addresses issues of intersectional inclusion/exclusion but, although it seeks to promote the active participation of young people in the labour market, specifically by awarding a bonus to enterprises that hire interns for, at least, a year after the conclusion of the internship, it does not focus on promoting any other form of participation by young people.

D17 - Programa Avançar (Portaria 187/2023). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/portaria/187-2023-215086004>

Document 17 is a governmental ordinance that creates and regulates the “Advance” program. The program follows the recognition by the Government that “the challenges that young people face in their life projects require transversal action, understanding as fundamental the implementation of specific measures for this segment of the active population, not only in order to value the investment made in their qualifications, but also in creating conditions for this new generation to find a favorable labour market so that they can build their life projects in Portugal”. Thus, in addition to a monthly supplement of 150€ (for a year) to the salary of young people hired under this program, it also includes the attribution of a financial support/award to enterprises that hire young people (up to 35 years old and higher education qualifications) for a minimum period of two years. This support includes a direct payment to the employer and the payment by the State of the social security contributions of the young person hired for a pre-set period. Special conditions (increases in financial support) are also defined for cases of enterprises that hire young people with disabilities and/or of a gender that is underrepresented in the profession. These conditions reflect one of the objectives of the program, which is to “promote gender equality in access and conditions in the labor market”. Thus, although the document does not mention which disabilities are eligible for these conditions and gender is not clearly specified, the document addresses issues concerning intersectional processes of inclusion/exclusion. Although the program supports young people inclusion in the labour market, it does not reflect concerns with other forms of participation by young people.

Health

D18 – Programa *Cuida-te+* (Portaria 258/2019). <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/portaria/258-2019-124044598>

Document 18 is an ordinance that creates the program “Take care+” and approves the respective regulation. The program stems from the National Youth Plan (see D1), which assumes youth health and well-being as a priority strategic area, especially concerning the right to health. This document starts by recognizing that “preventing disease and promoting the health of young people involves creating environments that promote healthy lifestyles across the board, as well as implementing activities designed to increase protective factors and minimize risk factors”. Additionally, in line with the National Youth Plan, the legislators underline the importance of addressing mental health at this age, especially because “an intervention capable of responding to the characteristics of this age group, recognizing it not only as a complex period of great changes, but also as a period particularly favorable for the prevention of risk behaviors and the promotion of healthy behaviors”. In this light, the program targets “young citizens, from 12 to 25 years of age, particularly individuals or groups in vulnerable or socially excluded situations”. It seeks to improve young people’s access to healthcare services and to promote their awareness about “health literacy and healthy lifestyles, mental health, nutrition, physical and sports activity, addictive behaviors and sexuality”. According to the regulation, this will be achieved by sensibilization campaigns and by providing young people with more information about these topics, as well as by the creation of other health services, such as Juvenile Health Offices, that should be prepared “to provide free, anonymous and confidential advice on the program's areas of activity, with the objectives of early detection, intervention and referral of the program's final target population to health structures”. Although there is no indication of specific measures to attend to the needs of young people at intersectional positions, the importance of intersectionality in processes of inclusion/exclusion is recognized by the special reference to “individuals or groups in vulnerable or socially excluded situations”. The document includes no information indicating that participation of young people is a concern of this program.

D19 – Gerações Mais Saudáveis: Políticas Públicas de Promoção da Saúde das Crianças e Jovens em Portugal (Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2018). <https://www.cns.min-saude.pt/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/GERACOES-MAIS-SAUDAVEIS.pdf>

Document 19 presents the “Healthier Generations” report, by the National Health Council. The report focuses on public policies to protect and promote the health of children and young people aged 0 to 18. It focuses on five main areas: (i) Health Promotion in Early Childhood, (ii) Health Promotion at School, (iii) Access to Health Care, (iv) Safe Environment, (v) Social Protection of Children. It starts by identifying some of the most important prevalent health issues in Portuguese children and young people, such as childhood obesity, oral health problems, mental health problems, accidents and respiratory diseases related to the environment. It recognizes the positive effects of existing policies, such as those regarding the protection of children from passive exposure to tobacco or the prohibition and criminalization of the sale of alcoholic beverages and tobacco to minors under 18 years of age, but also stresses the importance of ensuring that all children have an assigned family doctor, of addressing geographic discrepancies in vaccination coverage rates, and of providing mental health care aimed at children and young people. It also concluded that “the needs of the age group from 0 to 18 years old, probably due to the enormous heterogeneity of this population, are met unequally”. On a macro analysis, this report starts by stressing that “Governments shape children's living conditions by influencing how income is distributed and by determining the availability of housing and early education and care services”, going on to recognize that “in recent years, there has been an increase in inequalities in children's income, with children being the age group most at risk of poverty”. According to the report, this has significant impact on Portuguese children’s and young

people's health, which should encourage national authorities to implement additional policies that “promote the fight against poverty, social exclusion and violence, working with children, young people and families” and “reinforce support for children and young people with disabilities and their caregivers”. Thus, the report addresses socioeconomic issues that affect young people's health and stands for more social inclusion measures that protect young people in vulnerable conditions. The report also points to an increase of participation of young people in national health prevention programs (most of them at school) and the universal access of Portuguese children and young people to public health services. In this sense, the document addresses both issues concerning processes of inclusion and of participation as well.

D20 - Agenda da Juventude para a Saúde 2030 (Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2021).

https://fnaj.pt/uploads/editor_uploads/files/AgendaJuventudeSaude_2030.pdf

Document 20 presents the “2030 Health Agenda for Youth”, by the National Health Council. The Agenda describes children and young people as being “fundamental in the construction of society. They are, unequivocally, the most active defenders of the fight against climate change and the inequities experienced in today's society. The health of children and young people is, therefore, not only a human right but a fundamental resource for a healthier and fairer society”. The document advocates for the inclusion of children and young people in the definition of public policies and in their actual implementation. In that sense, the Agenda included “moments of consultation through focus groups, questionnaires, debates in schools and public debates” that involved young people in the identification of target areas that should be addressed by future national policies for promoting youth health. Following this approach – described in the document as “nothing for young people without young people” -, “this Agenda focuses on the areas that these children and young people considered priorities for their health in the next decade: the promotion of physical and psychological well-being, sexuality education, the prevention of smoking and other addictive behaviors, the promotion of healthy eating and physical activity, and the prevention of violence (including bullying and cyberbullying)”. In addition to measures for promoting young people's access to health information, training, and healthcare services, as well as for promoting healthy environments, the Agenda includes significant concerns regarding processes of inclusion of young people “living in more vulnerable situations, such as overcrowded housing, with poor structural and energy conditions, damp, without heating or ventilation, without access to digital media or food in adequate quantity and quality, or exposed to domestic violence”, as well as “neurodivergent children and young people, and/or those with intellectual, sensory or motor disabilities”. According to the document, young people at these intersectional positions “must be recognized, welcomed and supported by the various sectors of society, and their capabilities must be enhanced, in order to prevent social exclusion and achieve equity”. This deep concern with potential discrimination and exclusion is summarized in the following recommendation to national authorities: “respect for difference must be promoted and stigma and discrimination should be reduced in the face of any difference, be it racial, ethnic, gender, identity, or other”. In this light, the document not only addresses potential intersectional inclusion/exclusion, but it also advocates for the direct participation of young people in policymaking for improving the health of Portuguese youth.

D21 - Programa Nacional de Saúde Infantil e Juvenil (Norma da Direção-Geral da Saúde 010/2013).

<https://www.dgs.pt/directrizes-da-dgs/normas-e-circulares-normativas/norma-n-0102013-de-31052013-jpg.aspx>

Document 21 establishes the new “National Child and Youth Health Program” (NCYHP), which maintains the same structure of its previous version (2005) but introduces several modifications. It includes a detailed schedule for programmed appointments of children and young people (from 0 to 18 years old) with their family doctor. In this new program, diagnosing potential psychopathological at young age is defined as a priority, as well as early diagnosis of other health problems at this age interval. This new version of the NCYHP

includes significant concerns with processes of inclusion/exclusion in children's and young people's access to healthcare services. The document recognizes that "health inequalities that persist, when considering different social groups", stressing, for instance, the importance of "detecting and supporting children who have special needs, who are at risk or are particularly vulnerable, reducing inequalities in access to health services". This new version seeks to be "an instrument to support comprehensive child and youth health that contributes to equal development opportunities for all children and young people, regardless of the socioeconomic contexts of families and communities". In that sense, it warns health staff that "children and young people may experience risky situations or abuse, as well as have special health needs. Such cases require increased attention from health services, which must develop specific intervention strategies appropriate to them". In fact the legislators recognize that "it is not possible to list all situations involving children and young people at risk or with special needs, nor to establish a single action program", which is why it leaves "to the health team to identify, from a family-centered perspective, the special needs of each child, signal them, provide them with continued support and promote coordination between those involved in care". This shows that the program recognizes the heterogeneity of young people and seeks to promote the inclusion of those in particularly vulnerable individual and social circumstances. The program does not, however, address issues concerning the participation of young people, aside from the fact that it also mentions the importance of promoting "the personal and social development and self-determination of children and young people, with progressive responsibility for health-related choices".

D22 - Programa de Apoio à Promoção e Educação para a Saúde (Direção-Geral da Educação, 2014).

https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Esauade/papes_doc.pdf

Document 22 presents the "Health Promotion and Education Support Program" (HPESP), by the national Directorate-General for Education (DGE). DGE recognizes that "there is growing evidence that health and education are closely linked to each other" and that "healthy children and adolescents learn better and are more successful". Although it is argued that "In our country, the Ministry of Education has long been defining health promotion and education policy measures, with the aim of providing children and young people with knowledge and values that help them develop attitudes and adopt behaviors that promote health. health and physical, social and mental well-being", the HPESP seeks to increase initiatives by schools to "help children and teenagers learn and be healthy". To that aim, the program includes financing and a checklist to help with self-assessment and monitoring of projects in schools, as well as e-learning training/information for school staff on how to implement projects that help to "provide children and young people in pre-school, primary and secondary education with the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that allow them to value and adopt healthy behaviors and lifestyles throughout their lives, developing their full potential as citizens active, productive and responsible". According to the document, the HPESP targets children and young people in general, with no specific measures towards inclusion of young people at risk of intersectional exclusion. Furthermore, although the program mentions concerns with providing the students with favorable conditions to develop their democratic citizenship competences, it does not include concrete actions that could be seen as seeking the participation of young people.

Participation

D23 – Orçamento Participativo (2019) (Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 59/2019).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/resolucao-conselho-ministros/59-2019-121403392>

Document 23 is a resolution from the national Government that regulates the 3rd Edition of the "Youth Participatory Budget Portugal". The program was originally implemented to help in "combating the phenomenon of the progressive distancing of young citizens from political participation and other areas of public life, developing instruments of democratic participation and involvement of all layers of the population in various political processes". In the two previous editions, the program has welcomed "more

than eight hundred proposals were presented and around 15 thousand young people voted”, which leads to a very positive assessment of the program, with the Government claiming that “our country became the first, in the entire world, to implement this process in youth plan throughout the national territory”. According to official authorities, the Youth Participatory Budget is “an important contribution to increasing democratic literacy and the deliberative processes of young citizens and so that they are seen as a fundamental part of society, supporting the deepening of their citizenship skills”. More specifically, some of its main goals include “b) promote the active and informed participation of young citizens in decision-making processes, favoring the existence of a strong and active civil society, which pursues cohesive development at economic and social levels and the corresponding increase in quality of life; c) Promote the participation of young citizens in the definition of public policies suited to their needs and in accordance with their opinions; d) Strengthen education for citizenship and the feeling of belonging to the community as a whole, encouraging responsible civic action, by promoting privileged contact between young citizens and public entities, involving them in the permanent definition of the *res publica*”. Any Portuguese citizen that is between 14 and 30 years old can submit a proposal (individually or in a group) for changing something in their society. Proposals are then analyzed to verify their compliance with the eligibility criteria. If accepted, the authors must turn their proposal into a more concrete project that can be implemented on the field. The projects are submitted to vote by any national or foreign citizen legally residing in Portugal and aged between 14 and 30 years old, via the program webpage. The most voted projects are implemented by public authorities, spending the allocated budget (the 3rd Edition the program had a total budget of 500.000€) by the national Government. The program has been widely disseminated among the national media and has been deeply connected to school projects. The legal document does not indicate concerns with issues related to intersectional inclusion/exclusion processes. On the contrary, promoting Portuguese youth active citizenship is the main goal of the program.

D24 - Plano Nacional de Incentivo ao Associativismo Estudantil (Portaria 284/2020).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/portaria/284-2020-150946889>

Document 24 is a governmental ordinance that creates the “National Incentive Plan for Student Associations” (NIPSA). The document starts with the recognition by the legislators that “promoting the civic and political participation of young citizens is a central objective of the State, as a way of improving the quality of democracy. Student associations contribute to the democratic socialization and civic formation of young people, through active participation in the school community”. Additionally, it is stated that “student associations are the instrument of social intervention per excellence for young people, which allows them to influence and participate in decisions taken at the level of the school community and promote activities among the students, increasing the feeling of belonging to the community and reinforcing the conditions for civic participation”. In this acknowledgement, the program seeks to support the participation of young students in their school community by “reinforcing the role of non-formal education in their training process, through legal and institutional support to student associations or groups of students who wish to establish themselves as student associations”. Young people are also involved in the monitoring process of the program’s implementation, by nomination of members, by the National Youth Council, National Federation of Youth Associations and the National Federation of Basic and Secondary Education Student Associations, to the Monitoring Committee that assess the program implementation yearly. Altogether, the document establishing the NIPSA is specifically directed at improving conditions for the involvement of young students in their school environment, but it does not reflect concerns regarding other potential cases of intersectional inclusion/exclusion.

D25 - Regime Jurídico do Associativismo Jovem e Programa de Apoio Juvenil (Lei 23/2006).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/23-2006-359360>

Document 25 is a law that establishes the legal regime for youth associations, as well as programs to support the development of their activity. The document defines that “youth associations enjoy autonomy in the preparation of their respective statutes and other internal rules, in the election of their governing bodies, in the management and administration of their respective assets and in the preparation of activity plans, in compliance with the law and the principles of freedom, democracy and representation”. It also establishes the rules applicable to financial, technical, formative and logistical support provided to registered youth associations by the State. It further stipulates that “youth associations have the right to be represented in national, regional or local consultative bodies with responsibilities in the field of defining and planning youth policies, as well as in legally established co-management bodies in the implementation of youth policies”. To that end, the law defines that recognized youth associations should be consulted and involved in the definition of public policies to address young people’s needs and that student associations “have the right to issue opinions during the process of drafting legislation on education, particularly in relation to the following areas: a) definition, planning and financing of the educational system; b) school management; c) access to higher education; d) school social action; e) study plan, restructuring and creation of new groups and curricular areas or subjects”, as well as “the right to be consulted by school management bodies in relation to the following matters: a) school educational project; b) internal regulations; c) activity plans and budget; d) projects to combat school failure; e) assessment; f) school social action; g) organization of activities to complement the curriculum and school sports”. Although the document is geared towards young people in general, it implicitly shows concerns with intersectionality and processes of inclusion/exclusion, for instance, when it stipulates that assessment of youth associations’ applications for financial support by the State should consider “balance between young people of both sexes and promotion of goals converging with the valorization of gender equality” as an important criterion.

D26 - Programa de Apoio as Associações Juvenis (Portaria 354/96).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/portaria/354-405914>

Document 26 includes a governmental ordinance that establishes the rules for the “Support Program for Youth Associations”, which seeks to facilitate the Government’s priority of supporting “youth associations as a way, among others, of promoting civic participation and democratic learning among Portuguese young people”. The document “defines the modalities and areas of support to be provided to youth associations”, stipulating that “only youth associations and other entities registered in the National Register of Youth Associations (RNAJ) can benefit from the support”, and that this support could take “the following forms: a) development plans; b) specific support”. The financial support to be attributed could be destined to infrastructures, equipment, human resources, activities, international relations, operations, publications, training, documentation, information or legal advice. Although this ordinance reaches back to the year of 1996, an updated version of the program is still in place, renamed as “Support Program for Juvenile Associations”. The program promotes the participation of young people by providing youth associations with financial resources to achieve their goals. In addition, the rules also state that the “number of young people to be covered” and the “participation of young people in the definition, planning, execution and evaluation of the project” should be considered as relevant criteria in the assessment of proposals for support. The document refers to young people in general, with no mentions that indicate concerns with inclusion/exclusion of young people in intersectional positions.

D27 - Regime Jurídico dos Conselhos Municipais de Juventude (Lei 8/2009).

<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/legislacao-consolidada/lei/2009-107668124-107674476>

Document 27 is the law that establishes the “Legal Regime for Municipal Youth Councils” (MYC), as well as their composition, powers and operating rules. MYCs are the municipality's advisory bodies on matters

related to youth policy. According to this legal regime, MYCs “pursue the following purposes: a) collaborate in the definition and implementation of municipal youth policies, ensuring their articulation and coordination with other sectoral policies, particularly in the areas of employment and professional training, housing, education and higher education, culture, sport, health and social action; b) ensure the hearing and representation of public and private entities that, at the municipal level, carry out responsibilities relating to youth; c) contribute to deepening knowledge of economic, social and cultural indicators relating to youth; d) promote the discussion of matters relating to the aspirations and needs of the young population residing in the respective municipality; e) promote the dissemination of research work relating to youth; f) promote youth initiatives at local level; g) collaborate with municipal bodies in exercising their powers related to youth; h) encourage and support youth association activity, ensuring its representation before local authorities, as well as other public and private entities, national or foreign; i) promote collaboration between youth associations within their scope of action”. MYCs include representatives from each youth association based in the municipality registered in the National Register of Youth Associations (RNAJ), from each basic and secondary education student association based in the municipality; from each higher education student association based in the municipality, and from each student federation registered with the RNAJ whose geographic scope of action is limited to the municipality area. MYCs “are responsible for monitoring and issuing recommendations to municipal bodies on the following matters: a) execution of municipal youth policy; b) execution of the budgetary policy of the municipality and its business sector regarding youth policies; c) incidence of the evolution of the municipality’s socio-economic situation among its young population; d) civic participation of the municipality’s young population, particularly regarding youth associations. a) promote debate and discussion of matters relating to municipal youth policy, ensuring links between young people residing in the municipality and the heads of local authority bodies”. Although the opinions officially issued by MYCs are non-binding, they represent a significant channel for young people to influence local policymakers and local policies targeting youth. In this sense, the document is deeply related to the promotion of political participation by young people, it does this, however, without references that might indicate concerns with issues related to intersectionality or processes of inclusion/exclusion.

Local Policy Documents

Housing

LD1 – Manifesto Autárquico: Uma Proposta do Movimento Associativo Juvenil (FNAJ, 2017).

https://www.fnaj.pt/uploads/editor_uploads/files/Publicações/manifesto_autarquico_quadrado.pdf

The local document 1 is the “Local Manifesto”, by the National Federation of Youth Associations (FNAJ). FNAJ was founded in 1996 to represent the local youth associative movement in Portugal. It now represents more than a thousand youth associations distributed throughout the country. In this document, the importance of local authorities for addressing the needs of young people is underlined. It is stated that “local authorities are, among the power structures, the closest to young people and their reality, which is why they have a fundamental role in promoting their civic participation. The participation of young people in local life must be part of a global autonomous policy that encourages the participation of citizens in public life, through real policies for youth, articulating strategies for emancipation and the fight against inequalities and discrimination”. According to FNAJ, “active participation of young people in decisions and activities in local government is essential for the consolidation of a democratic, inclusive and prosperous society”, and that is why it has created the Manifesto with the “purpose of constituting a strategic municipal reference in a multiplicity of areas of governance that affect the lives of young people”, such as “education, employment, civic participation/associativism, employment, equality, health, sexuality, culture and sports”. The Manifesto also includes proposals for measures that FNAJ believes would be important to

address the difficulties of young people in having access to housing. In this area, the document includes proposals for more local “programs that promote more autonomous lifestyles for young people living alone, in families or in young cohabitation”. It is further proposed that “local authorities, in close collaboration with youth organizations, tenants, social housing institutions and social assistance programs, should promote the establishment/development of: a) local housing information services aimed at young people; b) local programs (low-cost loans or rental guarantee systems) to help young people gain access to their own housing and become emancipated; c) Local programs to support youth rentals and support the rehabilitation of buildings in historic centers for the same purpose”. The previous information shows that the document addresses issues concerning social inclusion/exclusion processes of young people in intersectional positions, while also advocating for deeper participation of youth in the planning and implementation processes of local policies to address issues affecting young people’s quality of life.

LD2 - Regulamento de Atribuição de Benefícios Fiscais no Âmbito de Impostos Municipais do Município de Braga (Regulamento 619/2024).

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.cm-braga.pt/pt/0502/municipio/camara-municipal/apoio-ao-cidadao/regulamentos/item/item-1-18187/download&ved=2ahUKEwj6kc6t5OCHAxW7BfsDHXe7OooQFnoECBMQAQ&usg=AOvVaw1NW-T9oK-CgGYtsDRXpldb>

The local document 2 is the official regulation for a support and incentives measure for purchasing housing for young people in the Municipality of Braga (North of Portugal). This measure seeks to facilitate young people’s purchase of their first permanent house, namely by reducing the amount of taxes paid upon the purchase, seeking to settle young people in the city (and outskirts) of Braga. This local measure is very similar to that implemented by the national Government in 2024 (see D5 in national policies). The regulation adds, however, an additional tax exemption for young people doing construction/reconstruction projects, as long as it is intended exclusively for their own permanent home and located in the territorial district of the Municipality of Braga. The document refers to young people in general, including no exceptions regarding young people in intersectional circumstances.

LD3 – 1º Plano de Ação Regional de Juventude do Algarve (ECOS – Cooperativa de Educação Cooperação e Desenvolvimento, CRL, 2015). <https://algarve2020.ecos.pt/plano-de-acao-regional-de-juventude-do-algarve/>

The local document 3 is the “1st Algarve Youth Regional Action Plan”, which is a strategic guidance document that includes specific action proposals, to be implemented in the Algarve region (South of Portugal) by 2020, in different areas of youth, such as: Associations, Volunteering and Civic Participation; Combating Inequalities of Opportunities; Interculturality and Intergenerational Solidarity; Access to Housing; Mobility and Access to Information; Education, Training and School Dropout; Employment, Innovation and Entrepreneurship; Culture, Sports, Leisure and Tourism; Environment and Rural Development; Health Promotion and Prevention of Risk Behavior and Road Prevention. The document includes the results of youth consultation actions that helped to identify obstacles faced by young people in the Algarve region in the areas previously mentioned. From these results, the document defines strategic objectives and concrete actions aiming to address the issues identified by young participants. For the purposes of this report, our analysis focused on the “Access to Housing” area. In this area, the obstacles identified included: “Rent and purchase of high-cost housing; Lack of construction of social housing at controlled costs for young people; Lack of support for young rentals; Lack of transparency in the allocation of social housing; Lack of measures and policies to support the rental and acquisition of housing for young people; Lack of effective dissemination of programs and measures to support housing for young people; Lack of financial autonomy for young people to access housing; Difficulty accessing housing credit”. Based

on these obstacles, the document proposed the following strategic objectives: to “Promote an information system capable of supporting young people in the Algarve region in accessing housing; Create conditions for easier access to the rental market to young people; Promote support measures for young people who, for academic or professional reasons, find themselves in a situation of temporary mobility; Support urban rehabilitation for youth housing purposes; Promote greater participation of young people in youth housing strategies”. The Plan also includes the following actions to achieve these objectives: “Create a regional information platform, coordinated by a regional entity with responsibility in the youth area, with information on supply/demand for housing aimed at young people and information on youth rental support programs; Develop information activities, among young people, on procedures for purchasing and renting own housing; Create a collective youth rental platform (home sharing); Create a housing program that facilitates processes of autonomy for young people from their family of origin, through low-cost temporary rental programs (e.g.: maximum duration of 2 years), aimed at young people looking for their first home; Facilitate access to renting for young people, creating their own lines of credit, with banking entities, that facilitate the acquisition of essential equipment and initial expenses; Creation of a housing sharing program, between young university students and the elderly population (similar to that developed in other cities in the country); Stimulate private investment to create housing aimed at younger people, through tax benefit”. In this light, the document addresses processes of intersectional inclusion/exclusion, namely by supporting young students and young people facing difficulties in paying rent. In terms of participation, the plan is targeted to young people in general, with no intersections mentioned or implied. Nevertheless, the proposed measures in the Access to Housing area do reflect a concern with promoting young people participation, especially in the definition of policies that facilitate housing to young people.

LD4 – Regulamento do Programa Municipal de Arrendamento Jovem (Câmara Municipal de Arcos de Valdevez, 2018).

https://www.cmav.pt/cmav/uploads/document/file/5003/regulamento_arrendamento_jovem.pdf

The local document 4 is the official regulation for a youth rental support measure by the City Hall of the Municipality of Arcos de Valdevez (North of Portugal). According to the document, with this measure, the Municipality “aims, on the one hand, to contribute to the retention, attraction and empowerment of young people and, on the other hand, to promote the rehabilitation and dynamization of urban areas in the city center of Arcos de Valdevez”. The measure consists in renting a set of housing units owned by the Municipality “at costs lower than those practiced in the rental market”. According to the regulation, “young people residing in the Municipality of Arcos de Valdevez for more than a year, aged 18 or over and under 35” years old are eligible to apply for these houses at lower rents. However, the regulation also adds other criteria that must be met by applicants, such as: “none of the candidates or other members of the household may own another building or housing unit; None of the candidates or other members of the household may have debt to the tax authority or social security; The household's monthly income cannot be less than one minimum monthly wage, nor greater than three minimum monthly wages; The family aggregate must be suitable for each of the typologies put up for competition, as advertised in the competition opening notice”. These criteria seem to exclude young people who are unemployed, however, the regulation also stipulates that “candidates who are not in an active professional situation, as a guarantee of compliance with the obligation to pay the rent assumed by the tenant, will be required to have a guarantor, jointly and severally liable with the tenant”. Applications complying with these criteria are eligible to enter a public raffle that will determine access to the housing units. The regulation for this measure seems to be somewhat contradictory. It is meant to attract young people to the municipality, however, it stipulates that applicants have to reside in the Arcos de Valdevez for at least a year to be eligible. This can be considered an exclusionary criterion for young people in general. The regulation also implicitly refers to an intersectional position of young people who are unemployed.

LD5 - Regulamento do Programa Municipal de Apoio ao Arrendamento Jovem — Vive Pombal (Aviso 15197/2023). <https://www.cm-pombal.pt/wpdm-package/regulamento-do-programa-municipal-de-apoio-ao-arrendamento-jovem/>

The local document 5 is the “Regulation of the Municipal Youth Rental Support Program — Live Pombal”, by the Pombal (Center of Portugal) City Hall. The Municipality recognizes that “access to housing represents, nowadays, one of the main challenges faced by young people, both at municipal and national level”, so with this program it intends to “on the one hand, to contribute to establishing, attracting and empowering young people and, on the other, promoting the rehabilitation and dynamization of urban centers, as well as combating the evident demographic losses”. The regulation for the program establishes that young people between 18 and 35 years old can apply, individually or in a household, for a monthly subsidy, corresponding to a percentage of the total value of their housing rent expenses, to be attributed by the Municipality for a maximum period of 3 years. The regulation also establishes inclusion and exclusion criteria, such as that applicants can be national or foreign (with a valid residence visa) citizens, that the household total income cannot be lower than the national minimum wage nor higher than three times its value, applicants cannot be owners of housing property, they cannot have pending debt with national or local public institutions, cannot be receiving other public subsidy to housing (such as by the program “Porta 65 Jovem”, see D8). Additionally, maximum rent values are indicated for each house typology (ranging from 450€ to 700€). Young people interested must submit an application to the program and will only be eligible if they “live in a rented property or intend to rent a property for their own permanent residence in the Municipality of Pombal”. Applications will be evaluated by a Jury and ordered according to their compliance with the criteria. The program will only attribute this financial support to a maximum number of applications allowed by the annual budget allocated to the program. The regulation for the program includes specific criteria for inclusion/exclusion of young people in particular circumstances, such as (un)employment. Although intersections are not explicitly mentioned, the rules implicitly exclude officially unemployed young people from accessing the program.

Participation

LD6 - Plano Municipal de Juventude do Porto 3.0 (Câmara Municipal do Porto, 2017). <https://www.cm-porto.pt/files/uploads/cms/1612453310-693EC7pBOg.pdf>

The local document 6 is the “Municipal Youth Plan 3.0” of the Porto (North of Portugal) City Hall. This is a general policy document that includes the plans of the Municipality to address young people’s needs in areas such as identity, culture, education, training, employment, housing, environment, health and sports. Local policymakers recognize that the plan is “anchored on the premise that to decide it is necessary to know the youth reality and the specificities of the territory. Knowing youth, in its heterogeneity, makes it possible to inform local policies that are intended to be sustained and that consider real inequalities in access to opportunities, whether at the labor market, cultural or educational levels”. One of the main objectives of the plan is “to promote greater and effective participation of young people”. To that end, the plan includes a Strategic Plan which includes strategic axes for intervention with young population. In this report, we focus on “Axis 2, Civic Participation, Identity and Citizenship”, which “is organized around the social relevance of youth participation in the development of the local contexts to which they belong”. This axis includes objectives such as: “raising awareness among young people, via formal and non-formal education, of the importance of their individual and collective participation in development and local social cohesion; Empower young people to actively participate in the development of local policies; Create and/or reinforce civic participation opportunities for young people; Promote articulation between associations in secondary education and other types of associations or other youth movements; Activate initiatives that provide young people with “structured”, formal or informal contact with transculturality, transnationality

and diversity (via tourism, academics, employment)". To achieve these objectives, the document also includes an Annual Action Plan presenting some concrete actions that will be implemented on the ground, with partners from the Porto City Council. Recognition of heterogeneity and inequalities among young people are visible throughout the document, with local officials recognizing "that equal participation opportunities are not equally distributed, assuming the existence of a significant set of different obstacles to active involvement and effective civic participation of young people. Therefore, it is necessary to provide different youth population groups with the necessary conditions to promote their participation". Although this points to concerns with processes of social and political inclusion/exclusion and participation being present in the plan, it is also worth mentioning that another one of its axes is focused on "Contexts and Phenomena of Social Exclusion, with the main purpose of raising awareness among young communities in Porto about different forms of social exclusion, with particular emphasis on discrimination and inequality of gender opportunities".

LD7 - Estratégia da Juventude do Porto 4.0 (Câmara Municipal do Porto, 2021). https://mailings.cm-porto.pt/tmp/juventude/CMP_2021_Estrategia_da_Juventude_do_Porto_4.pdf

The local document 7 is the "Youth Strategy 4.0" of the Porto City Hall, which establishes the Municipality political commitment to young people, the strategic framework for youth policies, an open and collaborative platform to activate Porto's Youth Goals, and a work, evaluation and continuous improvement tool. In the document, local policymakers state that they "want to return youth policies to young people, discover and learn how they want to participate in democratic and city life". It clarifies that its main target audience are "young people 15-32 years old who were born, live, study, work or visit Porto", but also "youth organizations and youth technicians". The strategy also establishes guiding principles for its implementation, including the use of "youth centered solutions created by and with young people to respond to young people's needs and aspirations" that promote "inclusion open to all young people and with special attention to young people with fewer access opportunities" and "participation co-creation, co-decision, collaboration, democratic culture, constructive dialogue". To that end, the strategy establishes specific goals, to be achieved between 2021 and 2025, to promote civic and political participation of young people living in the city. These objectives include the implementation of ideas and activities included in the A3 Declaration (proposed by the Municipal Youth Council), to support the development of young people's citizenship skills, to strengthen the collaboration, innovation and sustainability capabilities of youth organizations and to improve access to quality youth information. These objectives reflect the document's focus on promoting participation by young people, integrating an inclusive approach that promotes "accessible, clear, safe and visible equal opportunity for all young people". The document also reflects recognition of addressing the problems of young people at intersectional risk of exclusion, by stating, since the beginning of the document, that "whenever we refer to young people, we understand young men, young women and transgender young people, without any gender discrimination".

LD8 - Plano Nacional de Políticas Locais para a Juventude (FNAJ, 2019). [https://www.fnaj.pt/uploads/editor_uploads/files/documento_plano_nacional_web\(1\).pdf](https://www.fnaj.pt/uploads/editor_uploads/files/documento_plano_nacional_web(1).pdf)

The local document 8 presents the "National Plan for Local Youth Policies", by the National Federation of Youth Associations (FNAJ). The document includes a diagnosis of municipal youth policies, a presentation of European youth strategies, recommendations for Portuguese local youth policies, and a list of good municipal practices. The diagnosis, which "here resulted from the application of in-person and online consultation processes developed during the seven "Associativism and Youth Regional Summits", which brought together nearly 700 participants", indicates that Portuguese young people who have participated in the study believe that there is a lack of "awareness or low performance of Portuguese municipalities in implementing locally based youth policies, particularly with regard to: Municipal Youth Plans; Municipal

Youth Councils; Youth Participatory Budgets; Establishment of technical youth teams in Portuguese municipalities; Establishment of youth services geared towards the needs of young people; Investment plans in the Youth sector; Spaces for planning and executing young people's projects". From this diagnosis, FNAJ recommends that "municipalities and the youth sector must find space and create opportunities to implement European standards and recommendations", by promoting "the implementation of the rights and duties of young people in 21st Century democracy, particularly at the local level, and guarantee the attraction and retention of young people in the territories; [Promoting] the involvement of young people in the processes of associative and municipal participation, in their universality, as voters and elected officials, from a perspective of gender equality and opportunities; [Promoting] the organization and management of local youth policies with young people and for young people, according to their real needs; [Promoting] the planning and participation of young people in associative and municipal actions, which can be the target of impact assessment and monitoring of indicators that can be measured; [Promoting] the involvement of youth professionals in the development, planning, execution and evaluation of youth policies at the associative and municipal level; [and promoting] quality criteria in work with young people according to national and international indicators, recognized both by organizations representing young people and by public and governmental institutions". These recommendations reflect a concern with the participation of young people in local policymaking and implementation, while only implicitly referring to the inclusion of young people at risk of intersectional exclusion, particularly based on gender discrimination.

LD9 - Programa de Apoio e Incentivo Juvenil de Santa Maria da Feira (Câmara Municipal de Santa Maria da Feira, 2024). <https://cm-feira.pt/programa-de-apoio-e-incentivo-juvenil>

The local document 9 is the official regulation for the "Youth Support and Incentive Program" of the City Hall of Santa Maria da Feira (North of Portugal). The Municipality defined the objectives for the program according to the European Union's Youth Strategy 2019-2027 and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. The objectives include the following topics: mental health and well-being, sustainability, climate action, quality work for all, eradication of poverty, space and participation for all, gender equality, reduction of inequalities and quality education. According to the regulation, legal youth organizations, informal groups of young people, student associations, and individual young people (18 to 30 years old) born and/or living in Santa Maria da Feira can apply to a financial support by the City Hall. The maximum amount of the support is one thousand euros for each project. Applications are submitted via the Municipality's webpage, and should take into account that "social coverage: valuing the social impacts of the activity carried out by the entities, with a view of involving the community and promoting youth participation [...] Participation, involvement and training of young people throughout the entire activity execution process [...] Number of young people at whom the activity is aimed" are some of the main criteria for the evaluation of proposals. All financed projects must be executed until the end of the year of 2024. The objectives of the program reflect concerns with processes of inclusion/exclusion of young people in intersectional positions, however, the main target audience of the program seems to be young people in general, with no specific measures to promote the participation of young people in those positions.

LD10 - Regime de Políticas de Juventude para a Região Autónoma dos Açores (Decreto Legislativo Regional 30/2023/A). <https://jo.azores.gov.pt/api/public/ato/78cbd15c-d1bf-4fcc-af41-2c2d0fef70d/pdfOriginal>

The local document 10 is a regional legislative decree that establishes the "Youth Policy Regime for the Autonomous Region of Açores". Under its political autonomy status, the Legislative Assembly of the Autonomous Region of Açores approved the regime to serve as a general policy document that guides public policies for youth in Açores. The document assumes the general goal of encouraging "the creation of

conditions so that young people can assert themselves as solidary, responsible, active and tolerant citizens in plural societies". The regime establishes general guidelines for youth policies that target "areas of training, information and communication, youth associations, the occupation of young people's free time, the promotion of healthy lifestyles, volunteering, active citizenship, entrepreneurship, creativity, employability and mobility of young people". The decree is mainly focused on promoting civic and political participation of young people in Açores. It includes objectives such as "the development of democratic values, through the promotion of programs and actions aimed at enhancing coexistence, freedom, equality, tolerance and solidarity, as well as a critical spirit; Equal opportunities among young people, as well as between them and other age groups, in all areas of political, social, economic and cultural life in Açores; The active participation of young people in the planning, development and monitoring of youth policies, through associative or individual events; Young people's privileged access to complete information regarding all policies that concern them; The promotion of gender equality". Article 43 clarifies that "civic participation by young people is understood as the actions carried out by them, with the aim of developing constructive mechanisms for the life of their communities", while Article 44 includes general measures to encourage the participation of young people, such as "Initiatives to raise awareness of the importance of autonomous institutions and the democratic system; Interdepartmental partnerships with the purpose of encouraging young people to reflect and debate on issues relating to their community; Programs and initiatives that promote the development of skills, as well as the acquisition of enriching and stimulating knowledge and experiences, which encourage civic participation in young people, in its various aspects; Opportunities for young people to become autonomous citizens and actors involved in the political, social, cultural and environmental dimensions; Development of community intervention projects". Additionally, Article 11 presents a set of measures to provide young people living in rural communities with similar conditions for participation as those available to young people in urban communities. Considering these contents, the document addresses processes of inclusive participation of young people, including those who could potentially be vulnerable to intersectional exclusion in Açores.

Conclusions

The following conclusions include a summary and tentative interpretation of some of the results achieved by the codification process of each document/policy included in the national and local samples.

At the national level, most of the documents analysed deal with issues related to processes of inclusion/exclusion but with significant variations across the different areas. The policy documents in the Education area appear to be in line with an inclusive education perspective, since all documents in this area seek to expand the inclusion of students in public educational settings. This includes acknowledgement of the importance of addressing the needs of children and young students at intersectional positions, whether because of gender, socioeconomic background, nationality or physical and/or psychological limitations. The policies selected for the Employment area follow a similar pattern, with all documents indicating concern with expanding the inclusion of young people, including those at intersectional risk of social exclusion, like young people who are unemployed, not working nor studying, in low socioeconomic contexts, those who were victims of domestic violence, refugees, ex-inmates, who have disabilities; are single parents or those recovering from drug addiction. However, it is noteworthy that one of the documents in this area seems to point to a restriction of inclusion or to actual processes of exclusion by restricting access of sections of young people to the employment program that it regulates. The Housing and Health areas also indicate substantial concern with processes of inclusion/exclusion, with four of the five documents addressing topics related to this dimension. In terms of intersectionality, policies to help young people face current challenges in access to housing mainly focus on positionalities related to income disparities and on young people who are still studying, while policies to improve young people's access to

health focus on intersectional positionalities related to socioeconomic disparities and to young people with special needs, stemming from psychomotor disabilities. Surprisingly, the four of the five policy documents in the Participation area indicate no concern with processes of inclusion/exclusion and intersectionality. The only document in which the expansion of inclusion is visible deals with potential discrimination based on gender, while the rest of the policies are directed at young people in general.

On the contrary, in terms of participation (Dimension 2), all documents in the Participation area seek to promote young people's civic and political engagement by creating channels for participation. Notably, however, these policies are usually targeting young people in general, with only two documents indicating concern with gender equality and young students. In the Education and Health areas, two of the five documents indicated concern with promoting young people's participation, with special focus on children and young people living in different socioeconomic contexts and from different genders and cultures. In the Employment area, only one of the policies indicated concern with promoting the participation of young people, with particular focus on intersecting positionalities related to gender, socioeconomic status and psychomotor development. The selected documents in the Housing area were the only set of policies that did not indicate any concern with promoting young people's participation.

At the local level, the results of the analysis of the local policies in the Housing area are similar to those at the national level for Dimension 1, with four out of five documents indicating concern with processes of inclusion/exclusion, while being slightly higher for Dimension 2, with two of five documents indicating concern with promoting young people's participation. It is noteworthy that local policies in this area seem to follow a similar approach to policies at the national level, with incentives for young people to purchase or rent their first house at lower costs. However, usually, local programs do not overlap national ones, since they are only accessible to those who are not receiving national support and want to live in the corresponding municipality.

Regarding the results of the analysis of local policies in the Participation area, these are substantially different from those at the national level in Dimension 1. In fact, all five local policies included in the sample indicate concern with promoting the inclusion of young people from different genders and in different geographical and socioeconomic positionalities. This contrast may be related both to specific characteristics of the national and local levels and to the nature of the policy documents themselves. On one hand, it is possible that while national policies aim to target macro societal issues that affect young people's participation in general, local policies are more focused on specific issues, at the meso and/or micro levels, that hinder the participation of young people in their communities. On the other hand, it is also possible that the discrepancies between both levels are simply due to the nature of the documents included in each sample, with national documents including more concise and specific regulations while the local documents included more general frameworks and recommendations for youth policies in this area. Either way, a more in-depth analysis of each individual policy would be necessary to explore less visible (more implicit) connections between their textual contents and the coding criteria established for each of the two dimensions.

Overall, the sample of documents analysed in this report reflects substantial efforts, by national and local public organizations, to address some of the main problems faced by Portuguese young people and signalled in the "Second National Youth Plan" (D1) and in the "Agenda for Innovation in Youth Policies" (D2). Young people's difficulties in finding a stable job with reasonable salary, in buying or renting their first house, in taking care of their physical and mental health, and in being engaged citizens in their society and communities seem to have been considered by national and local policymakers in the creation of this set of youth policies. In terms of intersectionality, as expected, most national and local policies in these areas do not seem to promote exclusion processes (except in rare cases of documents that include very specific

criteria for inclusion/exclusion in particular programs). In fact, while some policies seem to be mainly directed at young people in general, others still reflect an explicit or implicit recognition of the importance of including those at potential risk of intersectional exclusion due to their age, gender, socioeconomic status, nationality or ethnicity and health related elements.

NATIONAL REPORT SWITZERLAND (UNIGE)

INTRODUCTION SECTION

Despite Switzerland ratifying the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child over two decades ago, Yvonne Feri, President of the Foundation Council of Child Protection Switzerland and National Councillor pointed out the existence of significant gaps in prioritizing young people and children's rights over their needs, making their participation in the Swiss context rather discretionary than mandatory (Rapport sur les droits de l'enfant à l'attention du Comité des droits de l'enfant de l'ONU, 2021 : 3). This echoes Patricia Von Falkenstein's statement at the National Council for the PLR party last June, underlying the lack of reliable data on young people across the country which is essential for ensuring equal rights and appropriate service. As a matter of fact, the exact number of young people in Switzerland who for example spent part of their lives in care homes or foster families is unknown. The MP therefore further questioned how the Federal Council plans to ensure national statistics which will include data on young people¹⁸. Additionally, the often-blurred distinction between children and young people makes it at times challenging to clearly define the intended beneficiaries of these policies (Holecz 2023). Considering and recognizing that young people are an heterogeneous groups facing different challenges and experience, we take a closer look of some of the situation occurring within a specific time frame in Switzerland for the national level and, the canton of Geneva for the local level. This national report provides a broader perspective on the analysed documents; however, it should be understood as a general overview with methodological limitations only.

Education:

Being in school

In the Swiss context, 21,7% of the population is between 18-35 years old (OFS 2023). Based on the most recent data from 2023, 6.7% of young individuals aged 18 to 24 without post-compulsory education were not engaged in any formal training programs. However, this figure masks significant disparities when considering both nationality and gender. Among Swiss citizens, 4.8% of young people were in this category, compared to a notably higher 13.1% of foreign nationals. Gender differences were also observed, with 7.2% of young men not participating in formal training, slightly higher than the 6.1% of young women¹⁹.

Scholarship

In 2022, Switzerland awarded cantonal scholarships to 46,285 individuals, accounting for 7.1% of all trainees. The total amount allocated for these scholarships was 356 million Swiss francs. Most of the scholarships, 57%, were granted for secondary school education, while 42% supported those in tertiary education. Notably, 76% of the recipients were under the age of 25, and 65% were Swiss nationals²⁰.

Employment:

NEETs

The NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) rate for individuals aged 15 to 29 stands at 7.7%, with significant variations based on gender and nationality. Among young men, 7.5% are classified as NEET, slightly lower than the 7.9% observed among young women. A more detailed

¹⁸<https://www.parlament.ch/fr/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaefft?AffairId=20247425>

¹⁹ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/fr/home/actualites/quoi-de-neuf.assetdetail.32072009.html>

²⁰ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/fr/home/statistiques/education-science/finances-systeme/bourses-publiques.html>

The HBSC 2022 findings indicate a significant decline in mental health and well-being among 11- to 15-year-olds, a trend that had already been observed in 2018, particularly among girls. Multiple factors, beyond the COVID-19 pandemic, likely contribute to this trend. There is a pressing need for enhanced mental health promotion and early detection of problems to prevent severe and chronic conditions (Delgrande et al. 2023:11).

Increased Stress from Schoolwork

In 2022, for the first time, the HBSC study measured general psychological stress among 11- to 15-year-olds. On a scale from 0 to 16, the average stress level was 6.6, with girls averaging 7.2 and boys 5.9. Stress levels increased with age among girls but not boys. Specifically, about 34% felt moderately to highly stressed by schoolwork, with older students and girls reporting higher stress levels. This proportion, stable from 2002 to 2018, saw a sharp increase in 2022, particularly among 11-year-olds and 13- and 15-year-old girls (Delgrande et al. 2023:14).

Feelings of Loneliness

Approximately 15% of 11- to 15-year-olds reported feeling lonely most or all of the time in the past year, with a higher proportion among girls (21%) compared to boys (9%). The frequency of loneliness increased with age among girls but not boys (Delgrande et al. 2023:14).

Body Image

In 2022, about 49% of 11- to 15-year-olds (54% boys, 44% girls) considered their weight to be about right, a decrease from 2018, especially among girls. The deterioration in body image, observed since 2018, was more pronounced among 14- and 15-year-olds, with boys generally having a more positive body image than girls. Around 14% of respondents (11% boys, 16% girls) were dieting or taking other measures to lose weight, a proportion that has remained relatively stable since 2002. This tendency increases with age among girls but remains stable among boys (Delgrande et al. 2023:21).

Young people and Disabilities

The Federal Act on the Elimination of Discrimination against People with Disabilities (DDA; RS 151.3), effective since January 1, 2004, is supported by three ordinances that address discrimination and accessibility in public transport for people with disabilities (RS 151.31, RS 151.34, RS 151.342). The DDA implements the constitutional mandate in Article 8, Paragraphs 2 and 4 of the Swiss Constitution, focusing on removing barriers and ensuring non-discrimination²⁵. However, no specific law exists for labor-related discrimination. According to Article 13 of the DDA, the Confederation must use all available means to ensure equal opportunities for disabled people as an employer²⁶.

The Act also mandates cantons to integrate children with disabilities into regular schools through suitable methods whenever possible, ensuring educational decisions are free from prejudice²⁷. While the DDA does not offer a direct right of appeal within basic education, appeals can be made based on the constitutional right to non-discrimination and adequate, free education (Article 29 of the Swiss Constitution). Cantons are

²⁵ <https://www.edi.admin.ch/edi/fr/home/fachstellen/bfeh/droit/schweiz/behindertengleichstellungsgesetz-behig.html>

²⁶ <https://www.edi.admin.ch/edi/fr/home/fachstellen/bfeh/droit/schweiz/behindertengleichstellungsgesetz-behig/arbeitsverhaeltnisse.html>

²⁷ <https://www.edi.admin.ch/edi/fr/home/fachstellen/bfeh/droit/schweiz/behindertengleichstellungsgesetz-behig/grundschulunterricht---aus--und-weiterbildung.html>

required to align their laws with the DDA, and a new intercantonal agreement on specialized education was adopted in 2007 and came into effect on January 1, 2011.

Suicide

The number of suicides among young men remains significantly higher than among young women, with 58 cases compared to 33 in 2020. However, suicides among young women have been on the rise, increasing from 25 cases in 2019 to 33 in 2020. In the specific, the annual average for this age group between 2010 and 2019 had been 18 cases. In contrast, the number of suicides among young men under the age of 25 has remained relatively stable, with 58 cases in 2020 compared to 56 in 2019. The average for this age group over the period 2010-2019 was 59 cases per year²⁸.

The number of calls for help regarding suicidal thoughts has been steadily rising. In 2023, consultations for suicidal thoughts among young people surged by 26%. On average, 9 children and adolescents per day reached out to hotlines help for their suicidal thoughts, a significant increase from the 3 to 4 consultations per day recorded in 2019²⁹.

LGBTQ+ youth are 2 to 5 times more likely to attempt suicide compared to their heterosexual peers. This danger is heightened when individuals first disclose their sexual orientation to those closest to them (Häusermann, 2014). Based on trends observed in other countries, the risk for transgender youth is likely even higher; however, no specific data are currently available. The school environment plays a pivotal role in the experiences of LGBTQ+ individuals related to suicide attempts, as they frequently encounter bullying, social exclusion, and pressure to conform within this setting (Bomolo et al., 2022).

Housing

According to the Swiss Tenants' Association (ASLOCA), nearly three-quarters of the Swiss population face housing issues, regardless of whether they live in rural or urban areas, with the problem being more acute in large cities. Certain groups, such as students, are particularly affected due to their generally limited financial resources. Students often seek accommodation in major cities, which frequently suffer from housing shortages, especially for affordable options. This edition of *Droit au logement* explores this issue and the development of student housing (ASLOCA 2022: 4).

In Switzerland, the fundamental right to assistance in emergencies, including access to food, clothing, emergency medical care, and shelter, is recognized under Article 12 of the Federal Constitution. However, the Constitution does not guarantee a universal legal right to housing. While federal social objectives classify housing as a basic need and support those seeking accommodation, they do not establish an individual entitlement to housing. Article 41 emphasizes personal initiative in securing housing, and cantons acknowledge their responsibility in preventing and combating homelessness, but implementation varies widely (Drilling, Küng, Mühlethaler, Dittmann 2022: 12). The concept of "homeless person" is not legally defined in Swiss law; homelessness is seen as a condition impacting all aspects of life and can be resolved by providing housing. Nonetheless, homeless individuals are entitled to basic social rights, including the right to emergency assistance, regardless of their residence status. Article 12 provides for essential benefits necessary for a dignified existence, excluding those capable of self-support, and does not guarantee specific benefits like a basic income. It is mainly applied in asylum cases and for undocumented foreign nationals (Drilling et al. 2022: 4).

²⁸ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/asset/fr/23446123>

²⁹ <https://www.projuventute.ch/fr/fondation/actualite/communiqués-de-presse/147-von-pro-juventute-beratungsnachfrage-wegen-multikrise>

The Affordable Accommodation Act (AAA) of 2003 aims to create more living spaces for low-income households and promote access to homeownership, benefiting families, single parents, people with disabilities, the elderly, and individuals in training. However, the act's focus on at-risk groups, particularly adults, often overlooks children and young people, despite their vulnerability (Drilling et al. 2022: 12). Structural causes of homelessness, such as housing market conditions and the exclusion of undocumented migrants from support services, are rarely addressed. The Victim Support Act provides emergency accommodation for up to 21 days, a recommendation that varies by canton and is not legally binding. Women's shelters are a recognized crisis intervention service for domestic violence, though places are limited and follow-up solutions are scarce. There are few programs for men affected by domestic violence, such as Zwüschehalt and Foyer le Pertuis in Geneva (Drilling et al. 2022: 10).

Few cantons have established comprehensive assistance systems or specific services for homelessness, resulting in significant uncertainty about the extent and nature of the issue. Many experts associate homelessness support closely with social assistance, which limits aid for those not meeting eligibility criteria. Nonetheless, some cantons have implemented best practices, including regional cooperation, cantonal housing provision, and expanded social planning (Drilling et al. 2022: 4). It is estimated that approximately 2,200 people are homeless in Switzerland, with around 8,000 at imminent risk of losing their homes. Homelessness is predominantly a challenge for larger urban communes, especially in the six major Swiss cities with over 100,000 inhabitants. The threat of homelessness also affects communes in rural and intermediate areas. Most communes lack their own accommodation facilities, rarely cooperate with others, and do not receive guaranteed support from cantonal or federal authorities. They also set access criteria that can lead to exclusion and displacement (Drilling et al. 2022: 4).

The Geneva Example

Student housing in Geneva is diverse. More than half of the students looking for accommodation in Geneva encounter significant difficulties. The University's Housing Office ([BLOG](#)) manages social housing for students and supports its expansion, offering around 800 beds in various residences. BLOG also facilitates a platform where residents can list available rooms for rent, simplifying the search process. This platform, launched in 2021, replaced the previous, more cumbersome system where students had to register with each residence separately. Additionally, innovative programs like "1h per m² - A Student Under My Roof" provide alternative housing solutions (ASLOCA 2022: 7).

On this notice, as the academic year approaches September 2024, students in both cantons Vaud and Geneva face significant difficulties in securing accommodation. Two weeks before the start of classes, many are still struggling to find housing, exacerbating an already challenging situation.

In Geneva, the student housing cooperative *La Ciguë* is currently overwhelmed by demand, receiving 1,400 applications for only 800 available units, according to Nicolas Rault, head of internal relations at the cooperative. While the situation in Neuchâtel is less critical, with fewer requests, concerns remain regarding the quality of available housing, as noted by Marius Hofer, co-president of the Neuchâtel Student Federation³⁰.

Participation:

³⁰ <https://www.rts.ch/info/regions/2024/article/avec-la-rentree-universitaire-le-parcours-du-combattant-pour-trouver-un-logement-28615673.html>

As wrote by Holecz (2023), “the Swiss population has a high level of political trust in the national political authority compared with other European countries (Bauer et al. 2019); however, trust tends to first decrease among the younger age groups and then increase from the age of 40 onwards (Marquis et al. 2022: 15 In Holecz 2023). Regarding the evolution of the political participation of Swiss citizens from 1999 to 2020, a recent study found that the older one gets, the more politicised one becomes (Marquis et al. 2022 in Holecz 2023). However, this is with some nuances: members of Generations X and Y (born between 1965 and 1994) tend to have the lowest engagement levels compared with older or younger generations. However, Lionel et al. (2022) used data from the Swiss Household Panel, and therefore, non-institutional forms of participation were not yet present alongside institutional forms of engagement” (Holecz, 2023: 29).

Voter turnout

A 2022 survey from gfs.bern indicates a growing trend among young people towards the use of institutionalised political instruments³¹. The survey reveals that 86% of young people eligible to vote in the upcoming referendum express their intention to participate. Similarly, 78% plan to engage in upcoming federal votes, marking the highest levels of participation recorded since the survey began. However, the likelihood of using other direct democracy tools, such as signing popular initiatives, referendums, or petitions, is significantly lower, with 51% of young people expressing interest. Additionally, only 45% consider participating in the next elections, indicating a more reserved engagement with electoral processes. When it comes to less formal political actions, such as attending protests or combining pleasure with political activism through events, only 34% of young people show interest in participating in such activities. These findings suggest that while young people are more inclined towards traditional voting mechanisms, they are less likely to engage in other forms of direct democracy or more informal methods of political participation.

The Swiss Conference of Gender Equality Delegates (CSDE) commissioned Sotomo to conduct the third National Equality Barometer, detailed in the 2024 report. This edition specifically focuses on generational and gender differences, with particular attention to Generation Z³². The findings reveal a significant gender gap in perceptions of equality in Switzerland as of 2024. Women generally have a more negative assessment of gender equality compared to men, a disparity observed across all generations and political orientations. The causes of this divergence are multifaceted, including differing experiences and realities, such as sexual harassment and workplace discrimination. Current societal debates, including issues related to women and gender, such as the #MeToo movement, have also gained prominence in recent years. The survey uncovered a notable gender gap among Generation Z, along with significant differences compared to older generations. While women from Generation Z tend to have a less critical view of gender equality compared to women from older generations, most young men believe that gender equality has largely been achieved (Baromètre 2023 : 13). Furthermore, more than four out of five women, compared to just over half of men, have experienced abusive situations. Political measures aimed at strengthening the rights and protections of LGBTIQ+ individuals are mainly supported by this demographic and women. Proposals for preventive measures against violence towards LGBTIQ+ individuals and the statistical recording of hate crimes enjoy majority support among the population (Baromètre 2024: 23).

³¹ <https://cockpit.gfsbern.ch/fr/cockpit/easyvote-politikmonitor-2022/>

³² Data was collected from October 11 to 26, 2023, from a linguistically integrated population residing in Switzerland, aged 16 and over. The survey was conducted online in German, French, and Italian, with participants recruited via the Sotomo panel and the Bilendi online panel. After final data validation, information from 2,500 individuals was analyzed.

LGBTQI+ Associations

In Switzerland, there are few activities and services specifically for LGBTQI+ children, and most offerings for LGBTQI+ youth and educational services are concentrated in larger cities like Zurich, Bern, Basel, Baden, Chur, and Winterthur. Rural areas often lack specialized healthcare centres and educational training, offering limited resources for LGBTQI+ youth (Panel, S. L., Lanfranconi, D., Eisner, L., Theissing, L., and Hässler, T., 2023:45). There are disparities not only between different cantons and regions but also within them, with most services being available in urban areas. For instance, conservative cantons like Aargau and Glarus have rejected initiatives for greater inclusion, while cities like Baden and Chur provide some services for LGBTQI+ youth. This uneven distribution contrasts with the needs of rural LGBTQI+ youth, who may rely on online support but still require essential in-person services.

In French-speaking Switzerland, there are also few activities and services specifically targeting LGBTQI+ children. However, disparities exist within this region as well, with cantons like Vaud and Geneva having more comprehensive services compared to others like Jura (Panel et al. 2023:66). In Ticino, there are similar issues with a lack of institutional policies and dedicated positions for LGBTQI+ issues, which limits the scope of action. Most workshops and activities in 2023 have been the result of individual and volunteer initiatives from students, teachers, or companies.

Considering now the Canton of Geneva, it is important to point out that in March 2023, Geneva's Grand Council approved a law to promote equality and combat violence and discrimination based on sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression, or intersex status, making Geneva a pioneer in this area. The law includes measures for prevention through training and awareness campaigns, a system for receiving complaints from victims and witnesses of discrimination against LGBTQI+ individuals, and the requirement to develop a cantonal action plan to be submitted to the Grand Council (Panel et al. 2023:56).

Participation in demonstrations

According to the 2022 gfs.bern survey, only 34% of young people reported show interest in participating activities such as attending protests or combining pleasure with political activism through events³³. The belief that youth movements are effective in changing societal attitudes has decreased significantly. In 2019, 52% of respondents considered youth movements to be a key method for influencing societal change, but in a 2022, this number had dropped to 36%. This represents a 16 percentage point decrease since 2019³⁴. The view that going on strike (instead of using established democratic instruments like referendums) is incomprehensible has remained steady. In a survey of 2022, 41% of respondents expressed this view, maintaining the same level as in previous years³⁵.

³³ <https://cockpit.gfsbern.ch/fr/cockpit/easyvote-politikmonitor-2022/>

³⁴ <https://cockpit.gfsbern.ch/fr/cockpit/easyvote-politikmonitor-2022/>

³⁵ <https://cockpit.gfsbern.ch/fr/cockpit/easyvote-politikmonitor-2022/>

Policy document sampling selection

Website Selection

We used two websites to search for documents at the national level: the Federal Law Publication Platform (Fedlex) and the Federal Administration website. These platforms were chosen to ensure a complete collection of national policy documents for Switzerland. Fedlex offers access to federal laws and related documents, while the Federal Administration website provides additional materials produced by various federal commissions, such as the Federal Commission for Children and Young People. This combination ensures a wide selection of documents, including not only legislation but also reports, public programmes and other government publications reflecting the scope of national policy initiatives.

Regarding the local level, we focused on the canton of Geneva. Documents were search through the following platform <https://silgeneve.ch/legis/index.aspx> and <https://ge.ch/grandconseil/m/index>. The first platform is an electronic database of legislative and legal information, including laws, case law from the Federal Court and a wide range of other information and documents related to the canton of Geneva. The second one is an electronic database which features session of the Grand Council since 1993.

Document Search Process

Fedlex, unfortunately, does not support complex search queries. Therefore, we conducted searches using the keywords 'youth' and 'youth', focusing on documents containing these terms in the title and/or text. On the federal administration website, on the other hand, we manually navigated through the pages of the relevant federal commissions and used the same keywords to identify documents related to youth.

A similar approach was used at the local level as well. As a matter of fact, we traced back from 2024 to identify amendments or projects of law containing keywords as "young people". This initial step was followed by a deeper understanding of the document to determine their relevance to the chose policy areas: participation and health. For the first policy areas, participation, a broader approach was adopted, including documents that could help foster participation rather than a strict sense of participation.

Results Selection

Youth-related documents in the policy areas of participation, education and health were easy to find. However, finding relevant documents in the areas of employment policy and housing policy proved more challenging. In the specific, two out of the five documents on employment policy, as well as all documents related to housing, only briefly mention young people.

At the local level, youth-related documents in participation policy areas were searched, focusing on broader aspects since participation is a cross-cutting domain. This approach involved examining potential changes in laws and ongoing debates.

Analysis: National level

Policy Areas	Education
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D1 is the "[Message on the Promotion of Education, Research, and Innovation from 2025 to 2028](#)". The document presents numerous federal decrees on the financing of vocational and continuing education, higher education, research institutes, international cooperation and innovation initiatives. The document underlines the commitment of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences to engage young people by promoting MINT skills (mathematics, computer science, natural sciences and technology), especially among children and young people, with a focus on promoting girls and ensuring equity for those from disadvantaged backgrounds. The document also claims that Swiss universities are committed to promoting equal opportunities, diversity and inclusion, integrating these issues into their organisational structures and strategies and regularly assessing progress. However, the document does not discuss young people's opportunities for political participation but focuses on improving social and political engagement through education.

D2 is an [ordinance on international cooperation and mobility in the field of education](#). It discusses the issue of funding for organisations offering extracurricular services which could increase opportunities for youth participation. However, it does not discuss the issue of inclusion and diversity among young people.

D3, an [ordinance](#), establishes a system of incentives for the Youth and Music Programme. The aim is to encourage the musical engagement of children and young people. This document treats young people as a homogenous group and does not discuss their opportunities for inclusion or participation.

D4 is a [Federal Decree](#). It allocates funds for international cooperation in education and scholarships for foreign students and artists for the years 2021 to 2024. Like the previous document, it does not address the inclusion of young people or their opportunities for participation, treating them as a homogenous group.

D5, "[Solid Foundations for Civic Education](#)" by the Federal Commission for Children and Youth, focuses on increasing participation opportunities for young people by supporting more effective civic education. However, it treats young people as a homogeneous group and without dealing with their inclusion.

Summary

Of the five documents, only one discuss youth inclusion, underlining the importance of schools in promoting MINT skills among children and youth, particularly girls, and ensuring equity for those from disadvantaged backgrounds. This document is also the only one of the five that does not treat young people as a homogenous group.

Only two documents talk about opportunities for youth participation. One mentions the funding of organisations offering extracurricular activities, potentially increasing participation opportunities, while the other encourages civic education.

Policy Areas	Employment
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D1 is the [Ordinance 5 related to the Labour Act](#). It discusses protection measures for young workers. However, it does not address the inclusion or opportunities for participation of young people, treating them as a homogeneous group.

D2, is the [Message concerning the approval of the agreement between Switzerland and the United Kingdom on the recognition of professional qualifications and its implementation](#). It mentions that young professionals would benefit from the agreement by allowing them to undertake work placements in the other country. Yet, it does not address the inclusion or participation opportunities for young people, treating them as a homogeneous group.

D3 is the [Message of the Swiss Federal Council concerning an amendment to the Unemployment Insurance Act](#). It includes a section focused on supporting young adults in their transition to the labour market by providing more opportunities to gain relevant work experience. Specifically, young adults who have just completed school or vocational training and have not yet paid contributions must observe a reduced waiting period of 120 days before receiving unemployment insurance benefits. The aim is to offer ongoing, targeted support to young adults seeking work, enabling them to gain practical work experience and improve their job market prospects. The document states that the amendment would positively impact the professional integration, social environment, and long-term socio-economic prospects of youth. However, it does not mention opportunities for participation and treats young people as a homogeneous group.

D4 is a [Federal Council Decree which extends the scope of the collective labor agreement in the Swiss building envelope sector](#). Youth leave is mentioned regarding the conditions that allow or prevent an employer from reducing a worker's holiday length in the event of prolonged absence. However, young people are not mentioned in any other context. Consequently, the document does not deal with the inclusion or opportunities for participation of young people, treating them as a homogeneous group.

D5 is the [Ordinance of the Federal Department of Finance on the Personnel of the Confederation](#). It includes a provision for paid leave for staff who participate in youth activities in a managerial capacity. However, this document also does not deal with the inclusion or opportunities for participation of young people, treating them as a homogeneous group.

Summary

Only one document deals with increasing the inclusion of young people by facilitating their entry into the labour market. None of the documents deal with increasing opportunities for young people to participate. All documents treat young people as a homogeneous group.

Policy Areas	Health
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D1 is titled "[Mental Health of Children and Young People: Stepping Up Prevention and Guaranteeing Access to Care](#)". It presents the position of the Federal Commission for Children and Youth. This document supports the motions "Safety of Care Provision in Child and Adolescent Psychiatry" and "For a Strategy and an Action Plan Against Racism and Anti-Semitism". It stresses the need to strengthen prevention against violence and discrimination, highlighting that young people experiencing discrimination are more likely to develop mental health issues. The document asserts that reducing discrimination enhances mental health. It acknowledges that young people are not a homogeneous group and notes that some have experienced specific forms of discrimination, such as racism, sexism, homophobia, and antisemitism. However, it calls for general prevention against discrimination without proposing targeted measures for different types of discrimination. Additionally, it lacks discussion on young people's opportunities for participation.

D2 represents the Position of the Federal Commission for Children and Youth titled "[Fully Protect Children and Young People from Tobacco Advertising](#)". It urges the implementation of the popular decision "Yes to Protecting Children and Young People Against Tobacco Advertising" without any changes that would weaken protection. This document does not address young people's inclusion or opportunities for participation, treats them as a homogeneous group, and refers to them together with children.

D3 is a [message concerning the amendment of the Federal Law on Tobacco Taxation](#), specifically the taxation of electronic cigarettes. It aims to establish a legal basis for taxing electronic cigarettes, stating that higher taxation on liquids in disposable e-cigarettes should positively impact addiction prevention, particularly among young people, who are more sensitive to price changes. This message does not address young people's inclusion or opportunities for participation and treats them as a homogeneous group.

D4, the [Ordinance on Pilot Trials within the Context of the Narcotics Law](#), sets conditions for trials involving narcotics with cannabinoid-like effects. It mandates that each trial include a prevention, youth protection, and health protection plan, and monitor its effects on youth. However, it does not mention young people's inclusion or opportunities for participation and treats them as a homogeneous group.

D5 is the [Amendment of 8 April 2020 of the Ordinance on Sports Promotion Programs and Projects, discusses the "Youth and Sport" program](#). The amendment increases the inclusion of young people by providing additional subsidies to enable young people with disabilities to participate in the program. However, it does not deal with young people's opportunities for participation.

Summary

Only two of the five documents concerning mental health mention young people's inclusion, and these are the same only two documents that do not treat young people as a homogeneous group. The first document addresses the impact of discrimination on mental health and calls for measures to combat discrimination. It mentions young women, implicitly refers to young Jews, and describes discrimination in terms of racism and homophobia, thereby recognizing young people from ethnic minorities, young migrants, and young LGBTQ+ individuals. The second provide additional subsidies to enable young people with disabilities to participate in sports. None of the five documents discuss opportunities for young people's participation.

Policy Areas	Housing
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D1 is entitled titled "[Housing Policy in Towns and Cities: Needs and Challenges](#)" and was commissioned by the Federal Housing Office. The paper points out that young couples, along with older couples, are significantly affected by the shortage of housing supply in more than half of the cities analysed. However, the report does not address issues of inclusion or participation opportunities for young people, nor does it acknowledge the heterogeneity of this demographic group.

D2, also commissioned by the Federal Office for Housing, is entitled "[Homelessness in Switzerland: Understandings, Policies, and Strategies of the Cantons and Communes](#)". This report notes that cantonal knowledge about people at risk of homelessness rarely, if ever, mentions young people or women. In particular, young women are rarely recognised for their specific vulnerabilities. Although the report recognises the exclusion of young people, particularly young women, it does not pursue this recognition in its recommendations. Furthermore, it does not address participation opportunities for young people.

D3 is a report commissioned by the Federal Social Insurance Office, entitled "[Housing Assistance for Vulnerable Households: A Guide for Cantons, Towns, and Municipalities](#)". It states that the housing shortage is a growing problem affecting both young and old people and families. However, the report does not mention the inclusion of young people, opportunities for participation or diversity within this group.

D4 is entitled "[The State of Public Housing: A Comparison with Rental and Owner-Occupied Housing](#)" and was also commissioned by the Federal Housing Office. The report indicates that young people often opt for rental housing due to a lack of financial resources or a desire to avoid long-term commitments in one place. The report does not mention the inclusion of young people, their opportunities for participation or their diversity.

D5, also commissioned by the Federal Housing Office, is entitled "[Housing Policy Dialogue between the Confederation, the Cantons, and the Cities](#)". The document notes that the housing market often neglects the needs of the elderly, the disabled and young people in training. It also mentions multigenerational housing as projects that help young people and families to settle down. Despite this, the report does not address the issue of inclusion and participation opportunities for young people.

Summary

Of the documents reviewed, only one addresses the issue of youth inclusion, noting that young people, and young women in particular, are neglected in discussions on homelessness. However, this recognition does not translate into actionable recommendations. Another report acknowledges that the housing market neglects the needs of specific groups, including young people in education, but it too does not offer practical solutions or focus on youth inclusion. None of the documents examine opportunities for youth participation.

Policy Areas	Participation
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D1 presents the [Federal Commission for Children and Youth's stance on citizenship education in Switzerland](#). This document proposes strategies to improve citizenship education and mentions its role in promoting social inclusion. In addition to proposing improvements in school curricula, it also recommends promoting the involvement of young people in associations. It also stresses the need to pay special attention to young people who, due to their family background, have not been exposed to politics. The document also stresses the importance of providing citizenship education also to children and young people who do not have Swiss citizenship.

D2 is entitled "[Forms of Political Participation and Motivating Young People to Get Involved](#)" and presents the recommendations of the Federal Commission for Children and Youth. It proposes measures to increase political participation among young people without, however, talking about social inclusion. The document acknowledges that factors such as socio-economic status and parents' level of education influence young people's interest in politics and impact their political participation. It also emphasises the need to strengthen digital forms of participation in order to enable the political participation of young people with social anxiety or reduced mobility. However, beyond this point, the document does not propose any further measures that take into account the different starting situations of young people, which it merely names, thus limiting the scope of the recommended initiatives.

D3 represents the Position of the Federal Commission for Children and Youth on "[Giving More Weight to the Recommendations of Children and Young People](#)". With this document, the Federal Commission for Children and Youth supports the proposal to allow the Youth Session and the Children's Conference to submit their petitions and proposals to the relevant committees. However, the document speaks of young people in a homogeneous way, ignoring their different needs and associates them with children, mentioning them together.

D4 is a research report by the Federal Social Insurance Office on the "[political participation and the motivation of young people to get involved](#)". It does not talk about social inclusion but suggests possible ways to improve young people's opportunities for participation. The report recognises that young people are not a homogenous group and that some encounter different barriers due to their social background, level of education, language skills and nationality. Practical measures are proposed to deal with these challenges, such as the creation of time-limited and easily accessible offers, the strengthening of digital forms of participation and the use of simple and understandable language.

D5 is an [ordinance on promoting extracurricular activities for children and young people](#). It focuses on the involvement of children and young people, particularly those from socially or culturally disadvantaged or disabled backgrounds, in extracurricular activities. It encourages their involvement in the whole process of initiating, planning and implementing activities. Financial support is provided for projects that serve as models or encourage participation in extracurricular activities in general, as well as for projects that promote political participation at federal level.

Summary

Two of the five documents focusing on participation deal with the topic of inclusion, emphasising the role played by participation for the social inclusion of young people. These documents also recognise that young people do not form a homogeneous whole. One document emphasises the importance of citizenship education also for young people who do not have Swiss citizenship and in particular for those who, due to their family background, have fewer opportunities to engage in politics. The other document emphasises the need to encourage the integration and political participation of children and young people with disabilities or from disadvantaged backgrounds by involving them in the planning and execution of such extracurricular activities. All five documents aim to increase opportunities for young people to participate. However, only two focus exclusively on young people, while the others mention children and young people at the same time. Four of these documents consider young people as a diverse group who face different challenges due to reasons such as socio-economic status, education, language and disability. This diversity is taken into account through the identification of specific needs, although the depth of the analysis and the practical measures proposed to address them differ considerably between the various documents.

Analysis: Local level, canton of Geneva

Policy Area	Health
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D1. *Projet de loi sur l'égalité et la lutte contre les violences et les discriminations liées au genre (LELVDG) (A 2 90)*

The document discusses the proposed law (PL12843) on equality and fighting violence and discrimination based on gender. The law aims to promote gender equality and address violence and discrimination related to sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression and intersex.

The proposed law project encompasses various key points, ranging from promoting equality (Article 1) to its context of implementation, which will apply to public institutions, private entities and the State to the private sector (Articles 18 to 23) to the implementation measures (Articles 24 to 27). The proposed law project explicitly addresses violence, discrimination, and health challenges faced by young people, in particular young women and young LGBTI individuals. Going into details, it addresses to combat cyber-harassment among young people, especially those aged 18 and 24 years old. Secondly, it points out challenges in accessing support within the familial context, emphasizing the critical role of family plays in young people's life. It is pointed out that LGBTI individuals often experience social isolation and can receive less familial support as their peers, which exacerbates their risk of social and health problems. Finally, the proposed law project draws attention to the high suicide rates among young people, especially young LGBTI, which have higher risk than those of their heterosexual peers.

The *Projet de loi sur l'égalité et la lutte contre les violences et les discriminations liées au genre (LELVDG) (A 2 90)* refers to young people in general, young people aged 18 and 24 years old, young women and young

LGBTI. It indeed addresses various intersections, detailing how it would benefit to citizens, young citizens and citizens facing multiple intersections such as gender, sexual orientation family support and indirectly socioeconomic status.

The score are as follows: social inclusion is acknowledged and the project of law was adopted the 23 March of 2023 and entry in force the 1st July 2023, therefore the direction is 1. While the opportunity for participation is addressed indirectly, resulting in a score of 0.

D2. Rapport du Conseil d'Etat au Grand Conseil sur la pétition en faveur de Laetitia, jeune femme genevoise en situation de handicap

The report issued by the Council of State of Geneva and presented to the Grand Council outlined a case of a young women from Geneva with disabilities. In the specific, the young women, Laetitia, has been staying at the Clair Bois institution for people with disabilities since childhood. However, after her family moved to France for better living conditions, Laetitia lost her Swiss disability insurance benefits, impacting her ability to continue living at Clair Bois. A petition with over 2'200 signatures was launched to support her in continuing to stay at the institution, arguing that it would be unfair to force her to leave, given her strong ties to the place and the territory. The debate focused on whether her residence was in Switzerland or France. Ultimately, the Swiss Federal Administrative Court ruled out that Laetitia should be considered as a resident of Geneva, which allows her to access the benefits needed it to remain at Clear Bois. The report emphasized the human and legal complexities of Laetitia's situation, pointed out the need for her to stay in a known supportive context where has had strong ties and personal connections.

The score are as it follows: the presence of inclusion in direction 1, but show a lack of opportunities for participation. The report outlines Laetitia's situation, highlighting her parents' need to move to France due to the housing shortage in Geneva. It also details the transition from childhood to adulthood, emphasizing the changes in social benefits (AI) as she turned 18, which are different from those available to minors. The report delves into the complexities of her disabilities, her Swiss origins, and the challenges her parents faced regarding housing, driven by their commitment to her well-being.

D3. Réponse du Conseil d'Etat à la question écrite urgente de M. Simon Brandt : Communication inhumaine du DIP après le suicide d'un jeune requérant d'asile

The analysed document is a response from the Council of State to an urgent written question by Simon Brandt concerning the communication by the Département de l'instruction public (DIP) after the suicide of a young asylum seeker. The answer addresses the concerns about the perceived inhumanity of the communication made by the DIP and clarifies the procedural missteps. In the specific, the communication of the death of a young 18 years old asylum seeker was perceived as insensitive and, the announcement was signed by the State Councilor (XX) without her prior approval. Therefore, the DIP's response included psychological support for affected students, organized by the Office Médico-Pédagogique's emergency unit. Moreover, the Council of State pointed out that there were measures taken to support the students and staff affected by the incident, including personal meetings with psychologists and social workers.

The document highlights the insensitivity of the communication by the DIP regarding the death of a young asylum seeker and seeks clarifications on why this happened. It emphasizes the impact on students, social workers, and the wider community. Additionally, it discusses the tragic situation of the young asylum seeker's death and the consequences of how the health communication was handled, particularly its effect on students. The response reflects an intention to include and address this issue (scoring a 1 for inclusion) but scores 0 for the opportunity to participate, indicating that participation or involvement from those affected was lacking or not adequately addressed

D4. Rapport de la commission des affaires sociales chargée d'étudier : a) M 2852-B Proposition de motion de Thomas Bläsi pour un rattachement de l'Unité mobile d'urgences sociales (UMUS) cohérent avec ses tâches

The document is a report on the motions M 2852-B and M 2949-A from the Grand Conseil of the Republic and Canton of Geneva, dated February 12, 2024. As there are two motions, there will be the focus on M 2949-A Motion, which proposes updates to the Mobile Unit for Social Emergencies (UMUS). It highlights the need for an in-depth review of UMUS's mission, organizational structure, and operational hours to adapt to the increasing demands and diverse interventions it handles. It also calls for potential legislative support to enhance and strengthen UMUS. The motion M 2949-A, titled "*Pour une unité mobile d'urgences sociales (UMUS) actualisée,*" was proposed by several deputies, including Patricia Bidaux and Léna Strasser, among others. The primary aim of the motion is to modernize and update the Mobile Unit for Social Emergencies (UMUS) to better meet the current needs of the Geneva population. UMUS operates during nights, weekends, and holidays, providing immediate social support in emergencies, such as for individuals facing homelessness, domestic violence, and psychosocial crises. The unit's workload and responsibilities have significantly increased over the years, with interventions rising from 605 in 2004 to around 2,500 annually. This rise is largely due to growing social issues like homelessness and increased demand for urgent social assistance.

The document highlights that UMUS intervenes in emergencies involving young people, specifically mentioning minors, including unaccompanied minors and those experiencing psychosocial distress or homelessness. The motion is adopted therefore, the score are as it follows: 1 for inclusion however there is 0 for participation.

D5. Proposition de motion. Protéger nos enfants des atteintes au développement de leur identité

The document is a motion titled "Protéger nos enfants des atteintes au développement de leur identité" submitted to the Grand Conseil of the Republic and Canton of Geneva by Michael Andersen, Stéphane Florey, Guy Mettan, Daniel Noël, Christo Ivanov, Virna Conti, Florian Dugerdil, and Patrick Lussi on September 26, 2023. The motion addresses concerns about "Drag Queen Story Hours" (DQSH), events where drag queens read stories to young children, promoting themes of gender diversity and non-binary identities. The signatories argue that these events can confuse children regarding traditional gender roles, promote non-binary sexualities, and negatively impact their identity development. The motion expresses concerns about the influence of such events on children's understanding of gender and the increase in diagnoses of gender dysphoria. Therefore, the motion requests that the Conseil d'État prohibit minors under 16 from attending such events, whether public or private, and exclude the promotion or participation of these events in schools or extracurricular activities, moreover it also calls for the withdrawal of any state funding or support for these activities.

The motion addresses young people and children in general, specifically mentioning those up to 16 years old. The scores are as follows: there is the presence of including young children and young people until the age of 16 years old, however as the motion been referred to the Commission on Education and Culture, it effectively maintains the status quo. Consequently, the opportunity dimension is scored as 0.

D6. Rapport du Conseil d'Etat au Grand Conseil sur la motion de Mmes Marie-Françoise de Tassigny, Fabienne Bugnon, Marie-Thérèse Engelberts, Janine Hagmann, Jeannine de Haller et Alexandra Gobet concernant l'intégration de la profession d'éducatrices et d'éducateurs du jeune enfant dans la future HES santé sociale (dated 1998)

The document is a report from the Conseil d'État to the Grand Conseil on a motion regarding the integration of early childhood educators into the future Health and Social Sciences University of Applied Sciences (HES) in Geneva. In the specific, the motion called for the inclusion of early childhood educators in the future HES health and social fields due to the growing complexity of their profession. Moreover, it discusses the division of responsibilities between federal and cantonal authorities concerning professional education and the criteria for recognition as a HES program. The Conseil d'État outlines the decisions made by various intercantonal bodies, which determined that the early childhood education field would not be included as a HES program but would remain a tertiary-level training not meeting HES requirements.

Policy Area	Participation

D1. Règlement d'application de la loi sur l'enfance et la jeunesse (REJ)

The Règlement d'application de la loi sur l'enfance et la jeunesse, establish a Youth Council which is composed to ensure a balanced representation of young people considering ages (14 up to 21 years old), sexes, professional and educational backgrounds, geographical distribution and socio-economic status. The scope of the Youth council is to advise on laws and parliamentary matters concerning young people, proposing actions to authorities and promoting youth participation. The council meets at least three times a year, with a decision made by majority vote and is supported by a secretariat that facilities its works. The score are as follows: 1 for inclusion as the law recognize the effort to provide young people with accessibility and considering representation through some intersections; 1 for opportunities to participate as it highlights the commitment to expanding opportunities to participate underling the willingness to expand participation opportunities through the Youth Council.

The Règlement d'application de la loi highlights various intersections concerning young people and children but does not elaborate on the specific types of intersections. Moreover, it does not specifically address gender rather uses the term "sex".

D2. Proposition de motion - Favoriser l'esprit critique du jeune public : un accès pour les jeunes aux médias romands

The motion from the Grand Council points out the growing issue of misinformation, especially among young people how more often rely on social media. The motion highlights the need for a reliable information which is essential for democratic debate. Therefore, policymakers who propose this motion call on the State

Council to ensure that all secondary II students have a free access to digital version of regional media through their school accounts helping them to develop critical skills by comparing traditional online media as *Le Courrier, Heidi.news, Le Temps et la Tribune de Genève* with online information which sometimes might be unverified. The proposal suggests providing secondary II students with digital subscription accessible through their school accounts (Eduge.ch) and anywhere to ensure they have access through their education. This access could prepare young people to navigate information landscape critically.

The Proposition *Favoriser l'esprit critique du jeune public: un accès pour les jeunes aux médias romands* refers to young people in general and to young students from the Secondary II. The score are as follows: 1 for inclusion as it aims to include young people in the public debate by providing free digital subscriptions to young students and 0 for opportunities to participation as it does not directly expand participation opportunities.

D3. Rapport de la commission des droits politiques et du règlement du Grand Conseil chargée d'étudier. La voix des jeunes compte : pour un droit de vote à 16 ans dans le canton de Genève

The Political Rights and Regulations Commission of the Grand Council reviewed bills 12489 and 12490 over 16 sessions between 2019 and 2022. After examining the bills and having several auditions with different groups, as some young students of Secondary School (II), the Young Geneva Parliament (Parlement des Jeunes Genevois), a dean of a Secondary School, a professor of the University of Geneva, the majority of the Commission on Political Rights and Regulations recommended that the Grand Council reject both proposals. These bills aimed to lower the voting age to 16, which would require amendments to the Geneva Constitution and the law on the exercise of political rights (LEDP). The Grand Council had also rejected such amendments in 2014. A key concern was the appropriateness of establishing a civic majority at 16 that does not correspond to civic responsibilities such as legal accountability, political eligibility and tax obligations which are at 18 years old. While supporters argue that voting at 16 prepares young people for political participation, others pointed out that *voting is not just a learning experience, but an act with concrete societal consequences*³⁶.

The score are as follows: both dimensions are indeed present in the law aiming at including young Swiss citizens of 16 years living in Geneva and abroad, and, broadening political participation. However, since the bills are not adopted, in both dimensions it maintains the status quo.

The *Rapport de la commission des droits politiques et du règlement du Grand Conseil chargée d'étudier. La voix des jeunes compte : pour un droit de vote à 16 ans dans le canton de Genève* mentions primarily young Swiss citizens aged 16 and 18 living in Geneva and abroad. during the three-year consultation, young students from Secondary School and members of the Young Geneva Parliament were also included. This inclusion was not explicitly stated in the bill, which focused specifically on young Swiss citizens aged 16. While some characteristics, such as family background and school situation, were noted, other intersections were not mentioned in the debate.

D4. Rapport de la commission des droits politiques et du règlement du Grand Conseil chargée d'étudier le projet de loi Projet de loi modifiant la loi sur la nationalité genevoise (LNat) (A 4 05) (Renforcement du degré d'intégration dans le respect du droit fédéral)

³⁶ Direct translation from the document at page 4 « Or, voter n'est pas un stage d'apprentissage. C'est un acte qui implique une conséquence très concrète pour toute la société ».

The document is a report on the proposed law (PL 12747-A), prepared by the Political Rights and Rules Commission of the Grand Council which aims to extend the restriction on receiving social assistance from three to ten years before applying for Swiss naturalization in Geneva. This amendment mirrors a similar legislation implemented in the canton of Argovie. In the specific, the one of the proposed amendment to the naturalization requirements (Article 12, letter g) would like to introduce a requirement that applicants must not have received financial assistance from social services within the last ten years before applying for Swiss' citizenship. Moreover, a second amendment (Article 35A) would allow individuals willing to apply Swiss' citizenship to voluntarily repay any financial assistance received, therefore enabling to meet the new naturalization criteria. During the discussion of the proposed new amendment, MPs (1 EAG, 3 S, 2 Ve, 2 PDC, 4 PLR, 2 MCG³⁷) raised the concern that young people, especially those still in school or starting working might receive minimal social assistance (for example health insurance subsidies). This could create additional challenges for them in repaying such assistances, potentially leading to a discrimination based on income levels. Most of the commission members voted against proceeding with the amendment.

Although in the new proposed amendment does not explicitly refer to young people, it would have impact them. More importantly, during the report and discussions with MPs, young migrants without Swiss nationality and from lower socio-economic backgrounds were specifically addressed and discussed. The scoring is as follows: both dimensions are present in the amendment. The opportunity for participate would have been evaluated at -1, however, since the amendment was not accepted the status quo prevails.

D5. Proposition de résolution pour une protection renforcée des réfugiés mineurs non accompagnés jusqu'à l'âge de 25 ans (Résolution du Grand Conseil genevois à l'Assemblée fédérale exerçant le droit d'initiative cantonale)

The proposition of the resolution highlights the need to extend the protection for unaccompanied minor refugees (RMNA) until the age of 25 years old – currently ending at the age of 18 years old. In the specific, the proposition urges the Federal Assembly to extend the protection, underlying the vulnerability and challenges RMNA face after turning 18. The proposal comes in reaction of a tragic event where a young Afghan refugee committed suicide after being ordered to return to Greece after turning 18. As a matter of face, the current law offer protection to RMNA during their stay in Switzerland which ends when they turn 18, leaving them vulnerable without the necessary support for their education or the integration. Back in 2019, the Geneva Grand Council adopted a motion requesting extended support for young adult refugees until 25 years old, a motion supported by the Conférence des directrices et directeurs cantonaux des affaires sociales (CDAS). The CDSA recommended that cantons “should establish support service as needed, allowing for socio-pedagogical monitoring of RMNA who have reached adulthood, until the completion of their first training and acquisition of the skills necessary for independent living”. According to CDSA, the “ services provided by child and youth policies should benefit children and young people up to 25 years old”. The Cour des comptes, in its audit on RMNA (136-2018), also empasized that ensuring their integration under the best possible conditions is essential.

Resolution 1010 was put to a vote and adopted by the Grand Council with 57 votes in favor, 25 against, and 8 abstentions (nominal vote), and was then forwarded to the Federal Assembly, where it was not adopted.

The proposed resolution refers to RMNA, in the specific it underlines the suicide of an 18 years old Afghan refugees who committed suicide, and stresses the need to extend social rights to RMNA up to 25 years old.

³⁷ Political parties who were opposed to this new amendment and rose concerns

Moreover, it emphasizes the need of supporting RMNA in various aspect, including integration, education and overall well-being. The score are as follows: both factors are present but although it was accepted at the cantonal level but not at the Federal level, the status quo remains.

Summary

Across the five documents, young people are framed as a diverse group, varying by age (14 up to 21 years old), sexes, professional and educational backgrounds (D1), their status as students (D2), their age, nationality and residency status in Geneva (D3), their citizenship status, socioeconomic background, and receipt of social benefits (D4) or unaccompanied minor refugees (D5). While the dimension of inclusion is present in all documents, only two (D1 and D2) where accepted, with D1 the only one that broadened opportunities. It is important to note that most documents are proposals for laws or project or even amendment, therefore the status quo predominately remains in place.

CONCLUSION

It is firstly important to mention that our national report has indeed limitations. In the specific, the small sample size limits indeed our analysis. Our analysis does not provide an in-depth view of the actual situation of young people in Switzerland. The limited number of documents reviewed within this specific timeframe further limits our findings. Moreover, as our analysis focuses on a specific period time, different results could potentially change if a wider timeframe were considered. Secondly, it was challenging to achieve a clear and consistent sampling strategy. Although we did indeed identify five polices areas, thematic variations, in the policy area itself there are broader texts and policies. As we aimed to capture policy narrative, this led us to analyse a diverse range of documents, from legal frameworks to strategic reports, adding complexity to our analysis. Thirdly, as the nature of the documents varies, each with its own legal framework, making comparisons challenging due to differing levels of competencies. For example, at the Federal level, more general guidelines are established, which cantons then need to implement as it its in their authority. Therefore, broader and more vague framings at the national level are more often the case, reflecting the federal system's characteristic delegation of interpretation and implementation to cantonal authorities, allowing them autonomy and flexibility in interpreting and adapting policies. Overall, our findings should be understood within these limitations.

The analysis of the sample documents shows that at the national level young people are often grouped together with children, revealing a lack of attention to their specific needs. This inattention is particularly evident in the areas of employment and housing policy, where it was extremely difficult to find recent documents concerning young people. Here, we had to rely on sources that mentioned young people, rather than identifying specific documents dedicated to them, as was more possible in other areas.

Among the 25 Swiss national documents analysed, only 11 propose recommendations or measures to improve the integration of young people and/or to broaden their opportunities for participation. Of these, only 6 documents discuss youth inclusion while only 5 provide practical solutions. The documents addressing inclusion are distributed across several policy areas, with two documents per area for the policy areas of participation and health, and only one document for the policy areas of education, employment and housing. In contrast, the only document on housing that discusses inclusion does not offer any practical recommendations.

A total of 7 documents addresses the enhancement of youth participation, with 5 of these documents falling under the participation policy area and the remaining 2 under education. Instead, documents in the areas of employment, health, and housing do not address youth participation. Moreover, except for one document, there is no suggestion that young people should be directly involved in policy-making processes. The primary measures proposed focus on encouraging associative life, civic education, and projects aimed at motivating young people to engage in political life.

Regarding intersectionality, 9 out of the 25 documents acknowledge one or more diversity factors among young people. The participation policy area has the most documents recognizing diversity, with 4 documents, followed by health and housing policies, each with 2 documents, and education with 1 document. The documents in employment policy area do not address diversity at all and treats youth as a homogeneous group.

The documents related to the policy area of participation are those that most recognise diversity among young people, for example mentioning young people from disadvantaged backgrounds or individuals with disabilities. However, although they mention various categories of disadvantaged young people, when it comes to concrete measures, they end up grouping them together without offering practical solutions tailored to each group.

The health document discusses the impact of discrimination on the mental health of young people, naming various forms of discrimination such as racism, sexism and homophobia. However, it does not propose targeted actions, instead simply calling for general prevention against discrimination.

The remaining documents typically address only a single part of youth diversity, such as 'young women' in the education document and one housing document, 'young people in training' in another housing document, and 'young people with disabilities' in a health document. Only in the cases of education (young women) and health (young people with disabilities) are targeted solutions proposed.

Interestingly, only one document explicitly mentions intersectionality, which is a document about education. However, it does so in a broad discussion about equal opportunities in universities, not focusing on young people. Moreover, none of the documents analysed provide an example of 'thick intersectionality', where multiple intersecting identities are considered in a detailed manner. It is however important to consider the differences in documents at the local level. As a matter of fact, analysed documents in the local level, young people and children are framed considering more intersections and contextual differences. In the specific, some motions or report children and young people are depicted as facing specific challenges such as discrimination, lack of familial support, cyber-harassment, social isolation and the need for emergency services. Moreover, local document break downs various aspects of young people's lives, including their rights, support of the system, mental health and protection. The intersections of gender, disability, refugee status, residency status, and citizenship status underscore a more nuanced and multifaceted ways young people are depicted at the cantonal level in Geneva. This small sample of documents reveals how these intersecting factors are documented and considered by (some) policymakers. For example, in which regard to gender influences experiences of violence and discrimination, as seen in the LELVDG law addressing issues faced by young women and LGBTI youth. Disability, as in Laetitia's case, shows the complexities of transitioning from childhood to adulthood in a supportive environment. Refugee and residency status further complicate access to services and rights.

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On Housing

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- 2) [Drilling, M., Küng, M., Mühlethaler, E., & Dittmann, J. \(2022\). Homelessness in Switzerland. Understandings, policies and strategies of the cantons and communes.](#)
- 3) [Offres d'aide au logement pour les ménages vulnérables: Guide pour les cantons, les villes et les communes \(29.01.2018\)](#)
- 4) [Le point sur le logement d'utilité publique. Une comparaison avec le locatif et la propriété \(15.11.2017\)](#)
- 5) [Dialogue en matière de politique du logement entre la Confédération, les cantons et les villes - Rapport du groupe de travail \(12.12.2016\)](#)

On Health

- 1) [Santé mentale des enfants et des jeunes: renforcer la prévention et garantir l'accès aux soins \(June, 2024\)](#)
- 2) [Protéger intégralement les enfants et les jeunes de la publicité pour le tabac \(February, 2024\)](#)
- 3) [Message concernant la modification de la loi fédérale sur l'imposition du tabac \(Imposition des cigarettes électroniques\) \(16.11.2022\)](#)
- 4) [Ordonnance du 31 mars 2021 sur les essais pilotes au sens de la loi sur les stupéfiants \(OEPStup\) \(16.04.2021\)](#)
- 5) [Ordonnance du DDPS sur les programmes et les projets d'encouragement du sport \(OPESp\) \(12.05.2020\)](#)

On Education

- 1) [Message relatif à l'encouragement de la formation, de la recherche et de l'innovation pendant les années 2025 à 2028 \(8.03.2024\)](#)

- 2) [Ordonnance du 23 février 2022 sur la coopération et la mobilité internationales en matière de formation \(OCMIF\) \(11.03.2022\)](#)
- 3) [Ordonnance du DFI instituant un régime d'encouragement relatif au programme «Jeunesse et Musique» \(21.12.2020\)](#)
- 4) [Arrêté fédéral ouvrant des crédits pour la coopération internationale en matière d'éducation et pour les bourses allouées à des étudiants et artistes étrangers pendant les années 2021 à 2024 \(05.05.2020\)](#)
- 5) [Des bases solides pour une éducation civique efficace - 3 minutes pour les jeunes : Prise de position du Commission fédérale pour l'enfance et la jeunesse \(CFEJ\) \(March, 2017\)](#)

On Employment

- 1) [Ordonnance 5 relative à la loi sur le travail \(Ordonnance sur la protection des jeunes travailleurs, OLT 5\) \(01.04.2024\)](#)
- 2) [Message relatif à l'approbation de l'accord entre la Suisse et le Royaume-Uni en matière de reconnaissance des qualifications professionnelles et à sa mise en œuvre \(modification de la loi sur les avocats\) ainsi qu'à la délégation au Conseil fédéral de la compétence de conclure des traités internationaux en matière de reconnaissance des qualifications professionnelles dans le champ d'application de la loi sur les professions médicales, de la loi fédérale sur les professions de la santé, de la loi sur les avocats et de la loi sur les professions de la psychologie \(01.03.2024\)](#)
- 3) [Message concernant une modification de la loi sur l'assurance-chômage \(système d'indemnisation des caisses de chômage\) \(20.12.2023\)](#)
- 4) [Arrêté du Conseil fédéral étendant le champ d'application de la convention collective de travail dans la branche suisse de l'enveloppe des édifices. Erratum \(12.12.2023\)](#)
- 5) [Ordonnance du DFF concernant l'ordonnance sur le personnel de la Confédération \(O-OPers\) \(08.12.2023\)](#)

On Participation

- 1) [Éducation à la citoyenneté en Suisse, Position de la CFEJ \(August, 2023\)](#)
- 2) [Formes de participation politique et motivation des jeunes à s'engager : recommandations de la CFEJ \(Mai, 2023\)](#)
- 3) [Donner davantage de poids aux recommandations des enfants et des jeunes - 3 minutes pour les jeunes : Prise de position du Commission fédérale pour l'enfance et la jeunesse \(CFEJ\) \(June, 2022\)](#)
- 4) [Formes de participation politique et motivation des jeunes à s'engager \(2022\)](#)
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NATIONAL REPORT UNITED KINGDOM (UNIMAN)

Introduction

This report starts by outlining the key challenges faced by young people in the UK currently (2024) as documented in the most recent relevant academic and grey literature. This literature suggests that three main issues have negatively influenced the lives of young people: the austerity measures imposed by the previous Conservative Government; the long-term impact of Covid-19; and the ongoing cost-of-living crisis. The impact of these three factors is outlined in more detail below in relation to each of the five policy areas focused upon in this report: education; employment, health; housing; and participation.

Education

Social class remains a strong predictor of educational attainment in the UK where there is a widening attainment gap between school students from more well-off and those from more economically deprived backgrounds. For example, 24% of all school students receive benefit related free school meals (FSM) (ADCS, 2024)³⁸ and lag behind students who are not eligible for FSM. White British FSM boys and Black Caribbean FSM boys achieve the lowest attainment scores at GCSE and A-level. The cost of buying uniforms, equipment and affording school trips are increasingly becoming barriers to inclusion for many young people (ADCS, 2024: 8). The rate of children being suspended and persistently absent from school has been increasing. There were 511,270 suspensions for the autumn and spring terms in 2022/23 and the Department for Education has highlighted that a fifth of all pupils have been persistently absent in 2023/24.³⁹ Students with additional learning needs, or who are from global majority backgrounds continue to be much more likely to be excluded and suspended compared to other groups (ADCS, 2024). Covid-19 has further exacerbated educational inequalities due to variable access to technology during remote learning leading to general disengagement from education. This has led students to be put under pressure in order to 'catch up' when restrictions were lifted (Barnardo's, 2022: 21).

Similar issues are witnessed in higher education whereby young people from working-class backgrounds account for just 1 in 20 enrolments into the elite Russell Group of universities (Jerrim, 2013). The percentage of students on FSM who go on to attend elite universities is just 0.9% and private school students are 55 times more likely than FSM students to gain a place at Oxford or Cambridge (Reay, 2017). Tuition fees – which are in excess of £9,000 p.a. – place an additional burden on students. Working-class young people who do go to university are less likely to graduate and less likely to achieve the highest degree classes (Crawford et al., 2016). As Ingram and Allen (2019) argue, class inequalities intersect with inequalities of gender, ethnicity and disability in British Higher Education as those who are white, male, middle-class and who graduated from elite universities, tend to have the highest employment rates and earnings after graduation.

38 Being eligible for free school meals is an indicator of lower socio-economic background.

39 See <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/pupil-attendance-in-schools>

Employment

It is estimated that 4.2 million children are living in poverty with 48% being from global majority groups and 70% living in a household where at least one adult works (ADCS, 2024). In comparison to 2020/21, it is estimated that 900,000 more people are living in absolute poverty, with 400,000 of them being children.⁴⁰ Against the backdrop of welfare reform (i.e., cuts to welfare) and the rising cost of living, more families and young people will experience financial difficulties alongside a growing number of young people who will grow up in poverty and rely heavily on food banks (Barnardo's, 2022: 14).

According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS), the unemployment rate for young people aged between 16 to 24 in the February-April 2024 quarter was 13.6%, which means that young people are three times more likely to be unemployed than any other age group in the UK.⁴¹ There is also a gender disparity whereby the rate of unemployed young men is higher than unemployed young women.⁴² The ONS also shows a worrying estimate of the number of young people not in education, employment or training (NEET) to be at 11.6%.⁴³ This is corroborated by The Prince's Trust survey which reports that 11% of its respondents were not currently in education, employment or training, and that 53% have been unemployed for more than six months (The Prince's Trust, 2024: 5). As to be expected, young people's financial and employment situation was worsened by Covid-19 where they faced scarce employment opportunities and felt hopeless about their prospects of achieving financial stability (Barnardo's, 2022: 15). The situation has arguably not improved since as, even when they find work, young people tend to be paid less than previous generations, and increasingly find themselves in insecure jobs such as being on zero-hour contracts and working in the gig economy.⁴⁴

The Prince's Trust's survey (2024: 8) highlights the impact the cost-of-living crisis is having on young people. For example, it reports that half of young people (49%) state that the cost-of-living crisis has had a worse impact on their life than Covid-19. Over half of young people (53%) worry that the cost-of-living implies they will never be financially secure, and a third of young people (34%) report that worrying about money has made their mental health worse (ibid.).

Health

Young people in the UK are facing a mental health crisis evident in rising cases of eating disorders, obsessive-compulsive disorder and suicidality (Barnardo's, 2022: 19). There are approximately 1.4 million children (aged 8-17 years) with a mental health condition in England alone, and 1 in 4 older young people had a mental health condition in 2022 - up from 1 in 10 in 2017 (ADCS, 2024). According to a survey conducted by The Prince's Trust (2024: 8), 40% of young people have experienced a mental health problem and one in five say their mental health has got worse in the

⁴⁰ <https://www.jrf.org.uk/news/annual-poverty-figures-show-government-failed-to-protect-most-vulnerable-from-cost-of-living>

⁴¹ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/bulletins/uklabourmarket/la-test>

⁴² <https://www.statista.com/statistics/280329/youth-unemployment-rate-by-gender-uk/#:%7E:text=Youth%20unemployment%20rate%20in%20the%20UK%201992%2D2023%2C%20by%20gender&text=As%20of%20the%20second%20quarter,and%209.8%20percent%20for%20women>

⁴³ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peoplenotinwork/unemployment/bulletins/youngpeoplenotineducationemploymentortrainingneet/august2023>

⁴⁴ [https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/articles/theoccupationsmostdependentonolderandyoungerworkers/2023-05-31#:~:text=Retail%20was%20the%20largest%20type,working%20in%20retail%20\(13%25\)](https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/articles/theoccupationsmostdependentonolderandyoungerworkers/2023-05-31#:~:text=Retail%20was%20the%20largest%20type,working%20in%20retail%20(13%25))

past year. One in five young people in the UK have missed school or work in the past year due to a mental health issue. Moreover, a mental health issue is reported to have stopped young people from applying for a job (18%), attending an interview during the last 12 months (12%), or asking for help with their CV or cover letter (10%), and one in ten young people from poorer backgrounds (10%) reported that they left work in the past 12 months due to a mental health issue. The Prince's Trust also highlights that there is a gender disparity as 28% of young women said they have missed school or work in the last 12 months due to their mental health, compared to 14% of young men.

Due to cuts and the underfunding of youth services, the limited funding available tends to be directed towards young people who are at immediate risk of harm as opposed to funding early intervention measures which may have helped prevent this. Additionally, funding has not increased in line with demand especially in the mental health care system, which means that services are now ill-equipped to tackle rising referrals and therefore young people face increasingly long waiting times to receive the support they need (Barnardo's, 2022: 13-14). In terms of intersections, mental health issues tend to affect marginalised young people (for example, due to gender, sexuality, race/ethnicity, disability) more than other youth groups (ibid., 24-25).

Housing

The UK has been witnessing a significant increase in house prices in recent decades, particularly in large cities where young people predominantly reside for education and employment purposes.⁴⁵ A large increase in mortgage rates alongside stagnating wages and low-paid insecure jobs (see *Employment*) have made it difficult for many young people to step onto the property ladder. Moreover, there is insufficient provision of social housing which leaves young people, especially care leavers,⁴⁶ without stable, suitable, and secure accommodation putting them at risk of becoming homeless (Barnardo's, 2022: 16). According to the youth homelessness charity Centrepoin (2023), almost 136,000 young people have asked for help from their local council in 2022/2023 because they were homeless or at risk of homelessness. In other words, 1 in 52 young people are estimated to be homeless or at risk of homelessness in the UK.

Participation

Not only have the cuts to council-run youth services led to increased referrals to specialist support services (see *Health*), but the widespread closure of youth clubs and community centres have reduced the opportunities available for young people to reach out for information and advice (Barnardo's, 2022: 13-14). The loss of hundreds of youth centres, children's centres, and other community-based services such as libraries, leisure and cultural centres have negatively impacted young people's access to opportunity; this has hit those who cannot afford to travel or who live far away hardest (ADCS, 2024: 8). A conspicuous example of the severity of such cuts is arguably the closure of the British Youth Council (BYC) in March 2024. The BYC was a UK charity founded in 1948 that worked to empower young people and promote their interests. It was run by young people to represent the views of young people to government and decision makers, and importantly promote increased participation of young people in society and public life. The UK Youth

⁴⁵ For the most recent UK House Price Index (as of December 2023) see: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/inflationandpriceindices/bulletins/housepriceindex/december2023>

⁴⁶ A Care Leaver is any adult who spent time in care as a child (under the age of 18).

Parliament, which the BYC was contracted to deliver, has been transferred to the National Youth Agency for 2024/25, but its long-term future remains uncertain.⁴⁷

The recent General Elections (4 July 2024) witnessed a low turnout by share of the population with only around 60% of British adults casting their ballots; down from 67% in the 2019 General Elections.⁴⁸ According to a report published by the Institute for Public Policy Research (IPPR), there was a much higher turnout in constituencies where the larger share of the population were older, wealthy homeowners, and white compared to constituencies where a smaller share of people came from those demographics (Patel and Valgardsson, 2024). This implies that voter turnout for young people was low which is in line with previous elections⁴⁹ and relates to young people's concerns that their opinions are rarely heard or taken into consideration, and that party manifestos are not geared towards young people.

Policy document sampling and selection

In the UK, there is no ministry or government department directly responsible for youth policy. Youth policy is devolved to national administrations of England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. In England, this responsibility lies with the Civil Society and Youth Directorate within the Department for Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS).

National level document sample

National level policy documents for each of the five policy areas – education, employment, health, housing and participation - were selected by, first, searching the <https://www.gov.uk> website for the responsible ministry or government department (e.g. Department of Health and Social Care or Department for Education) using 'youth' and 'young people' related search terms. Where there was no clearly discernible ministry or department responsible for the policy area (e.g. 'participation'), the government website was searched by 'policy papers and consultation' across all ministries and departments. These searches were cross-checked by searching the DCMS website for youth-related policy. This initial search was supplemented by searching the House of Commons Library (<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/>) and House of Lords Library (<https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/>) for summaries of policies (in the form, for example, of Research Briefings prepared for forthcoming debates). These sites were searched by both policy area and by 'youth' related search terms. The All-Party Parliamentary Group on youth affairs (<https://youthappg.org.uk/>) as well as other relevant APPG sites were also searched for relevant documents. In all cases, documents were initially searched for the period 15.06.2024 to 15.06.2023 and then backwards from these dates until sufficient documents were identified.

Table 1 provides a list of documents selected for analysis alongside key contextual information that is important for understanding the findings of the analysis. It should be noted that the document Promoting Children and Young People's Mental Health and Wellbeing: A Whole School or College Approach (Education, Document 2) cuts across both education and health policy areas. In order

47 <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/government-secures-future-of-uk-youth-parliament#:~:text=Since%202011%2C%20the%20Government%20has,to%20participate%20in%20the%20programme.>

48 See <https://www.economicsobservatory.com/what-do-we-know-about-voter-turnout-in-parliamentary-elections> and <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/live/2024/jul/06/keir-starmer-labour-cabinet-meeting-uk-general-election-conservatives-leadership>

49 <https://post.parliament.uk/election-turnout-why-do-some-people-not-vote/>

not to duplicate documents in the analysis, this document was included in the education policy analysis only.

Table 1 Overview of selected national level documents

	Title of document	Date (publication/ update)	Contextual information
Education			
1	The Power of Music to Change Lives: A National Plan for Music Education	June 2022, updated May 2024	Emphasises the importance of making music education more inclusive, paying particular attention to Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND) students but also acknowledging the needs of students from lower socio-economic backgrounds (hence two intersections). The document does not meet the criteria for participation, however.
2	Promoting Children and Young People's Mental Health and Wellbeing: A Whole School or College Approach	September 2021, updated May 2024	Does not directly deal with inclusion/exclusion but acknowledges the diversity of young people's experiences (e.g. in terms of ethnicity, sexual orientation). Sections on the importance of student voice in shaping mental health and wellbeing policy and support in schools and colleges indicate that young people are being offered opportunities for participation.
3	Participation of Young People in Education, Employment or Training	April 2024	Focuses on increasing the participation of young people in education, employment or training. The document consistently acknowledges the differing identities, backgrounds, and needs of young people in terms of their disabilities, sexual orientation, gender, being young parents, etc., and the barriers they might face in continuing their education, training or obtaining employment. Despite emphasising the diverse needs and experiences of young people, no reference is made to opportunities for their participation in shaping how these issues are addressed.
4	Enhancing Physical Education Provision and Improving Access to Sport and Physical Activity in School	March 2024	Outlines guidance for ensuring equal opportunities for all students to participate in a range of sports in schools and in extra-curricular settings. It promotes widening inclusion through challenging stereotypes and biases linked to gender, disabilities, and low socio-economic backgrounds in order to promote equality of access to sport. It emphasises the importance of student voice and participation in encouraging under-represented groups to participate and improve equality of access. It calls for students to be asked what they want and be directly involved in shaping the physical education curriculum in schools.
5	Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND) and Alternative Provision (AP) Improvement Plan	March 2023	Outlines the plan for creating a new more inclusive national SEND system to enable students and young people to fulfil their academic and professional potential. It specifically focuses on SEND students and does not refer to any other intersections (e.g., race, gender, etc.) and thus represents 'thin' intersectionality. It consistently underlines that this national system should be co-produced with families, children and young people in order to reflect their unique needs, personal circumstances and backgrounds.
Employment			
1	The National Minimum Wage Beyond 2024	March 2024	This document is published by the Low Pay Commission, which advises the government about the National Living and National Minimum Wage. It proposes lowering the age of eligibility for the National Living Wage to 18 (it is currently 21 and over) and reducing the gap between the National Minimum Wage rates of young people and adults. It contributes positively to inclusion as it encourages youth employment and fairer pay for those under 21. However, it approaches young people in a general sense and does not offer opportunities for participation.
2	The Impact of Place Based Approaches to	July 2023	This document is published by the All-Party Parliamentary Group for Youth Employment (APPGYE) and argues for a 'place-based' approach

	Tackling Youth Unemployment		to tackling youth unemployment, which recognises the distinct challenges, contexts and opportunities of different geographical locations. This would help address regional disparities and geographical inequality in the UK. It encourages inclusion through expanding opportunities for youth employment and training regardless of their place (e.g., urban, rural, coastal). It also acknowledges the 'thick' intersectionality of youth particularly those from economically disadvantaged backgrounds and living in under-resourced places. The importance of youth voice is emphasised, calling for young people to play an integral role in the design and delivery of any place-based approach to tackling unemployment.
3	The Impact of Mental Ill Health on Young People Accessing the Labour Market and Quality Work	January 2023	This document is published by the APPGYE and focuses on the impact of mental ill-health on young people's ability to access the labour market and obtain quality jobs. It proposes holistic support that is inclusive and tailored towards the different needs of young people belonging to different demographics and those with protected characteristics. The aim is to expand young people's inclusion by taking part in the labour market through providing the required mental health support. This attention to a tailored approach demonstrates recognition of the 'thick' intersectionality of youth. Youth voice is emphasised by arguing that future services, support and policy initiatives should include opportunities for youth to share their experiences, co-design mental health services, and review and feedback on the services they have received.
4	The Impact of Vocational Qualifications on Young People's Employment and Labour Market Outcomes	January 2022	This document critically responds to the government's proposals to streamline post-16 qualifications by removing funding for certain vocational and technical qualifications and replacing them with others. The document highlights how these proposed changes will disproportionately affect the most disadvantaged students given their overrepresentation among those studying for these qualifications. Although the document refers to both inclusion and exclusion, it does not refer to expanding inclusion, but rather to keeping things as they are or at least delaying the changes until more research has been conducted on their impact. The document's predominant focus is on young people with SEND and those from minoritised communities. There was no opportunity for young people's participation highlighted in the document. This document is written in response to Document 5.
5	Skills for Jobs Lifelong Learning for Opportunity and Growth	January 2021	This document is a White Paper in which the Government sets out its proposals for future legislation intended to reform the Further Education system by improving its delivery of technical skills, the quality of its qualifications, and the funding system. The document clearly calls for the expansion of young people's inclusion in the labour market through being equipped with the required technical skills and higher technical qualifications regardless of their background. While it pays particular attention to young people with SEND, it is considered to reflect a 'thin' intersection due to the focus on students within education. No opportunities for participation or youth voice are mentioned throughout the document.
Health			
1	Children and young people's mental health: policy and services (England)	January 2024	This document is a Research Briefing prepared by the House of Commons independent research team to support the work of MPs. It sets out the structure of children and young people's mental health services and recent policy from relevant government departments and NHS England (e.g. on suicide prevention, post-COVID-19 strategy, waiting time standards and quality of services). It contributes to expanding inclusion in that it indicates that mental health support teams embedded in schools and colleges will be rolled out to include between 20-25% of the country and that services will be extended from 0-18 to 0-25 years. However, it refers only to young people in general and does not refer to any opportunities for participation.

2	Youth Vaping in England	January 2024	This document is a Research Briefing prepared by the independent House of Commons research team. It sets out a government policy designed to restrict access and appeal of vapes to young people including the prohibition of sale of non-nicotine vapes to under-18s. Although the policy seeks to protect young people's health, it effectively excludes young people from access to products that they previously could access and that older people retain the right to access. For this reason, it is categorised as restricting inclusion. The document refers to young people (or, in this case, under-18s) in general and does not indicate any opportunities for participation in shaping policy.
3	Stopping the start: our new plan to create a smokefree generation	October 2023, updated November 2023	This document is a government Command Paper, i.e. is a major initiative presented by the government to parliament. It sets out the rationale for legislation that will prohibit the younger generation, defined as anyone born on or after 01.01.2009 (i.e. turning 14 in 2023) from ever being able to buy tobacco products. The proposed legislation is presented as a measure to protect people's health but in its action, it excludes young people from something older people will continue to have the right to do and for this reason, is categorised as restricting inclusion. Although a particular specification of 'anyone born on or after 01.01.2009' is made in this document, this is the specific category relating to this piece of legislation and thus is classified as referring to young people in general. The document does not indicate any opportunities for participation in shaping policy.
4	'You're Welcome' establishing youth-friendly health and care services	June 2023	This is a government guidance document setting out revised standards and associated quality criteria for youth-friendly health and care services. This guidance updates original standards published in 2007 and 2011 and has been revised and refreshed through engagement with young people. The document expands participation in that it focuses on the importance of putting young people's voices at the heart of services and sets out how young people were involved in designing and prioritising the revised guidance. While it is less explicit about the expansion of inclusion, it notes particular issues arising from exacerbated health inequalities for some groups of young people (e.g. ethnic minority groups, young carers, LGBT people, looked-after children or those with a learning disability) and argues that involving young people in revising standards is crucial to improve young people's confidence and trust to access support.
5	Mental Health Act Reform - Children and Young People	November 2022	This document is a UK Parliament POST (Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology) note, which is an impartial, peer-reviewed briefing on issues emerging and challenges they pose and solutions sought. It focuses on the government's draft Mental Health Bill, specifically its implications for children and young people. The document points to elements of the draft legislation that might extend certain protections to young people alongside others that fail to include those under 16 among those who will benefit from additional rights. For this reason, the document is evaluated as referring to inclusion/exclusion but neither expanding nor restricting inclusion. The document points to focus groups held with young people to provide their views on specific elements of the proposed legislation and what these views were. For this reason, it is judged to refer to opportunities for participation. However, since the outcome (what is finally in the legislation) is not indicated, it is evaluated as pointing to neither an expansion nor a restriction of participation. The document refers to young people in general, although implicitly may refer in particular to young people with mental health issues.
Housing			
1	Youth Homelessness	April 2024	This document is a Debate Pack document prepared by the independent House of Commons research team to support MPs ahead of a parliamentary debate on youth homelessness. It covers data on the issue as well as outlining current legislation and government policy. It sets out government policy intended to improve support for young people at risk of homelessness and help local authorities to tailor interventions to meet the needs of individuals in specific groups including young people. It

			mentions a number of specific categories of young people at risk and in so doing, shows awareness of the intersection of lived experience affecting young people's opportunities. The document also notes the continuation of funding for a charity to continue its youth voice programme ensuring young homeless people's voices are heard. This signals reference to opportunities for participation but since this is a continuation rather than a new initiative, it is judged to point to neither an expansion nor restriction of such opportunity. This opportunity is related to young homeless people, which indicates an intersection of youth and homelessness ('thin' intersection).
2	Housing needs of young people	March 2024	This is a UK Parliament House of Lords 'In Focus' article providing a summary of issues, government policy and potential challenges and solutions ahead of a scheduled House of Lords debate on the housing needs of young people. It discusses the exclusion of young people from home ownership due to rising prices and lack of affordable housing and indicates the closure of the government's help to buy ISA from 2019 as excluding young people further from opportunities to buy property. The document refers only to young people in general and does not refer to opportunities for participation.
3	Single Homelessness Accommodation Programme (SHAP): prospectus and guidance	Published December 2022, updated February 2024	This is a Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (DLUHC) guidance document setting out the SHAP programme objectives, scope, timeline, funding and local authority application process. The document includes young people aged 18-25 as one of two key target groups of the SHAP programme. It also refers to one intersection, namely risk of homelessness ('thin' intersection). The document does not refer to any opportunities for participation.
4	Homes for Ukraine: welcome guide for Ukrainian children under 18	Published August 2022, updated February 2024	This is a DLUHC guidance document for Ukrainian children under 18 moving from Ukraine to England under the Homes for Ukraine scheme. It constitutes an expansion of inclusion in that it indicates how young people from Ukraine can be sponsored for accommodation in homes of UK residents and provides detailed guidance on their rights once in the UK. It refers to one intersection, namely young people moving from Ukraine to England ('thin' intersection). The document does not refer to any opportunities for participation.
5	Housing Benefit Eligibility	Guidelines available as of 23.07.2024	These are government guidelines on eligibility for Housing Benefit (monetary support for housing costs). The guidelines indicate an exclusion of full-time students from eligibility for Housing Benefit. This reflects one intersection of young people with full-time student status ('thin' intersectionality) since young people in other situations may be eligible for housing benefit. The document does not refer to any opportunities for participation.
Participation			
1	Government secures future of UK Youth Parliament	Published May 2024	This document is a government press release stating that the government has 'secured' the future of the UK Youth Parliament by appointing the National Youth Agency to run it following the collapse of the British Youth Council which previously held the grant to run the UK Youth Parliament. The document indirectly refers to inclusion in that it notes the importance of the inclusion of 11–18-year-olds in representing peer views on a range of issues through the Youth Parliament process. However, the actions taken neither expand nor restrict inclusion – they simply secure a temporary solution to retain a system established 25 years ago. The document focuses on opportunities for young people's participation but neither points to an expansion nor a restriction of those opportunities. No new opportunities are created but restriction is avoided. The document refers to young people in general only in relation to both inclusion and participation.
2	'We all have a voice': Disabled children's vision for change	Published October 2023	This is a report by the UK government's Children's Commissioner putting forward disabled children's voices ahead of the Cabinet Office publication of its Disability Action Plan. The report focuses on the inclusion of disabled children and refers to a number of intersections of children with

			special educational needs, disabilities, gender, ethnicity etc. The report refers to the hundreds and thousands of children, young people and parents whose voices contributed to the report. These participants include those with disabilities and with special educational needs ('thick' intersectionality).
3	Youth Engagement Impact Study	Published March 2023	This document is a DCMS report on the impact of youth engagement programmes and how they might be improved. The report advocates an expansion of inclusion, specifically, the need to broaden access routes to engagement programmes to include and represent a broader range of young people. It refers to the intersection of class and rural residence as intersecting factors excluding young people from engagement. The report specifically discusses young people's opportunities to participate in the UK Youth Parliament and Youth Policy Development Group and refers to a range of intersecting categories that affect opportunities including age (within youth category), area of residence, ethnic background, status (e.g. not in education, employment or training) and special educational needs. It thus displays 'thick' intersectionality in terms of both inclusion and participation.
4	Political Disengagement in the UK	Published November 2022	This is a House of Commons Research Briefing prepared by an independent research team to support MPs. It is concerned with inclusion and exclusion in as much as it refers to policies and campaigns run by government to tackle political disengagement, and thus include more people in political engagement. In addition to young people, it also discusses university students ('thin' intersectionality). In terms of opportunities for participation, the document briefly mentions the expansion of voting rights to 16–17-year-olds in local elections in Wales in 2022. It also mentions that the Electoral Commission partnered with The Democracy Box to include young people in generating feedback on its resources for young people. In this sense it points to an expansion of opportunities. In terms of participation, it refers only to young people in general, however.
5	National Youth Guarantee	Published and updated, February 2022	This document is a government press release setting out the government's plan to 'level up' activities for young people through the Youth Investment Fund. It commits to delivering up to 300 new and refurbished youth facilities in the most deprived parts of England, tackle youth group waiting lists and offer DoE award participation opportunities to all state secondary school and extend funding to National Citizen Service to ensure it reaches thousands more young people. The document claims it constitutes an expansion of inclusion by suggesting that youth services in 45 Local Authorities and around 600 district wards in the most deprived parts of England will be eligible to apply to the Youth Investment Fund. It is not clear whether this actually constitutes greater inclusion given massive reduction in youth services over the last few years (see Introduction). In terms of inclusion, the document refers to intersection of young people with special educational needs and disabilities ('thin' intersectionality). The document refers to opportunities for participation in that it mentions a 'Youth Review' conducted, which reportedly gathered views from 6,000 young people and 175 youth sector organisations on what they wanted. However, it does not point to either an expansion or restriction of participation and refers to young people in general only in relation to participation.

Local level document sample

Local level policy documents were selected from the Greater Manchester Combined Authority (GMCA). The GMCA is a city-region level authority which consists of the ten Greater Manchester councils plus a directly elected Mayor. Beyond the devolution to Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, relatively little power is devolved away from national government in the UK. Moreover, the Combined Authority regions across the country differ significantly in terms of size and the powers

devolved to them. The GMCA benefits from devolved power to govern city-region policy in areas including transport, health and social care and planning and housing.

The Greater Manchester city region is a particularly interesting sub-national level authority to study because it was the first to establish a ‘shadow’ Youth Combined Authority (in February 2018). Known as the Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority (GMYCA), this initiative dates back to 2017 when two young people from Salford (one of the constituent council areas of Greater Manchester) began demanding more voice for young people. Today the GMYCA is an umbrella organisation made up of 29 youth groups of which 10 are the Youth Councils of Greater Manchester and a further 19 are organisations that represent young people from a diverse range of identities and backgrounds in the area. These organisations include those representing LGBTQ+, working class, Black and Syrian young people. Each organisation nominates two young people (aged 11-18 or up to 25 for those with additional needs) and serves for up to two years. The GMYCA meets monthly and gives young people in Greater Manchester the opportunity to influence GMCA policy and decision making. It does this through providing a critical voice for young people to advise and scrutinise the work of the Mayor and GMCA as well as undertaking specific pieces of work on key issues. Its current priority areas are: transport and active travel; education, employment and skills; the environment; and equity, equality and inclusion.

The two policy areas selected for this analysis at the Greater Manchester level are *Education* and *Participation*. This is because they have clear relevance for young people and the GMCA has recently introduced new policies in these areas that have been informed by youth voice. Documents were selected via the GMCA website, which can be searched for a range of policy areas and has a dedicated section detailing the work of the GMYCA. The role of individual young people and the GMYCA in the process of initiating and developing some of these policy areas such as the Our Pass scheme, is also known to the researchers from interactions with participating organisations within the GMYCA. Table 2 provides an overview of the documents selected alongside important contextualising information.

Table 2 Overview of selected local level documents

No.	Title of document	Date (publication/ update)	Contextual information
<i>Participation</i>			
1	Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority (GMYCA) 2024-2026: Our vision for the future	n.d.	This is a document of the Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority (GMYCA), which gives young people in Greater Manchester the opportunity to have their voices heard and influence GMCA policy and decision making. It aims to provide advice to the Mayor of Greater Manchester and the Combined Authority on key concerns of young people and to provide solutions. This document is prepared by the outgoing cohort of elected members and sets out the key policy issues it has identified over its term. The document is designed to help guide the discussion and work of the GMYCA for the incoming 2024/2026 cohort of elected members. It is the second such vision document since the establishment of the GMYCA in 2018. The focus of the document is on inclusion of young people’s voices and thus considers both inclusion and participation. It is hard to say if the document indicates an expansion of inclusion and/or participation, in and of itself but, as it builds on what has gone before, it should cumulatively increase the areas young people’s voice is heard and is thus categorised as expanding both inclusion and opportunities for participation. The

			document refers to young people in general but also implicitly addresses intersectionality through discussion of the importance of working across other equality panels (which focus e.g. on racial equality, gender equality) and of including all people. As it only mentions specifically one other intersection that is with the race equality panel, it is evaluated as 'thin' rather than 'thick' intersectionality.
2	Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority Annual Report 2023-2024	n.d. but covers period up until March 2024	This document is the annual report of the GMYCA, covering its activities over the last year. The document directly discusses the contribution of the GMYCA to the GMCA priority of Equity, Equality and Inclusion and since it brings youth voice into the GMCA work on inclusion, it is considered to enhance inclusion. The document refers to the purpose of the GMYCA as being to 'constructively challenge political and system leaders on progress to improve outcomes for all young people, including those that face discrimination and disadvantage because of their identity'. However, it does not specify individual intersectionalities. For this reason, it is categorised as demonstrating 'thin' rather than 'thick' intersectionality. The document clearly refers to opportunities for young people to participate directly in policymaking. Whether this constitutes an expansion of opportunities is more difficult to judge, given that the GMYCA is not new. However, in the sense that the report covers the work of the GMYCA over the last year, it reflects an expansion of opportunities to participate – for that cohort and also in those areas selected for work. For this reason, it is categorised as indicating an expansion of participation opportunities. No further intersectionality is noted in relation to participation than that identified for inclusion and thus it is judged to evidence 'thin' intersectionality.
3	GMCA Greater than Violence: A Ten-Year Strategy for Reducing and Preventing Violence	Published November 2023	This is a GMCA document which sets out a strategy for reducing and preventing violence across the city region. The document was produced after extensive consultation with young people (via the GMYCA) and launched with GMYCA members present. The document refers to the importance of inclusion of young people's voice in tackling violence and knife crime and thus expands inclusion. It also refers specifically to the importance of recognising the specific issues for young women and girls and young people of colour. Hence it is considered as demonstrating 'thick' intersectionality. In relation to opportunities for participation, the document notes that the strategy embraces a community-led approach in which residents of Greater Manchester (GM), including children and young people, have a voice in deciding how priorities are identified and how services are delivered. It also lists a series of ways in which the GM Violence Reduction Unit will work with partners in education, sport, the voluntary sector and youth justice team to engage young people in high quality activities to help prevent crime and violence. The document also notes inclusion of participatory workshops with young people across GM related to their experiences of violence and how the findings of this have fed into the strategy. In this participation dimension, young people in general are discussed.
4	Greater Manchester Moving in Action 2021-2023: Active Lives for All	Published September 2021	This GMCA document sets out a strategy for increasing physical activity for people in the city region. It signals an expansion of inclusion in that it focuses on how to include everyone and make access to movement accessible to all. The strategy is partially in response to COVID-19 and its exposure and exacerbation of health inequalities. It approaches physical activity as an important factor in improving social and economic inclusion. It specifically notes that the strategy has become more inclusive over time especially in making language and visuals more inclusive, diverse and expansive – shifting the emphasis from sport to active lives for all. It has as a priority to 'Enable children and young people to lead active lives and to move every day with greater choice, say and independence in when and how they move in safe and age appropriate ways.' It also notes the importance of targeting communities who are currently underserved and underrepresented. Whilst it notes a number of groups targeted for

			inclusion, these are cited alongside youth rather than intersecting with youth and thus the document is categorised as referring to young people in general. The document refers to opportunities for participation, emphasising that physical activity increases social trust, belonging and community participation. It notes that it embraces a mantra of ‘nothing about us, without us’ and that this has led to a series of GM Moving in Action conversations which engaged over 2000 people and organisations. These explored how to tackle racism and racial inequality, widening access and participation for low-income families, disabled people, people with long term health conditions, children and young people, older adults, LGBTQ+ community, women and girls. It is thus judged to have expanded opportunities for participation. As above, a range of groups are listed alongside but not intersecting with youth.
5	Our Pass	February 2022	The document is a GMCA website advertising the Our Pass scheme which provides free bus travel for 16–18-year-olds across the city region as well as a range of other benefits, including free and discounted access to a wide range of employment, education, cultural and leisure activities, which may have previously been out of reach for young people. It thus indicates an expansion of inclusion of young people whilst referring to young people in general. The document points to an expansion of participation in that the young people, especially the GMYCA, were heavily involved in inspiring the Our Pass scheme as well as designing how it worked, choosing the name and the card design. In discussing this involvement in designing the policy, young people in general are referred to.
Education			
1	Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority 2024-2026: Our vision for the future	n.d.	One of the document’s four key themes is ‘Education, Employment and Skills’. It predominantly focuses on young people’s involvement in helping develop and promote the Manchester Baccalaureate (MBacc) (see Document 3), as well as their role in sharing and collaborating on information focusing on their life skills. The document clearly calls for an expansion of inclusion through its focus on the involvement of young people in educational matters (particularly developing the MBacc). It briefly makes reference to the Schools’ race charter emphasising issues of race/ethnicity, thus representing ‘thin’ intersectionality. It is also clear that the document refers to opportunities for expanding participation, although this seems to refer to young people more generally.
2	Greater Manchester Youth Combined Authority Annual Report 2023-2024	n.d. but covers up until March 2024	Similar to Document 1, the report covers the work of the YCA on the theme of Education, Employment and Skills. It highlights the role the Education and Skills team played in helping shape the MBacc through creating a report of their recommendations that helped shape the branding of this qualification (see Document 3). The expansion of youth voice and inclusion is explicitly prioritised in this document. However, young people tend to be addressed in a general sense with implicit recognition of intersectionality (e.g., through recognising that young people can face discrimination and disadvantage due to their identities). The document evidences the work done by the YCA to expand opportunities for young people to participate (such as through their involvement shaping the MBacc).
3	Greater Manchester Baccalaureate (MBacc) Young People’s Perspective	May 2024	As referred to above, this document was published by the GMYCA and reports the collaborative discussions that took place between the YCA and members of the MBacc team, in addition to a survey conducted with the involvement of young people across Greater Manchester to collect a diverse range of opinions, critiques, and suggestions. The document refers to an expansion of inclusion as it focuses on the proposed MBacc which aims to address the imbalance in the education system that prioritises academic over technical education. The MBacc aims to give a clear and equal path to all young people in Greater Manchester (although young people are addressed generally here). The document outlines ‘3 Asks’ or suggestions to improve the MBacc. For example, by having a designated

			accessible website for young people to access information about the qualification and to make apprenticeships more attractive. The document also highlights an expansion of participation as it was written by young people who have been engaging in discussions with decision makers, and reflected on the perspectives of other young people who took part in the survey.
4	Local Skills Report and Labour Market Plan: Greater Manchester Employment and Skills Advisory Panel	March 2022	There are overlaps between ‘education’ and ‘employment/labour’ policy areas in this document, but given its focus on Further Education (e.g., apprenticeships, high-quality technical and vocational education) it was considered to be relevant under this policy area. The document outlines four core strategic priorities for Greater Manchester, one of which relates to young people being able to complete their education and training and obtain the required skills to succeed in the labour market. The document calls for more inclusion through focusing on offering young people (more generally) opportunities to obtain the required technical (i.e., STEM) skills to contribute to Greater Manchester’s economy which currently suffers from gaps in these aforementioned skills. A number of action plans are put forward, however there are no opportunities for young people’s participation as the onus is on these initiatives being employer-led.
5	Greater Manchester STEM Framework	n.d.	This Framework is in response to the shortage of STEM skills locally and nationally (see Document 4) and is aimed towards Greater Manchester residents including young people (in a general sense). Similarly to previous documents, it proposes an expansion of inclusion through putting forward a framework for providing more people with STEM skills to enable them to take part in large-scale STEM-based projects around the region, such as those related to health innovation, digital and creative industries, low-carbon industries and advanced materials. However, this framework does not allude to expanding young people’s participation in such plans, and it is predominantly employer-led.

Analysis

When interpreting the findings of the UK documents, however, it is important to note the limitations arising from this very small, time- and theme-limited study. As set out in Section 2, to facilitate cross-national comparison, the documents were selected according to pre-set themes designed to capture key policy areas across a number of national contexts and focusing on the most recent period. In the UK context, the policy themes of education and health do capture important sites of policy discussion related to youth. For example, in health, there is a rich vein of documents that particularly focus on young people’s mental health following the COVID-19 pandemic. On the other hand, policy areas such as employment, show a marked lack of concern with young people and this might be seen as a finding in itself. The lack of any distinct policy area around ‘participation’, however, made this a tricky area to capture policy documents, despite the frequent concern expressed by political actors about the disengagement of young people from the political system. It is also important to note that key areas of policy in which young people feature strongly in the UK are not included in these five themes. For example, young people are often inscribed in policy that focuses on crime and violence reduction where young people are positioned as both victims and perpetrators (e.g. knife crime). They are also the object of much punitive legislation and regulation concerning anti-social behaviour and ostensibly protective legislation (e.g. around online harm). Accordingly, policy areas around crime and public order and/or media and culture would have captured some key moments of policy debate on youth that do not appear in the analysis below.

Regarding the time period over which documents were selected, it is important to note that General Elections took place in the UK on 4 July 2024 and returned a Labour government following a series of Conservative governments in power since 2010. Thus, the documents analysed reflect previous government(s) policy rather than that of the current government. It should also be noted that the UK 'local' policy analysis was centred on the city-region of Greater Manchester. This is a Combined Authority comprising 10 different councils and a directly elected Mayor and, in contrast to the national political picture, in Greater Manchester the vast majority of constituent councils have been Labour controlled since the city-region was established, and the Mayor, since 2017, has been the former Labour MP Andy Burnham. This should be taken into account when interpreting the differences identified between national and local policies.

The small number of documents selected for each policy area and the focus on the most recent documents, in general mean that only a snapshot of policy discussion and opinion is captured. In order to help interpret the findings, below we thus provide some brief reflections relating to each policy area that might be taken into consideration during cross-national comparison.

Education

The selected policy documents on *education* predominantly focused on school (primary and secondary) pupils in the UK and were concerned with making aspects of the education system more inclusive for students, particularly those with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND). The exception here was Document 3 which focused on the participation of young people in education, employment and training. Two key points should be highlighted. The first, is the presence of youth voice in the documents analysed (Documents 2, 4, and 5). The importance of students' perspectives, feedback, and even involvement in helping design the physical education curriculum and mental health support, for example, is commendable. The second, as will be elaborated further under *employment*, is the focus on reforming Further Education, including technical education. A number of documents, especially at local level, were concerned with STEM and technical education that enabled young people to pursue careers that did not require a university qualification. There was also a discernible overlap between education and employment, which arguably reflects a wider approach to policy on youth in the UK which considers education, skills, training and employment together and tightly links education with future employment, for good or ill. It also reflects ongoing, long-term concern among policymakers with the need to reform vocational education to provide high-quality, attractive alternatives to the higher education (university) route for young people post-16. However, as indicated in Section 1, the education system (including Higher Education) suffers from a range of inequalities that intersect across many categories (class, gender, race/ethnicity, disabilities). The recent turn towards reforming vocational education, albeit welcome, will not be enough to tackle other forms of inequality.

Employment

As noted above, a number of documents overlapped in their focus between education and employment. Documents categorised under employment were chosen due to their predominant focus on young people's future labour market outcomes (e.g. Documents 4 and 5) which is of relevance here. The documents analysed addressed various issues related to young people's employability, particularly against the backdrop of COVID-19 and represented an amalgam of policy documents and reports published by government affiliated bodies aiming to shape future policy

decisions. With the exception of Documents 2 and 3, young people's participation did not feature as much as in other policy areas, however, the majority of documents acknowledged the 'thick' intersectionality of young people in the UK. The documents aimed to address issues ranging from lowering the eligibility of the National Living Wage (Document 1), to proposing local solutions to tackling youth unemployment in under-resourced places (Document 2). The documents are consistent with current debates surrounding geographical inequalities within the UK (e.g. the 'North/South divide'), the cost-of-living crisis and the need for ensuring secure, well-paid and stable employment for young people. Technical education and STEM-related skills are prioritised, but the proposed reforms could have a negative impact on disadvantaged young people (Document 4). It remains to be seen how a new Labour government will approach these issues.

Health

The health-related documents address two main foci of concern in public discussion of youth and health: mental health; and substance use. However, in face of the significant mental health crisis among young people outlined in Section 1, it must be noted that the policy documents analysed provide extremely modest solutions. For example, Document 1 notes the extension of mental health support teams embedded in schools and colleges to reach 20-25% of the country and the extension of services from those up to age 18 to those up to age 25. In other cases, the reforms described are not unambiguously positive for young people. For example, the reforms to ensure the voice of patients is heard outlined in Document 5, only partially include young people; in some provisions, young people are omitted from those who will benefit. Similarly, documents 2 and 3 – on vaping and smoking – are ostensibly 'good for' young people. However, they reflect a protectionist approach to young people in outlining the prohibition of sale of certain products (disposable vapes and tobacco) to young people under a certain age. They thus exclude young people from access to products available to older people without any apparent inclusion of participation in policy formation by young people themselves. The most positive example is Document 4, which sets out revised standards and associated quality criteria for youth-friendly health and care services and details how young people's voice has been taken into account in revising the guidance. It also acknowledges the exacerbated health inequalities for some intersectional groups of young people.

Housing

In the UK access to housing – both home ownership and affordable decent quality rented accommodation – is at the heart of national public debate about intergenerational inequality. While this is reflected in the background research section of Document 2, this central issue around youth inequality is remarkably absent from the policies found in the documents analysed. Indeed, this is one of only two policy areas found to further exclude young people (scoring -1 on direction of inclusion). This was evident in the closure of a scheme designed to help young people buy their first home (Document 2) and through the exclusion of students from state benefit to help with rented housing costs (Document 5). The dominant area of concern in the policy documents selected relates to youth homelessness (Documents 1 and 3). This is an important area of national public concern but the policies identified deal with only the most acute cases and position young people as 'vulnerable' to or 'at risk' of homelessness rather than empowering young people through policy measures that would allow them to access affordable independent housing. The most positive of the housing-related policies was that addressed to young Ukrainian refugees coming to the UK on the 'Homes for Ukraine' scheme. While this was a youth-friendly information document setting out

the rights and opportunities for young Ukrainians including in relation to housing, it clearly addresses a very small contingent of young people and the 'Homes for Ukraine' scheme itself essentially passes responsibility for refugee accommodation from the state to individual citizens.

It is evident from the documents studied, that significant responsibility for addressing youth homelessness in the UK is left to the charity and voluntary sector. This is reflected in the documentation where the only positive (+1) score for opportunities for participation is found in Document 1, which describes the continuation of funding for a charity to continue its youth voice programme, ensuring young homeless people's voices are heard.

Participation

The documents analysed suggest a striking absence of any national level policy directed towards promoting participation of young people. While the scores show relatively positive directions in terms of inclusion and participation in the analysis, these are primarily documents related to the specific inclusion of previously marginalised groups of young people (e.g. disabled young people, young people displaced by the war in Ukraine). Other documents with positive scores reflect more report-oriented work referencing programmes designed to increase political engagement of young people, which are temporally or spatially discrete. While the documents addressing the Youth Parliament and the National Youth Guarantee address the whole country, they represent temporary solutions (Youth Parliament) or the introduction of competitive based funding to local authorities that can do little more than fill some of the most gaping holes left by the massive disinvestment in youth services set out in Section 1. The massive cuts to local authority budgets have decimated youth work, youth clubs and other youth-oriented cultural and civic participation opportunities across the country and there is little evidence of national policy to address this.

In contrast, at the local level, the GMCA documents analysed indicate a strong awareness of factors such as the cost of transport that are a barrier to young people's employment and training opportunities but also their ability to participate in a range of cultural and leisure activities and simply move about outside of their local area. The *Our Pass* policy seeks to address this and consciously notes the wider impact on community participation and involvement for young people. The establishment of the GMCYA also shows a genuine commitment to, and investment in, a mechanism for the inclusion of youth voice across Greater Manchester policy areas. It should be noted, however, that the GM region was selected for this exercise because it presented an interesting case in this respect and is not representative of local authorities across the country.

Conclusion

Notwithstanding the limitations of the documents selected for understanding the much broader policy landscape (see start of Section 3), we might conclude that, at both the national and the local level, 'inclusion' is referenced in most policy relating to youth across the policy areas of education, employment, health, housing and participation. Only one document at the national level was considered not to mention 'inclusion' and no documents at the local level failed to note 'inclusion'. In most cases the outcome of this inclusion was considered to be positive for young people. It was only in the areas of *housing* and *health* (at national level) that the outcomes were deemed to be negative for young people's inclusion. For example, failing to include young people when granting additional rights to mental health services and the prohibition of tobacco and vapes.

Unsurprisingly, it is in the *participation* policy area that opportunities for participation are strongest for young people in comparison to other areas. At the local level, expanded opportunities for participation are evident in all five documents. At the national level, all five documents mention opportunities for participation and in three of those cases, this denotes an expansion of opportunity. In *education*, more than half of the national policies evince expanded opportunities for participation whilst at local level, all 5 documents do so. However, in the remaining three policy areas (health, housing and employment), there is little evidence of opportunity for participation. The worst example is *housing*, where there is just one mention of such opportunities and no indication of whether this expands or limits opportunity.

In terms of the criterion of *'inclusion'*, national level documents on participation, education, employment and housing do generally recognise the diverse experiences of young people and explicitly refer to intersectional categories. In the policy sphere of *health*, in contrast, most national level documents consider the inclusion of young people only in general terms. Among local level documents, six of ten documents recognise diverse, intersectional experiences of young people when talking about *'inclusion'*, although only one of those documents mentions more than one intersection.

In relation to the criterion of *'opportunities for participation'*, just over half (thirteen of twenty-five) national level documents refer to such opportunities. Of those, the majority (eight) refer to young people in general terms while just three mention more than one intersectional category. In contrast, at the local level, eight of ten documents mention opportunities for participation and half of these mention intersectional youth. However, all those mentioning intersectional youth reference just one intersection (i.e. demonstrate *'thin'* intersectionality).

On the broader question of reference to *'empowerment'*, it is evident that where *'participation'* is the direct focus of policy, there is considerably more attention paid to youth voice and empowerment than in other policy areas. This attention to empowerment is also more evident at the local level than at the national level.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1 - GUIDELINES FOR THE POLICY ANALYSIS

PART I: GENERAL OVERVIEW

Spatial Coverage: Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Switzerland, United Kingdom

Time Method: Cross-sectional policy documents

Analysis Unit: Standardized scores based on content analysis of policy documents

Universe: Not applicable-

Mode of Data Collection: Compilation / Synthesis

Sampling Description: 5x5=25 documents at the national level, 5 x 2= 10 at the local level

Data Collection Instruments: Guidelines

This document provides guidelines and includes the items that will be used for measuring data collection regarding social narratives on youth inclusion and participation in public policies. It encompasses the introduction section, indicators, lists the policy areas and the concluding section to be included by all teams in the dataset that will be collected through Workpackage 4.1.1. The data collection should be given to the UNIGE team, at latest the 15th of August 2024.

PART II: INTRODUCTION

Write a brief introduction (3 pages maximum) with a presentation of the situation concerning the current (2024) situation of young people in your country. This introduction aims to provide a comprehensive and succinct overview of the current situation of young people in each country. It should include the following aspects:

1. A description of the **kind** of challenges faced by young people in the following areas: housing, education, health, employment and participation. Outline the primary barriers that young people encounter in each category and provide a brief description. For example:

Housing:

Example: In the last three decades, escalating property prices and rental rates in urban areas such as Zurich and Geneva have posed significant challenges for young people in securing affordable housing. (...)

Education:

Example: Increasing tuition fees for higher education institutions have made it harder for young people from low-income backgrounds to pursue further studies. (...)

Health:

Example: After COVID-19, the increased demand for mental health support highlights the limited access to affordable healthcare services (...)

Employment:

Example: High youth unemployment rates, lack of job security, and limited opportunities for career advancement contribute (...)

Participation:

Example: Limited opportunities for young people to participate in decision-making processes at various levels and lack of access to resources and platforms for expressing their opinions (...)

2. A frequency analysis of the **diversity of experiences** (being in school, recent graduates, those entering the workforce, those neither in school nor in the workforce, those with visa problems, those with children, etc.) that young people face in these five different areas.

In the specific, it would be important to provide details on the number – from for example relevant statistics offices data – on these five different areas. For example, in the educational area could be: the number of young people enrolled in mandatory school versus those not attending; how many young people received scholarships or any kind of state funding. For the employment areas could be: how many young people are living below the poverty line; how many young people seeking employment. For the participation area factors such as the presence of youth associations, voter turnout in previous elections, participation in demonstrations, and engagement in various associations are significant. Health-related statistics should cover hospitalization rates, healthcare needs, suicides, and other relevant information. Housing should encompass the number of homeless youth, those residing in shelters or other communal housing arrangements, etc.

3. A frequency analysis of who are "young people" in your countries. In the specific, a description of how many young people embodies different intersections as disability status, gender, migration background, race, socioeconomic status, sexual orientations and other intersecting identities.

PART III: CODING INSTRUCTIONS

PART IIIA: SAMPLING STRATEGY FOR THE NATIONAL LEVEL

Each team will create a sample of policy documents at the national level which encompasses laws, public programs, and government reports. To develop your national-level sample, consider the following criteria:

- Main lines of recent laws/public programs/ government reports in the following areas: housing, education, health, employment and participation. Each area should encompass a minimum of 5 laws/ public policies/ government reports for each area, resulting in a total of 5 x 5 = 25 laws, public programs, or reports. If teams wish to include additional policy areas, they are more than welcome to do so.

	Policy areas
1	Participation would include: Laws regulating for example electoral and protest participation, involvement in civil society, founding or assistance for youth association
2	Education would include: Education system and civic education
3	Labour would include: labour and unemployment policies, laws which regulate for example minimum wages,

4	Health would include: mental health initiatives, addiction prevention measures, and sexual health policies
5	Housing policies would include : affordable housing initiatives, youth homelessness prevention, student housing support, youth housing assistance programs, youth refugees shelters

- a. The laws/public programs/ government reports must mention **at least** the general term/ keywords such as "young individual", "young people", "youth", "young", "teenagers". Or even more specifics as "minor", "adolescent", "younger generation", "generation z", "Gen Z", "generation Alpha, "millennials / Generation Y", "young students" ...
- Teams should review policies backward, starting from the most recent, 2024, until they identify policies where young people are mentioned within the respective areas.

PART IIIB: SAMPLING STRATEGY FOR THE LOCAL LEVEL

Each team will create a sample of policy documents at the local level which encompasses laws, public programs, and government reports. To develop your local-level sample, consider the following criteria:

- Main lines of recent laws/public programs/ government reports in at least **two** of the following areas: housing, education, health, employment and participation. When analyzing the national level, if you notice one or more issues that are particularly relevant or prominent, we recommend focusing on those. Each of the two areas should encompass a minimum of 5 laws/ public policies/ government reports for each area, resulting in a total of 5 x 2 = 10 laws, public programs, or reports. If teams wish to include additional policy areas, they are more than welcome to do so.

	Policy areas
1	Participation would include: Laws regulating for example electoral and protest participation, involvement in civil society, founding or assistance for youth association
2	Education would include: Education system and civic education
3	Labour would include: labour and unemployment policies, laws which regulate for example minimum wages,
4	Health would include: mental health initiatives, addiction prevention measures, and sexual health policies
5	Housing policies would include: affordable housing initiatives, youth homelessness prevention, student housing support, youth housing assistance programs, youth refugees shelters

- The laws/public programs/ government reports must mention **at least** the general term/ keywords such as "young individual", "young people", "youth", "young", "teenagers". Or even

more specifics as “minor”, “adolescent”, “younger generation”, “generation z”, “Gen Z”, “generation Alpha”, “millennials / Generation Y”, “young students”.

- Teams should review policies backward, starting from the most recent, 2024, until they identify policies where young people are mentioned within the respective areas.

PART IIIC: CODING STRATEGY FOR THE NATIONAL LEVEL

In the public policies section, we aim to analyze how national policies address social inclusion and exclusion, and to what extent they expand or restrict participation opportunities, while recognizing the diverse needs and identities of young people as citizens. Our analysis will be conducted on two aspects:

- i) Does the document deal with social inclusion or exclusion? If yes, do the proposed or actual policies result in positive or negative outcomes for young people?

In particular, we define **social inclusion** as the deliberate efforts made by governments and institutions to implement policies (laws/public programs/ government reports) that ensure young people are considered and integrated into societal structures. These efforts can include, for example:

- Recognition: Acknowledging the diverse needs and experiences of different youth groups.
- Representation: Ensuring that policies reflect the interests of all young people, including marginalized groups.
- Accessibility: Making sure that services, resources, and information are available to all youth.
- Non-discrimination: Actively working to eliminate barriers and biases that may exclude certain groups of young people.

- ii) Does the document deal with opportunities for political participation? If yes, do the proposed or actual policies expand or restrict opportunities for participation?

In particular, we understand **opportunities for political participation** as the creation of **specific channels and platforms** that enable the political engagement of young people. These opportunities can include, for example:

- Youth councils: Formal structures where young people can voice their opinions on local or national issues.
- Volunteering programs: Initiatives that allow youth to contribute to their communities.
- Political engagement: Encouraging youth voting, running for office, or joining political parties.
- Political involvement in educational contexts: Student unions, school councils, or peer education programs.
- Digital platforms: Online forums or social media campaigns for youth expression and activism.
- Youth-led organizations: Supporting the creation and operation of organizations run by young people.

Note:

- *Inclusive policy* is about the overall framework, typically established by authorities in a top-down manner. Participation opportunities, on the other hand, are specific channels for political

engagement that can be initiated both top-down (by the government) and bottom-up (by the youth themselves). These opportunities ensure that young people have platforms where they can express their views and be heard.

Each team, after analysing the documents, will assign a score to each document as follows.

For the first criterion (presence/absence), the scoring will be as follows:

- **Score 0:** Indicates that the document does not refer to inclusion/exclusion.
- **Score 1:** Indicates that the document refers to inclusion/exclusion.

For the second criterion (direction), the scoring is as follows:

- **Score 1:** If the document points to an expansion of inclusion.
- **Score 0:** If the document neither points to an expansion nor a restriction of inclusion.
- **Score -1:** If the document points to a restriction of inclusion (i.e. exclusion).

For the third criterion (intersectionality), the scoring is as follows:

- **Score 1:** The document refers to young people in general (i.e. no intersectionality).
- **Score 2:** The document refers to young people in general but implicitly addresses intersectionality in the narrative. (e.g. young people are not a homogenous group, they have a multitude of identities and diverse needs, resources, backgrounds, life situations and interests).
- **Score 3:** The document refers to one or more intersections within the category of young people, including at least one additional characteristic (e.g. young women).

For the fourth criterion (how many intersections) the scoring is as follows:

- **Score 1:** The document refers explicitly to a “thin” intersectionality, defined as young people with one additional characteristic (e.g., young women).
- **Score 2:** The document refers explicitly to a “thick” intersectionality, defined as young people with two or more additional characteristics (e.g. young migrant women).
- **Note:** The coding depends on the policy area of the document being analyzed. For instance, in the education policy, general terms are “young people”; “youth” but as well “students” or “pupils.” Therefore, it is crucial to analyze and code these terms based on their intersections within different contexts. The coding will be as it follows: Example: *Education policy*:
 - “Young students” should be classified as a general term (score 1)

Other policies (health, housing, participation):

- “Young students” should be classified under “thick” intersectionality=2

For the fifth criterion, specify the group that the document refers to.

Examples: young migrants, young women

The following table explains the scoring system in more detail.

Policy area 1	Inclusion / exclusion	Opportunities for participation
Document 1	<p>Does the document deal with inclusion or exclusion?</p> <p><i>Yes, the document refers to inclusion/exclusion : 1</i></p> <p><i>No, the document does not address inclusion or exclusion : 0</i></p>	<p>Does the document deal with opportunities for participation?</p> <p><i>Yes, the document refers to opportunities (either it restricts or expands) for participation: 1</i></p> <p><i>No, the document does not refer to opportunities for participation: 0</i></p>
	<p><i>Code only if the code on the previous criterion is 1.</i></p> <p>Do the proposed or actual policies result in positive or negative outcomes for young people?</p> <p><i>If the document points to a restriction of inclusion (i.e. exclusion): -1</i></p> <p><i>If the document neither points to an expansion nor to a restriction of inclusion (i.e. exclusion): 0</i></p> <p><i>If the document points to an expansion of inclusion (i.e. exclusion): +1</i></p>	<p><i>Code only if the code on the previous criterion is 1.</i></p> <p>Do the proposed or actual policies expand or restrict opportunities for participation?</p> <p><i>If the document points to a restriction of participation: -1</i></p> <p><i>If the document neither points to an expansion nor to a restriction of participation: 0</i></p> <p><i>If the document points to an expansion of opportunities: +1</i></p>
	<p><i>Code for all documents.</i></p> <p>The document refers to...</p> <p>“young people” in general: 1</p> <p>“young people in general and implicitly addresses intersectionality in the narrative”:2</p> <p>“young people and at least one intersection”:3</p>	<p><i>Code for all documents.</i></p> <p>The document refers to...</p> <p>“young people” in general: 1</p> <p>“young people in general and implicitly addresses intersectionality in the narrative”:2</p> <p>“young people and at least one intersection”:3</p>
	<p><i>Code only if previous criterion is 2 or 3.</i></p> <p>The document refers to...</p> <p>“thin” intersectionality, understood as young + at least one intersection: 1 Ex.: young women</p> <p>“thick” intersectionality, understood as young + at least two intersections: 2 Ex.: young migrant women</p>	<p><i>Code only if previous criterion is 2 or 3.</i></p> <p>The document refers to...</p> <p>“thin” intersectionality, understood as young + at least one intersection: 1 Ex.: young women</p> <p>“thick” intersectionality, understood as young + at least two intersections: 2 Ex.: young migrant women</p>
	Specify the group that the document refers to...	Specify the group that the document refers to...

	Ex.: young migrants	Ex.: young migrants
Document 2	Repeat the coding	Repeat the coding
Document 3	Repeat the coding	Repeat the coding
Document 4	Repeat the coding	Repeat the coding
Document 5	Repeat the coding	Repeat the coding

If a policy document includes some groups of young people while excluding others, focus on the category that the document primarily addresses. However, in your summary, make sure to mention the groups that are excluded.

The scores will be inserted in an excel file. After analyzing each area, teams should offer a brief summary (maximum a page) of the analyzed documents, covering their scope and the evaluations used to contextualize the analysis scores. This summary should also discuss how the documents address the inclusion and opportunities for participation of young people as outlined by government policies.

Policy Areas	Participation
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National level

PART IIID: CODING STRATEGY FOR THE LOCAL LEVEL

The same strategy applies to the local level.

PART IV: CONCLUDING SECTION

Write a brief conclusion (1-2 pages maximum) with a broader assessment of whether the public policy at the national and at the local level take into account the following points:

- i) Does governmental policies deals with inclusion or exclusion? If yes, to what extent do these policies result in positive or negative outcomes for young people?
- ii) Does governmental policies deals with opportunities for participation? To what extent do they expand or restrict opportunities for participation?
- iii) If governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations, how governmental policies navigate the complexities of youth experiences, identities, and aspirations?
- iv) Does governmental policy typically categorize young people using general terms, or does it incorporate considerations for intersectionality? Are inclusivity, empowerment addressed comprehensively within governmental policy?